

THÈSE

En vue de l'obtention du

DOCTORAT DE L'UNIVERSITÉ DE TOULOUSE

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Présentée et soutenue le *25/05/2023* par :

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**Searching Habitable Exoplanets with the SPIrou Spectropolarimeter:
Tackling Stellar Magnetic Activity**

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SDU2E : Astrophysique, Sciences de l'Espace, Planétologie

Unité de Recherche :

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“Non est ad astra mollis e terris via”
(there is no easy way from the earth to the stars)
Hercules furens, Seneca

Abstract

The search and characterization of habitable Earth-like planets have been substantial drivers for both current (e.g., *TESS*, *CHEOPS*, *JWST*) and mid-term (*PLATO*, *Ariel*) space missions. The consequent investigation of the chemical variety of exoplanet atmospheres will drive significant progress in our understanding of planet formation and evolution, as well as a baseline to assess potential signatures of life. At present, the output of transit photometry campaigns dominates the planet detection statistics, but this method conveys only partial knowledge on the planet (i.e., the radius), and requires complementary follow-up in order to constrain (an upper limit of) the planetary mass, mainly via radial velocity surveys. Once radius and mass are known, it is possible to infer the bulk density of the planet, which is a crucial, first-order ingredient to a precise bulk composition determination and atmospheric characterisation.

At the low mass end of the main-sequence, M dwarfs represent key targets toward this goal. They outnumber the other spectral types in the solar neighbourhood, feature higher Earth-like planet occurrence rates, and possess habitable zones closer-in, owing to their lower temperatures. However, M dwarfs can be highly active, which hampers the success of radial velocity searches. Stellar magnetic activity is in fact responsible for surface inhomogeneities (e.g. dark spots and faculae) that generate spurious radial velocity signatures (so called “activity jitter”) which, in turn, drown the planetary signature completely or prevent a precise mass determination. In this sense, stellar magnetic activity produces a noise floor that limits our sensitivity to small planets.

To tackle this issue and mitigate the stellar contamination, we have to develop physically-motivated, jitter-filtering techniques and understand the jitter sources at play thoroughly, which thus requires an accurate model of the underlying magnetic field. During my Ph.D. project, I used high-resolution spectropolarimetric data in optical and near-infrared collected with ESPaDOnS, Narval and SPIRou, which enable us to efficiently combine velocimetry and magnetometry.

In the first part of the project, I designed an algorithm that performs a randomised selection of “stable” spectral lines. Using the output line list to compute radial velocity time series, we observed a reduction of at least 50% in dispersion, demonstrating its potential at cleaning spurious signals. The algorithm was tested extensively, to corroborate its portability over M dwarfs of different activity levels and spectral types, and its applicability to time series with injected synthetic planets, to verify that the associated signal would not be significantly affected. To understand further the physical reason as to why some spectral lines combinations lead to time series with smaller jitter than others, I reconstructed the brightness map of the stellar surface by means of the Doppler Imaging technique while using distinct line selections and attempted at filtering the associated radial velocity curves. The results of this analysis are still preliminary, but we already observe differences in the brightness image of a star when selecting atomic rather than molecular lines.

In the second part, I monitored the large-scale magnetic field at the surface of well-known, active M dwarfs on both sides of the fully-convective boundary, exploiting the spectropolarimetric capabilities of the aforementioned instruments. In particular, I analysed time series of longitudinal magnetic field, Full-Width at Half Maximum of unpolarised mean profiles, and magnetic fluxes obtained via Zeeman broadening modelling, and I reconstructed the magnetic field topology by means of tomographic inversion (i.e. Zeeman-Doppler Imaging) across different epochs. I sought for a secular evolution of these quantities, potentially revealing the presence of magnetic cycles. These are known to introduce spurious noise in radial velocity time series, and modulations of the energetic radiation (e.g. UV, X-rays) and

stellar wind impinging on planets. I found a variety of long-term trends that have some complementarities with our understanding of the solar magnetic cycle. Ultimately, these findings provide practical feedback to dynamo theories, which are incomplete and still debated even for the Sun.

Resumé

La recherche et la caractérisation de planètes habitables semblables à la Terre ont été des moteurs importants pour les missions spatiales actuelles (par exemple, *TESS*, *CHEOPS*, *JWST*) et à moyen terme (*PLATO*, *Ariel*). L'étude conséquente de la variété chimique des atmosphères des exoplanètes permettra de réaliser des progrès significatifs dans notre compréhension de la formation et de l'évolution des planètes, ainsi qu'une base de référence pour évaluer les signatures potentielles de la vie. Actuellement, les résultats des campagnes de photométrie dominent les statistiques de détection de planètes, mais cette méthode ne transmet qu'une connaissance partielle de la planète (c'est-à-dire le rayon), et nécessite un suivi complémentaire afin de contraindre (une limite supérieure de) la masse planétaire, principalement par les mesures de vitesse radiale. Une fois le rayon et la masse connus, il est possible de déduire la densité de la planète, qui est un ingrédient crucial pour une caractérisation atmosphérique précise.

À l'extrémité inférieure de la séquence principale, les naines M représentent des cibles clés pour atteindre cet objectif. Elles sont plus nombreuses que les autres types spectraux dans le voisinage solaire, présentent des taux d'occurrence plus élevés de planètes semblables à la Terre, et possèdent des zones habitables plus proches, en raison de leurs températures de surface plus basses. Cependant, les naines M peuvent être très actives, ce qui entrave le succès des recherches sur les vitesses radiales. L'activité magnétique stellaire est en effet responsable d'inhomogénéités de surface (par exemple des taches sombres et des facules) qui génèrent des signatures de vitesse radiale parasites (appelées "jitter d'activité") qui, à leur tour, noient complètement la signature planétaire ou empêchent une détermination précise de la masse. En ce sens, notre sensibilité aux petites planètes est principalement dictée par l'activité magnétique stellaire.

Pour résoudre ce problème et atténuer la contamination stellaire, nous devons mettre au point des techniques de filtrage de jitter, et comprendre en profondeur les sources de jitter en jeu, ce qui nécessite donc un modèle précis du champ magnétique stellaire. Au cours de mon projet de doctorat, j'ai utilisé des données spectropolarimétriques à haute résolution dans l'optique et l'infrarouge proche recueillies avec ESPaDOnS, Narval et SPIRou, qui nous permettent de combiner efficacement vélocimétrie et magnétométrie.

Dans la première partie du projet, j'ai conçu un algorithme qui effectue une sélection aléatoire de raies spectrales "stables". En utilisant la liste de raies spectrales résultantes pour calculer les séries temporelles de vitesse radiale, nous avons observé une réduction d'au moins 50% de la dispersion, ce qui démontre le potentiel de l'algorithme à nettoyer les signaux parasites. L'algorithme a été testé de manière extensive, pour corroborer sa portabilité sur des naines M de différents niveaux d'activité et types spectraux, et son applicabilité aux séries temporelles avec des planètes synthétiques injectées, pour vérifier que le signal associé ne serait pas significativement affecté. Pour mieux comprendre la raison physique pour laquelle certaines combinaisons de raies spectrales conduisent à des séries temporelles avec un bruit d'activité plus faible que d'autres, j'ai reconstruit la carte de brillance de la surface stellaire au moyen de la technique d'imagerie Doppler en utilisant des sélections de raies distinctes et j'ai tenté de filtrer les courbes de vitesse radiale associées. Les résultats de cette analyse sont encore préliminaires, mais nous observons déjà des différences dans la distribution de brillance d'une étoile lorsque l'on sélectionne des raies spectrales atomiques plutôt que moléculaires.

Dans la deuxième partie, j'ai suivi le champ magnétique à grande échelle à la surface des naines M actives très étudiées, en exploitant les capacités spectropolarimétriques des instruments susmen-

tionnés. En particulier, j'ai analysé les séries temporelles du champ magnétique longitudinal, de la largeur à mi-hauteur des profils moyens non polarisés et des flux magnétiques obtenus par modélisation de l'élargissement Zeeman, et j'ai reconstruit la topologie du champ magnétique au moyen d'une inversion tomographique (c'est-à-dire l'imagerie Zeeman-Doppler) à différentes époques. J'ai cherché une évolution séculaire de ces quantités, révélant potentiellement la présence de cycles magnétiques. Ceux-ci sont connus pour introduire des bruits parasites dans les séries temporelles de vitesse radiale, et des modulations du rayonnement énergétique (par exemple UV, rayons X) et du vent stellaire frappant les planètes. J'ai trouvé une variété de tendances à long terme qui présentent des complémentarités avec notre compréhension du cycle magnétique solaire. Finalement, ces résultats fournissent un retour pratique aux théories de la dynamo, qui sont incomplètes et encore débattues, même pour le Soleil.

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Acknowledgements

I conducted my Ph.D. project as an international co-supervision between France and the Netherlands. My headquarter has been the *Institut de Recherche en Astrophysique et Planétologie* (IRAP) in Toulouse, France, but I had the distinct opportunity to spend half of the project hosted at the *European Space Research and Technology Centre* (ESTEC) of the European Space Agency in Noordwijk, The Netherlands.

First and foremost, I would like to thank my Ph.D. supervisors: Pascal Petit, Julien Morin, and Gaitee Hussain. There are not simple ways to encapsulate my gratitude in a few sentences, but I will do my best. I had the unique pleasure to experience first-hand an outstanding guidance, leadership, and encouragement in every aspect of the Ph.D. project. From a “peculiar” start in France amid the pandemic, to my move in the Netherlands, you have tirelessly provided me with enormous support in my endeavours. You taught me exactly what being a researcher is all about, and having you as role model will undeniably be pivotal for my career. It has been a pleasure learning from you, thank you so much.

I am also thankful to the The SPIrou Planet Search for Habitable worlds (SPLaSH) program funded by the French National Research Agency (ANR) under contract number ANR-18-CE31-0019, as well as the European Space Agency studentship funding scheme.

Many thanks should also go to the *SPIrou Legacy Survey consortium*, and in particular to Jean-Francois Donati, Claire Moutou, Pascal Fouqué, Xavier Bonfils, Andres Carmona, Eder Martioli, Etienne Artigau, and Neil Cook, for the fruitful advice on handling near-infrared spectropolarimetric data, ultimately improving my results. At the same time, I wish to extend my gratitude to the *Physique du Soleil, des Etoiles et des Exoplanètes* research group at IRAP, especially to Jérôme Ballot for patiently keeping track of my Ph.D. progress, and to Arturo Lopez Ariste and Philippe Mathias for the insightful discussions regarding data acquisition and reduction with the Neo-Narval instrument.

I would like to sincerely thank Theresa Lueftinger at ESTEC for introducing me to the *Ariel* consortium, as well as sub-working group leaders like Sudeshna Boro Saikia, Camilla Danielski and Giuseppina Micela for being firm supporters of a future project. Many thanks to Ana Heras and Colin Wilson for making me take part of the local organising committee of ESLAB-55 at ESTEC, as I definitely learnt a lot about the “backstage” of conferences. I am also particularly grateful to Aline Vidotto at the University of Leiden and Harish Vedantham at ASTRON for giving me the opportunity to visit and network with their research groups, fostering new collaborations and making my work branch out in different fields.

A special *merci* goes to all the Ph.D. students, interns, and post-docs at IRAP with whom I spent hilarious and unforgettable moments, from chaotic discussions during lunch breaks, to matches of petanque and tarot, to the organisation of the PhD day, and to wonderful picnics in the Jardin de Plantes. Very big thanks go to Bonnie, Paul, Marjorie, Jean-Sebastien, Alix, Joey, Benjamin, Anthony, Thea, Gregoire, Lisa, Maitrayee, Florian, Baptiste, Louise, Benjamin, Merwan, Erwan, Veronika, and Nais. Despite a bumpy ride due to lockdown, I am glad we had special occasions to bond and become friends.

Studying in the Netherlands would not have been the same without the fleet of amazing research fellows and young graduate trainees that I had the pleasure to meet. Thank you for the “sesh”, the bouldering evenings, the trip to Texel, the game nights, the borrels at ESCAPE and all the fun activities I participated to. Enormous thanks go especially to the ESTEC unicorns: Max, Jess, Ricky, Sam, Victor, Sarah, Rach, Ryan, Thomas, Ines, Laura, Sophie, Oli, Lisaanne, Eleni, Chris, Willi, Csilla, Diane, Guada, Mayssa, Katja, Francois, Anne, Charlotte, and Sascha. Although I spent a little more than a year at ESTEC, I will treasure our friendship.

While attending conferences, workshops, seminars and summer schools, I had the pleasure to meet fantastic people that made these event memorable. Massive thanks to Billy, Amy, Chris, Andrew and the crew in Les Houches for the hilarious climbing adventures, all the memes, and the unanswered philosophical questions. Same goes to Thomas, Nico and the Leuven Ph.D. team, with whom I spent awesome nights singing karaoke, tasting korean barbecue or attending a baseball match in Busan, South Korea. A special thanks also to Pia, as I could not stop laughing for the entire workshop in Roscoff and then the CoolStars conference in Toulouse. I just have one question for you: does your family laugh?

A big thanks goes to my fellow astronomers from the MSc studies in Copenhagen. Thanks Isabelle for the “therapy” zoom sessions we had during the pandemic, we definitely needed them, and thanks Francisco for not making me lose all my money in Las Vegas, it was a blast to meet you there.

Un ringraziamento speciale va alla mia famiglia estesa. Grazie di cuore alle mie tre donzelle Cami, Faby ed Ila, con cui condivido avventure e ricordi ormai da quindici strepitosi anni. Fare la lista di ricordi felici con voi sarebbe quasi sminuente, poiché siete un caposaldo della mia vita.

Infine, ma di sicuro non meno importante, ringrazio infinitamente la mia famiglia, mamma, papà, Nisi, Tigro, Gabri e Dina. La vostra costante presenza ed il vostro incondizionato supporto in tutti questi anni di sfide e cambiamenti é stato, é, e sarà il cuore pulsante della mia ambizione a raggiungere le stelle. Questa tesi é dedicata a voi.

Foreword

With the first confirmed discovery of a planet around a solar-like star by Michel Mayor and Didier Queloz in 1995, a new field of research called exoplanetology was begun. After almost thirty years, the field has grown exponentially, and especially thanks to its high degree of interdisciplinarity, making it unique among astronomy domains. Naturally, one of the key questions that powered such growth and interest has been whether there is life in the universe besides Earth. The first step toward this goal is to find as many planets as possible, especially focusing on those that resemble our own Earth, i.e. small, rocky, with an atmosphere, and orbiting at the right distance from the host star to receive the right amount of irradiation to sustain life. The second step is to investigate the chemical composition of their atmosphere, and understand whether specific signatures can be explained by biological processes.

Currently, more than 5000 planets have been announced. They were primarily detected with indirect methods such as transit, i.e. the temporary eclipse induced by the planet on its parent star, and radial velocity, i.e. the measurement of the stellar motion along our line of sight. The ever-growing number of confirmed planets is correlated with significant advances in instrumentation, which pushed our sensitivity toward smaller and smaller planets over time. However, finding potentially-habitable, Earth-like planets is not a straightforward task, owing to the weak signals that they induce in both transits and radial velocity. Moreover, there are only a handful of such targets that are close enough to Earth for an efficient atmospheric characterisation.

An important aspect to consider is that most of the planet detection methods are *indirect*, i.e. what we measure is the influence of the planet on its host star, rather than direct observables. For this reason, we are susceptible to phenomena occurring on stars that do not relate to planets, so we must be capable of efficiently disentangling the two. Stellar activity is a well-known example of phenomenon posing a severe limitation, since it manifests a plethora of phenomena like granulation, flares, brightness inhomogeneities (e.g., spots, faculae, and plages), and cycles, all acting with distinct time scales and spatial scales. The origin of most of these phenomena resides in the magnetic field of the star, which is powered by dynamo processes. A thorough understanding stellar activity and the underlying magnetic field is therefore a crucial task to discern genuine planetary signatures.

M dwarfs are favourable targets when searching for small worlds. The lower mass and radius compared to earlier stellar types makes the effect of planetary companions stronger, and the frequency of small planets is expected to be higher. However, M dwarfs are efficient at being magnetically active, an aspect that excluded them from early exoplanet surveys. Indeed, their high activity levels translate into noise that can drown a genuine planetary signal, preventing a reliable detection, and into hazardous space environments in which planets are embedded, affecting their habitability. These aspects motivate detailed studies of stellar activity and of the underlying magnetic field, as well as the development of efficient filtering techniques whose goal is to mitigate and ideally remove completely the activity-induced contamination.

My Ph.D. thesis fits within this picture, since I used high-resolution spectropolarimetric data sets collected in the optical domain with Narval and ESPaDOnS and in the near-infrared with SPIRou, in order to extend our knowledge on stellar magnetic activity further. I used data sets of well-known, very active M dwarfs in order to design a new activity-filtering technique based on a smart selection of spectral lines, which are less sensitive to sources of noise. Such technique has a high degree of flexibility, since it could be easily adapted to different stars and spectroscopic data sets, and does not require a complicated machinery. I also reconstructed brightness maps of an active M dwarf (V374 Peg) to connect

the choice of spectral lines that are more suitable for precise radial velocity measurements with the underlying physics at the stellar surface. I also exploited the full capabilities of spectropolarimetry, which is the most effective technique to study stellar magnetic fields, as it relies on the Zeeman effect, i.e. the splitting of spectral lines in distinct components characterised by specific polarisation properties. In practice, I studied the long-term behaviour of the large-scale magnetic field at the surface of active M dwarfs with distinct approaches, among which tomographic inversion (i.e. Zeeman Doppler Imaging) of time series of circularly polarised spectra, and searched for secular evolution.

Avant-propos

Avec la première découverte d'une planète autour une étoile du type Solaire par Michel Mayor et Didier Queloz en 1995, un nouveau domaine de recherche appelé exoplanétologie a vu le jour. Après presque trente ans, ce domaine a connu une croissance exponentielle, notamment grâce à son haut degré d'interdisciplinarité, ce qui le rend unique parmi les domaines de l'astronomie. Naturellement, l'une des questions clés qui a alimenté une telle croissance et un tel intérêt a été de savoir s'il existe de la vie dans l'univers ailleurs que sur la Terre. La première étape pour atteindre cet objectif est de trouver autant de planètes que possible, en se concentrant sur celles qui ressemblent à la Terre, c'est-à-dire petites, rocheuses, avec une atmosphère, et orbitant à la bonne distance de l'étoile hôte pour recevoir la bonne quantité d'irradiation pour entretenir la vie. La deuxième étape consiste à étudier la composition chimique de leur atmosphère, et à comprendre si des signatures spécifiques peuvent être expliquées par des processus biologiques.

Actuellement, plus de 5000 planètes ont été annoncées. Elles ont été principalement détectées par des méthodes indirectes telles que le transit, c'est-à-dire l'éclipse temporaire induite par la planète sur son étoile hôte, et la vitesse radiale, c'est-à-dire la mesure du mouvement stellaire le long de notre ligne de visée. Le nombre toujours croissant de planètes confirmées est corrélé aux progrès significatifs de l'instrumentation, qui ont poussé notre sensibilité vers des planètes de plus en plus petites au fil du temps. Cependant, trouver des planètes potentiellement habitables, semblables à la Terre, n'est pas une tâche aisée, en raison des faibles signaux qu'elles induisent à la fois dans les transits et la vitesse radiale. De plus, il n'existe qu'une poignée de ces cibles qui sont suffisamment proches de la Terre pour permettre une caractérisation atmosphérique efficace.

Un aspect important à considérer est que la plupart des méthodes de détection de planètes sont indirectes, c'est-à-dire que ce que nous mesurons est l'influence de la planète sur son étoile hôte, plutôt que des observables directes. Pour cette raison, nous sommes sensibles à des phénomènes qui se produisent sur les étoiles et qui ne concernent pas les planètes, nous devons donc être capables de démêler efficacement les deux. L'activité stellaire est un exemple bien connu de phénomène posant une limite sévère, puisqu'elle se manifeste par une pléthore de phénomènes tels que la granulation, les éruptions, les inhomogénéités de luminosité (par exemple, les taches, les facules et les plages), et les cycles, tous agissant avec des échelles de temps et des échelles spatiales distinctes. L'origine de la plupart de ces phénomènes réside dans le champ magnétique de l'étoile, qui est alimenté par des processus de dynamo. Une compréhension approfondie de l'activité stellaire et du champ magnétique sous-jacent est donc une tâche cruciale pour discerner les véritables signatures planétaires.

Les naines M sont des cibles favorables pour la recherche de petits mondes. La masse et le rayon plus faibles par rapport aux autres types stellaires rendent l'effet des compagnons planétaires plus fort, et l'on s'attend à une fréquence plus élevée des petites planètes. Cependant, les naines M sont efficaces pour être magnétiquement actives, un aspect qui les a exclues des premières relevés systématiques. En effet, leurs hauts niveaux d'activité se traduisent par un bruit qui peut noyer un signal planétaire, empêchant une détection fiable, ainsi que par des environnements spatiaux dangereux dans lesquels les planètes sont plongées, affectant leur habitabilité. Ces aspects motivent des études détaillées de l'activité stellaire et du champ magnétique sous-jacent, ainsi que le développement de techniques de filtrage efficaces dont le but est d'atténuer et idéalement d'éliminer complètement la contamination induite par l'activité.

Ma thèse de doctorat s'inscrit dans ce cadre, puisque j'ai utilisé des jeux de données spectropolarimétriques à haute résolution collectés dans le domaine optique avec Narval et ESPaDO nS et dans le proche infrarouge avec SPIRou, afin d'étendre encore nos connaissances sur l'activité magnétique stellaire. J'ai utilisé des jeux de données de naines M bien connues et très actives afin de concevoir une nouvelle technique de filtrage de l'activité basée sur une sélection intelligente de raies spectrales, qui sont moins sensibles aux sources de bruit. Cette technique a un haut degré de flexibilité, puisqu'elle peut être facilement adaptée à différentes étoiles et à différents ensembles de données spectroscopiques, et peut facilement être mise en oeuvre. J'ai exploité toutes les capacités de la spectropolarimétrie, qui est la technique la plus efficace pour étudier les champs magnétiques stellaires, car elle repose sur l'effet Zeeman, c'est-à-dire la division des lignes spectrales en composantes distinctes caractérisées par des propriétés de polarisation spécifiques. En pratique, j'ai étudié le comportement à long terme du champ magnétique à grande échelle à la surface des naines M actives avec des approches distinctes, parmi lesquelles l'inversion tomographique (c'est-à-dire l'imagerie Zeeman-Doppler) de séries temporelles de spectres polarisés circulairement, et j'ai cherché une évolution séculaire, de manière analogue au cycle magnétique solaire.

Chapter 1

Overview on exoplanets

In this introductory Chapter, I contextualize my doctoral project with respect to one of the current focus of exoplanetary sciences: searching and characterising habitable Earth-mass planets around low-mass stars. I start by summarising the current status of exoplanet discoveries and the future goals of the field. Given its central role in this work, I describe the principles of the radial velocity method in further detail, as well as the serious challenges posed by the host star, acting as an obstacle to reliable detections and precise characterisation. Finally, I review the filtering techniques developed by the community to mitigate the stellar contamination. Extensive information on the topics referred here can be found in the [Exoplanet Science Strategy \(2018\)](#) and [Perryman \(2018\)](#).

1.1 State of the art

Historically, the first announcement of a planetary companion was by [Campbell et al. \(1988\)](#) around the K giant γ Cep A using the radial velocity (RV) method, but it was recognised only later by [Hatzes et al. \(2003\)](#). [Latham et al. \(1989\)](#) claimed the existence of a companion orbiting the F9 dwarf HD 114762, but the nature of such object (whether a planet or brown dwarf) could not be constrained precisely due to its large mass ($11 M_{\text{Jup}}$) and orbital eccentricity. This object was then established to be an M dwarf by astrometric measurements with *Gaia* ([Kiefer 2019](#)). Other examples of discoveries that were confirmed only later are ε Eri b and β Gem b ([Campbell et al. 1988](#); [Hatzes et al. 2006](#)). Finally, two $4-M_{\oplus}$ planets were detected by [Wolszczan & Frail \(1992\)](#) around the pulsar PSR 1257+12 using the timing method, i.e. the by monitoring the occurrence of the pulse arrival time, and then a third moon-like world was also found ([Wolszczan 1994](#)).

The first discovery of an exoplanet around a main sequence star occurred in 1995, at the Haute-Provence Observatory, France. [Mayor & Queloz \(1995\)](#) analysed RV observations of the solar-like star 51 Peg performed with the ELODIE spectrograph ([Baranne et al. 1996](#)) and announced the existence of a $0.5 M_{\text{Jup}}$ planet on a 4.2-d orbit (0.05 au). Such a small separation from the host star was discordant with planet formation theories, mainly based on Solar System knowledge, which predicted an in-situ generation. Planetary migration scenarios had to be developed in order to explain the presence of these so-called “hot Jupiters”, for which the planet formed away from the star where there is sufficient building material in the protoplanetary disk and then moved towards the star via dynamical interactions ([Alibert et al. 2005](#)).

More generally, the discovery of 51 Peg b set the basis for another branch of astronomy called exoplanetology, a research field that has grown enormously in the past 30 years and witnessed the deployment of both ground- and space-based facilities with the aim to the search and characterise planets outside the Solar System. Since that discovery, we have witnessed an exponential increase of planet detections ([Mamajek 2016](#)). Currently, dedicated online databases such as the [NASA Exoplanet archive](#) and [exoplanet.eu](#) count more than 5000 confirmed objects, ranging from ultra hot (KELT-9 b; [Gaudi et al. 2017](#)), ultra cold (Kepler-167 e; [Rowe et al. 2014](#)), massive (π Men b; [Jones et al. 2002](#)), tiny (Kepler-

Figure 1.1: Parameter space of the current confirmed planet detections. Different methods probe different regions of this plot. We can appreciate how the transit and radial velocity methods are the most prolific techniques. It is known that the transit and radial velocity method are more sensitive to planets close to their host star and with larger radii and masses, respectively. Direct imaging finds massive planetary companions at large separations from the host more favourably. Data are taken from NASA Exoplanet Archive.

37 b; [Barclay et al. 2013](#)), puffy (Kepler 51 b,c,d; [Libby-Roberts et al. 2020](#)), and on highly eccentric orbits (HD 80606 b; [Naef et al. 2001](#)) worlds. The adopted detection methods are in principle distinct, but most rely on indirect measurements, i.e. they seek the indirect effect of the planet on its host star. In the following section, I highlight well-known detection methods and recall the planetary taxonomy along with statistical properties. The current planetary parameter space sampled by the different methods is shown in Fig. 1.1. Given the central role of the RV method for this thesis, it will be discussed in more detail in Sec.1.2.

1.1.1 Methods and instruments

Direct Imaging

Taking a picture of the surroundings of a star is the only direct way to determine whether it hosts one or more planetary companions (Fig. 1.2). The main challenge is indeed to discriminate between starlight and light emitted or reflected off a planet. For this reason, direct imaging is most sensitive to massive (more than $2 M_{\text{Jup}}$) planets at large separations (tens of au) from the parent star, because they would yield smaller planet-star brightness contrasts. Naturally, the most favourable targets are close-by stars because the planet would appear brighter and located at a larger projected separation. A powerful aspect of direct imaging is that, when combined with high-resolution spectroscopy, it enables the direct atmospheric characterisation of the planetary companions ([Currie et al. 2022](#)).

The first directly imaged planetary system was HR 8799 at 40 pc by [Marois et al. \(2008\)](#), who reported three young, self-luminous gas giants, i.e. still radiating light from gravitational contraction. A

Figure 1.2: Two examples of exoplanet detecting methods. Left: Direct image of the HR 8799 planetary system acquired at the Keck II telescope. Taken from [Marois et al. \(2010\)](#). Right: Sketch illustrating the transit method, i.e. the apparent dimming of the host starlight by the passage of a planet in front of the visible disk. Credit: NASA.

fourth self-luminous planet was discovered at a later stage ([Marois et al. 2010](#)). The observations were performed with the Keck-NIRC2 and Gemini-NIRI instruments ([McLean & Chaffee 2000](#)), which were sensitive to planet-star contrasts between $10^{-4} - 10^{-5}$.

The instrumentation is typically equipped with adaptive optics to correct for Earth's atmospheric turbulence and increase the spatial resolution. In addition, devices such as coronagraphs and starshades (in the future) can be used to block starlight. Improvements in coronagraphic technology and adaptive optics allowed instruments such as Spectro-Polarimetric High-Contrast Exoplanet Research (SPHERE, [Beuzit et al. 2008](#)) and Gemini Planet Imager (GPI, [Macintosh et al. 2014](#)) to reach planet-star contrasts of about 10^{-6} . However, it will be only with the advent of future ground-based facilities like ELT-EPIC ([Kasper et al. 2008](#)) or space-based observatories like *LUVUOIR-ECLIPS* ([Juanola-Parramon et al. 2019](#)) and *HabEx* ([Gaudi & HabEx Observatory Team 2020](#)) that we will reach a contrast sensitivity between $10^{-7} - 10^{-9}$. This is indeed the level required to catch the reflected light of an Earth analog that has cooled off after formation and is orbiting around, e.g., Proxima Centauri, which is situated at 1.3 pc from the Solar System (e.g., see Fig. 1 in [Bellotti et al. 2020](#)).

Transit

If a planet orbits across the stellar disk, the light coming from the star will dim temporarily and by an amount proportional to the square of the planetary radius (see Fig. 1.2). This phenomenon will repeat at the time scale of the planet orbital period, meaning that we observe successive starlight dips over time. Measuring the planetary radius from photometric transits is a key task to determine the density of the planet, whenever the mass is known, because it would allow us to infer the planetary composition at first order.

The probability to observe such transient phenomenon randomly is small, and depends on the ratio between the stellar radius and the orbital distance of the planetary companion. In other words, the closer the planet is to the host star, the higher the chance of transit. Moreover, assuming that the planetary orbit is coplanar to the stellar equator, the most favourable system geometry to observe transits is equator-on. In terms of observing strategy, longer temporal baselines give access to planets located at wider orbits from the host star.

The first detection was established by [Henry et al. \(2000\)](#) and [Charbonneau et al. \(2000\)](#) for the hot Jupiter HD 209458 b around a G0 dwarf, with a transit depth of 0.02 mag, even though the planet was known from the radial velocity method. In general, the signature of a hot Jupiter around a solar-like star is about 1%, whereas for an Earth twin is 0.01%. Accounting for the photometric accuracy needed for such measurements and the challenge posed by atmospheric turbulence over a nearly-continuous monitoring of the sky, the community decided to deploy space-based facilities. Noteworthy is the french satellite CoRoT ([Auvergne et al. 2009](#)), which showed the efficiency of searching for transits in space while implementing synergies with asteroseismology studies, as well as the *Kepler* ([Borucki et al. 2010](#)) and the Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite (*TESS*, [Ricker et al. 2015](#)). The contributions of

the latter missions to the exoplanet field have been particularly remarkable, with ~ 2500 and ~ 5000 candidate discoveries, respectively (Howell 2020; Kunimoto et al. 2022), which have to be confirmed by other methods. Ground-based projects like the Wide-Angle Search of Planets (WASP, Pollacco et al. 2006) and the Hungarian Automated Telescope Project (HAT-P, Bakos et al. 2002) have reported several planetary systems around bright stars as well, revealing a multitude of properties. In the future, the ESA mission Planetary Transits and Oscillations of Stars (*PLATO*, Rauer et al. 2014) will join the fleet of space-based facilities dedicated to hunting planetary transits.

Monitoring planetary transits allows us to study the architecture of the systems further. For instance, we can track the timing at which the transit occurs and seek for variations that would betray the presence of additional (perhaps non-transiting) companions. With this method, known as Transit Timing Variations (TTV), we constrain both the mass and the orbital distance of the potential companion. Furthermore, we can carry out emission spectroscopy when the planet is about to be occulted by the star and/or transmission spectroscopy when it passes in front of the star, in order to inspect the chemical composition of its atmosphere and eventually detect signatures of life. This is indeed one of the main goals of present and future missions such as James Webb Space Telescope (*JWST*, Gardner et al. 2006) and the Atmospheric Remote-Sensing Infrared Exoplanet Large-survey (*Ariel*, Tinetti et al. 2018).

Astrometry

The aim of astrometry is to measure the star's position in the plane of the sky (photocentre) and monitor whether it undergoes temporal variations. It relies on the same dynamical principle as the RV method, but the effects are sought in the plane of the sky, rather than along the line of sight (see Sec. 1.2). For this reason, massive planets are more favourably detected.

The first confirmed planet detected with astrometry was HD 176051 b (Muterspaugh et al. 2010), with a mass of $1.5 M_{\text{Jup}}$ and orbiting at 1.8 au. Today we count around 15 planets and/or sub-stellar companions detected with this method, which is not surprising given the required precision and extensive observational time for the measurements.

A displacement of roughly 10^{-7} arcsec of the photocentre would reveal the presence of a Earth-mass companion at 10 pc. Such precision is four orders of magnitude lower than what could be achieved with previous space missions like *Hipparcos* (Perryman et al. 1997), and is currently out of reach even for state-of-the-art missions like *Gaia* (Gaia Collaboration et al. 2016), that is sensitive to Jupiter-mass planets on a few au orbits around bright stars with visual magnitude smaller than 12.

Microlensing

Gravitational lensing is a phenomenon predicted by general relativity for which a distribution of mass interposed between the observer and a distant source bends the light coming from the latter and focuses it towards the observer. This way, the observer will see the light of the background source magnified several times. In the exoplanet context, the background source is a star and the intermediate object is either a free-floating planet or another star that can potentially host multiple planets. The light amplification effect could last for days, and a planet presence is observed as a temporary spike in the brightness of the background star.

Microlensing events are rare and require continuous monitoring of the sky. The first of such detections was OGLE-2003-BLG-235L b by Bond (2012). They are sensitive to planets at long separations from the host star, as well as planetary systems at kpc distances, but their characterisation is automatically unfeasible. Spatial missions involving microlensing surveys are, e.g., *Euclid* (Beaulieu et al. 2010) and *Nancy Grace Roman Space Telescope* (Yee 2013), both expected to yield more than 1000 planets at more than 1 au.

1.1.2 Planet taxonomy and trends

Owing to more than 5000 confirmed exoplanets, it is possible to perform a demographic exploration of their properties, classify them in different categories, and inform theories of planet formation and evolution. Table 1.1 summarises possible classifications based on fundamental features like planetary radius and mass.

Generally, we recognise giant planets by having their mass dominated ($>50\%$) by hydrogen and helium (Clanton & Gaudi 2014), analogously to Jupiter and Saturn. A specific sub-class of gas giants is the hot Jupiters, defined by their short orbital distances (≤ 0.1 au) and characterised by high irradiation levels compared to other classes (Gaudi 2005). These properties made hot Jupiters favourable detections during early exoplanetary campaigns, as their photometric or spectroscopic impact on the light of the host star is stronger. The ignition of deuterium thermonuclear fusion is expected to occur above approximately $13 M_{\text{Jup}}$, which defines a different family of objects known as brown dwarfs (Schneider 2018), even though this boundary is not strict and the distinction between the two objects is subtle (Chen & Kipping 2017).

Neptunian planets are smaller and analogous to the homonymous planet in the Solar System. Their bulk composition is either dominated by water or by a rocky core with heavy elements surrounded by a hydrogen/helium atmosphere (Owen & Wu 2017; Zeng et al. 2019). Super-Earths do not have a Solar System benchmark, hence there is more to discover and understand about these objects (Morbidelli & Raymond 2016). They are terrestrial planets in size between Earth and Neptune, with various atmospheres and compositions similar to Neptunes. It is worth mentioning two sub-classes of super-Earths: 1) close-in, tidally locked lava worlds with high levels of irradiation from the host star (Rouan et al. 2011; Hamano et al. 2013) and 2) ocean worlds formed beyond the snow line, i.e. the region of the protoplanetary disk delimiting where water ice can exist (Léger et al. 2004). It is important to stress that the boundaries in parameter space given in Table 1.1 are not sharp, because the understanding of the bulk composition of these planets is still limited (Turbet et al. 2020).

Terrestrial planets have sizes similar to Earth or smaller and are composed of silicate rocks and metals. We cannot discern exactly the ratio of the chemical components because models are degenerate when only radius and mass are known; we would need information on the atmosphere to break the ambiguity (Adams et al. 2008). The mass-radius diagram in Fig. 1.3 illustrates the dearth of terrestrial planets among the current discoveries, compared to the other classes. This highlights the biases of the detection methods and their limitations in terms of precise measurements, as large error bars like those shown do not allow us to constrain the bulk density.

Overall, this sets a precise goal towards which the community has to push. The search and atmospheric characterisation of exo-Earths is indeed a central focus of current exoplanetology, because they are primary targets for habitability investigations. Expanding the detections towards this planetary parameter space will yield relevant feedback for planet formation models.

The following list encompasses main features and trends of the aforementioned planetary classes that emerged from observational surveys (for a comprehensive description, see Exoplanet Science Strategy 2018; Perryman 2018):

- Planetary systems do not follow an individual relation on the mass-radius diagram, but feature intrinsic scatter. This is a manifestation of a rich diversity in formation, evolution, and structure (Petigura et al. 2018; Neil & Rogers 2020).
- Giant planets in close-in orbits are common around metal-rich stars (Fischer & Valenti 2005). Their occurrence rate for Sun-like stars was estimated by Cumming et al. (2008) to be $1.5 \pm 0.6\%$ and by Howard et al. (2012) to be $0.5 \pm 0.1\%$ using *Kepler* data. At larger orbital distances, warm and cold Jupiters feature an increased rate by at least one order of magnitude (Cumming et al. 2008; Bryan et al. 2016).
- Owing to a larger quantity of protoplanetary building blocks, massive planets are found more favourably around more massive stars (Pascucci et al. 2018; Fulton & Petigura 2018; Lozovsky

Figure 1.3: Mass-Radius diagram of exoplanets, showing the diversity of the planetary population discovered so far. The visible scarcity of planets around $5\text{--}10 R_{\oplus}$ is the *Fulton Gap* (Fulton & Petigura 2018), attributed to atmospheric evaporation due to high-irradiation stellar environments. Theoretical curves of pure-iron, rocky and ice planets are displayed (Seager et al. 2007), as well as hydrogen-dominated planets at 0.045 au from the host star and with an age of 0.3 Gyr and 1.0 Gyr (Fortney et al. 2007). Data are taken from the NASA Exoplanet Archive.

et al. 2021).

- Neptunes in close-in orbits ($<50\text{ d}$) are one order of magnitude more common than giants, and Super-Earths in $<100\text{ d}$ orbits are amongst the most common planet type around Solar-like stars (Howard et al. 2010; Mayor et al. 2011).
- The “Fulton gap” separates gas-rich giants from small planets that have a thin atmosphere or lack one. The origin of the gap is attributed to the high irradiation level which triggers atmospheric mass loss via photoevaporation (Fulton et al. 2017; Mordasini 2020). Alternatively, mass loss theories relying on the gradual cooling of the planetary core can reproduce the gap as well (Ginzburg et al. 2018; Gupta & Schlichting 2019).
- The occurrence rate of Earth-like exoplanets is highest around M dwarfs (Kopparapu 2013; Gaidos et al. 2016; Ment & Charbonneau 2023). This was estimated to be 2.5 ± 0.2 exoplanets with size $1\text{--}4 R_{\oplus}$ and $<200\text{ d}$ orbit per M dwarf by Dressing & Charbonneau (2015).

1.1.3 Habitability and future goals

A central goal of exoplanetology is to find Earth-like planets that potentially host life, hence it is necessary to set a planetary assessment framework based on precise and reliable definitions. From an insolation perspective, the concept of habitable zone has been introduced as the region around the host star

Table 1.1: Exoplanet taxonomy. The columns are: 1) typical nomenclature to describe the object, 2) radius interval according to [Borucki et al. \(2011\)](#), 3) mass interval according to [Stevens & Gaudi \(2013\)](#), 4) fraction of the total number of discoveries (based on the radius and computed from the NASA Archive database).

Class	Radius	Mass	Fraction
Gas giants	$6 R_{\oplus} - 15 R_{\oplus}$	$100 M_{\oplus} - 13 M_{\text{Jup}}$	18.4%
Neptunes	$2 R_{\oplus} - 6 R_{\oplus}$	$10 M_{\oplus} - 100 M_{\oplus}$	45.4%
Super-Earths	$1.25 R_{\oplus} - 2 R_{\oplus}$	$1 M_{\oplus} - 10 M_{\oplus}$	25.6%
Earths	$< 1.25 R_{\oplus}$	$0.1 M_{\oplus} - 1 M_{\oplus}$	10.6%

Figure 1.4: Definition of the habitable zone around stars of different spectral types. The blue region is where liquid water is supposedly found at the surface of telluric planets. Inside or outside this region the planetary temperature is too high or low to maintain such condition, respectively. Cooler and fainter stars have their habitable zone closer in to meet the requirement of surface liquid water. Taken from [Kasting et al. \(2014\)](#).

in which a telluric planet could maintain liquid water on its surface, as illustrated in Fig. 1.4 ([Kasting et al. 1993](#); [Kopparapu 2013](#)), and it is dictated by our knowledge of life on Earth ([Cockell et al. 2016](#)). As described in [Kopparapu \(2013\)](#), the first inner edge of the habitable zone is determined by the runaway greenhouse limit, at which oceans evaporate completely (0.97 au for an Earth-like planet around a Sun-like star), and the second inner edge by the moist greenhouse limit, for which the water vapor content in the atmosphere is increased substantially (0.99 au). The outer edge is given by the maximum greenhouse limit, where greenhouse gases dominate (1.7 au). As an example, Proxima Centauri b is a potentially habitable planet following the previous definition ([Turbet et al. 2016](#)). However, additional variables such as the presence of volcanic and tectonic activity, large-scale magnetic fields, distribution of oceans, asteroid impacts, and the presence of stellar companions are key to obtain a comprehensive definition of habitability ([Lenardic et al. 2016](#); [Driscoll & Bercovici 2013](#); [Jaime et al. 2014](#); [Soto 2017](#); [Childs et al. 2022](#)). The interstellar environment in which planets are embedded also plays a fundamental role on habitability. High-energy radiation in the X-ray and UV impinging on the planet in the form of stellar wind can drive atmospheric erosion and alter its chemical constituents ([Lammer et al. 2003](#); [Owen & Jackson 2012](#); [Rugheimer et al. 2015](#)). In this context, a planetary magnetosphere would act as a shield against these hazardous environments ([Vidotto et al. 2013](#); [See et al. 2014](#)).

Figure 1.5: Illustration of distinct mechanisms that originate false-positives for O_2 as a biomarker. To discriminate false-positive mechanisms, the circled should be detected, and the forbidden molecules should not be detected. For instance, on a desiccated CO_2 -rich planet around an M dwarf, the presence of CO and CO_2 and the absence of H_2O is a strong indicator of a photochemical source of O_2 induced by photolysis of CO_2 . This shows how biosignature interpretation requires a suite of observations rather than the detection of a single molecule. Taken from [Meadows et al. \(2018\)](#).

In parallel, a biosignature is defined as an impact of life on a planetary scale that may be detected at interstellar distances ([Schwieterman et al. 2018](#)), but identifying reliable molecules that would unambiguously confirm the presence of life is not a straightforward task (see Fig. 1.5). The presence of O_2 (or O_3) and CH_4 in transmission spectra has been interpreted as clear indicator of life because it represents an atmosphere out of chemical equilibrium. This may be misleading however, since recent studies have established plausible abiotic mechanisms, like photochemistry and atmospheric escape, that could lead to false positives ([Domagal-Goldman et al. 2014](#); [Schwieterman et al. 2016](#); [Meadows 2017](#)). Support for upcoming observations in this direction will necessarily see the interdisciplinary coordination between astrobiology, exoplanetology, and planetary science communities, in order to fully understand the significance of a potential biosignature and eventually identify new ones.

Naturally, there are many unanswered questions that exoplanetology has to face and that are stressed by the planetary census now available. For example, *is the Solar System commonplace? How does it compare to other systems? What are exoplanets made of? What are unambiguous biosignatures?* Indeed, we want to understand planets as astronomical objects (their formation, dynamics, evolution) and characterise their environments (i.e., atmospheres, habitability, biosignatures).

Addressing these key questions will require a step-by-step process involving a synergistic effort by the exoplanet community, as well as a parallel and progressive refinement of observational technology. Maximising the yield of dedicated programs will naturally see a reciprocal feedback between space-based missions and ground-based follow-ups. As an example, the ongoing *TESS* space mission has already provided numerous interesting targets, whose ground-based RV monitoring gave access to the planetary mass (see Sec. 1.2) and consequently to the bulk density. This enabled a tailored target selection for short- and mid-term space-based missions, i.e. *JWST* and *Ariel* respectively, which aim at exploring the chemical variety of exoplanets' atmospheres, from terrestrial-size to gas giants. On the long-term, all this work will pave the scientific track for the deployment of both ground-based facilities

(ELT, [Udry et al. 2014](#); GMT, [Johns et al. 2012](#); TMT, [Skidmore et al. 2015](#)) and space-based missions (*LUVOIR*, [The LUVOIR Team 2019](#); *Habex*, [Gaudi & HabEx Observatory Team 2020](#)).

In the meantime, the RV method will likely continue to be the primary technique for confirming planetary candidates and estimating their mass, an aspect that requires understanding and correcting all sources of noise, whether astronomical or instrumental, that can prevent a reliable measurement. The community has already initiated projects and efforts towards this goal, as it will be outlined in [Sec. 1.4](#).

1.2 Radial velocity method

The radial velocity technique, also known as Doppler spectroscopy, has been one of the most prolific hunting techniques in exoplanetary sciences, accounting for 19% of current confirmed discoveries¹. With this method, we can estimate the planetary mass or its lower limit in case the orbital inclination (i.e., the angle between the orbital plane and the plane of the sky) is unknown. Together with the planetary radius, a mass estimate is necessary to determine the bulk density, and understand the internal composition of the planet to a first order. The RV method is also useful to confirm planetary candidates discovered with the transit method. For these reasons, transit observations are often complemented by RV follow-ups (or vice-versa).

The physics underlying this technique is the following: when a planet orbits a star, the latter is subject to a gravitational pull with respect to the barycentre of the system, causing a stellar reflex motion. Because of this dynamic effect, the lines of the star's spectrum experience periodic Doppler shifts, depending on whether the star is approaching the observer (blueshift) or receding from it (redshift), as illustrated in [Fig. 1.6](#). In wavelength units, the displacement is quantified as

$$\Delta\lambda = \lambda_{\text{obs}} - \lambda_{\text{rest}}, \quad (1.1)$$

where λ_{obs} and λ_{rest} represent the wavelength in the observer and stellar reference frames, respectively (see [Perryman 2018](#)). The RV is then the component of the star's motion along the line of sight, and can be estimated from the Doppler shift as

$$\text{RV} \simeq c \frac{\Delta\lambda}{\lambda_{\text{rest}}}, \quad (1.2)$$

with c the speed of light and the symbol \simeq because relativistic effects have been neglected. Measuring the wavelength shift by means of precise spectrographs is therefore equivalent to measuring the RV. The job of an exoplanet hunter consists in collecting several spectra of the star over months or years, assemble a corresponding time series of RV measurements, and analyze its temporal behavior ([Fig. 1.7](#)).

If a star is orbited only by one planet, then the temporal behaviour can be modelled by a periodic signal of the form

$$\text{RV} = K(\cos(\omega + \nu) + e \cos(\omega)), \quad (1.3)$$

where ω is the argument of pericentre, ν the true anomaly and e the eccentricity. The semi-amplitude (K) encapsulates important dynamical information of the system

$$K = \left(\frac{2\pi G}{P_{\text{orb}}} \right)^{1/3} \frac{M_p \sin i_p}{(M_p + M_s)^{2/3}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - e^2}}, \quad (1.4)$$

where G is the gravitational constant, P_{orb} is the orbital period, i_p the orbital inclination, M_p the planet mass, and M_s the stellar mass. In most cases the orbital inclination is not known, hence only an estimate of the minimum mass $M_p \sin i_p$ can be obtained.

For known transiting planets, we can use velocimetric follow-up observations to estimate the planetary orbital inclination via the Rossiter-McLaughlin effect ([Rossiter 1924](#); [McLaughlin 1924](#)). In fact, as the planet crosses the stellar disk, it occults the approaching (blueshifted) and receding (redshifted)

¹www.exoplanet.eu

Figure 1.6: Principle of the RV method. The planet exerts a gravitational tug on the star, making it orbit around the common barycentre. The stellar motion translates in periodic Doppler shifts of the lines in the stellar spectrum. When the star approaches the observer, the lines are blueshifted, whereas when it recedes, the lines are redshifted.

hemispheres at different times, producing a periodic distortion of the spectral lines. Ultimately, we obtain an RV signal whose symmetry depends on the sky-projected orbital inclination: the more the orbital plane is misaligned with the stellar rotation axis, the larger the asymmetry is (e.g., [Ohta et al. 2005](#); [Fabrycky & Winn 2009](#)). The Rossiter-McLaughlin effect relies on the projected rotational velocity of the star, hence it would not work for a star seen pole-on with a significant rotation.

With Eq. 1.4, we realize that massive planets in short orbits yield large RV semi-amplitudes and are detected more favourably as a consequence. For instance, a Jupiter-mass planet on a 1 au orbit around a $1 M_{\odot}$ star corresponds to a semi-amplitude of 30 m s^{-1} , while an Earth-mass planet at the same distance to 10 cm s^{-1} . In turn, a signal of 10 cm s^{-1} at 550 nm corresponds to a wavelength shift on the order of 10^{-7} nm (from Eq. 1.2), which cannot be measured directly from a single spectral line since the signal-to-noise ratio (S/N) would be insufficient.

Increasing the S/N requires the use of numerical techniques that combine the displacement information of several spectral lines, such as cross correlation ([Baranne et al. 1996](#); [Pepe et al. 2002](#)), Least-Squares Deconvolution (LSD, [Donati et al. 1997](#); [Kochukhov et al. 2010](#)) and least-squares template matching (e.g., [Anglada-Escudé & Butler 2012](#); [Astudillo-Defru et al. 2015](#)). The latter compares each observed spectrum with a master spectrum template computed empirically, i.e. from the observations themselves. The template has a high S/N and a richer RV content than a synthetic spectrum with a lower number of absorption lines, thus providing precise RV data sets. With cross-correlation, the observed spectrum is slid smoothly relative to a template spectrum in order to build the cross-

Figure 1.7: Radial velocity measurements of 51 Peg, with planetary signal fit of the hot Jupiter 51 Peg b. Taken from [Mayor & Queloz \(1995\)](#).

Figure 1.8: Planetary mass as a function of the year of discovery with the RV method. As more precise instruments are built and m s^{-1} sensitivities are reached, the lower limit of detectable planetary mass is diminished, thus increasing the number of low-mass planet detections. The mass of Jupiter, Neptune and the Earth are shown. Source: NASA Exoplanet Archive.

correlation function (CCF), which will peak when the spectrum and the template align best. The CCF symbolises an average, high S/N line profile and summarizes the features of all the observed spectral line profiles. The template can be either a master spectrum ([Astudillo-Defru et al. 2015](#)) or a synthetic line list, i.e. a Dirac comb replicating the arrangement of the stellar lines (in the stellar reference frame)

over a specific spectral range. Finally, LSD returns a high-S/N mean line profile in an analogous manner to cross-correlation, under the assumption that the observed spectrum is the convolution between such mean line profile and a line list (see Sec. 2.2). The output mean profile in this case is cleaned from line blends (Kochukhov et al. 2010). An important benefit of using cross correlation and LSD compared to template matching is the possibility to compute activity indicators, i.e. proxies to investigate the presence of stellar surface inhomogeneities which make our RV time series deviate from the model in Eq. 1.3, as it will be outlined in Sec. 1.3.

The mean line profile resulting from the numerical techniques is fitted with a Gaussian or Voigt function and the RV measurement is derived as the centroid of the fit. The precision with which we measure such centroid determines our capability to detect a small planet (perhaps Earth-like) orbiting around the star. Achieving a high level of precision requires sophisticated instruments, as there are several aspects to take into account: changes in the refraction index of air, thermal and mechanical effects, inaccurate wavelength calibration, and slit illumination are some examples of phenomena that can induce 10 to 100 m s⁻¹ variations (Lovis & Fischer 2010). Over time, spectrograph technology has tackled these problems efficiently, reaching a precision of a few dozens of cm s⁻¹ in the optical domain (ESPRESSO, Suárez Mascareño et al. 2020; EXPRESS Petersburg et al. 2020 and NEID Schwab et al. 2016), against an initial 15 m s⁻¹ level (e.g. ELODIE, Baranne et al. 1996). This steady improvement is reflected in a larger number of low-mass planet detections, as shown in Fig. 1.8, and has opened an uncharted planetary population. As the RV sensitivity of state-of-the-art spectrographs reaches sub-m/s levels, the main issue to reliably detect exoplanets and estimate precise masses is dictated by stellar activity, as described in the next section.

1.3 Stellar activity

By definition, the most prolific techniques to detect exoplanets are indirect, i.e. what we measure is the planet influence on starlight over time, instead of planetary observables. A successful detection and characterisation of exoplanets requires reliable disentangling of the various causes of such starlight variability. The natural implication is that the better we know stars, the better we can study exoplanets.

As instruments with an ever-improving precision are developed, we have become sensitive to signals of stellar origin that represent a serious limitation to our detection goals. They are generated by various surface features and phenomena collectively known as “stellar activity”, which are mostly related to the stellar magnetic field powered by dynamo action. A detailed study of these fields is therefore necessary to understand the mechanisms that originate activity, as explained in Chapter 4.

Signatures of stellar activity at optical and near-infrared wavelengths originate from the photosphere and chromosphere (see Fig. 1.9). The former is the bottom layer of the stellar atmosphere and features an effective temperature of 5772 K (Mamajek et al. 2015), while the latter sees both a temperature minimum at a height of 500 km, and a steep rise around 2000 km (Hall 2008). Beyond the chromosphere there is the corona, which extends out into space and is the hottest ($\sim 10^6$ K) part of the stellar atmosphere. The corona is observed mostly at X-rays and radio wavelengths (White 1999). X-rays are due to collisionally-excited ions and provide information on density and structural complexity, while radio emission is due to thermal bremsstrahlung or gyroresonance of free electrons and is sensitive to the coronal magnetic field.

Despite being particularly crucial for the RV method, the impact of stellar activity extends to photometric light curves, transmission spectroscopy (e.g., Rackham et al. 2018), and astrometric measurements as well (Sowmya et al. 2022). For radial velocities, stellar activity induces noise (called “jitter”) that can mask or mimic planetary companions (Queloz et al. 2001; Rajpaul et al. 2021). Taking the Sun as an example, if we imagine to observe it from as far as any other star and search for the Earth using the RV technique, its signal would be completely drowned by stellar activity, as shown in Fig. 1.10. This becomes particularly important considering that the Sun is relatively inactive, compared to other stars of similar spectral types. Therefore, an essential step towards the detecting small planets is to understand the temporal structure of the activity signals, as it is the main aspect with which we can unravel gen-

Figure 1.9: Images of the Sun in December 2022 for the flattened brightness (left), line of sight velocity (middle), and magnetic field (right) acquired with the Solar Dynamic Orbiter. Examples of visual stellar activity manifestations are photospheric inhomogeneities, like faculae and spots which are hotter and cooler than the rest of the surface, respectively. These are connected to the underlying magnetic field. At a higher spatial resolution, it is possible to see at the convective cells emerging at the surface and sinking back inside the star, in a phenomenon collectively known as granulation. Credit: NASA/SDO and the AIA, EVE, and HMI science teams.

uine planetary signatures. Here, I recall the classification of activity phenomena sorted by increasing time scale, and touching upon their contamination to RV time series, as illustrated in Fig. 1.11.

1.3.1 Phenomena over minutes and hours

Oscillations

Turbulent motions of plasma in the outer layers of stars with convective envelopes yield acoustic oscillations (called p- or pressure modes) that make the stellar surface wobble. These oscillations induce RV variations of tens of cm s^{-1} for a few minutes (Bouchy et al. 2005), and can be straightforwardly averaged out with a high-cadence observing strategy (e.g., three 10-min exposures each night, Dumusque et al. 2011). However, more caution is required when hunting planets around young (a few tens of Myr) or massive ($\sim 2M_{\odot}$) stars since the amplitude of the oscillations is intensified. The latter can reach km s^{-1} levels and become a more important noise source, like for the A6V star β Pictoris (Mékarnia et al. 2017; Lagrange et al. 2019).

Granulation

Studies of the solar surface revealed a granular pattern due to motions of convective cells: hot plasma rises to the surface from the interior, cools down and sinks back in because of the higher density relative to the surrounding. A convective cell is therefore approaching or receding the observer, generating a blueshift or redshift of the emitted light, respectively. The vertical flow velocity of a single convective cell ranges between 1 and 4 km s^{-1} . However, when the 10^6 cells on the visible solar disk are taken into account, the RV effect averages out to dozens of m s^{-1} because of cancellation between upflow and downflow (Gray 2005; Cegla et al. 2019). The size of the granular structure ranges from a few Mm to 40 Mm (supergranulation) and correlates with their lifetime: 10 min for the smallest structures and up to 36 hr for the largest ones (Roudier et al. 1998; Del Moro 2004; Hall 2008). Scaling relations (Guo et al. 2022) and informed observing strategies (Dumusque et al. 2011) can then be applied to mitigate the noise induce by this phenomenon.

Moreover, there is an imbalance between the number of photons coming from the hot (bright) material relative to the cold (dark) one, which results in a net blueshift of the spectral lines. This phenomenon, known as “convective blueshift” and estimated to be around 200 m s^{-1} for the Sun (Meunier

Figure 1.10: Radial velocity time series of the Sun spanning between 2015 and 2018, taken with HARPS-N at Telescopio Nazionale Galileo in La Palma, Spain (Collier Cameron et al. 2019). The Earth signal is superimposed as a red line for the same time span. Even for a low activity star like the Sun, the amplitude of the Earth’s signal is drowned by the activity jitter, the latter being one order of magnitude larger.

Figure 1.11: Activity phenomena sorted by their time scales and RV contribution. The RV amplitude induced by Jupiter, Neptune and Earth is also shown. From the left, credit of the images goes to: G. Pérez (SMM/IAC), Swedish 1-m Solar Telescope/CHROMIS (L. Rouppe), NASA/SDO, Swedish 1-m Solar Telescope/CHROMIS (L. Rouppe and S. Jafarzadeh, J. de la Cruz Rodríguez), NASA/Goddard Space Flight Center Scientific Visualization Studio - HAO & NSO PSPT project team, Hinode XRT.

et al. 2010), translates in an asymmetry of the spectral line profile. The line bisector, i.e. the locus of me-

dian points dividing the profile into two halves of equal equivalent width (Perryman 2018), represents an important tool to determine the granulation velocities and thus the star’s activity. We will discuss this further in Sec. 1.4.1 in the context of activity diagnostics.

Flares

Flares are impulsive eruptions associated to the release of magnetic energy accumulated in active regions (Hathaway 2010). They lead to a sharp increase in brightness within few minutes followed by a slower decay with a timescale on the order of hours (Pettersen 1989). They have been detected for cool, main-sequence stars via $H\alpha$ emission (Reiners 2009; Medina et al. 2020) and represent a primary concern for the habitability of planets orbiting active stars (e.g., Günther 2021; Ramsay et al. 2021). In terms of RV contamination, they produce spurious outliers that fall tens or hundreds of m s^{-1} away with respect to the bulk of the RV times series.

1.3.2 Phenomena over days

Spots

The surface features on the Sun have been scrutinised extensively, given the accessible spatial resolution. Studies revealed that active regions originate from the emergence of magnetic flux tubes above the photosphere (Schüssler 2002). The magnetic fields at the emergence location can be intense enough to quench convective motions and inhibit the energy transport, giving origin to cool and dark regions called spots (Schrijver & Zwaan 2000; Strassmeier 2009). Moreover, from the pioneering study of Hale et al. (1919), we know that spots emerge at low latitudes and in pairs, with opposite magnetic polarities. The leading polarity is reversed between the two hemispheres and switch polarity over consecutive magnetic cycles (see Chapter 4). In general, starspots can be between 500 and 2000 K colder than the quiet photosphere for later and earlier spectral types than the Sun, respectively, and correspond to local fields on the order of kG (Berdyugina 2005). A comprehensive review on the properties and physics associated with sunspots and starspots can be found in Berdyugina (2005) and Strassmeier (2009).

Spots are a notorious source of variability in photometric, spectroscopic and spectropolarimetric time series. The balance in the emitted flux between the approaching stellar hemisphere (blueshifted) and the receding one (redshifted) is in fact broken by the presence of a dark spot on the surface. As the spot crosses the visible disk, it stops part of the starlight and produces distortions in the profile of spectral lines, which translates into spurious Doppler shifts modulated at the stellar rotation period (Saar & Donahue 1997). These surface inhomogeneities last between few days and several rotation cycles (Hussain 2002), and in proportion to their size and the star’s spectral type (Berdyugina 2005; Giles et al. 2017), and contaminate light curve or RV data sets for as much time (Robertson et al. 2020).

On the Sun, RV variations are at most a few m s^{-1} (Lagrange et al. 2010), but they can reach up to km s^{-1} levels in the most active stars (e.g., T Tauri stars, Donati et al. 2016). Therefore, a spotted stellar surface threatens the success of RV searches because the associated signal can either drown the planetary signal or mimic its temporal behaviour (e.g., Huélamo et al. 2008; Huerta et al. 2008). For this reason exoplanet surveys targeted moderately active or quiet stars, for which about a dozen of m s^{-1} is generated by activity (e.g., Bellotti & Korhonen 2021). Spots represent an important source of contamination also in transmission spectroscopy: when unocculted, they prevent the correct retrieval of the planetary radius (Pont et al. 2008), or affect the transit depth with at least the same order of magnitude as transiting exoplanets, emulating the presence of specific chemical species like H_2O (Rackham et al. 2018). This is of crucial relevance in light of future dedicated missions like *Ariel*.

Faculae and plages

The emergence of narrow magnetic flux tubes gives origin also to bright photospheric and chromospheric features called faculae and plages, respectively, which are best observed at the solar limb (Schrijver & Zwaan 2000). They can be 300 to 500 K hotter than the photosphere (Topka et al. 1997) and, al-

though they can appear separately from spots and clump to form a larger feature, they tend to surround spots. Depending on whether they are isolated or clumped in groups, their duration spans between hours or days (Hirayama 1978; Solanki 1993).

As for spots, the intense magnetic field present in faculae inhibits the convective motions of the plasma with consequent suppression of the blueshift arising from granulation, resulting in a RV contamination of a few m s^{-1} (Meunier et al. 2010; Miklos et al. 2020). In principle, an equal amount of faculae and spots could balance their RV contribution out, but Radick et al. (1998) and Reinhold et al. (2019) demonstrated that active stars can be either faculae- or spot-dominated depending on the spectral type, age and activity level. For instance, faculae are the most importance source of noise in slow-rotating, low-activity, older stars, whereas spots cover a larger fraction of the surface for cool, more active stars (M-type especially). Finally, faculae are also a source of uncertainty in the radius determination of exoplanets with the transit method (Guenther 2022).

1.3.3 Phenomena over years

Magnetic cycles

Nearly periodic variations of a star's activity level are collectively known as magnetic cycles. First evidence of such phenomenon for the Sun is attributed to Schwabe (1844), who monitored the number of sunspots on the visible disk and discovered an 11-yr modulation. In the context of exoplanets searches, magnetic cycles modulate the distribution of dark and bright surface features, inducing spurious RV variations of tenths of m s^{-1} . This emulates the presence of a long-period Jupiter-mass companion or hinder the detection of a short-period low-mass planet when the observational sampling is not ideal (Lovis et al. 2011). Moreover, as the activity maximum is approached, the occurrence of energetic events such as flares, prominences and coronal mass ejections increase. Magnetic cycles are of central focus for this thesis and will be discussed in more detail in Chapter 4.

1.4 Filtering stellar activity

Radial velocity measurements are blind to the origin of the temporal variations, since Doppler shifts are induced by both displacements and distortions of the spectral lines. In fact, the combination of thousands of spectral lines when applying cross-correlation or Least-Squares Deconvolution makes us sensitive to any physical phenomenon that may deform the lines. For this reason, the development and optimization of techniques aimed at filtering the effects of such distortions has become a crucial task to achieve the required velocimetric precision for small planet detections (Meunier 2021). Several numerical methods were developed over the years, with the key requirement to remove the RV contribution of stellar activity from the data sets while leaving the planetary signal intact. This is not a straightforward job, since modelling precisely stellar activity requires solid knowledge about the numerous processes involved and their stochastic nature. Moreover, inaccurate estimates of stellar parameters (e.g. rotation period due to differential rotation) or a restricted portability (e.g. to different spectral types) affect negatively the overall performance of the techniques.

The problem can be tackled from two directions. We can simulate stellar activity and the expected RV variability for a set of stars (e.g., Desort et al. 2007; Lagrange et al. 2010; Santos et al. 2015; Dumusque 2016), but our prior assumptions and knowledge are of fundamental importance (Meunier 2021; Bellotti & Korhonen 2021). For example, we can only postulate how the surface of a star looks like by indirect means, given the inexorable lack of spatial resolution of the observations. Although reliable results have been achieved with different numerical implementations like, e.g., SOAP (Boisse et al. 2012; Dumusque et al. 2014), DEEMA (Korhonen et al. 2015; Andersen & Korhonen 2015), STARSIM (Herrero et al. 2016), simulating realistic RV and photometric variability is challenging. An alternative approach is to develop data-driven techniques, i.e. to extract as much stellar activity information as possible from the observations and search for efficient ways to remove it from the data sets.

We can conveniently classify data-driven, activity-filtering techniques based on the RV computation step at which they operate. From the description in Sec. 1.2, we can summarise the computation in three steps

$$\text{spectrum} \Rightarrow \text{mean line profile} \Rightarrow \text{RV time series} \quad (1.5)$$

In the following sections, I will describe a small but representative sample of techniques that have been adopted in RV studies over the years. Because this is very active field of research, extending the list of techniques would inevitably distract from the aim of this thesis.

1.4.1 Operating on time series

Activity tracers

Several works have shown that some quantities, known as “activity tracers”, feature a temporal behaviour that correlates with the RV variability induced by stellar activity. In practice, time series of indicators are inspected by means of Lomb-Scargle periodograms (Lomb 1976; Scargle 1982; Zechmeister & Kürster 2009) to search for a periodic signal that is similar to the one modulating the RV data set, since it would corroborate the presence of activity-induced variations (see Fig. 1.12). The comparison of the periodic information is therefore an efficient way to distinguish signals of planetary or stellar origin, correct the RV variations induced by activity, and provide the timescale at which the activity-induced variations are modulated. This is common practice to remove activity signals due to magnetic cycles (Lovis et al. 2011; Costes et al. 2021). However, intricate patterns of the active regions on the stellar surface and their finite lifetime may complicate the interpretation of the periodograms (Schöfer et al. 2019, 2022). More recently, (Binnenfeld et al. 2022) introduced new periodograms that are capable of distinguishing periodic line shifts (due to a planet) or distortions (due to activity) from RV time series, provided that the time scales of variations are well separated.

Some activity tracers are computed directly from specific lines in the observed spectra, and are called “indices”: CaII H&K at 393.3 and 396.8 nm (yielding the S or $\log R'_{\text{HK}}$ index; Wilson 1968; Vaughan et al. 1978; Noyes et al. 1984), Na I D_{1,2} doublet at 589.0 and 589.6 nm (e.g., Borsa et al. 2015), H α at 656.3 nm (Gizis et al. 2002; West et al. 2004), CaII infrared triplet at 849.8, 854.2, and 866.2 nm (Andretta et al. 2005), HeI triplet at 1083.2, 1083.3 and 1083.3 nm, Pa β at 1282.2 nm, and Br γ at 2160.0 nm (Schöfer et al. 2019; Moutou et al. 2020; Klein et al. 2021); while other tracers characterize the shape and asymmetry of the mean profile: full width at half maximum (FWHM; Queloz et al. 2001; Figueira et al. 2013) and bisector velocity span (BIS SPAN; Queloz et al. 2009; Boisse et al. 2009). The definition of the latter is illustrated in Fig. 1.13.

A simple but efficient method to reveal the presence of stellar activity in the data sets is to look for an anti-correlation between the RV and BIS SPAN data sets (Boisse et al. 2009; Hébrard et al. 2014), as shown in Fig. 1.14. We can inspect the RV and the chromatic index in a similar fashion because an anti-correlation would indicate that the RV variations are chromatic, and therefore generated by co-rotating surface inhomogeneities on the stellar surface. Other tracers such as FWHM or chromospheric lines indices might feature more complex relations (Gomes da Silva et al. 2012; Perger et al. 2017; Tal-Or et al. 2018) and cannot be used to spot the presence of activity easily. In general, there is no rule specifying which activity tracer is the most useful, as they can manifest significantly different behaviour between individual stars. Thus the choice should be considered case-by-case, and often more than one indicator is used. Recently, Simola et al. (2022) developed an algorithm to locate temporal segments in the entire time series associated to changes in the correlation between RV and activity indicators. Correcting the full time series with this method leads to $\sim 70\%$ improvement in the RV RMS that can be observed also in periodograms. The benefit can be appreciated especially for data sets with a long baseline, e.g. for α Cen.

Additional indicators are the chromatic index (Zechmeister et al. 2018) and the longitudinal magnetic field (Donati et al. 1997). The former quantifies the chromatic trend of the RV measured in several spectral orders, which derives from to the wavelength dependence of the photospheric contrast of active

Figure 1.12: Generalised Lomb-Scargle periodogram (Zechmeister & Kürster 2009) applied to optical time series of longitudinal field measurements collected with SPIRou for the active M dwarf TOI-1759. The idea is to fit the observed time series with sine models on a grid of user-defined frequencies, each time quantifying the quality of the fit with a statistical power. This produces peaks at the periodicities that are most prominent in the observed time series, which are then distinguished by noise using the False Alarm Probability (FAP, VanderPlas 2018). The latter represents the probability that the periodicity is due to white noise, hence the higher peak than the FAP, the more likely it is real. In this case, there is a significant (FAP<0.001%) peak at the stellar rotation period of 35.7 d. Taken from Martioli et al. (2022).

regions (Baroch et al. 2020). Indeed, spots appear less contrasted in near-infrared relative to optical, reducing their contribution to the RV. As a result, designing velocimeters that operate in the near-infrared benefits from acquiring observations with an intrinsically reduced jitter, but caution should be exerted because the effect of *magnetic* spots increases due to an enhanced Zeeman effect instead (Zeeman 1897; Reiners et al. 2013). The longitudinal magnetic field is the line-of-sight projected field generated by magnetic regions on the visible disk and it is a powerful activity tracer (Hébrard et al. 2016; Folsom et al. 2016; Bellotti et al. 2021) that can be computed when spectropolarimetric observations are available (see Chapter 2).

All these indicators are in principle insensitive to the presence of planetary companions, but there is some evidence that stars with close-in giant planets may manifest an intensified chromospheric activity due to magnetic or tidal interactions (Shkolnik et al. 2003; Krejčová & Budaj 2012; Maggio et al. 2015), thus affecting the $\log R'_{\text{HK}}$ index for instance. However, the exact enhancing mechanism at play is not clear (Figueira et al. 2016). Another aspect to consider when computing, for example, the $\log R'_{\text{HK}}$ index is the bias introduced by the interstellar medium (Fossati et al. 2017).

Figure 1.13: The *bisector* is the locus of median points dividing the profile into two halves of equal equivalent width (Perryman 2018). The curvature is expected to form a “C”-shape for cool stars up to spectral type G2 and then an “inverse-C”-shape for earlier type stars. The *bisector velocity span* is the difference between the average velocities in the top (v_t , within 10% and 40% of the profile depth) and bottom (v_b within 60% and 90% of the bisector) (Queloz et al. 2001; Hébrard et al. 2014). Taken from Queloz et al. (2001).

Alternative techniques

Many techniques are designed using solar data which has an extremely long baseline compared to any exoplanet host. For instance, Milbourne et al. (2021) used machine learning to estimate filling factors (i.e. surface occupancy) of sunspots, faculae and network to model the RV contribution of brightness inhomogeneities and suppression of convective blueshift. They found tight correlations between the estimated filling factors and those observed with Solar Dynamics Observatory (*SDO*, Schou et al. 2012), and the filtered RV featured a reduced dispersion of 40% compared to the full data set. Moreover, Ervin et al. (2022) developed SOLASTER, a pipeline to combine the content of *SDO* Dopplergrams and magnetograms, and estimate RV associated to rotationally-modulated surface inhomogeneities and suppression of convective blueshift. When RVs and magnetic activity proxies are decorrelated, an RMS scatter of 60 cm^{-1} can be achieved. While we lack the spatial resolution to perform similar measurements on other stars, some studies started to use interferometry in an attempt to image spots on Sun-like stars like ϵ Eri (Roettenbacher et al. 2022). Dense coverage of the stellar rotation is crucial for such observations.

Some filtering techniques exploit the temporal variations to isolate or partially remove the activity signal. Queloz et al. (2009) used a pre-whitening approach on CoRoT-7 observations to iteratively identify the highest peaks in the RV periodogram and subtract the corresponding signal. This method allows the periodic content to be cleaned from the most dominant timescales, but it does not recognize aliases stemming from the observation cadence, which may have a more significant power than true timescales. In addition, Boisse et al. (2011) applied an harmonic decomposition method, which consists of fitting the RV time series with three sinusoids: one at the stellar rotation period and the others at

Figure 1.14: Example of anti-correlation between RV and BIS SPAN that reveals the presence of stellar activity contributions. The explanation is that the mean profile shape is distorted periodically (at the stellar rotation period) by surface inhomogeneities, hence the bottom of the bisector oscillates with the same period around zero velocity (see Fig. 1.13): when the oscillation is blueward, the RV is negative and BIS SPAN is positive ($v_t > v_b$), and vice versa. Taken from [Queloz et al. \(2001\)](#).

the first two harmonics. While 90% reduction of the RV jitter amplitude can be achieved with this approach, important limitations restrict its general application: the time series needs to span at least one stellar cycle, the amplitude of the planetary signal has to exceed the stellar one and most importantly the orbital period must not coincide with the stellar rotation period.

It is possible to exploit photometric data to filter radial velocity curves using the FF' method developed by [Aigrain et al. \(2012\)](#). The idea is to model the RV variations induced by spots and suppression of convective blueshift within magnetised areas, using the photometric light curve (F) and its first time derivative (F'). This way, a detailed spot model or knowledge about the stellar rotation are not needed, which is a major benefit with respect to several methods described before. In addition, it is a fast tool with which to predict RV variations for several targets. However, the method cannot reproduce all spots configurations and represents a first-order approximation of the most dominant sources of RV noise. In the design of the FF' method, the contribution to faculae was neglected, which is a reasonable assumption for stars significantly more active than the Sun and M dwarfs ([Reinhold et al. 2019](#)), but for Sun-like stars the suppression of convective blueshift induced by faculae is dominant and has to be taken into account ([Meunier et al. 2010](#)).

A powerful tool to disentangle planetary and stellar activity signals is based on Gaussian Process Regression (see Appendix B for more details). The idea is to model the RV variations with two components: a deterministic one representing the planetary companion(s) and a stochastic one encapsulating stellar activity ([Aigrain & Foreman-Mackey 2022](#); [Nicholson & Aigrain 2022](#)). This has now become common practice after [Haywood et al. \(2014\)](#) demonstrated the flexibility of this approach to characterize complicated RV signals for CoRoT-7. Furthermore, [Rajpaul et al. \(2015\)](#) defined a Gaussian Process framework (later implemented by [Jones et al. 2017](#)) in which the RV time series is modelled jointly with

some activity tracer, in order to efficiently constrain and unravel the activity signature. Later, [Camacho et al. \(2022\)](#) showed the possibility to combine GPs and neural networks applied on solar data, achieving a model quality comparable to previous studies.

The benefit of using Gaussian Processes over other approaches resulted also from the RV fitting challenge ([Dumusque 2016](#); [Dumusque et al. 2017](#)), which saw eight international research teams testing the capabilities of different filtering techniques. In particular, GP-based techniques were the most efficient at retrieving the stellar rotation period and the planetary signal, and with a higher confidence. However, extreme caution should be exerted when a blind planetary search is performed, since the capability of GPs to model any signal is itself their main drawback. This is countered by including tight prior information in the model which is often the case in RV follow-up analyses of photometric surveys (e.g., [Plavchan et al. 2020](#); [Petit et al. 2021](#); [Martioli et al. 2022](#)).

The Extreme-precision Spectrograph (EXPRES) Stellar Signals Project (ESSP) is another challenge conducted in this direction ([Zhao et al. 2022b](#)), seeing 22 techniques tested for EXPRES spectroscopic data. The performance of the techniques was assessed by the total RV dispersion, but no method reached sub m s^{-1} level. At the same time, comparing the output of different techniques was hindered by different levels of interpretability, indicating the need of a homogeneity in the results.

1.4.2 Operating on the mean line profile

We now take a step back in the RV computation and focus on the techniques that act on the mean line profile obtained via cross-correlation or LSD.

[Collier Cameron et al. \(2021\)](#) developed a data-driven approach called SCALPELS which exploits the shift-invariant nature of the autocorrelation function (ACF) of the cross-correlation function (CCF) to separate activity signals from planetary ones (see Fig. 1.15). They compute the ACF residuals of all observations with respect to a master ACF template, which are unaffected by the presence of planetary companions. They then model the variations of these residuals via principal component analysis (PCA), to obtain a time series of activity-induced RVs with which to correct the observed one. This technique was tested on solar data and successfully retrieved synthetic planets at various orbital periods with $K = 40 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$.

Another technique that discerns deformations from genuine shifts is ϕ_{ESTA} ([Zhao & Tinney 2020](#)). The idea is to project the CCF onto Fourier basis functions and then inspect the amplitude of the modes, which should be invariant if a genuine Keplerian shift is present. A CCF deformation is singled out as several shifts of the Fourier modes. By applying this technique on solar HARPS-N data, [Zhao et al. \(2022a\)](#) achieved a mitigation of the RV dispersion of a factor of two, and distinguished different sources of noise associated to activity such as the solar rotation and the magnetic cycle.

An approach based on convolutional neural network (CNN) was described by [de Beurs et al. \(2021\)](#). They applied it to the residuals of the CCF relative to a master CCF for solar HARPS-N observations, where the model learns how to correlate asymmetries in the shape of the CCF profile with observed RVs. The method is once again used to isolate activity-induced RV variations and subtract them from the observed RVs. The authors reported a 50% reduction of the RV RMS in the corrected data set and recovered the signal of a synthetic planet with a higher significance. However, these planetary recovery tests represent an ideal scenario as the injection was performed after the correction of the data set and not before training. A complementary evaluation on whether the technique could confuse planetary and stellar signals is necessary to obtain more realistic results.

Doppler Imaging reconstructs maps of the stellar brightness and can be used to mitigate activity (see Chapter 3 for more details). It has been proven an efficient technique at filtering RV data sets from the activity contribution ([Hébrard et al. 2016](#); [Donati et al. 2016](#); [Klein et al. 2021](#)). The maximum entropy brightness map of the stellar surface is used to produce synthetic RV data sets, which are then subtracted from the raw RVs, and to reduce the activity jitter by a factor of 2 or 3 ([Hébrard et al. 2016](#)). Alternatively, [Petit et al. \(2015\)](#) showed that it is possible to determine planetary parameters as part of the map reconstruction itself. The procedure consists of correcting the mean line profiles by the reflex motion of synthetic planets over a grid of orbital parameters (semi-amplitude, period, phase)

Figure 1.15: Translation invariance at the basis of the SCALPELS technique. Left: CCF residuals obtained by subtracting a master CCF template from each individual CCF. We observe periodic Doppler shifts in the CCF plot that are induced by Jupiter. Right: Same as left but using the ACF. Both the center of the ACFs and the continuum level vary with time, but no periodic shift is recorded as a consequence of the translational invariance of the ACF. This property is exploited in SCALPELS to derive activity-driven RVs and correct the raw RV variations. Taken from Collier Cameron et al. (2021).

and reconstructing a Doppler map each time. The planet is then characterized by the set of parameters associated to the map that best fits the observations. As pointed out by Heitzmann et al. (2021), Doppler Imaging is limited by the absence of surface variability modelling (appearance and disappearance of surface inhomogeneities as presented by Petit et al. 2004), so the planetary detection capability is less reliable when compared to a Bayesian framework offered by Gaussian Processes. Furthermore, because the spatial resolution of the brightness map is an increasing function of the projected rotational velocity, filtering via Doppler Imaging is more efficient for fast rotating stars. However, contrarily to a data-based stochastic model of RVs which represent only the first moment of spectral line profiles, Doppler Imaging allows a physical modelling of the line distortions.

1.4.3 Operating on the spectrum

Finally, we focus on techniques that operate directly on the wavelength domain of the observations, i.e. the first step of the RV computation. Rajpaul et al. (2020) applied GPs to model portions of spectra (orders or smaller) directly, and filter out those whose RV data have high dispersion and correlate strongly with activity indicators. One important benefit is that there is no requirement of prior astrophysical knowledge.

Dumusque (2018) and Cretignier et al. (2020) designed a line-by-line RV extraction method on α Cen B spectra and a filtering technique based on the different sensitivity to activity of some spectral lines (e.g., Davis et al. 2017; Lisogorskyi et al. 2019). By examining the correlations of the RVs when calculated using individual lines and all the lines in the spectrum, they isolate activity-insensitive lines that enable a reduction of the activity jitter by a factor of two. With the same procedure, activity-sensitive lines can be identified and their effect can be removed from the activity-insensitive RV time series to improve the filtering. However, this procedure would alter a potential planetary signal, because it would be present in both activity-sensitive and insensitive RV time series.

The line-by-line technique works efficiently to obtain high-precision RV data sets for stars similar to the Sun, for which the suppression of convective blueshift is the dominant activity-related phenomenon (Liebing et al. 2021). The performance is even increased when deep spectral lines are considered, since they form close to the stellar surface where convective blueshift is weaker (Reiners et al. 2016; Cretignier et al. 2020). The robust extraction of individual spectral lines is limited by blends and photon noise, two significant aspects when considering cooler stars in the optical domain, since they feature dense spectra

(in particular on the blue side) and are intrinsically dimmer. Switching to the near-infrared, [Artigau et al. \(2022\)](#) and [Radica et al. \(2022\)](#) showed that line-by-line frameworks can be efficiently applied to M dwarfs to achieve m s^{-1} accuracy levels, despite the presence of strong telluric absorption bands and emission lines. However, reaching a cm s^{-1} precision level in the near-infrared around active M dwarfs remains a challenge.

Finally, a few techniques act on the reduction pipeline directly, hence they could be approximately classified to lie before the first step of the RV computation presented in Eq.1.5. For instance, [Lienhard et al. \(2022\)](#) presented a multi-mask pipeline that employs LSD to flexibly remove lines and pixels affected by stellar variability, resulting in a 12% dispersion improvement compared to HARPS-N CCF-based pipeline, when applied on the Sun and FGK stars.

In Chapter 2, I will describe the filtering technique I developed and tested for active M dwarfs as part of the thesis project. The main goal is to select the spectral lines that yield the most precise RV data set, possibly without activity contribution. In this sense it has been inspired by the line-by-line method developed in [Dumusque \(2018\)](#), but works with the line lists employed in LSD rather than the observed spectra themselves. For the same reason, it belongs to the class of techniques operating on the spectrum. The technique benefits from the multi-line nature of LSD, since it produces a high-S/N profile without line blends.

1.5 The interest of M dwarfs

Stars are born via gravitational collapse of giant interstellar clouds of gas and dust. At the end of this process, they ignite hydrogen fusion in their cores via thermonuclear reactions and enter a phase known as main-sequence. To visualise stars at different stages of their life and the corresponding diversity of observables, astronomers use the notorious Hertzsprung-Russel diagram ([Hertzsprung 1910](#)). Stars are located based on their temperature (or color) and luminosity (or magnitude), as shown in Fig. 1.16. The Harvard system was introduced to classify stars based on prominent spectral lines and identifies them as O-B-A-F-G-K-M, and it was later extended with the Yerkes system, which assigns a roman number according to the star's luminosity class (e.g., [Jaschek & Jaschek 1987](#), and references therein). Main-sequence stars are also called dwarfs and indicated with “V”; they run the diagram diagonally from top left to bottom right.

This thesis concentrates on M dwarfs, which are the coldest stars on the main-sequence and the most common spectral type in the solar neighbourhood ([Reid et al. 2004](#); [Winters et al. 2019](#)). Their effective temperature ranges 2500-4000 K and their mass 0.08-0.57 M_{\odot} , thus including the fully-convective boundary at 0.35 M_{\odot} ([Pecaut & Mamajek 2013](#); [Chabrier & Baraffe 1997](#)). For this reason, they are excellent laboratories to test dynamo theories for the generation of magnetic fields under different conditions with respect to the Sun (see Chapter 4). At optical wavelengths, the spectra of M dwarfs feature several absorption bands of diatomic metal oxides (TiO especially), whereas in infrared they show CO, FeH and H₂O bands. These forests of absorption lines strengthen toward later spectral types, complicating the identification of individual atomic lines ([Hyland 1974](#); [Jaschek & Jaschek 1987](#)).

In the context of exoplanet searches, M dwarfs represent favourable targets for the detection and characterisation of planets that may harbor life. The frequency of small planets is expected to be high for these stars, a result to which both ground-based campaigns and space-based surveys converged to ([Bonfils et al. 2013](#); [Dressing & Charbonneau 2015](#)). The lower mass and radius compared to earlier stellar types makes the effect of planetary companions stronger, i.e. both the RV semi-amplitude and the transit depth are boosted (see Eq.1.4). For instance, the same Earth-like planet around a Sun-like star and an M dwarf would lead to a signal on the order of cm s^{-1} and m s^{-1} , respectively.

Owing to a lower brightness, the habitable zone around M dwarfs is located closer in, implying an additional boost in RV semi-amplitude and a higher chance of transits. A smaller habitable zone also means a shorter orbital period and a simplified observational follow-up. In turn, the increased number of transits in a relatively narrow temporal window is beneficial for atmospheric studies with, e.g., *JWST* and *Ariel*. The clear benefits of targeting M dwarfs motivated the deployment of dedicated ground-

Figure 1.16: Hertzsprung-Russel diagram showing the luminosity vs effective temperature of stars at different stages of their life. The Sun is superimposed as a green symbol. Taken from (Gaia Collaboration et al. 2018).

based spectrographs operating at near-infrared wavelengths, where the luminosity of the stars peaks and the spectra are rich of lines (and thus of RV content). A list of current near-infrared instruments is provided in Table 1.2.

At the same time, M dwarfs can host strong magnetic fields and manifest intense activity levels (Kochukhov 2021) that can jeopardise the success of habitable-zone exoplanet surveys. The time scales during which they stay active is on the order of Gyr, longer compared to earlier spectral types on

Table 1.2: List of some high-resolution near-infrared spectrographs currently operating. The columns are: instrument name, wavelength coverage, resolving power, location and main literature reference. Credit: <https://carmenes.caha.es/ext/instrument/>

Name	Coverage [μm]	R	Location	Ref
HPF	0.97-1.75	50 000	Hobby Eberly Telescope	Mahadevan et al. (2012)
GIANO-B	0.97-2.45	50 000	Telescopio Nazionale Galileo	Claudi et al. (2017)
SPIRou	0.95-2.50	70 000	Canada-France-Hawaii Telescope	Donati et al. (2020)
IRD	0.97-1.75	70 000	SUBARU Telescope	Kotani et al. (2014)
iSHELL	1.15-5.40	70 000	NASA Infrared Telescope Facility	Rayner et al. (2012)
MAROON-X	0.50-0.92	80 000	Gemini North	Peck (2020)
CARMENES	0.52-1.71	80 000	Calar Alto Observatory	Quirrenbach et al. (2018)
Veloce	0.58-0.93	80 000	Anglo-Australian Telescope	Gilbert et al. (2018)
CRIRES+	0.92-5.20	100 000	Very Large Telescope	Follert et al. (2014)
NIRPS	0.97-1.81	110 000	La Silla Observatory	Wildi et al. (2017)

the main-sequence ([West et al. 2008](#)). More precisely, the consequences of high activity levels are the following:

- Dark and magnetic spots are the main surface inhomogeneities ([Reinhold et al. 2019](#)), whose effect dominates the contribution to the RV jitter. Inside spots, the magnetic field is on the order of kG ([Berdyugina 2005](#)), hence spectral lines are split due to Zeeman effect ([Zeeman 1897](#)). This act to distort the shape of line profiles, increasing the dispersion in RV measurements especially when the broadening of the lines is not rotationally-dominated ([Hébrard et al. 2014](#)). Overall, the activity-induced RV jitter reaches dozens to hundreds of m s^{-1} at optical wavelengths ([Saar & Donahue 1997](#); [Andersen & Korhonen 2015](#)), swamping any signature of small, Earth-like planets. Compared to spots, simulations showed a slower convection and a lower contrast between granules and intergranular lanes which would make their RV influence weaker ([Beeck et al. 2013](#); [Allende Prieto et al. 2013](#)).
- Strong large-scale stellar magnetic fields can lead to planetary induction heating, i.e. the generation of currents in the planetary mantle with subsequent dissipation and heating ([Kislyakova et al. 2018](#)). This would result in extreme volcanic activity and the presence of magma oceans ([Kislyakova & Noack 2020](#); [Guenther & Kislyakova 2020](#))
- Abundant flares and coronal mass ejections occur ([Hawley et al. 2014](#); [Moschou et al. 2019](#); [Alvarado-Gómez et al. 2022](#)), showering habitable-zone planets with energetic particles and high-frequency radiation ([Stelzer et al. 2016](#)). It is however unclear whether or not they could be detrimental for life to originate and survive. On one side, high-energy flares ($> 10^{34}$ erg) can progressively deplete the O_3 layer in planetary atmospheres and expose the surface to harmful radiation ([Estrela & Valio 2018](#); [Tilley et al. 2019](#)). The impact of energetic particles is more dangerous than UV radiation² in this sense ([Segura et al. 2010](#); [Abrevaya et al. 2020](#)). On the other side, flares could be required to trigger prebiotic chemical reactions to form ribonucleic acid (RNA, [Sutherland 2015](#)), and not all M dwarfs produce flares with sufficient energy to erode the O_3 layer ([Bogner et al. 2022](#)). Finally, flares can be responsible of interior heating and enhanced volcanism, that would replenish the atmosphere of a planetary companion and reduce the impact of erosion ([Grayver et al. 2022](#)).

²From our experience on Earth, we are aware of biological mechanisms that can cope with radiation damage ([Kaltenegger 2017](#); [O'Malley-James & Kaltenegger 2017, 2019](#)). One of them is photoprotective biofluorescence, i.e. the absorption of energetic UV radiation by means of specific proteins and the re-emission at longer wavelengths, which has been observed for some coral species. The impulsive nature of flares would induce a temporary increase in UV irradiation which, in turn, could enhance the visible planetary flux. In other words, the biofluorescence could be observed as an additional biosignature.

- Intense X-ray and UV stellar winds drive atmospheric mass loss (Penz & Micela 2008; Zendejas et al. 2010; Ribas et al. 2016) and to a more or less extent depending on the global geometry of the stellar magnetic field (Vidotto et al. 2014). The effect is accentuated during the pre-main-sequence phase of M dwarfs, as they experience a superluminous period (Shkolnik & Barman 2014; Peacock et al. 2020; Pineda et al. 2021). The natural consequence is a planetary evolution path that may deviate from Earth's unless a secondary atmosphere, formed via volcanic activity or cometary impacts, can be envisioned (France et al. 2020). Studies showed that ocean and temperate worlds around M dwarfs could survive due to a less efficient hydrodynamic escape (Yoshida et al. 2022), but questions remain on how much water planets around M dwarf can retain (Luger & Barnes 2015).

In summary, M dwarfs are at the centre of active research both in terms of exoplanet searches and habitability, since it is still debated whether they can host habitable environments or not (Kaltenegger 2017). A comprehensive understanding of their properties is far from complete, hence additional work in this direction is required.

1.5.1 A new planet detection method?

M dwarfs are interesting targets because they offer the possibility to understand new detection methods using radio observations (Zarka 2007; Vidotto et al. 2019). In particular, coherent low-frequency (144 MHz) radio emission with high brightness temperature ($> 10^{12}$ K), circular polarisation ($> 60\%$) was reported. The first of such detections was for GJ 1151 (Vedantham et al. 2020), followed by 19 recent observations within the LOFAR Two-meter Sky Survey (LoTSS) (Callingham et al. 2021) for a sample of M dwarfs spanning between M1 and M6. The survey was performed blindly to prevent any observational bias toward active stars, for which radio emissions have been already established. In fact, the 19 stars of Callingham et al. (2021) ranged between fast and slow rotators, i.e. between very active and more quiescent, which led the authors to exclude intense stellar activity to be the sole mechanism producing the 144 MHz emission.

Accounting for the specific properties of the radio emission, i.e. coherency, brightness temperature, degree of circular polarisation, bandwidth, and duration, Callingham et al. (2021) boiled down the plausible mechanism driving the emission to be electron cyclotron maser instability (ECMI). Such phenomenon occurs when electrons are accelerated along magnetic field lines toward the stellar magnetic poles and then reflected back due to magnetic mirroring (Sprangle & Drobot 1977), which is already known to power planetary aurorae in the Solar System (Zarka 1998; Louarn et al. 2017). The magnetic interactions between a planet and a star could be the source of the ECMI-induced radio emission, similarly to a scaled-up version of the Jupiter-Io system, as shown in Fig. 1.17. In this case, the stellar magnetic field lines connect to those of the exoplanet magnetosphere forming a circuit and allowing electrons to reach the star's pole, driving radio emission. In principle, planets as small as Mercury could be detected with this method, since it is independent of planetary mass.

The planet-induced radio emission was modelled theoretically by Kavanagh et al. (2021) around AU Mic and Prox Cen, and by Kavanagh et al. (2022) around WX UMa, assuming a certain mass, orbital period and magnetic field for the planet. For AU Mic, the emission is consistent with the presence of the two known planets (Boccaletti et al. 2018; Plavchan et al. 2020), whereas for Prox Cen the simulated planet would orbit too far to trigger ECMI. For WX UMa, a Neptune-sized planet on a 7.4 d orbit could explain the radio emission, but additional follow-up is necessary to reach a definite conclusion. A crucial ingredient for such modelling lies in the large-scale magnetic field of the star: its configuration needs to be determined reliably and with data sets that are ideally simultaneous with the radio observations.

Finally, adopting reliable values of planetary magnetic fields is complicated because such measurement is not straightforward. Magnetohydrodynamic simulations have however shown the possibility to estimate such quantity from monitoring of radio transits (Hazra et al. 2022). In general, the validation of a planetary companion requires long-baseline light curves in which to search periodicities and modulations, owing to the beaming properties of the ECMI emission. Overall, this radio method could be

Figure 1.17: Sketch depicting the planet-induced electron cyclotron maser instability radio emission. Stellar magnetic field lines are connected to the planet magnetosphere, creating a potential difference and allowing electrons to be accelerated from the planet to the star. As they move toward the star, they experience a stronger magnetic field, until they are reflected back and power radio emission. Taken from [Kavanagh et al. \(2022\)](#).

adopted in synergy with RV or transit techniques to confirm detections and to complement habitability analyses of exoplanets ([Callingham et al. 2020](#)).

1.6 Scope of this thesis

The main goal of this thesis is to make new advances in our understanding of stellar magnetic activity and how we can use such information to feed back the quest of hunting small, Earth-like exoplanets around M dwarfs. In general there is a natural synergy between RV searches of exoplanets and studies of stellar activity, stemming from the fact that both can be analysed using the same data sets, which is convenient in terms of observing time. My work has had a significant observational contribution as I analysed high-resolution optical and near-infrared data acquired with Narval (at Telescope Bernard-Lyot, Pic du Midi, France), ESPaDOnS and SPIRou (at Canada-France-Hawaii Telescope, Mauna Kea, Hawaii, USA).

I started from archival optical spectropolarimetric data to design a new activity-filtering technique based on selecting sets of spectral lines that would reduce the RV dispersion. The description of this work is outlined in Chapter 2. An important benefit of this technique is its portability over different stars, data sets, instruments and wavelength domains. Indeed, it can be flexibly adapted to optical and

near-infrared data sets acquired with both spectropolarimeters and spectrographs.

In Chapter 3, I dive deeper into the physics underlying the selection of specific spectral lines and the output of the filtering technique, focusing on the near-infrared domain covered by SPIRou. More precisely, I apply Doppler Imaging to build brightness maps of a fast-rotating, very active M dwarf using various combinations of spectral lines. The idea is to seek for a connection between the selected line lists and reconstructed brightness inhomogeneities on the stellar disk.

Further advancements in understanding stellar activity are inexorably tethered to the characterisation of the star's magnetic field. The latter is best studied with spectropolarimetry, whose main concepts are recalled in Chapter 4. Using Zeeman-Doppler Imaging, we are able to reconstruct the geometry of the large-scale magnetic field and determine its main properties. If data sets are collected over a long temporal baseline, we are able to recover the secular evolution of the magnetic field, providing useful observational constraints to dynamo theories. Chapter 5 is dedicated to the description of the long-term monitoring of the large-scale field I carried out for a sample of well-studied active M dwarfs, which were observed as part of the SPIRou Legacy Survey. Setting robust time scales to magnetic activity phenomena is pivotal for exoplanet surveys, as they can be used to inform observing strategies.

Finally, in Chapter 5.6.3, I will summarise the conclusions of this thesis and insert them into the broader context of exoplanets and stellar activity. I will end with prospective work in this direction, that has either been initiated already or that my results will branch out into.

Chapter 2

Activity mitigation via spectral line selection

Is there a combination of spectral lines that efficiently mitigates RV jitter?

In this Chapter, I will first introduce how “traditional” activity indicators are limited at conveying practical information to filter out stellar contamination for well-known active M dwarfs. I will then present the initial part of my Ph.D. project, i.e. the development of a jitter-mitigating technique based on spectral line selection, and inspired by line-by-line methods. The technique is designed using optical archival spectropolarimetric data. The description will include initial attempts based on straightforward line selection, a more sophisticated algorithm and its application, and its portability tests over different data sets. Finally, I will describe preliminary results obtained using near-infrared SPIRou observations.

2.1 Observations

We analyse archival spectropolarimetric data of two very active M dwarfs: EV Lac (GJ 873) and AD Leo (GJ 388). The observations were acquired in the optical domain using the twin spectropolarimeters ESPaDOnS on the 3.6-m Canada–France–Hawaii Telescope (CFHT) located atop Mauna Kea in Hawaii, and NARVAL on the 2-m Telescope Bernard Lyot (TBL) at the Pic du Midi Observatory in France (Donati 2003). The data reduction was performed with the LIBRE-ESPRIT pipeline (Donati et al. 1997), and the reduced spectra were retrieved from the PolarBase archive (Petit et al. 2014). For EV Lac and AD Leo, 57 spectra between 2005 and 2016 and 48 between 2006 and 2016 are available on PolarBase, respectively.

The magnetic field properties of the two stars have been studied extensively (e.g., Morin et al. 2008b; Shulyak et al. 2019). EV Lac is an M4 dwarf with a rotation period of 4.36 d. The activity level is quantified by a logarithmic X-ray-to-bolometric luminosity ratio ($\log(L_X/L_{\text{bol}})$) of -3.10 (Wright et al. 2011) and a $\log R'_{\text{HK}}$ index of -3.75 (Boro Saikia et al. 2018; Noyes et al. 1984). AD Leo is an M3.0 dwarf with a rotation period of 2.24 d (Morin et al. 2008b), i.e. approximately half of EV Lac’s, and is slightly less active, with $\log(L_X/L_{\text{bol}}) = -3.62$ (0.5 dex less; Wright et al. 2011) and $\log R'_{\text{HK}} = -4.00$ (0.25 dex less; Boro Saikia et al. 2018). The high activity level of both stars makes them optimal targets for our study, because it is the dominant source of noise in the RV data sets and enables a performance comparison between different line selection approaches. The study has been benchmarked mainly on EV Lac, but parallel analyses have been carried out for AD Leo as well, and will be included for completeness.

2.2 Least-Squares Deconvolution

We use LSD to produce high-S/N mean line Stokes profiles in both unpolarised and circularly polarised light (Donati et al. 1997; Kochukhov et al. 2010). This numerical technique is used extensively in spectropolarimetry in order to enhance the S/N of the observations, and eventually detect Zeeman signatures and stellar large-scale magnetic fields (more details in Chapter 4).

Figure 2.1: Synthetic mask generated with a LTE model atmosphere from VALD showing atomic lines for M dwarfs like EV Lac and AD Leo. Left: the mask itself, Right: Synthetic lines (vertical dashes) overplotted to a portion of the spectrum for one ESPaDOnS observation of EV Lac. We can see how the line position in the mask locates most of the lines in the spectrum. If mismatches are present as well, they would produce noise in the final LSD profiles.

Basically, we postulate that the observed spectrum is the convolution between a mean line profile and a line list, also called “mask” for historical reasons¹. From a formal standpoint, assuming that all spectral lines have the same shape (eventually scaled by a certain factor) and that they add up linearly, the convolution problem is written as

$$Y(v) = M(v) * Z(v), \quad (2.1)$$

where $Y(v)$ is the observed spectrum, $Z(v)$ is the mean line profile, and $M = \sum_i w_i \delta(v - v_i) Z(v_i)$ is the mask. The positions are expressed in velocity units v and the weight associated to each spectral line is indicated with w_i . When computing Stokes I (unpolarised light) and V (circularly polarised) line profiles, the weights are respectively given by

$$w_I = d/d_n, \quad (2.2)$$

$$w_V = (d \cdot \lambda \cdot g_{\text{eff}}) / (d_n \cdot \lambda_{0,n} \cdot g_{\text{eff},n}), \quad (2.3)$$

where d is the line depth, g_{eff} is called Landé factor and encapsulates the line sensitivity to magnetic fields, and the subscript n indicates the normalisation values. There is no specific rule to set the normalisation values, as they are chosen arbitrarily. However, one must use them consistently throughout the entire analysis and state them explicitly for reproducibility purposes (Kochukhov et al. 2010).

For my thesis, the line normalisation parameters are chosen so that the LSD weights are close to one, using

$$\lambda_n = 700 \text{ or } 1700 \text{ nm}, \quad (2.4)$$

$$d_n = d_0 \cdot \langle w_{I,0} \rangle, \quad (2.5)$$

$$g_{\text{eff},n} = g_{\text{eff},0} \cdot \frac{\langle w_{V,0} \rangle}{\langle w_{I,0} \rangle}, \quad (2.6)$$

In practice, I select λ_n based on the wavelength domain of the observations and two arbitrary values of depth and Landé factor indicated by d_0 and $g_{\text{eff},0}$. Then, I 1) run LSD on all spectra with these values, 2) compute the mean of the LSD weights for both unpolarised ($\langle w_{I,0} \rangle$) and circularly polarised ($\langle w_{V,0} \rangle$) light, 3) apply Eqs. 2.4-2.6, and 4) run LSD on all spectra again with the updated normalisation profiles.

¹The name “mask” has been historically used in relation to early echelle spectrographs, in which physical filters with holes at the location of the absorption lines were employed to compute a cross-correlation function analogously (Baranne et al. 1979), and also for early magnetic field measurements, including cool stars (e.g., Borra et al. 1984).

This recipe ensures $\langle w_I \rangle = \langle w_V \rangle = 1$ for each spectrum, and a final LSD profile that can be interpreted as an actual spectral line with those properties.

Least-Squares Deconvolution aims at inverting Eq. 2.1, and obtain the best-fitting mean profiles $Z(v)$ for a given mask and set of observations. The problem is formulated in terms of χ^2 minimisation and the solution in matrix form is given by

$$\mathbf{Z} = (\mathbf{M}^T \cdot \mathbf{S}^2 \cdot \mathbf{M})^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{M}^T \cdot \mathbf{S}^2 \cdot \mathbf{Y}, \quad (2.7)$$

with \mathbf{S} the diagonal matrix of the inverse variance for every point in the observed spectrum. Because line blends show up at random velocities around the LSD profile, the combination of multiple spectral lines performed with LSD reduces their impact, leading to output Stokes profile cleaned from line blends (Kochukhov et al. 2010).

A mask $M(v)$ is a weighted Dirac comb representing the arrangement of lines in a spectrum, and can be empirical or synthetic (see Fig. 2.1). While in the empirical case we benefit from a large number of lines, leading to a higher S/N mean profile and more precise RV data sets, a synthetic mask contains information on the depth of the lines relative to the unpolarised continuum, as well as Landé factors, excitation potentials, and atomic numbers (or whether it is molecular line). Also, the location of the spectral lines in an empirical mask has limited precision when compared to data calibrated on laboratory measurements. The synthetic is synthesised depending on the physical properties of the star such as temperature (T_{eff}), metallicity ($[M/H]$), microturbulence velocity (v_{micro}), and surface gravity ($\log g$).

In practice, synthetic masks are automatically generated via the Vienna Atomic Line Database² (VALD, Ryabchikova et al. 2015) with a local thermodynamic equilibrium model (Gustafsson et al. 2008). For EV Lac and AD Leo in particular, we input $T_{\text{eff}} = 3500$ K, $\log g = 5.0$ [cm s^{-2}] and $v_{\text{micro}} = 2$ km s^{-1} , and obtain a synthetic mask with 4216 atomic lines between 350–1080 nm (Fig. 2.1) and deeper than 40% the continuum level. Given the wavelength coverage in the observations, the effective number of lines is 3300. Emission lines (e.g., $H\alpha$) and strong absorption lines with broad wings are omitted from the masks, because they do not meet the requirement of self-similarity. Molecular lines tend to be excluded as well because they easily feature blends due to the forest of lines in the spectra of M dwarfs, and also because theoretical spectrum synthesis is more complicated.

2.3 Temporal variations of activity tracers

The RV is measured by simultaneously fitting a Voigt function and a linear continuum to each Stokes I profile and then taking the centroid. For EV Lac and AD Leo, the fit is performed within a ± 20 km s^{-1} velocity interval from profile center. I cautiously add the linear component to prevent biases of the RV measurement due to an imperfect spectrum normalization. The time series for both EV Lac and AD Leo are shown in Fig. 2.3, and are phase-folded at the expected stellar rotation period of 4.36 d and 2.23 d, respectively.

The inspection of the periodic signals encoded in the RV time series is carried out via Generalised Lomb-Scargle periodogram (Zechmeister & Kürster 2009; Czesla et al. 2019), as mentioned in Sec. 1.4.1. For EV Lac, a significant (FAP < 0.01%) peak at the expected P_{rot} is found both when considering the full time series and the 2007 and 2010 data sets (see Fig. 2.2), which contain most of the observations. The list of measurements is reported in Appendix C. Making a separate analysis on data sets selected by epoch is a quality check because stellar activity loses coherency over long time-scales. Indeed, according to the solar paradigm, active regions appear on the surface, evolve, and then disappear. For AD Leo, we observe a peak at P_{rot} for the full, 2007, and 2008 RV time series, but they are less significant (FAP > 0.1%) than EV Lac. This is not completely surprising taking into account that EV Lac is observed at 60° inclination, while AD Leo at 20° (almost pole-on). By definition of RV (Sec. 1.2), the amplitude of variations is reduced by geometrical effects.

Fig. 2.3 illustrates the phase-folded variations of a handful of activity tracers as well. The $\log R'_{\text{HK}}$ was not computed as it is less reliable for M dwarfs, owing to their low S/N in the blue part of the

²<http://vald.astro.uu.se/>

Figure 2.2: Generalised Lomb-Scargle periodogram of RV (top) and B_l (bottom). Left: periodograms for EV Lac 2010 data set. A significant ($FAP < 0.01\%$) peak at a rotation period of 4.36 ± 0.05 d is found for both time series. Right: periodograms for AD Leo 2008 data set. A significant ($FAP < 0.01\%$) peak at a rotation period of 2.23 ± 0.07 d is found only for the B_l time series because of geometric effects. Both are consistent with previous studies (e.g., [Wright et al. 2011](#); [Morin et al. 2008b](#)).

spectrum. The $H\alpha$ and CaII infrared triplet do not manifest evident rotational modulation, which is also reflected in the absence of significant peaks in the corresponding periodograms. This can be attributed to a more dynamic structure of the chromosphere relative to the photosphere. The variability between rotational cycles is larger in the chromosphere, drowning the signal at the stellar rotation period. In fact, chromospheric indexes are better activity diagnostics for slower rotators and less active stars ([Bonfils et al. 2007](#); [Folsom et al. 2016](#)).

Together with cross-correlation, an important benefit of using LSD is the possibility to compute activity indicators based on the shape of the mean line profiles: FWHM and BIS SPAN. The error bar on these indicators was computed with a Monte Carlo approach, and it is representative of photon noise. In practice, for each unpolarised spectrum, we inject white noise based on the point-wise flux error bar and then compute the activity proxies each time. Repeating this process for 100 times allows us to obtain distributions of the activity proxies values and infer their error bars.

As mentioned in Sec. 1.4.1, there is no rule of thumb as to which proxy to use, but it depends on the case at hand ([Lafarga et al. 2021](#)). The FWHM does not reveal evident rotational modulation for any of the two stars, except for the 2007 and 2010 data set of EV Lac, but we see a significant peak in the periodogram at P_{rot} only for 2010. [Klein et al. \(2021\)](#) showed that for AU Mic, a young active M1 dwarf, the FWHM variations were correlated to the RV. In our case, we can observe such behaviour only for EV Lac in 2010, confirming that there is no simple relationship between the two ([Gomes da Silva et al. 2012](#); [Tal-Or et al. 2018](#)). We interestingly observe that AD Leo values of FWHM are stacked by epoch, possibly hinting at an evolution over time. This point will be addressed further in Chapter 5.

The situation is similar for the BIS SPAN, i.e. despite noticing oscillations that seem to be rotationally

Figure 2.3: Phase-folded time series of RV and different activity proxies for EV Lac (left) and AD Leo (right). From the top, each panel contain: RV, B_l , FWHM, BIS SPAN, $H\alpha$ index and CaII IRT index. For visualisation purposes, the panels include a sine fit for the 2007 and 2010 time series for EV Lac, and for 2007 and 2008 for AD Leo. In all panels, the data points are color-coded by the year of acquisition.

modulated in the phase-folded curves, we retrieve a marginally significant ($FAP > 1\%$) peak at P_{rot} only for the 2008 data set of AD Leo. If we look at the bisector shape at more detail, we note that it features distortions and an overall reversed-C shape, which would be expected for hotter stars (Gray & Toner 1986; Gray 1988). The Pearson correlation coefficient between BIS SPAN and RV is -0.6 and -0.4 for EV Lac and AD Leo data, respectively. This consistently indicates that the activity is dominant in the RV time series, but a word of caution is necessary, since Saar & Donahue (1997) demonstrated that the BIS SPAN signal is drowned by measurement noise more quickly than the radial velocity signal for decreasing projected rotational velocity $v_{\text{eq}} \sin(i)$. For EV Lac and AD Leo, $v_{\text{eq}} \sin(i)$ is 2 and 3 km s^{-1} , respectively, which could explain the moderate anti-correlation despite the notoriously high activity level.

An excellent activity proxy is the longitudinal magnetic field

$$B_l [G] = \frac{-2.14 \cdot 10^{11}}{\lambda_n g_{\text{eff},n} c} \frac{\int vV(v)dv}{\int (I_c - I)dv}, \quad (2.8)$$

where I and V are the flux values of the Stokes I and V profiles, respectively, I_c is the continuum level, v is the radial velocity associated to a point in the spectral line profile in the star's rest frame and c the speed of light in vacuum (Donati et al. 1997). B_l measurements are performed within a velocity interval of $\pm 30 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, to include the absorption ranges of both Stokes I and V profiles. The corresponding periodograms are illustrated in Fig. 2.2, where we observe the successful recovery of the stellar rotation period for both stars. This represents practical prior information on a fundamental parameter of stellar activity.

It may be tempting to model the RV variations with a Gaussian Process (see Appendix B), but without prior or complementary information on the presence of planetary companions, there is the

danger of incurring in false positives. Besides, intra-epoch data sets are not dense or rich enough for a reliable GP modelling. In case of AD Leo, Carmona et al. (2023, in press in A&A), submitted used a dense near-infrared time series collected with SPIRou to fit both RV and B_l temporal variations with a joint GP framework and rejected the hypothesis of a planet introduced by Tuomi et al. (2018).

The conclusion of this initial analysis is that the usefulness and applicability of activity proxies is limited, as they have to be tailored case-by-case. Even though we can draw some information about stellar activity (e.g., P_{rot}), we are far from filtering its contamination out efficiently enough to reach the RV precision required for reliable exoplanet detection.

2.4 A new activity-filtering technique

At this point, we attempt to design a data-driven numerical technique that suppresses noise induced by stellar activity. The procedure consists in computing RV and B_l data sets with different sub-sets of the full mask (or “sub-masks”) and determine which (if any) reduce the dispersion. For the analyses presented in the following, I employed a synthetic full mask, but this is not a strict requirement and an empirical one can be used instead. This already hints at the flexibility of the technique. I proceeded with a synthetic mask because it allows to select spectral lines easily based on their properties, which is relevant to assess and understand the efficiency of the technique.

The performance of the sub-masks is quantified primarily by the dispersion of the associated data sets. We will indeed use the word “stable” or “unstable” to identify sub-masks leading to an improvement or a degradation in RMS relative to the full mask case, respectively. We will also perform contemporaneous Monte Carlo simulations to determine the RV precision associated to each sub-mask and use it as a metric to discern whether the line selection is photon noise limited. More precisely, for each time series examined, we (1) select the spectrum corresponding to the Stokes I profile with S/N closest to the S/N of the median Stokes I profile, (2) inject white noise into the spectrum in the form $\mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_i)$ (with σ_i the error bar for each data point of the chosen spectrum), (3) apply LSD with the examined sub-mask and (4) measure RV. The RV RMS of 100 iterations will be representative of the photon noise level associated to the sub-mask. From a single spectrum, it will not be surprising if some estimates of the photon noise are lower than the stability of the instrument (30 m s^{-1} , Moutou et al. 2007).

2.4.1 Parametric selection

For this first approach, the full mask is cleaned of lines close to $H\alpha$ or belonging to telluric windows, i.e. in the ranges [627,632], [655.5,657], [686,697], [716,734], [759,770], [813,835], and [895,986] nm; hence we conservatively use 3240 lines in total. The starting RV dispersion for EV Lac is 167 m s^{-1} and a photon-noise-limited precision of 8 m s^{-1} .

We split the full mask based on the following line parameters: depth, wavelength and Landé factor. The parametric threshold is set so that the S/N distribution of the observed Stokes V profiles for the two sub-masks is comparable; this way we ensure the same S/N and a consistent comparison of the effects of different sub-masks (Fig. 2.4). For each sub-mask, we perform a three-parameters (semi-amplitude K , phase correction and offset) Levenberg-Marquardt least squares sinusoidal fit to both the RV and B_l data sets, assuming the stellar rotation period obtained from the periodogram applied to B_l in Sec. 2.4. The inclusion of higher order harmonics of the stellar rotation period as done in Boisse et al. (2011) does not improve the results substantially, so it is not applied for the line selection approaches. The fits are illustrated in Fig. 2.5 for EV Lac and Fig. 2.6 for AD Leo and summarised in Table 2.1 for different parametric selections. We will comment primarily on the statistics of EV Lac, but the results for AD Leo are analogous.

Depth case

We select lines with depth lower than 0.6, between 0.6 and 0.8, and larger than 0.8, resulting in three sub-masks of 926, 1231, and 1058 lines, respectively. For EV Lac, the RV RMS is decreased only in the

Figure 2.4: S/N distributions of the sub-masks generated based on line depth. The depth thresholds are chosen so that the distributions overlap reasonably, and thus define iso-S/N sub-masks.

$d > 0.8$ case by 6%, while it is deteriorated up to 25% in the other cases. The semi-amplitude follows a similar trend, but with a more moderate deterioration in the $d < 0.6$ case. Depending on the sub-mask considered, the RV data sets show systematic shifts up to 100 m s^{-1} relative to the full-mask data set, likely due to a different line sensitivity to convective motions and corresponding velocity fields (Gray 2005; Morgenthaler et al. 2012; Beeck et al. 2013; Meunier et al. 2017). Another reason could be instrumental systematics affecting specific spectral lines (Cretignier et al. 2020). For B_l , no significant improvement in either RMS or semi-amplitude is observed. The $d < 0.6$ case yields the least precise estimates, resulting in deviant magnetic field measurements (with respect to the full mask) and a poorer sinusoidal fit (increased χ^2_ν). This suggests that deeper lines have a stabilizing effect on the time series (also given their higher effective S/N) in agreement with Reiners et al. (2016) and Cretignier et al. (2020).

Wavelength case

Activity signatures induced by spots are strongly chromatic (Reiners et al. 2010; Baroch et al. 2020), hence a wavelength selection may help locate spectral regions with reduced RV dispersion. We select lines with wavelength above and below 550 nm, resulting in two sub-masks of 314 and 2872 lines, respectively. The RV values exhibit a loss of precision up to 3.6% for both sub-masks, and the B_l values feature a negligible $< 4\%$ improvement in RMS only when using red ($> 550 \text{ nm}$) lines. Likewise, the semi-amplitude of the sinusoidal fit for both quantities shows either a degradation or marginal improvement. Note that despite the different number of lines in the sub-masks (due to the larger S/N in the red part of the spectrum), the RV and B_l estimates are highly compatible with the full mask values.

We also compared the FWHM of the Stokes I profiles when computed with the full mask and the two sub-masks (see Fig. 2.7) to explain the more scattered RV data sets when red lines are used. We observe a larger width for red lines (which is expected), which translates in a less precise localization of the Stokes I centroid and therefore in a larger RV dispersion.

Figure 2.5: Comparison of RV and B_l data sets obtained with a parametric selection of sub-masks for EV Lac. Top: RV (left) and B_l (right) data sets obtained with a depth selection. Middle: same with a wavelength selection. Bottom: same with a Landé factor selection. In all panels, black data points correspond to either the RV or the B_l values obtained with the full mask, whereas the continuous lines represent the sinusoidal fit of the associated data set. The mean of the data set is subtracted to allow a simpler comparison. For RV estimates, we set the error bars to 30 m s^{-1} as derived from the telluric lines-based wavelength calibration of the spectra (Moutou et al. 2007), while for B_l we use the formal uncertainties. The displayed data sets are $3\text{-}\sigma$ clipped to prevent outliers from affecting the results. For B_l we display the densest epoch (i.e. 2010).

Landé factor case

An additional line parameter to examine is the Landé factor, considering that Johns-Krull & Valenti (1996) reported measurable Zeeman broadening in magnetic-sensitive optical lines for EV Lac. We select lines with g_{eff} above and below 1.2, resulting in two sub-masks of 1649 and 1495 lines, respectively. The RV dispersion (semi-amplitude) shows a $< 10\%$ (16%) improvement when using magnetically insensitive lines and a 20% (21%) degradation with the opposite sub-mask; the results for B_l are similar to the full mask with a slight deterioration with both sub-masks, and the values are reasonably consistent within error bars. We also tried to use the product $\lambda_0 \cdot g_{\text{eff}}$ as selection criterion, to have a more accurate measure of the magnetic susceptibility, but the result did not change.

The FWHM of the sub-masks displays the expected behaviour: lines with high Landé factor are broader. For EV Lac, the mean FWHM is 12.4, 11.8 and 14.0 km s^{-1} for the full mask, low g_{eff} , and high g_{eff} sub-masks, respectively, and for AD Leo we obtain 10.5, 9.5 and 12.3 km s^{-1} . This is a direct consequence of the Zeeman broadening, which scales linearly with g_{eff} . Once again, a larger width leads to a more scattered RV data set.

Figure 2.6: Comparison of RV and B_l data sets obtained with a parametric selection of sub-masks for AD Leo. For B_l we display the densest epoch (i.e. 2008). The plot is analogous to Fig. 2.5.

Figure 2.7: Comparison of FWHM for both EV Lac (left) and AD Leo (right) when different masks are used: full mask (black), $\lambda > 550$ nm sub-mask (orange) and $\lambda < 550$ nm sub-mask (blue). Respectively, the mean FWHM is 12.4, 11.6, and 12.8 km s^{-1} for EV Lac and 10.5, 10.2, and 10.7 km s^{-1} for AD Leo. As expected, we observe that red lines are broader than blue lines, and consequently yield a larger RV dispersion.

The magnetic sensitivity case allowed us to test the importance of adding a linear continuum component to the Stokes I Voigt fit when measuring RVs. Indeed, when only a constant fit is included, we observe artificial gaps between the RV data sets corresponding to the two sub-masks (see Fig. 2.8). At first, a possible explanation could be the asymmetric de-saturation of deep lines by means of Zeeman

Figure 2.8: Effects of different continuum models when measuring RVs with the two g_{eff} sub-masks, for EV Lac. The y axis is the RV computed with the sub-masks, whereas the x axis with the full mask. The dashed 1-to-1 line locates the RV data set obtained with the full mask. Left: fitting the continuum with a constant, Right: fitting the continuum with a linear function. In the former case, artificial gaps between the RV data sets appear, and cannot be explained by neither an asymmetric de-saturation of deep lines nor the departure from the weak-field approximation.

effect: as this effect is symmetric, line asymmetries are preserved when the splitting occurs, thus generating an imbalance between the red side and blue side of the line. To test this hypothesis, I computed RV and B_l values while removing $d < 0.8$ lines from the two sub-masks. We found a degradation in the dispersion of both RV and B_l , as well as an increased gap between the two RV data sets, indicating that the asymmetric de-saturation cannot be the underlying cause of the gap. We also checked the validity of the weak-field approximation, for which the Stokes V profile scales with the first derivative of Stokes I . We compared the observed Stokes V profiles with those expected from weak-field approximation for different epochs and different sets of line masks: even though significant noise is present, I do not report a difference between them, implying that the weak-field approximation is reasonably valid. We indeed backtracked the origin of these gaps in the residual slope when modelling the Stokes I profile continuum with a constant component only.

Excitation potential and atomic number cases

We tested the parametric selection further, using the excitation potential of the lines and the atomic number of the associated element. The former is the energy budget required to increase the energy state of an atom, and is directly linked to the line formation depth: lines with higher excitation potential need high temperatures for their lowest excitation state to be populated, and are thus formed in deeper photospheric layers (Grossmann-Doerth 1994; Gurtovenko & Sheminova 2015). We select lines with excitation potential above and below 1.8, resulting in two sub-masks of 1862 and 1410 lines, respectively. The RV dispersion and semi-amplitude both show no improvement, while the B_l dispersion and semi-amplitude feature and improvement up to 10% when low excitation potential lines are considered.

From the atomic number distribution of the initial mask, I identified the four elements with the most numerous lines and built as many sub-masks. These are iron (Fe), titanium (Ti), vanadium (V) and chromium (Cr) sub-masks, and contain 1152, 665, 371, 359 lines, respectively. For RV, the largest improvement is given by V lines (7% in RMS and 12% in semi-amplitude), whereas Fe lines yield the worst degradation (34% in RMS and 23% in semi-amplitude). For B_l the situation is analogous, with Cr lines reducing by 4% the RMS and by 16% the semi-amplitude, and Fe lines increasing by 41% the RMS

Figure 2.9: Distributions of the excitation potential for the sub-masks containing lines of specific elements: vanadium (yellow), titanium (red), chromium (green) and iron (blue). The vanadium distribution ranges between 0.0 and 2.3, with mean 0.84. The titanium distribution ranges between 0.0 and 3.9, with mean 1.41. The chromium distribution ranges between 0.0 and 2.3, with mean 2.43. The iron distribution ranges between 0.0 and 4.5, with mean 2.72.

and by 31% the semi-amplitude.

We compare the distributions of the excitation potential for the lines in the four sub-masks in Fig. 2.9, to study possible correlations between the atomic element and the line formation depth. We note that vanadium lines have the lowest excitation potentials with a mean around 0.8, followed by titanium, chromium and iron with a mean of 1.4, 2.4, and 2.7, respectively. This indicates that iron lines form deeper in the photosphere than vanadium and, considering that convective velocities increase with depth (Keil & Yackovich 1981; Gray 2005), explains why the associated RV data sets feature higher scatter.

We also extended the initial mask to contain lines as shallow as 10%. With 9470 lines in total, I applied similar parametric thresholds as before (the depth case was modified to ensure same S/N) to investigate any benefit of the substantial increase in the number of lines, especially for the case of M dwarfs. We found similar trends to the previous analysis, with a general degradation of the precision and of B_l reliability, confirming that very shallow lines should be rejected when defining line masks.

Table 2.1: Summary of the RV and B_l data sets characteristics. The columns are: (1) the parametric criteria used, (2) the number of lines in the sub-mask, (3) the RMS of the data set, (4) the RV precision from the MC simulations, (5) the semi-amplitude of the sinusoidal fit to the data set, (6) the reduced χ^2 , and (7) the RMS of the fit residuals. Columns (8)-(12) are the same as (3)-(7) but for AD Leo. The RV statistics refer to 57 observations for EV Lac and 48 observations for AD Leo, whereas the B_l statistics is related to the epoch with most observations (2010 for EV Lac with 20 observations and 2008 for AD Leo with 14 observations), which was used in Sec. 2.4.

Selection	n_{lines}	EV Lac					AD Leo				
		RMS	RV_p	K	χ^2_ν	RMS_{res}	RMS	RV_p	K	χ^2_ν	RMS_{res}
Radial Velocity [m s^{-1}]											
Full	3240	167	5	124 ± 26	23.2	140	57	1	30 ± 10	3.4	53
$d < 0.6$	1058	208	22	147 ± 32	36.6	176	74	8	39 ± 14	5.7	69
$0.6 < d < 0.8$	926	183	10	141 ± 28	27.1	152	71	3	43 ± 13	4.9	64
$d > 0.8$	1231	157	8	107 ± 25	22.0	136	45	2	20 ± 8	2.2	42
$\lambda > 550 \text{ nm}$	314	168	8	125 ± 26	23.6	141	69	3	27 ± 13	5.2	66
$\lambda < 550 \text{ nm}$	2872	173	7	121 ± 27	26.2	149	48	3	23 ± 9	2.4	45
$g_{\text{eff}} > 1.2$	1649	199	8	149 ± 31	32.9	167	62	3	30 ± 12	4.1	58
$g_{\text{eff}} < 1.2$	1495	151	7	104 ± 24	20.0	130	54	3	15 ± 10	3.4	53
$\text{exc} > 1.8$	1862	164	8	119 ± 26	22.9	139	79	3	29 ± 15	7.0	77
$\text{exc} < 1.8$	1410	178	6	124 ± 28	27.4	152	57	2	39 ± 11	3.1	50
Z=22 (Ti)	665	163	9	123 ± 24	21.5	135	65	3	29 ± 13	4.6	62
Z=23 (V)	371	156	17	109 ± 25	21.4	135	58	10	32 ± 11	3.5	54
Z=24 (Cr)	359	176	9	133 ± 27	25.3	146	63	9	15 ± 12	4.7	62
Z=26 (Fe)	1152	223	10	152 ± 37	44.8	195	115	4	30 ± 23	15.2	113
Longitudinal Magnetic Field [G]											
Full	3240	133	...	158 ± 15	10.6	48	34	...	45 ± 3	0.3	7
$d < 0.6$	1058	200	...	222 ± 26	30.9	82	59	...	74 ± 11	4.6	28
$0.6 < d < 0.8$	926	129	...	149 ± 16	12.7	53	37	...	46 ± 6	1.6	17
$d > 0.8$	1231	152	...	190 ± 15	10.1	46	36	...	41 ± 6	1.3	15
$\lambda > 550 \text{ nm}$	314	128	...	148 ± 15	10.4	48	37	...	48 ± 4	0.7	11
$\lambda < 550 \text{ nm}$	2872	146	...	184 ± 15	11.6	50	41	...	41 ± 9	3.1	24
$g_{\text{eff}} > 1.2$	1649	137	...	157 ± 17	14.8	55	36	...	47 ± 4	0.6	9
$g_{\text{eff}} < 1.2$	1495	138	...	170 ± 14	8.9	51	36	...	43 ± 5	1.0	14
$\text{exc} > 1.8$	1862	157	...	172 ± 22	23.6	69	38	...	49 ± 6	1.5	15
$\text{exc} < 1.8$	1410	119	...	148 ± 11	6.7	39	33	...	42 ± 4	0.6	10
Z=22 (Ti)	665	114	...	133 ± 17	13.7	55	35	...	36 ± 8	2.3	20
Z=23 (V)	371	163	...	182 ± 23	24.9	76	55	...	42 ± 19	11.7	44
Z=24 (Cr)	359	131	...	153 ± 18	15.9	61	31	...	32 ± 8	2.7	22
Z=26 (Fe)	1152	188	...	207 ± 25	30.1	80	49	...	63 ± 8	2.1	19

2.4.2 Randomised selection

Basic principle

For the second selection approach, I applied a randomised algorithm to extract the sub-mask minimizing the RV dispersion, which is inspired by the line-by-line method developed in Dumusque (2018). The idea is to build sub-masks with a randomly sampled number of lines (n_{sample}) from the full mask, apply LSD and derive the RV time series. Because the number of line combinations (i.e. sub-masks) is very large, I stop the iteration when each line in the full mask has been drawn at least a certain amount of times (n_{stop}).

The RV dispersion associated with each sub-mask is the criterion used to discriminate between “stable” and “unstable” sub-masks. From the RV RMS distribution, I isolate three groups of “stable” sub-masks: those with RMS lower than the 10th, 5th and 1st percentile. For each group, I find the maximum number of draws and I build a sub-mask with the lines that are drawn at least a third of this maximum number ($f_{\text{select}} = 0.33$). The f_{select} values is already the optimal one, while $f_{\text{select}} = 0.5$ for the tests outlined in the following section. Finally, I obtain the RV time series from these three sub-masks and determine the best according to the associated RMS.

Overall, two caveats stem from the randomised nature of the approach: each complete run corresponds to sampling a different region of the sub-mask space, and it is not possible to predict exactly which of the three percentile-selected sub-masks gives the lowest RMS. In our analysis, I train the best sub-mask on the 2010 data set of EV Lac, since it has the largest number of observations (i.e., 20), and because the activity signal is expected to lose coherency over timescales longer than months. Moreover, I do not remove lines in telluric windows from the full mask as in Sec. 2.4.1, to further check the reliability of the extracted best sub-mask. The starting number of lines is then 3300. The summary of the results for the analyses in the following sections can be found in Table 2.3.

Optimisation of the control variables

We investigate the optimal control variables of the randomised approach, namely the number of sampled lines (n_{sample}) and the number of times each line has to be drawn for the algorithm to stop (n_{stop}). The purpose is to find a sweet-spot between the achievable reduction of RV dispersion and the number of lines in the sub-mask (n_{lines}), to still obtain a moderate S/N improvement in the final LSD profile.

We consider a grid of ($n_{\text{sample}}, n_{\text{stop}}$) combinations for the following cases: $n_{\text{sample}} = [20, 50, 100, 200, 500, 1000, 2000]$ and $n_{\text{stop}} = [10, 20, 50, 100]$. For each value of n_{sample} , I applied the randomised approach with $n_{\text{stop}} = 100$ to obtain the largest sample of sub-masks or, equivalently, to explore the largest region of line combination space. Then, because the $n_{\text{stop}} = 100$ run contains the lower n_{stop} cases by construction, I simply extracted the corresponding sub-masks. This procedure enables us to save computational time and ensure consistency when comparing results given a certain n_{sample} . The number of sub-masks examined for the grid are reported in Table 2.2.

Given that our randomised algorithm examines the 1st, 5th and 10th percentiles of the RV RMS distribution to build the final sub-masks, the output of the simulation grid is threefold, as illustrated in Fig. 2.10. In all cases, the number of lines in the sub-mask decreases systematically with a smaller number of samples (i.e. lower n_{sample}), while it is not affected by n_{stop} . The RV RMS correlates mainly with the number of sampled lines, reaching a minimum at $n_{\text{sample}} = 50$ and rising again for $n_{\text{sample}} = 20$, presumably due to the photon noise contribution when a small number of lines is used. Overall, the RMS also tends to improve (i.e. its value decreases) with increasing n_{stop} , until it stabilizes between $n_{\text{stop}} = 50$ and 100. Combining these features, I am able to locate the optimised control variables at ($n_{\text{sample}}, n_{\text{stop}}$) = (50, 100), ensuring a dense and statistically robust exploration of the sub-mask space (~ 9000 sub-masks are examined on average). A visual inspection of the Stokes I profiles resulting from the best sub-masks of the grid reveals that our algorithm identifies deep and sharp lines reliably when n_{sample} is decreased, which validates further our optimisation. From Fig. 2.10 we note that the output of our randomised algorithm can be strategically adapted according to the S/N tolerance of the observations,

Table 2.2: Number of sub-masks examined for each $(n_{\text{sample}}, n_{\text{stop}})$ combination of the simulation grid.

n_{sample}	20	50	100	200	500	1000	2000
n_{stop}							
10	3918	1689	857	394	161	72	34
20	6448	2504	1389	715	244	116	54
50	13464	5295	2588	1342	521	233	108
100	23208	9281	4549	2345	880	447	200

Figure 2.10: optimisation of the randomised algorithm control variables. The simulation grid for each $(n_{\text{sample}}, n_{\text{stop}})$ combination is shown, with data points color-coded and size-coded according to the RV RMS and number of lines within the sub-mask, respectively. The optimised $(n_{\text{sample}}, n_{\text{stop}})$ pair is (50, 100), ensuring both a precise RV data set and a dense exploration of the sub-mask space. Panels from left to right illustrate the 10th, 5th and 1st percentile case, respectively.

Figure 2.11: Testing the portability of the 2010-trained sub-masks to the 2007 data set of EV Lac, for the simulated grid of $(n_{\text{sample}}, n_{\text{stop}})$ combinations. We note that almost all the sub-masks yield the same RV RMS improvement for both 2007 and 2010 (i.e. the improvement ratio is close to 1), demonstrating the portability of the randomised approach output to other years than the training one. In few cases, the improvement ratio is either greater or lower than one, meaning that the benefit of the sub-mask is greater for 2007 or 2010, respectively. Panels from left to right illustrate the 10th, 5th and 1st percentile case, respectively.

i.e., the best sub-mask is chosen based on both the number of lines (hence, S/N) and achievable RV precision.

The simulated grid of sub-masks enables us to test their portability to other epochs in which the star has been observed. In particular, we examine whether the RV RMS improvement associated with each sub-mask can be transferred to the 2007 time series (15 observations), by performing LSD on this data set with the 2010-trained sub-masks of the grid. We then compute the RMS improvement ratio between 2007 and 2010, i.e. $\text{RMS}_{2007, 2010\text{-trained}} / \text{RMS}_{2010, 2010\text{-trained}}$, as shown in Fig. 2.11. Except for a couple of outliers, indicating sub-masks with a predominant benefit for a certain year, we observe a general ratio close to 1.0, demonstrating that the RMS improvement is the same for both years. Furthermore, we note the absence of outliers when n_{stop} is large, confirming our previous choice of $n_{\text{stop}}=100$.

Figure 2.12: Test of the f_{select} variable in the randomised algorithm, i.e. the fraction determining the number of draws each line must have to be included in the three percentile sub-masks. From top to bottom: using the full mask, $f_{select}=0.5$ sub-mask, $f_{select}=0.33$, and $f_{select}=0.25$. All the f_{select} cases refer to the 1st percentile sub-mask, as the other percentiles show deteriorated, but analogous features. In each panel the solid line indicates the sinusoidal fit at the stellra rotation period. We observe that $f_{select}=0.33$ is the best trade-off between number of lines included and achievable RV RMS.

In our randomised algorithm, the “stable” sub-masks are isolated based on the the 10th, 5th and 1st percentiles of the RV RMS distribution. Then, the three final sub-masks (one for each percentile) are built including lines that are drawn at least a fraction (f_{select}) of the maximum number of draws for the specific percentile. f_{select} is therefore an additional variable to be optimised, as it determines the number of lines in the best sub-mask and affects the achievable RV precision.

The simulation tests for (n_{sample}, n_{stop}) were performed with $f_{select}=0.5$. Here, we start from the optimised $(n_{sample}, n_{stop})=(50,100)$ run and compare the results using $f_{select}=0.25$, 0.33, and 0.5. From Fig. 2.12, we realize that $f_{select}=0.5$ is a strong constraint, given that we obtain a similar RV RMS for the other two cases, but with smaller number of lines. Instead, the $f_{select}=0.25$ is a weak constraint, yielding a deterioration in both RMS and semi-amplitude; this is evident with additional runs of the randomised algorithm. We therefore conclude that $f_{select}=0.33$ is the appropriate value to obtain a substantial improvement in RMS while maintaining a moderately large number of lines in the final sub-masks.

Selecting lines for the three percentile sub-masks based on a fraction of the maximum number of draws (for that percentile) may lead to a lower number of lines in the e.g. 5th percentile relative to the 1st. In fact, if only few sub-masks fall below the 1st percentile of the RV RMS distribution, the maximum number of draws will inevitably be small and consequently more lines will be selected in the

Figure 2.13: Distribution of the RV RMS associated with 9281 sub-masks of an example run with $n_{\text{sample}} = 50$ and $n_{\text{stop}} = 100$. Each RMS value is obtained after a $3\text{-}\sigma$ clipping of the RV data set, to prevent outliers from contaminating the distinction between “stable” and “unstable” sub-masks. The RMS values are sorted in ascending order and truncated at 1 km s^{-1} for visualization purposes (the maximum can reach up to 100 km s^{-1}). Shown are the 1st (black solid line) and 10th (dashed black line) percentiles of the distribution.

corresponding percentile sub-mask.

Finally, we tested an alternative method to build the three percentile sub-masks and use them in LSD. Instead of rejecting lines that do not satisfy the constraint imposed by f_{select} , we kept all the lines of the sub-masks within a percentile and employed the number of draws as an additional weight in the LSD computation. We therefore updated Eq. 2.2 by multiplying the weight on Stokes I with the number of draws. We found a systematic deterioration in both RMS and semi-amplitude for all three percentile sub-masks, relative to the $f_{\text{select}}=0.33$ case, of about 20-30%.

In the initial design, the technique was sampling the spectral lines with a probability proportional to their S/N. Then, the penalisation factor used to select the final combination of lines was the ratio between RV RMS and their S/N: lines with a ratio below the 50% percentile (i.e., the median) of the distribution were selected. Such design did not yield significant improvement in the final RV RMS (only a handful of m s^{-1}), hence it was discarded.

Training for stable lines

Fig. 2.13 and Fig. 2.14 illustrate the output for an example run. The full mask is associated with a RV RMS of 182 m s^{-1} and a semi-amplitude of 175 m s^{-1} . The best sub-mask in this case is composed of 198 lines, none of which falls in the telluric windows, and yields a $\sim 63\%$ reduction in the RV dispersion. Considering that a $>50\%$ RMS improvement is consistently achieved for multiple runs, we inspect the union of the output best sub-masks; in this case the S/N of the computed Stokes profile would benefit from an increased number of lines. We find that uniting two sub-masks (721 lines in total) reduces the RMS by the same amount as the individual ones, and that only four (out of 60) lines within the telluric windows are present in the sub-mask. Furthermore, the semi-amplitude is decreased by 51%, as shown in Fig. 2.15, reducing the RV modulation occurring at the stellar rotation period, and the RV precision remains around 5 m s^{-1} despite the lower number of lines than the full mask.

The purpose of the randomised approach is to train the best sub-mask on the year with the largest number of observations, and subsequently use it to reduce the RV dispersion of time series from other epochs. As mentioned previously, we performed tests of the sub-masks portability by using 2010-trained sub-masks on the 2007 data set and concluded that there is approximately the same benefit as when

Figure 2.14: Output from an example run of the randomised selection. Shown are the $3\text{-}\sigma$ clipped RV data sets computed using the full mask (black) and the sub-masks associated with the 10th (light-blue), 5th (dark blue), and 1st (green) percentiles of the RV RMS distribution.

Figure 2.15: Phase-folded plot of the RV time series computed with the union of two best sub-masks (721 lines). The RV RMS of the data set is reduced by 63%, and the RV semi-amplitude by 51% relative to the full mask case. Noteworthy is also the decreased residual scatter around the fit.

applied to the 2010 data set. We now compare the effects of using the 2007-trained best sub-mask on the 2007 data set with respect to the 2010-trained one. Starting from an initial 225 m s^{-1} dispersion, the two cases yield a 64% and 48% reduction, respectively, indicating that the benefit of the randomised approach is maximized when the data set examined coincides with the training data set. Even so, applying the 2010-trained best sub-mask on 2007 leads to a substantial improvement.

When the training is applied to a less-than-ideal data set, i.e. with few and sparse observations, the portability of our approach is compromised. We indeed tested the randomised algorithm on the 2006 observations (seven in total), and obtained a sub-mask yielding an impressive 73% improvement of the

Figure 2.16: Anti-correlation between BIS and RV for the data sets obtained with the full mask (black) and the union of the 2010-trained best sub-masks (green). We observe a decrease in the Pearson R coefficient, indicating a partial mitigation of the stellar activity contribution.

Figure 2.17: Mitigation of the activity signal seen in the periodograms. Left: GLS periodogram of the EV Lac 2010 RV data set obtained with the full mask. Right: Same but using the 2010-trained best sub-mask. We notice how the significance of the peak at the stellar rotation period decreases in the latter case, confirming the mitigating benefit of using the sub-mask derived from the randomised selection. There is a peak at 30 d showing an increase in power when the best sub-mask is applied. A period analysis of the window function (VanderPlas 2018) reveals that the peak is most likely due to the observing span (~ 2 months) and cadence of the 2010 data set.

dispersion (from 249 m s^{-1} to 67 m s^{-1}). However, when the same sub-mask was applied to the 2010 data set, we observed a severe (42%) degradation of the RV RMS. At the same time, using this sub-mask loses meaning, as it contained only seven lines. The photon noise in this case is increased by six times relative to the full mask.

Finally, when all epochs were considered, the application of the 2010-trained best sub-mask led to a consistent RMS improvement of 45% (from 242 m s^{-1} to 134 m s^{-1}).

Overall, because the RMS is blind to the source of dispersion, its systematic improvement does not imply that the “stable” lines extracted by our randomised approach are restricted to those insensitive

to activity. Indeed, telluric windows, instrumental errors (e.g. bad spectral orders), possible errors in the line list, or specific combinations of lines all introduce scatter to some degree, and are thus filtered out with our algorithm. This is noticeable when all observations are considered: in this case the activity signal has lost coherency thus, if the algorithm removes activity-sensitive lines only, using our sub-mask would be less beneficial.

The effect of stellar activity in RV data sets can be diagnosed by the presence of anti-correlation between bisector velocity span and measured radial velocity (see Sec 2.3). We therefore checked the variation of the anti-correlation when using the union of the 2010-trained best sub-masks and the full mask with the telluric windows removed a priori, to ensure that the variations in the RV data set are dominated by activity. We observed a decrease of the Pearson R coefficient from -0.68 to -0.46, implying that the best sub-mask mitigates the activity effect, but does not remove it completely (Fig. 2.16).

An additional way to show the mitigating effect of the 2010-trained best sub-mask is to inspect its impact on the GLS periodogram of the RV data sets, as illustrated in Fig. 2.17. We notice that the power (i.e. significance) of the peak associated with the stellar rotation period decreases of ~ 0.1 , implying that the corresponding activity signal is reduced. This feature occurs systematically also in the 2007 and full data sets when the 2010-trained best sub-mask is employed.

Training for unstable lines

We implement the randomised algorithm to work in the opposite direction, i.e. to isolate spectral lines that are susceptible to dispersive sources. If activity-sensitive lines are selected, the output data set could feature an enhanced modulation of the activity signal, therefore providing a more precise measurement of the stellar rotation period (useful for stellar physics and gyrochronology) and the possibility to model and filter the jitter efficiently. The difference is that the sub-masks are generated considering the 90th, 95th and 99th percentile of the RV RMS distribution. Because the sub-mask exploration given by the choice $(n_{\text{sample}}, n_{\text{stop}})=(50,100)$ leads also to line combinations with extreme RV RMS values (i.e. larger than the km s^{-1} level, see Fig.2.13), the three sub-masks associated with these percentiles will inevitably contain a low number of lines (less than 10) if built using $f_{\text{select}} = 0.33$ as for the “stable” lines. Therefore, we require the lines to be drawn at least a tenth of the maximum number of draws for the percentile ($f_{\text{select}} = 0.1$). Finally, from each of the three sub-masks, we remove the lines that are shared with the sub-masks obtained from the 10th, 5th and 1st percentiles, respectively, to additionally deteriorate the resulting RV dispersion.

The result is illustrated in Fig. 2.18. The worst sub-mask has 83 lines and the associated RV dispersion is increased from 182 to 13342 m s^{-1} (i.e. by 73 times). The measurements do not manifest an evident rotational modulation and span extreme values between -40 and 9 km s^{-1} , resulting in an artificially high RV semi-amplitude. Likewise, the union of the worst sub-masks from different runs of the algorithm does not yield useful insights.

We repeat the test, but cleaning the full mask of lines falling within telluric windows, similarly to Sec. 2.4.1. In this case, the algorithm produces a sub-mask of 2117 lines and with a corresponding RMS of 255 m s^{-1} (Fig. 2.18), 1.9 times larger than the initial value without telluric windows (133 m s^{-1}). The photon noise level is nine times lower than the RV RMS and it is seven times larger than when using the full mask, which could be due to a poorer modelling of the Stokes I profile when distorted and “unstable” lines are searched. Compared to the full mask, no evident trend is displayed in the depth, wavelength and g_{eff} distributions (see Fig. 2.19). Contrary to when the telluric windows are present, the RV data set shows a clearer rotational modulation, meaning that the worst sub-mask may contain more activity-sensitive lines. This marks the severe additional contamination that lines in telluric windows (or residuals from telluric correction) introduce when coexisting with the activity jitter as dispersion sources. Indeed, in that scenario, our algorithm does not precisely identify the most activity-impacted lines.

We test whether a different sub-mask selection criterion can improve the extraction of activity-sensitive lines. Instead of using the RV RMS, which does not distinguish random noise from a coherent signal, we select based on the semi-amplitude of the sinusoidal fit of the RV data set, exploiting the

Figure 2.18: Phase-folded plot of the 2010 RV time series of EV Lac computed with: the worst RMS-based sub-mask including telluric windows (top), the worst RMS-based sub-mask discarding telluric windows (middle), and the worst K -based sub-mask discarding telluric windows (bottom). The symbol “T” indicates that the telluric windows are removed from the start. The first case demonstrates how lines falling in telluric windows severely contaminate the RV measurements and thus prevent a precise selection of the worst sub-mask. The second case illustrates the improvement in finding the worst sub-mask containing activity-sensitive lines, providing a clear rotational modulation of the data set. The third case shows how selecting the sub-masks based on the RV semi-amplitude, i.e. a feature that is directly connected to activity, yields the most precise selection of activity-sensitive lines. The sinusoidal fit in each panel is computed analogously to Fig. 2.15.

modulated nature of the activity signal. In this case, the two-step algorithm performs a (Levenberg-Marquardt least squares) sinusoidal fit for the RV data set corresponding to a generated sub-mask. The

Figure 2.19: Distributions of the line parameters for three examined masks: the full mask without telluric windows a priori (top row), union of best sub-masks (central row), and 2010-trained worst RMS-based sub-mask without telluric windows a priori (bottom row). The parameters shown are (from left to right) depth, wavelength and Landé factor. The statistics (mean, median and standard deviation) of the depth distributions is $(\mu=0.73, \tilde{\mu}=0.74, \sigma=0.19)$, $(\mu=0.72, \tilde{\mu}=0.72, \sigma=0.18)$, and $(\mu=0.71, \tilde{\mu}=0.71, \sigma=0.19)$ for the three masks, respectively. Analogously, the wavelength distribution statistics (in nm) is $(\mu=433.1, \tilde{\mu}=401.2, \sigma=97.9)$, $(\mu=454.6, \tilde{\mu}=424.3, \sigma=88.9)$, and $(\mu=435.9, \tilde{\mu}=412.3, \sigma=75.8)$ and the g_{eff} statistics is $(\mu=1.25, \tilde{\mu}=1.21, \sigma=0.41)$, $(\mu=1.27, \tilde{\mu}=1.24, \sigma=0.42)$, and $(\mu=1.26, \tilde{\mu}=1.22, \sigma=0.41)$.

output sub-mask is then based on the distribution of K and should contain lines that are more sensitive to stellar activity than other dispersive sources. The output RV data set features a semi-amplitude increase from 172 to 373 m s^{-1} , a visible rotational modulation and a reduced scatter around the sinusoidal fit (Fig. 2.18), and a photon noise 13 times lower than the RMS, suggesting that the algorithm most likely isolates lines that are mainly sensitive to activity.

Lastly, shallow or low-S/N lines at the bluest and reddest boundaries of the full mask may represent a possible source of confusion, as they might bias the selection of the sub-mask and pollute the resulting RV dispersion measurement. We therefore discarded lines with effective S/N (i.e., S/N multiplied by normalized depth) lower than ten and repeated the test: no improvement was recorded for the identification of the worst sub-mask and the resulting RV dispersion increased even further. This is explained considering that the bluest lines ($\sim 400 \text{ nm}$) are deep, and thus less likely to be affected by velocity fields (as discussed in Sec. 2.4.1). In this sense, their presence stabilizes the results as indicated by a lower RV RMS of the data set. The presence (or absence) of the reddest lines ($\sim 1000 \text{ nm}$) has no significant impact on the results, since their number is negligible (< 20).

Interesting information is contained once again in the distributions of the line properties for dif-

Figure 2.20: Time series of the Stokes I profiles for the 2010 observations of EV Lac computed with (Left) the full mask without telluric window a priori, (Middle) union of the 2010-trained best sub-masks, and (Right) the 2010-trained worst RMS-based sub-mask without telluric windows a priori. The Stokes profiles are shifted vertically for visibility, and sorted with ascending observation date. We observe an increased sharpness when the union of best sub-masks is used, and a broad, distorted profile when the worst sub-mask is used, implying the presence of “stable” and “unstable” lines in the sub-masks, respectively.

ferent sub-masks, as well as in the shape of the associated Stokes I profiles. We therefore compare the distributions for three different masks: the full mask without telluric windows a priori (3240 lines), the 2010-trained union of best sub-masks (721 lines), and the 2010-trained worst RMS-based sub-mask without telluric windows a priori (2117 lines). In particular, we look at the distributions of line depth, wavelength and Landé factor (Fig. 2.19). The depth distribution for the full mask spans between 0.4 and 1.0 the continuum intensity, with a third of the lines deeper than 0.9 and with a mean of 0.73. The wavelength distribution features an almost exponential decay from 350 to 1080 nm and a mean of 433.1 nm, while the g_{eff} distribution ranges between 0.0 and 3.4, with a mean of 1.25 and two peaks at 1.0 and 1.5.

Apart from the different number of lines in the histogram bins due to our randomised downselection approach, the two other sub-masks do not feature particular trends or quantitative differences in the statistics, implying that it is not possible to straightforwardly build “stable” or “unstable” sub-masks with a selection based on these parameters. This is in agreement with the conclusions of Sec. 2.4.1. We note that lines between 600 and 700 nm are over-represented in the best mask, but they are too few to significantly affect the statistics.

Despite the absence of a particular feature in the distributions, the effects on Stokes I profiles of these masks are striking. From Fig. 2.20 we observe how the union of the best sub-masks leads to deeper and narrower profiles than the full mask, which would result in a more precise RV estimate. On the contrary, the application of the worst sub-mask yields shallow and distorted profiles, therefore increasing the dispersion of the associated RV data set. These features help us demonstrate further the capability of our algorithm to discern “stable” and “unstable” lines.

Figure 2.21: Phase-folded plot of the 2008 RV time series (26 observations) of DS Leo computed with (from the top): the full mask including telluric windows, the 2008-trained best sub-mask, the worst RMS-based sub-mask, and the worst K -based sub-mask. We use a stellar rotation period of 13.57 ± 0.04 d, computed via GLS periodogram. From the second panel we notice a remarkable reduction of both the RV dispersion and semi-amplitude, reaching the instrumental limitation of NARVAL (~ 30 m s^{-1}). The third and fourth panels display an RMS-based selection which is plagued by different sources of dispersion (telluric contamination in particular), and an ineffective K -based selection following the low level of activity of the star, respectively.

Training on other stars

We examine the efficiency and consistency of the randomised approach on AD Leo and the moderately active M1 dwarf DS Leo (GJ 410). DS Leo is a slower rotator, with a period of 13.83 d (Hébrard et al.

2016), and is the less active than EV Lac and AD Leo: $L_X/L_{\text{bol}} = -3.80$ (0.7 dex less than EV Lac) and $\log R'_{\text{HK}} = -4.16$ (0.41 dex less than EV Lac). Therefore, activity is not the dominant source of variability for DS Leo. In these cases, photon noise and instrumental stability are expected to dominate. For both AD Leo and DS Leo analysis, we do not remove the telluric windows from the initial mask.

For AD Leo, we train the best sub-mask on 14 optical observations collected in 2008. The RV dispersion of the data set computed with the full mask is 110 m s^{-1} , while our approach allows us to reach 26 m s^{-1} (76% improvement), i.e. consistent with the instrumental stability of NARVAL ($\sim 30 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, Moutou et al. 2007). In comparison, applying the 2010-trained best sub-mask obtained for EV Lac results in a 66% decrease in RMS, which extends the portability of the sub-mask trained for EV Lac to other active stars, and suggests that stars with similar properties (comparable spectral type, activity level, etc.) and atmospheres have similar “stable” lines. When searching for the maximum benefit overall, the sub-mask training should be performed on the most dense data set of each star separately.

For DS Leo, we apply the randomised approach on 26 optical observations collected in early 2008 (Fig. 2.21). Starting from a RV dispersion of 37 m s^{-1} and semi-amplitude of 23 m s^{-1} associated with the full mask, the 2008-trained best sub-mask yields a 46% and 22% reduction, respectively, reaching again the instrumental stability of NARVAL. This confirms that our approach is able to mitigate dispersion also on moderately active stars, where the contribution of telluric-affected lines is more important than EV Lac and AD Leo. In comparison to Hébrard et al. (2016), who employed HARPS-pol observations and Doppler mapping as activity-filtering technique, our values of 20 m s^{-1} and 18 m s^{-1} for dispersion and semi-amplitude are a factor of 2.5 and 1.2 higher, respectively. We will investigate the appealing possibility of combining our randomised line selection with Doppler mapping in Chapter 3.

We also attempt to isolate activity-sensitive lines using both an RMS and a semi-amplitude selection criterion. As DS Leo is less active than EV Lac, the randomised algorithm should be in principle less confused by the coexistence of different sources of noise. The results of the RMS-based selection are analogous although less extreme than EV Lac, with an RV dispersion amplified by a factor of 3.9 and the absence of a clear rotational modulation. The K -based selection increases the RMS by 1.5 and does not affect the semi-amplitude of the fit, as expected given the lower activity level. Moreover, an inspection of the RMS-based worst sub-mask content reveals that about 20 lines fall within telluric windows, at least 10 lines more than when the randomised approach is applied on EV Lac. This demonstrates further that the randomised algorithm is capable to better discern the sources of RV noise. Finally, we remove the 800 lines of the worst RMS-based sub-mask from the full mask (using 2500 lines in total), and note a 24% improvement in RV dispersion and a degradation of 30% in semi-amplitude, indicating that the best sub-mask training alone is already optimal to yield a substantial improvement.

Training with injected planets

We now investigate the application of the randomised algorithm when a synthetic planetary signal is included in the RV data sets. We carry out planetary recovery tests for both EV Lac and DS Leo, in order to study the detectability over two different activity regimes.

The planet injection is applied to all the collected spectra using

$$RV_p = K_p \sin \left(2\pi \left(\frac{t - T_0}{P_{\text{orb}}} \right) + \phi \right), \quad (2.9)$$

where we fixed $T_0 = 2450000$, $\phi=0.0$, $P_{\text{orb}}=10 \text{ d}$ and we assumed circular orbits. This value of orbital period is chosen since it is different enough from the rotation period of the stars, and short enough to be clearly detected in all data sets. We considered three planets separately with a $2\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$, $3\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$, and $4\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$ signal ($1\sigma_{\text{NAR}} = 30 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, i.e. the intrinsic stability of NARVAL), and corresponding to $0.3\text{-}0.6 M_{\text{Jup}}$ and $0.4\text{-}0.9 M_{\text{Jup}}$ planets for EV Lac and DS Leo, respectively. Note that the telluric contamination is not represented realistically in these simulations, as the whole wavelength axis is coherently shifted during injection. However, this limitation is only marginal considering the negligible planet-induced shift compared to the displacement of telluric lines with respect to stellar lines throughout a year.

Table 2.3: Summary of all tests and simulations outlined in Sec. 2.4.2. The columns are: (1) the specific (sub-)mask and epoch considered, (2) the number of lines in the sub-mask, (3) the RMS of the data set, (4) the RV precision from the MC simulations, (5) the semi-amplitude of the sinusoidal fit to the data set, (6) the reduced χ^2 , and (7) the RMS of the fit residuals. The symbol “T” indicates that telluric windows are removed from the full mask. The number of observations for EV Lac are 20 in 2010, 15 in 2007, 7 in 2006, for AD Leo 14 in 2008 and DS Leo 26 in 2008.

Case	n_{lines}	RMS [m s ⁻¹]	RV_p [m s ⁻¹]	K [m s ⁻¹]	χ^2_ν	RMS_{res} [m s ⁻¹]
EV Lac						
Full mask - 2010	3300	182	4	175	23.7	134
Example run 10th percentile - 2010	666	79	11	105	1.2	30
Example run 5th percentile - 2010	636	79	19	104	1.3	31
Example run 1st percentile - 2010	198	67	14	93	1.2	30
Union of best - 2010	721	68	8	86	1.4	32
Full mask - 2007	3300	225	5	129	60	204
2010-trained best - 2007	198	118	17	142	6.2	66
2007-trained best - 2007	26	82	16	77	5.7	64
Full mask - 2006	3300	249	4	282	42.6	147
2006-trained best - 2010	7	259	24	140	78.4	244
Full mask - all epochs	3300	242	5	101	62.7	231
Union of 2010-trained - all epochs	721	69	7	96	15.2	113
2010-trained worst RMS-based - 2010	83	13342	44	12718	1.3x10 ⁵	10041
Full mask - 2010 (T)	3240	133	5	172	3.3	50
2010-trained worst RMS-based - 2010 (T)	2117	255	28	326	26.7	142
2010-trained worst K -based - 2010 (T)	2209	246	19	373	7.6	76
AD Leo						
Full mask - 2008	3300	110	2	80	14.2	100
2008-trained best - 2008	524	26	5	42	0.3	13
Union of EVLac-2010-trained best - 2008	721	31	4	37	0.7	21
DS Leo						
Full mask - 2008	3300	37	2	23	1.5	34
2008-trained best - 2008	571	20	3	18	0.35	16
2008-trained worst RMS-based - 2008	800	143	6	51	24.4	138
2008-trained worst K -based - 2008	845	59	3	20	4.2	57
Full mask without worst RMS-based - 2008	2500	29	2	29	0.64	22

Figure 2.22: Generalised Lomb-Scargle periodograms of the full RV time series for EV Lac. Left: periodogram of the data set obtained with the full mask and a $2\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$ injected planet. Middle: periodograms of the residuals (of a sinusoidal fit at the stellar rotation period) obtained with the three 2010-trained percentile sub-masks and a $2\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$ injected planet. Right: periodograms of the residuals (of a sinusoidal fit at the stellar rotation period) obtained with the three 2010-trained percentile sub-masks and a $4\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$ injected planet. In each panel, the stellar rotation period and injected planetary period are indicated by a dotted and solid red line, respectively. When the 2010-trained sub-masks are used, we observe a systematic quench of the peak at the stellar rotation period and the rise of the peak at the injected orbital period as the mass of the planet increases. In the $2\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$ case, the planetary peak is not distinguishable because the dispersion is still twice larger, while in the $4\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$ case the peak becomes the highest one (with $\text{FAP} > 1\%$).

The training of the best sub-masks is performed on the injected spectra of the densest year for the two stars, analogously to the previous sections. The three percentile best sub-masks are then applied to the full time series comprising 57 and 93 observations spanning between 2005-2016 and 2006-2014 for EV Lac and DS Leo, respectively. Using the full time series allows us to have a time span that is more representative of a RV planet search, with an expected loss of coherency of the activity signal, but the sampling is not optimal, therefore hindering our planetary signal retrieval. The results for both stars are summarised in Table 2.4; the RV precision is not reported since in all cases it is compatible with the values in Table 2.3 for each star.

For EV Lac, the dispersion of the RV data set computed with the full mask is $8\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$, hence no injected planetary signal is detectable. The application of the three percentile best sub-masks enables the signal to emerge instead. Compared to the full mask, for which there is more variability, the sub-masks cases feature a decrease in RMS larger than 43%, translating in a more constrained model (sinusoidal fit at the stellar rotation period) and therefore cleaner RV residuals. This is confirmed by the systematic reduction in χ^2_{ν} , even though its absolute estimate suggests that our method does not account entirely for the random activity. We also apply a GLS periodogram to the residuals and find that the power of the 10 d period peak increases (more significantly in the $4\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$ case) when the sub-masks are used (Fig. 2.22). By re-phasing the RV residuals with P_{orb} , we indeed reveal the expected planetary modulation (Fig. 2.23) and we extract a semi-amplitude which is lower, but consistent with the injected one within uncertainties. Moreover, we observe that the best (i.e. lowest RMS) of the three percentile sub-mask is also the one that removes the planetary signal the most (with K residuals reduced by at least 30%). This indicates a possible trade-off in the choice of the percentile sub-mask to choose, which should be considered on a case-by-case basis.

For DS Leo, the results are analogous and complementary to EV Lac, since we recover all planetary signals within error bars. With a lower activity level, the improvement represented by using the three percentile sub-masks is only marginal, and the semi-amplitude of the corresponding RV residuals is consistent with the estimate of the full mask (less than 24% in all cases). This reinforces our finding that the randomised line downselection does not significantly suppress the planetary signal with respect to the full mask. Similarly to EV Lac, we also observe that the lowest-RMS percentile sub-mask underestimates the retrieved semi-amplitude.

Removing the telluric windows from the start has a beneficial effect for the full mask (see Table 2.4),

Figure 2.23: Phase-folded RV data sets of EV Lac when using the full mask and the 10th, 5th and 1st percentile sub-masks on all the epochs with a $2\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$ synthetic planet (red dashed line). The raw RV data sets phased at the stellar rotation period (upper panel) and the residuals to the sinusoidal fit phased at the planet orbital period (bottom panel) are illustrated. The planetary signal is evidently recovered when using the three percentile sub-masks, whereas the variability of the data set associated with the full mask does not enable a reliable recovery.

Figure 2.24: Same as Fig. 2.23 for DS Leo. We observe no substantial difference between using the full mask or the three percentile sub-masks, meaning that the planetary signal is recovered with the same confidence.

Table 2.4: Results of the planetary injection tests, for both EV Lac and DS Leo. The columns are: (1) the specific (sub-)mask considered, (2) the number of lines in the sub-mask, (3) the RMS of the data set, (4) the semi-amplitude of the sinusoidal fit to the data set (phased at the stellar rotation period), (5) the reduced χ^2 , and (6) the RMS of the fit residuals and (7) the semi-amplitude of the residuals (phased at the injected orbital period), (8) the reduced χ^2 of the residual sinusoidal fit, and (9) the power of the injected P_{orb} peak when a GLS is applied on the residual data set. We consider a $2\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$, $3\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$, and $4\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$ circular planet on a 10 d orbit separately and train the best sub-masks on the densest epochs. The sub-masks are then used on the full time series for both stars. The units are m s^{-1} in columns (3), (4), (6) and (7) and the symbol ‘‘T’’ indicates that the telluric windows are removed from the full mask. Formal uncertainties for the semi-amplitude are reported.

Case	n_{lines}	RMS	K	χ^2_{ν}	RMS_{res}	K_{res}	$\chi^2_{\nu,\text{res}}$	Power
EV Lac								
Full mask with $2\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$ planet	3300	244	96 ± 45	64.7	234	90 ± 41	59.2	0.08
Full mask with $2\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$ planet (T)	3240	169	120 ± 27	24.8	145	53 ± 28	23.2	0.07
10th percentile with $2\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$ planet	1133	139	99 ± 23	16.7	119	42 ± 22	15.6	0.06
5th percentile with $2\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$ planet	385	131	88 ± 21	15.4	114	44 ± 22	14.3	0.08
1st percentile with $2\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$ planet	58	121	77 ± 22	13.9	108	37 ± 22	13.1	0.05
Full mask with $3\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$ planet	3300	248	95 ± 46	66.9	238	108 ± 41	59.1	0.12
Full mask with $3\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$ planet (T)	3240	174	117 ± 28	27.0	151	82 ± 28	23.1	0.14
10th percentile with $3\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$ planet	1133	144	97 ± 23	15.6	125	71 ± 23	15.6	0.16
5th percentile with $3\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$ planet	385	136	85 ± 22	17.3	121	73 ± 23	14.2	0.18
1st percentile with $3\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$ planet	58	126	67 ± 22	16.0	116	59 ± 23	14.0	0.13
Full mask with $4\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$ planet	3300	253	92 ± 47	70.1	244	131 ± 41	59.0	0.16
Full mask with $4\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$ planet (T)	3240	180	115 ± 30	30.1	160	111 ± 28	23.1	0.23
10th percentile with $4\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$ planet	1133	151	94 ± 23	21.4	134	101 ± 25	15.6	0.27
5th percentile with $4\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$ planet	385	144	82 ± 22	20.2	131	102 ± 25	14.2	0.29
1st percentile with $4\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$ planet	58	134	62 ± 22	18.9	126	88 ± 26	14.3	0.24
DS Leo								
Full mask with $2\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$ planet	3300	75	26 ± 11	6.1	73	52 ± 9	4.4	0.27
Full mask with $2\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$ planet (T)	3240	57	20 ± 8	3.6	55	58 ± 6	1.5	0.59
10th percentile with $2\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$ planet	631	55	19 ± 8	3.3	53	53 ± 5	1.5	0.55
5th percentile with $2\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$ planet	396	54	19 ± 8	3.2	52	51 ± 5	1.5	0.52
1st percentile with $2\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$ planet	566	50	18 ± 7	2.7	48	44 ± 5	1.4	0.47
Full mask with $3\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$ planet	3300	149	30 ± 22	25.3	148	105 ± 18	18.5	0.27
Full mask with $3\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$ planet (T)	3240	76	27 ± 11	6.3	74	86 ± 5	1.6	0.74
10th percentile with $3\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$ planet	631	73	26 ± 10	5.8	71	81 ± 5	1.6	0.72
5th percentile with $3\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$ planet	396	72	26 ± 10	5.6	69	79 ± 5	1.7	0.71
1st percentile with $3\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$ planet	566	67	23 ± 10	4.9	65	72 ± 5	1.6	0.68
Full mask with $4\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$ planet	3300	106	41 ± 15	12.1	102	108 ± 9	4.8	0.60
Full mask with $4\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$ planet (T)	3240	97	35 ± 14	10.1	93	114 ± 6	1.8	0.82
10th percentile with $4\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$ planet	631	93	34 ± 13	9.3	90	109 ± 6	1.8	0.80
5th percentile with $4\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$ planet	396	92	34 ± 13	9.1	88	106 ± 6	1.9	0.72
1st percentile with $4\sigma_{\text{NAR}}$ planet	566	85	28 ± 13	8.0	83	99 ± 6	1.7	0.79

since the dispersion of the data set is decreased. In comparison, the output percentile sub-masks lead to both a lower dispersion and a more constrained sinusoidal fit of the RV residuals, quantified by a lower χ^2_{ν} . We also observe similar periodogram powers at the injected P_{orb} both with the telluric-removed full mask and the three sub-masks, further indicating that our method discerns planetary signals.

We performed a similar analysis considering only the two densest epochs for each star (2007 and 2010 for EV Lac, and 2008 and 2010 for DS Leo). The idea is to exploit the increased coherence of the

activity signal and obtain two separate and improved sinusoidal fits at the stellar rotation period. We combined the respective residuals into a single data set and examined its periodic content analogously to the full time series case (GLS periodogram and re-phasing at P_{orb}). For EV Lac, the results with the sub-masks show no substantial change, while for DS Leo we underestimate the retrieved planetary semi-amplitude in a systematic way, probably following the low activity level of the star and thus the absence of dominant signal to filter out.

The overall positive outcome of the planetary injection tests demonstrates that our randomised approach is capable of finding the least dispersive lines without prior information on telluric windows, while preserving the planetary signal. This is especially important in view of near-infrared RV planet searches, as an accurate telluric correction in this domain is notoriously challenging (Artigau et al. 2014).

2.5 Application to near-infrared data

In terms of activity proxies, the near-infrared is a rather uncharted territory, relative to the optical. Studies by Schöfer et al. (2019) and Fuhrmeister et al. (2019) have shown that the HeI triplet at 1080.3 nm, known to trace extreme ultraviolet irradiation from stellar coronae, is a useful diagnostic that correlates with $H\alpha$ emission and flaring events. Klein et al. (2021) demonstrated that it is a practical tracer of RV variations for the young, active M dwarf AU Mic. In comparison, $\text{Pa}\beta$ traces different (more polar) regions, while $\text{Br}\gamma$ does not show rotational modulation. Terrien et al. (2022) investigated the KI line at 1243.5 nm, and reported rotationally-modulated variations consistent with photospheric magnetic fields changes. The line indeed features Zeeman splitting (see Sec. 4.1.1). However, the line has neither sensitivity to flares, nor a correlation/anti-correlation with $H\alpha$ emission (Fuhrmeister et al. 2022).

Other indicators based on specific spectral lines are currently investigated (Cortes-Zuleta et al. 2023). Some aspects add complexity to this task: different lines are sensitive to different active regions, and the diagnostic power of a line varies as the active region evolves with time. Therefore, the absence of a correlation with known activity tracers does not necessarily exclude a certain line.

With this in mind, I proceeded to extend the line selection activity-filtering technique in the unexplored near-infrared. In this section, I will outline some preliminary work aimed at extending the applicability of the technique in this domain. The idea is to combine the activity-mitigating power of the technique with the supposedly lower jitter at near-infrared wavelengths (Baroch et al. 2020).

The tests are carried out on EV Lac and DS Leo data sets collected with SPIrou, the near-infrared spectropolarimeter at Canada-France-Hawaii Telescope (more details in Sec. 4.3.1). The data reduction has been performed with *A PipelinE to Reduce Observations* (APER0 v0.6.132, Cook et al. 2022). EV Lac has 163 observations between September 2019 and November 2021, and DS Leo 130 observations between November 2020 and June 2022. As opposed to the optical data sets, here we have collected data sets suited to RV planet search: densely sampled with many points, and using a very stable instrument. The same data set is used for magnetic field analysis in Chapter 5.

Once again, high-S/N Stokes profiles are computed for unpolarised (I) and circularly polarised (V) light using LSD. Considering that the near-infrared domain is polluted by deep telluric absorption bands originated in the Earth's atmosphere, we ignored the following spectral intervals: [950, 979], [1081, 1169], [1328, 1492], [1790, 1985], [1995, 2029], [2380, 2500] nm. Basically, we are removing spectral bands where the signal is very low and that would be assigned a small weight in LSD anyway. We proceed this way to be conservative, and prevent imperfections in the telluric correction to affect the outcome of the RV analysis. To assess whether removing these telluric intervals optimises the quality of the Stokes V profiles, we carried out a couple of tests: first, we searched for stellar absorption lines deeper than 75% of the continuum level and within $\pm 100 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ from telluric lines included in the transmission model of APER0 (see Sec. 4.3.1 for more details). This approach allowed us to identify stellar lines that are contaminated by the displacement of telluric lines throughout the year. When the telluric-affected spectral lines were removed, no significant improvement was reported in the final LSD profiles. In a second test, we extended the intervals by 25 and 50 nm or reduced them by 10 nm and noticed an

Figure 2.25: Radial velocity and longitudinal magnetic field curves of SPIRou time series. The data points are phase-folded at the stellar rotation period of EV Lac (left) and DS Leo (right), and are computed with the full mask (black), magnetically sensitive (yellow), and insensitive (purple) sub-masks. The RV variations of EV Lac are better represented by a sine fit including a signal at the first harmonic ($P_{\text{rot}}/2$).

increment of the noise level in LSD profiles up to 20 %, so we proceeded with the previous intervals. Considering these exclusions, the number of lines of a synthetic, near-infrared mask of atomic lines associated with $T_{\text{eff}} = 3,500 \text{ K}$, $\log g = 5.0 \text{ [cm s}^{-2}\text{]}$, $v_{\text{micro}} = 1 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, and depth larger than 3% the continuum level is therefore reduced from 1400 to 830.

2.5.1 Parametric selection

I started from a direct selection based on the main parameters of the line mask similarly to Sec. 2.4.1. I inspected line selection effects on both RV and B_l curves for the entire SPIRou time series, and I assessed the quality of the sub-masks mainly based on the RMS of the corresponding curves. The threshold defining the sub-masks are set to ensure the same Stokes V S/N, and are indicated in Table 2.5 along with the results. The photon noise remains limited compared to the RV RMS in all cases considered, but when unstable (e.g., shallow) lines are selected, we note a severe increase.

At start, the RV RMS for EV Lac and DS Leo with the full mask is 411 m s^{-1} and 50 m s^{-1} , respectively, roughly two times larger compared to the optical domain. Part of the difference can be attributed to the Zeeman splitting (see Sec. 4.1.1), for which red lines of magnetically active stars are sensitive to. This effect produces additional broadening for some lines and an evident splitting of the central core for others, resulting in increased distortions of the LSD profiles. As a consequence, the principle of self-similarity at the base of LSD, for which spectral lines are assumed to be of equal shape and differ only by a scaling factor, may have less validity. Furthermore, the activity jitter does not simply decrease in near-infrared because of chromatic photospheric-spot contrast, but shows a more subtle trend, as already pointed out by Reiners et al. (2013) for AD Leo. In terms of B_l , we see that the RMS has increased in near-infrared for EV Lac by 16%, and decreased for DS Leo by 41%. Along with a physical difference between the two wavelength domains, the values may reflect an underlying long-term evolution of the magnetic field, which will be inspected in Chapter 5. Furthermore, possible origins of such difference result from the fact that the SPIRou data sets are densely collected over 2-3 yr, while the archival optical data are sparse and over ~ 10 yr.

The semi-amplitude (K) of RV variations is twice larger for EV Lac in near-infrared, while it is

Table 2.5: Summary of the RV and B_l data sets characteristics when using near-infrared SPIRou data sets. The columns are: (1) the parametric criteria used, (2) the number of lines in the sub-mask, (3) the RMS of the data set, (4) the RV precision from the MC simulations, (5) the semi-amplitude of the sinusoidal fit to the data set (or sine+harmonic when EV Lac RV values are concerned), (6) the reduced χ^2 , and (7) the RMS of the fit residuals. Columns (8)-(12) are the same as (3)-(7) but for DS Leo. The RV statistics refer to 163 observations for EV Lac and 130 observations for DS Leo.

Selection	n_{lines}	EV Lac					DS Leo				
		RMS	RV_p	K	χ^2_ν	RMS_{res}	RMS	RV_p	K	χ^2_ν	RMS_{res}
Radial Velocity [m s^{-1}]											
Atomic	1400	411	40	221 ± 27	4884	346	50	6	25 ± 5	90.4	46
$d < 0.1$	469
$d > 0.1$	358	413	38	217 ± 27	5009	350	47	6	24 ± 5	81.2	44
$\lambda > 1650 \text{ nm}$	307	3969	1716	1128 ± 305	$6 \cdot 10^5$	3805	134	14	32 ± 16	717.5	132
$\lambda < 1650 \text{ nm}$	524	276	30	199 ± 14	1473	190	48	6	23 ± 5	84.8	45
$g_{\text{eff}} > 1.2$	417	762	80	287 ± 56	$2 \cdot 10^4$	706	77	7	36 ± 9	217.8	72
$g_{\text{eff}} < 1.2$	406	333	40	207 ± 20	2741	259	45	8	16 ± 5	78.0	43
Molecular	3904	75	3	25 ± 5	206	71	57	3	20 ± 7	129.5	56
CO lines	1208	28	4	8 ± 2	31	27	26	3	6 ± 3	27.6	25
Longitudinal Magnetic Field [G]											
Atomic	1400	199	...	261 ± 8	15.8	84	20	...	22 ± 1	3.7	14
$d < 0.1$	469
$d > 0.1$	358	197	...	257 ± 8	15.2	82	20	...	22 ± 1	3.8	14
$\lambda > 1650 \text{ nm}$	307	237	...	285 ± 11	25.0	107	22	...	21 ± 2	5.9	17
$\lambda < 1650 \text{ nm}$	524	192	...	250 ± 8	16.0	81	22	...	22 ± 1	4.7	16
$g_{\text{eff}} > 1.2$	417	199	...	256 ± 9	16.0	86	18	...	20 ± 1	3.0	12
$g_{\text{eff}} < 1.2$	406	178	...	226 ± 8	16.7	86	25	...	18 ± 2	9.6	22

compatible for DS Leo. Note however that the phase-folded variations of EV Lac manifest a clear harmonic structure, hence K in this case refers to a sinusoidal fit with an additional periodic component at $P_{\text{rot}}/2$, as presented in Fig. 2.25. The harmonic signal may be introduced by the fact that the large-scale magnetic field of EV Lac features a non-axisymmetric dipole geometry (Morin et al. 2008b), hence the RV vary each time we observe one polarity of the field. With the dense sampling of the SPIRou observations we are more sensitive to such variations compared to the optical data sets. For B_l , the semi-amplitude is also larger than the optical, but the variations are all sinusoidal.

Results of parametric approach

When split based on depth, we realise that shallow ($d < 0.1$) lines yield meaningless Stokes profiles, as illustrated in Fig. 2.26, hence both the RV and B_l computations fail. If I lower the depth threshold, I note that lines shallower than 0.05 the unpolarised continuum are the problematic ones. On the contrary, deep lines contain most of the signal, as RMS and K in both RV and B_l are the same as the full mask. This is not surprising, since the LSD computation is S/N-weighted, meaning that the contribution of shallow lines is basically neglected.

When split based on wavelength, we note that bluer ($\lambda < 1650 \text{ nm}$) lines yield a 33% RV RMS improvement for EV Lac, while a marginal 4% for DS Leo. The semi-amplitude is only improved by 20% for EV Lac. Redder ($\lambda > 1650 \text{ nm}$) lines are visibly broader and shallower (Fig. 2.26), and lead to severely deteriorated scatter, a factor of ~ 10 for EV Lac and 2.7 for DS Leo. Regardless of the wavelength selection, B_l does not feature significant changes, the RMS being slightly improved (up to 4%) or deteriorated (up to 16%) for bluer and redder lines.

When split based on Landé factor, the magnetically insensitive ($g_{\text{eff}} < 1.2$) sub-mask yields an RV

Figure 2.26: Near-infrared mask of atomic lines with known Landé factor and sample of Stokes I profiles for the same near-infrared SPIRou observations, but computed with different atomic sub-masks. Left: $d > 0.1$ (dark pink) and $d < 0.1$ (light pink) lines. The latter are unusable. Middle: $\lambda < 1650$ (blue) and $\lambda > 1650$ nm (orange) lines. The latter are broad and distorted. Right: $g_{\text{eff}} < 1.2$ and $g_{\text{eff}} > 1.2$ lines. Vertical dashed lines indicate the RV measurement.

RMS of 333 m s^{-1} (19% decrease) and 45 m s^{-1} (10% decrease) for EV Lac and DS Leo, respectively. At the same time, K is 207 m s^{-1} (6% reduction) and 16 m s^{-1} (40% reduction) relative to the full mask. Lines with high Landé factor ($g_{\text{eff}} > 1.2$) deteriorate the RV dispersion and K for both stars. The RMS increases by a factor of 1.8 and 1.5 for EV Lac and DS Leo, and K by 1.3 and 1.4. Once again, the B_l values are robust against the line selection, giving similar properties as the full mask. The largest change is recorded for EV Lac, since the RMS is reduced by 11% and K by 16% when using magnetically insensitive lines, remaining marginally consistent with other sub-masks. At the same time, we observe that the scatter in B_l for DS Leo increases for the $g_{\text{eff}} < 1.2$ sub-mask, probably due to the progressive disappearance of Zeeman signatures for magnetically insensitive lines (see Sec. 4.1.1). This indicates that optimised velocimetry and magnetometry should be carried out with different sets of lines.

If we compare these results with the optical analysis performed in Sec. 2.4.1, we note that the RV precision is more susceptible to the selected near-infrared lines. While a straightforward approach did not yield any preferential line property with which to choose lines when applied to optical data, in near-infrared we would tend to conclude that deep, bluer and magnetically insensitive lines represent a sweet-spot to perform precise RV measurement. In contrast, the longitudinal field is robust against any (meaningful) line selection, yielding reasonably compatible dispersion and rotationally-modulated semi-amplitude, despite the case above for DS Leo.

Figure 2.27: Computing LSD Stokes profiles with a synthetic near-infrared molecular mask. Left: the mask, where the y axis indicates the depth as a percentage of unpolarised continuum. Right: Comparison of atomic (orange) and molecular (red) Stokes I profiles overplotted for all observations. In the solid black line is the median profile in either case. It is evident how molecular lines are narrower and deeper, resulting in more precise RV measurements.

Figure 2.28: Radial velocity curves phase-folded at the stellar rotation period of EV Lac. Left: Computation with molecular mask. Right: Computation with ($\lambda > 2200$ nm) CO mask. In both panels, the black data points are computed with the full atomic mask, for comparison. We note that the dispersion and rotational modulation is severely reduced when molecules, and especially CO lines, are adopted.

2.5.2 CO lines

Exploiting the wavelength coverage of SPIRou fully, I performed a similar analysis using a molecular mask containing 4670 lines (3900 in the range of SPIRou observations). As depicted in Fig. 2.27, the mask is composed by overtones of distinct molecules: OH, CO, CN, and MgH. The corresponding Stokes I profile is sharper than when computed with the atomic mask, and the continuum is more easily identified. An important aspect to consider is that the quantum description of molecules is more complicated than atoms, hence line properties such as Landé factor are not well-known. Most of the lines in the mask do not possess a value of g_{eff} , which prevents us from computing a circularly polarised Stokes profile. Consequently, we cannot compute useful activity proxies like the longitudinal magnetic field.

From Fig. 2.27, we note that there is a dense forest of lines in K band. Indeed, this is the first overtone of the roto-vibrational transitions of CO (around 2300 nm; Goorvitch 1994), which were already established to feature narrow and deep lines, suitable for RV measurements (Bean et al. 2010). These CO lines are indeed insensitive to the Zeeman effect ($g_{\text{eff}}=0$). For instance Reiners et al. (2013) saw that the RV RMS associated CO lines did not display a chromatic trend, contrarily to other (atomic) lines. At the same time, they are not sensitive to magnetic fields, since line distortions are minimised even for strong fields. Caution should be exerted when using these lines, as they fall within deep telluric

Figure 2.29: Example runs of the randomised approach for near-infrared SPIRou data of EV Lac (left) and DS Leo (right). shown are the atomic (top) and molecular (bottom) cases when telluric intervals are included a priori. The algorithm outputs percentile sub-masks that reduce the RV scatter significantly. The dispersion around the sinusoidal (or sine plus first harmonic) fit is decreased as well.

absorption bands, therefore an accurate recipe that cleans their contamination is a crucial requirement. In my case, the telluric contribution to SPIRou spectra is handled by a Principal Component Analysis method integrated within APERO (Artigau et al. 2014; Cook et al. 2022; more details in Sec. 4.3.1). In the following, I do not remove any telluric interval a priori.

I compute RV time series with the entire molecular mask and the $\lambda > 2200$ nm CO lines, as illustrated in Fig. 2.28. The statistics is reported in Table 2.5. When all molecules are used, the RV RMS and semi-amplitude are decreased by 83% and 87% for EV Lac, respectively. For DS Leo, the RV RMS is slightly increased by 7%, while K is reduced by 20%. The RMS increase is probably generated by including shallow molecular lines in the mask. Noteworthy is the case of CO lines, for which the RV RMS is decreased to 28 m s^{-1} (92% reduction) and K to 8 m s^{-1} (96% reduction) for EV Lac, and 26 m s^{-1} (48%) and 6 m s^{-1} (76%) for DS Leo. This corroborates the robustness of CO lines when precise RV measurements are targeted, as they allow m s^{-1} precision even for very active M dwarfs like EV Lac. For completeness, when atomic and molecular lines are adopted altogether, the results are generally deteriorated.

2.5.3 Randomised selection

I applied the randomised algorithm to both EV Lac and DS Leo data. I trained the sub-masks on subsets of the respective time series, namely late 2020 - beginning of 2021 (2020b2021a, 67 observations) for EV Lac and late 2021 - beginning of 2022 for DS Leo (2021b2022a, 69 observations). Stable lines were sought for three cases: from the atomic mask when telluric intervals are removed (830 initial lines), from the atomic mask including telluric intervals (1300 initial lines), and from the molecular mask including telluric intervals (3900 initial lines). Considering the large number of molecular lines, I set the control variables to $(n_{\text{sample}}, n_{\text{stop}}, f_{\text{select}}) = (50, 100, 0.33)$ to ensure a dense sampling of 10^4 sub-masks. For the same reason, I adopted $(n_{\text{sample}}, n_{\text{stop}}, f_{\text{select}}) = (20, 100, 0.20)$ when considering both cases of atomic lines, since the initial number of lines to sample from is smaller. The results are listed in Table 2.6 and a couple examples are reported in Fig. 2.29.

The randomised algorithm is successful for the cases examined. For EV Lac, when using the per-

centile sub-masks obtained from the atomic mask with telluric intervals excluded, the RV RMS is reduced by at least 60%, from 387 m s^{-1} to 160 m s^{-1} , and K by $> 50\%$, from 225 m s^{-1} to 63 m s^{-1} . For DS Leo, there is a systematic reduction of at least a factor of two in both RMS and K as well. For both stars, the improvement is accompanied by a reduced scatter around the sinusoidal fit, encapsulated by a lower reduced χ^2 , as well as only a marginally increased photon noise.

The benefit of the sub-masks is enhanced when the telluric intervals are not removed a priori. In this case, as opposed to the optical, we are dealing with telluric lines residuals (after correction) and the associated decrease in S/N. Both the RMS and K reach similar (slightly larger) values to when the telluric intervals are excluded, confirming the power of the algorithm in efficiently filtering out lines that are affected by telluric lines. For EV Lac, the reduction in RMS and K is a factor of 4.4-5.0 and 1.8-2.7 from an initial 751 m s^{-1} and 213 m s^{-1} , respectively. For DS Leo, the reduction in RMS and K is a factor of 2.0-2.5 and 2.0-6.0 from an initial 60 m s^{-1} and 34 m s^{-1} , respectively. Some sub-masks are composed by only a handful of lines, and correspondingly the photon noise increases.

For the molecular mask, the RMS and K gains are on the same level as the previous cases for EV Lac and larger for DS Leo. We achieve RV RMS of $\sim 25 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ for EV Lac, which is comparable to the direct selection of CO lines, and consistent with the fact that the RV variability of EV Lac appears dominated by the Zeeman effect (hence is quenched with $g_{\text{eff}} = 0$ CO lines). For DS Leo, we reach $\sim 10 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, twice smaller than when only CO lines were adopted. Depending on the star considered, the output of the randomised algorithm could surpass the CO lines then, but further tests are needed.

When looking at the distribution of depth, wavelength and Landé factor of the percentile sub-masks against the full atomic or molecular mask (see Fig. 2.30), no particular trend emerge. Indeed, the structure of the respective full mask distribution is maintained (with smaller counts by construction). However, for both atomic and molecular lines, the statistics of the distribution reveal a slight but consistent tendency to prefer deep, low- g_{eff} and bluer lines, in accordance to the conclusions of the parametric near-infrared analysis (see Sec. 2.5.1). This means that, with respect to the optical domain, it could be possible to select the most stable lines for precise RV measurements based on a combination of parameters, but additional tests are necessary. Another difference seems that the 1st percentile sub-mask does not perform as well as in the optical domain, since the algorithm starts from a low number of lines in the full mask.

2.6 Summary

Parametric selection

From the results of this first approach applied to the optical domain, we conclude that building a sub-mask using a direct selection based on the line parameters does not significantly reduce the effect of activity jitter on RV measurements. A comparison between RV RMS and precision indeed confirms that the dominant source of noise in the data sets is the activity jitter, which is unchanged and one order of magnitude larger than photon noise regardless of the line selection (see Table 2.1). The presence of RV shifts when using different sub-masks emphasizes the importance of always using the same mask for a RV time series, i.e. always excluding lines that for some observations are blended with telluric lines or fall at the edge the echelle order. Finally, this analysis confirms the robustness of B_l because the measurements show a clear rotational modulation and are all reasonably consistent, provided that the mask contains deep lines.

Randomised selection

The randomised approach applied to the optical domain successfully produces sub-masks with stable lines, i.e. that significantly improve the RV RMS. We obtain a reduction of RV dispersion by more than 50%, both from sub-masks that are individually output by the algorithm or from the union of sub-masks belonging to different runs. The photon-noise-induced RV dispersion is always well-below the overall scatter of the data points, indicating that the dominant source of noise is stellar activity and

Table 2.6: Summary of all tests and simulations outlined in Sec. 2.4.2. The columns are: (1) the specific (sub-)mask and epoch considered, (2) the number of lines in the sub-mask, (3) the RMS of the data set, (4) the RV precision from the MC simulations, (5) the semi-amplitude of the sinusoidal fit to the data set, (6) the reduced χ^2 , and (7) the RMS of the fit residuals. The symbol “T” indicates that telluric windows are removed from the full mask. The number of observations for EV Lac is 67 in 2020b2021a, and for DS Leo 69 in 2021b2022a.

Case	n_{lines}	RMS [m s^{-1}]	RV_p [m s^{-1}]	K [m s^{-1}]	χ^2_ν	RMS_{res} [m s^{-1}]
EV Lac						
Atomic mask - 2020b2021a T	831	387	30	225	4132	314
Example run 10th percentile	181	129	18	108	203	69
Example run 5th percentile	26	158	29	114	499	109
Example run 1st percentile	7	134	35	63	587	117
Atomic mask - 2020b2021a	1300	751	33	213	21726	720
Example run 10th percentile	71	165	19	118	549	114
Example run 5th percentile	21	146	23	117	311	86
Example run 1st percentile	5	170	43	80	942	150
Molecular mask - 2020b2021a	3888	72	2	32	175	64
Example run 10th percentile	1184	26	3	22	7	12
Example run 5th percentile	990	24	3	20	8	14
Example run 1st percentile	244	29	5	20	19	21
DS Leo						
Atomic mask - 2021b2022a T	831	43	6	15	74	42
Example run 10th percentile	350	22	7	9	19	21
Example run 5th percentile	282	21	6	7	18	20
Example run 1st percentile	134	24	8	3	25	24
Atomic mask - 2021b2022a	1300	60	5	34	129	55
Example run 10th percentile	482	24	6	15	21	22
Example run 5th percentile	75	25	7	15	22	23
Example run 1st percentile	19	33	11	6	45	23
Molecular mask - 2021b2022a	3888	61	2	16	154	60
Example run 10th percentile	244	15	< 1	6	9	14
Example run 5th percentile	672	10	2	3	4	10
Example run 1st percentile	669	14	3	2	8	14

Figure 2.30: Distributions of the line parameters for four examined masks: the full atomic mask including telluric intervals a priori (top row), corresponding 10th percentile sub-mask (second row), the full molecular mask including telluric intervals a priori (third row), and corresponding 5th percentile sub-mask (bottom row). In the atomic case, the parameters shown are (from left to right) depth, wavelength and Landé factor. The statistics (mean, median and standard deviation) of the wavelength distributions (in nm) is ($\mu=1637.9$, $\tilde{\mu}=1639.9$, $\sigma=395.2$) and ($\mu=1579.9$, $\tilde{\mu}=1554.8$, $\sigma=367.4$). The g_{eff} distribution statistics is ($\mu=1.23$, $\tilde{\mu}=1.22$, $\sigma=0.38$) and ($\mu=1.22$, $\tilde{\mu}=1.21$, $\sigma=0.30$), and the depth statistics is ($\mu=0.13$, $\tilde{\mu}=0.08$, $\sigma=0.13$) and ($\mu=0.20$, $\tilde{\mu}=0.13$, $\sigma=0.19$). In the molecular case, the parameters shown are (from left to right) wavelength, molecular number and depth. The molecular number is given by $Z = 500 + \sum Z_i$, where Z_i is the atomic number of the i -th element constituting the molecule. The statistics (mean, median and standard deviation) of the wavelength distributions (in nm) is ($\mu=1980.7$, $\tilde{\mu}=1962.0$, $\sigma=476.7$) and ($\mu=1914.3$, $\tilde{\mu}=1777.8$, $\sigma=437.9$). The atomic number statistics features the four molecules (in descending order of counts): CO, OH, MgH, and CN for both masks. The depth statistics is ($\mu=0.13$, $\tilde{\mu}=0.04$, $\sigma=0.14$) and ($\mu=0.17$, $\tilde{\mu}=0.06$, $\sigma=0.18$).

that the corresponding signal is reduced with the sub-masks. Correspondingly, both a periodogram on the filtered data sets and the BIS SPAN vs RV plot demonstrate that the activity signal is decreased. In addition, the algorithm is capable of filtering out lines within telluric bands (that may not have been cleaned out correctly in the reduction pipeline).

There is no specific property of the line (depth, wavelength, magnetic sensitivity, excitation potential) that allows us to single out the physics behind which a combination of lines is more suitable for precise RV measurements. To analyse this further, I combine the selection of spectral lines with brightness imaging, as described in Chapter 3.

The training of the best sub-mask is optimised for data sets that densely cover the rotation of a star, but the improvement in RV dispersion is portable over different data sets collected at distinct epochs. Moreover, the algorithm can be applied with similar benefit in RV dispersion to stars of different activity levels. It is also possible to search for activity-sensitive lines, that would enhance the rotational modulation of the RV measurements and could help constrain the stellar rotation period more efficiently.

Although the optical spectropolarimetric data sets I analysed were not optimised (and even meant) for planet searches, the randomised algorithm is capable of producing sub-masks that preserve a synthetic planetary signal, within uncertainties. Where very active stars are concerned, the reduction of RV dispersion is more than 50%, and it allows the planet signature to emerge in the periodograms, compared to the full mask. For moderately active stars instead, the benefit of the algorithm is automatically limited, i.e. the reduction in RV RMS is smaller, but the planet signal is nevertheless recovered and not suppressed.

Finally, it is also possible to use B_l as a selection basis for the randomised algorithm as well, making full use of the spectropolarimetric data. The idea is analogous to RV, i.e. we look for sub-masks that would reduce/increase the rotational modulation of the B_l phase-curve to. In the former case we would aim at finding lines that may be less sensitive to the magnetic field, while in the latter case we would obtain lines that would make B_l an even better tool to estimate stellar rotation periods. Initial tests in this direction are promising, but additional work is required.

Near-infrared extension

The preliminary application of both parametric and randomised line selections to mitigate stellar activity RV jitter yield promising results. Compared to the optical, the sub-masks obtained with the parametric approach produce RV time series with a moderate (20-30%) reduction of the dispersion. The largest benefit is obtained by choosing molecular lines, and in particular CO lines in the 2200 nm band, because the resulting RV dispersion is decreased by a factor of 2.7 compared to using all molecules or by 15 relative to the atomic lines.

The parametric approach confirms that the longitudinal magnetic field is robust against different line selection, since the dispersion is compatible across selections and the rotational modulation is always recovered. Moreover, no systematic shift is found.

The randomised algorithm is successful when searching for stable lines that decrease RV dispersion, starting both from atomic and molecular lines, and regardless of excluding telluric windows a priori. Once again, the algorithm works for stars of different activity levels, and in some cases it produces sub-masks whose associated RV RMS is lower than that obtained from CO lines only.

Overall, lower RV scatter is correlated with selecting deep, magnetically insensitive and bluer lines, owing to a weaker Zeeman effect. This can be argued from the conclusions of both approaches, even though the distribution of line properties of the sub-masks does not pinpoint any peculiar feature. For this reason, additional tests aimed at better understanding the physics behind certain line selections are needed.

Additional tests of the randomised technique

While several tests of the randomised approach have been carried out already, validating the technique, there are a handful of additional checks to conduct.

For instance, the technique should be tested on spectra taken from high-resolution spectrographs. It was indeed designed using spectropolarimetric data, but the algorithm can be straightforwardly adapted to different instruments. In a similar manner, tests should be carried out on CCF line profiles, instead of LSD profiles, or using an empirical line list, instead of a synthetic one. Clearly, these checks aim at extending the portability and flexibility of the technique, rather than validating it further.

Finally, the products of the randomised algorithm should be studied/compared relative to line-by-line (LBL) RV measurements recently made accessible to M dwarfs as well (Artigau et al. 2022). On one side, LBL estimates can achieve RV precision at m s^{-1} level for very active stars (Carmona et al. 2023, in press), but when fast rotators (time scales lower than a day) are considered, the induced rotational broadening and consequent complexity in identifying individual lines may be a limitation for LBL techniques. The comparison with theoretical masks we performed allows one to investigate in detail which lines are “stable” and to obtain physical insight on the origin of the stellar noise.

Chapter 3

Line selections and Doppler Imaging

How does the brightness map of a star look like when different LSD line selections are adopted?
This Chapter presents the combination of brightness reconstruction via Doppler Imaging with the line selection technique developed in the context of my Ph.D. project. The idea is to find a combination of spectral lines for which we may have less temporally-modulated distortions and therefore brightness maps cleaned from active regions. After briefly summarising the physics behind the formation of lines composing stellar spectra and the principles of brightness imaging, I will describe preliminary attempts aimed at finding a correlation between the lines used in LSD and the brightness inhomogeneities on the stellar surface. The analysis is currently in progress and is benchmarked on V374 Peg, a notoriously active, fully-convective M dwarf for which I obtained SPIRou observations in summer 2021.

3.1 Spectral lines as probes of the stellar atmosphere

Absorption lines in spectra represent a decrease in continuum intensity, and correspond to a deficiency of photons in a narrow frequency range relative to the nearby frequencies. In stars, photons reach the outermost atmospheric layers and get absorbed by atoms and molecules, giving origin to absorption lines. In this regard, and depending on which height of the stellar atmosphere they are formed, atomic and molecular absorption lines can be used as probes of the conditions of the stellar photosphere. Given the diverse sensitivity to magnetic field and temperature (hence to different surface inhomogeneities), some lines could then be representative of “more quiet” regions than others, and thus allow more precise RV measurements.

For instance, spots are originated by intense magnetic fields that quench convective motions and inhibit the energy transport (Schrijver & Zwaan 2000; Strassmeier 2009). Knowing that these inhomogeneities are a few hundreds of K colder than the quiet photosphere (Berdyugina 2005), specific atomic and molecular lines may originate within them more favourably. Such lines could be more prone to variability and their removal from LSD or CCF line lists could improve the precision of RV measurements. We tackle this idea by selecting lines according to their main properties as in Chapter 2 and reconstructing brightness maps from the associated time series of Stokes I profiles, to check the influence of the sub-masks on surface inhomogeneities and line distortions. This is performed by means of Doppler Imaging, as outlined in Sec. 3.2.

From high-resolution spectral observations of the Sun, we already know that deep lines are less sensitive to convective motions (Dravins 1982; Reiners et al. 2016), hence are preferable for RV estimates. This reasonably reflects the fact that deeper lines are formed in the outer layers of the photosphere, where convective velocities are weaker (Keil & Yackovitch 1981; Gray 2005). Moreover, the magnetic field is height-dependent, increasing towards deeper internal layers (Zayer et al. 1989; Solanki 1993). This could be studied using lines with increasing excitation potential, since it correlates with larger depth of formation (Grossmann-Doerth 1994; Gurtovenko & Sheminova 2015).

Following the first measurement of magnetic fields within starspots for M dwarfs (Berdyugina et al.

Figure 3.1: Illustration of the height-dependence of the stellar magnetic field for M dwarfs, with the corresponding atomic and molecular species probing certain atmospheric depths. Spots reach higher layers than network (i.e., small-scales magnetic fields) and cover most of the upper atmosphere. The network dominates the lower atmosphere instead. Distinct chemical species allows us to probe different strengths and structures of the magnetic field. Taken from [Afram & Berdyugina \(2019\)](#).

2006), [Afram & Berdyugina \(2019\)](#) estimated magnetic fields at distinct atmospheric depths adopting certain chemical species, as illustrated in Fig. 3.1. They established that TiO and FeH form in the upper and lower atmosphere, respectively, whereas atomic lines at intermediate heights. Furthermore, the lower atmosphere of early-M dwarfs was reported to feature simpler magnetic spots than later M dwarfs, while the upper atmosphere has more complex structures regardless of the spectral type. On the contrary, [Shulyak et al. \(2017, 2019\)](#) found consistent values of magnetic for atoms and molecules, implying that further investigations are needed.

3.2 Principles of Doppler Imaging

Observations of the Sun do not reveal an immaculate disk, but rather a seething plethora of surface inhomogeneities, as mentioned in Sec. 1.3. When observations of other stars are performed, we actually collect *integrated* light over the stellar disk. Therefore, we cannot draw conclusions with the same level of detail, since we inexorably lack the necessary spatial resolution. For instance, many starspots close together would appear as an individual big spot, with more or less granularity depending on the resolution.

With Doppler Imaging, we reconstruct a brightness map of a star exploiting temporally-modulated distortions that surface inhomogeneities induce on the shape of spectral lines ([Deutsch 1957](#); [Vogt & Penrod 1983](#); [Rice et al. 1989](#)). Indeed, as a consequence of disk integration, all points on the stellar surface with the same radial velocity contribute to the same point of a spectral line profile whose broadening is dominated by rotation, making the spectrum equivalent to a 1D image of the stellar surface. The location of the distortion on the line profile thus correlates with the location of the inhomogeneity on the stellar disk, for fast rotators.

With a single spectrum, one can determine the longitude of such inhomogeneity, whereas the latitude can only be inferred from a time series of spectra covering the stellar rotation. The idea is to track the temporal evolution of the line distortion, and correspondingly the inhomogeneity position from different angles. The extent of the blue-to-red excursion in velocity space informs us of the latitude of the spot: an equatorial spot has maximal excursion, while a polar one has a minimal one (the bump

Figure 3.2: Principle of brightness mapping. Stellar rotation allows us to track the temporally-modulated mean line profile distortions associated with surface inhomogeneities. The result is a brightness image of the stellar surface. Adapted from an animation available at http://www.ast.obs-mip.fr/article.php?id_article=457.

remains around profile centre). The magnitude of the distortion depends on the properties of the spot such as temperature contrast with the quiet photosphere and size. The result is a 2D image of the stellar surface, as illustrated in Fig. 3.2. During my thesis, I used the ZDIPY code developed by Folsom et al. (2018) to perform Doppler Imaging and Zeeman-Doppler Imaging (see Sec. 4.2.2), which is largely a python translation of the C code used in Donati et al. (2006); Morin et al. (2008a). ZDIPY was indeed benchmarked on the C version of ZDI.

3.2.1 Applicability

The longitudinal resolution of the brightness maps scales with the equatorial rotational velocity $v_{\text{eq}} \sin(i)$ (e.g., Hussain et al. 2009). Formally, the number of resolution elements at equator is

$$n_{\text{resel,eq}} = 2\pi \frac{v_{\text{eq}} \sin(i)}{W}, \quad (3.1)$$

with W the line width in the absence of rotation (typically 10 km s^{-1} for cool stars).

Therefore, Doppler Imaging can be adequately applied only to fast rotators, where rotational broadening dominates the shape of the line profile. As a rule of thumb, stars with $v_{\text{eq}} \sin(i) \geq 15 - 20 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ ensure that the line profiles are sufficiently broadened. There is also a rotational upper limit, however, because the lines of ultra-fast rotators would tend to blend, distorting further the mean line profile from which the brightness map is recovered (Unruh & Collier Cameron 1995). Moreover, broader lines imply shallower lines and lower effective S/N as well, making the distinction between a genuine spot-induced bump from noise more subtle. Recent results show applications of differential Doppler Imaging to lower $v_{\text{eq}} \sin(i)$ values like Hébrard et al. (2016) and Klein et al. (2021).

In terms of inclination, stars seen pole-on ($i = 0^\circ$) do not produce radial velocity variability and those observed equator-on ($i = 90^\circ$) are subject to a degeneracy between the north and south hemisphere (we cannot distinguish where the spot is located), thus Doppler Imaging cannot be used (Vogt et al. 1987). The quality of the final map depends also on the rotational phase coverage, signal-to-noise ratio of the mean line profile, and the instrumental resolution, since it would be easier to catch smaller bumps travelling across the line profile. At the same time, the observations should span less than the intrinsic evolution and emergence timescales of the spots, or we would lose coherency of the signal.

3.3 SPIROu observations of V374 Peg

An excellent laboratory to study activity is V374 Peg (GJ 4247), a bright and active M4 dwarf. The mass is $0.28 M_{\odot}$ (Delfosse et al. 2000), corresponding to a fully-convective interior (Chabrier & Baraffe 1997). The star is at a distance of 9.1 pc (Gaia Collaboration 2020) and has an H band magnitude of 7.04 (Cutri et al. 2003). Its rotation period is 0.445 d and equatorial rotation velocity is 36.5 km s^{-1} (Morin et al. 2008a), making it an optimal target for Doppler Imaging studies. Indeed, Morin et al. (2008a) reconstructed the surface brightness for three epochs and found a handful of low-contrast spots covering 2% of the surface mostly between 0 and 50° latitude, and varying on a time scale of 1 yr. Although high-latitude spots are expected for fast rotators (Cang et al. 2020) because the Coriolis force would overcome the buoyancy force, making magnetic flux tubes ascend parallel to the rotation axis (Schuessler & Solanki 1992; Granzer et al. 2000), no polar spot was reconstructed for V374 Peg (Morin et al. 2008a). Such polar spots are actually observed on partly convective stars (e.g. AB Dor Hussain et al. 2007), but the aforementioned model may not apply to fully convective stars

V374 Peg is highly active, with a $\log(L_X/L_{\text{bol}})$ of -3.15 (Wright et al. 2011; Magaudda et al. 2020), similar to EV Lac's. The high activity and fast rotation translate in large RV jitter, typically on the order of 500 m s^{-1} . For this reason, the star was excluded from the target list of the SPIROu Legacy Survey (SLS, see Sec. 4.3.1). During my Ph.D. project, I wrote a proposal to monitor V374 Peg with SPIROu, and successfully obtained 55 observations (7.2 hours exposure time) in semester 2021B. This way, the analyses presented here complement the stellar activity analyses of the SLS.

The data reduction has been carried out with APERO v0.7.273 (Cook et al. 2022), and the list of observations is reported in Table C.10. Stokes I profiles were computed with LSD using an atomic, molecular and atomic+molecular near-infrared mask generated via VALD (Ryabchikova et al. 2015; Gustafsson et al. 2008), similarly to Sec. 2.5. For all masks, we restricted the line selection to those that are deeper than 3% the continuum level, resulting in 831 (atomic), 2037 (molecular), and 3530 (atomic+molecular) lines, respectively. The number of lines of the atomic mask accounts for the removal of spectral intervals contaminated by deep telluric bands, similarly to Sec. 2.5. The associated time series of Stokes I profiles are shown in Fig. 3.3, where we immediately notice a difference in depth and width: the Stokes I profile of atomic, molecular and atomic+molecular lines span between $\pm 70 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, $\pm 45 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, and $\pm 60 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ from line center, respectively.

3.4 Brightness maps

We applied Doppler Imaging to the time series of Stokes I profiles adopting an inclination of 60° , $P_{\text{rot}} = 0.4455 \text{ d}$ and solid body rotation, similarly to the Zeeman-Doppler Imaging analysis described in Sec. 3.3, and consistently with Morin et al. (2008a). For each of the three masks, we optimised the following line model parameters: depth, Doppler width, Lorentz width, radial velocity of the centroid and equatorial projected rotational velocity ($v_{\text{eq}} \sin(i)$). The optimisation was carried out by generating a synthetic Stokes I profile and comparing it to the median of the observations for a grid of parameter values. The optimised parameters then correspond to those providing the minimum χ_r^2 . Finally, the algorithm was allowed to model both dark and bright surface inhomogeneities (see Appendix A for more details) because, although M dwarfs are expected to be spot-dominated (Reinhold et al. 2019), we allow more flexibility of our reconstructions. The results of the brightness reconstructions for the three line lists are shown in Fig. 3.4 and Fig. 3.5.

When using the atomic mask, the Stokes I data set can be fitted to a S/N level of 3230. The dynamic spectrum shown in Fig. 3.4 exhibits the signatures of mid latitude spots travelling over the line profiles from the blue to the red wing and crossing the line of sight around phases 0.15, 0.35, and 0.75, as well as bright features at phases 0.20, 0.45, and 0.65. The obliquity of these signatures is reasonably the same, indicating that the profile distortions travel across the same amount of profile or, in other words, the brightness inhomogeneities are located at similar latitudes. The signatures are well-reproduced in the model, but the residuals feature stationary bumps in the form of vertical positive bands (i.e. present at

Figure 3.3: Stokes I profiles obtained with different line selections for the 2021b SPIRou data of V374 Peg. Each panels shows a different line selection: atomic (top), molecular (middle) and atomic+molecular (bottom). The time series of Stokes I profiles is presented in blue, and the median profile in red.

all rotational phases), due to the presence of systematic profile distortions that are not accounted for by the inversion algorithm. When looking at the brightness map in Fig. 3.5, we confirm the location of the

surface inhomogeneities from the dynamic spectrum. The dark and bright patches have approximately 20% smaller and larger intensity than the quiet photosphere, and have a mean coverage of 7% of the surface.

When using a molecular mask, the Stokes I data set is fitted to a S/N level of 3150, and the dynamic spectrum does not reveal any specific pattern that can be visually associated to brightness inhomogeneities. The algorithm seems to find numerous small surface features compared to the atomic case as shown in the model panel, which would be expected to first order considering that molecules probe cooler temperatures (an investigation of using the temperature dependence of spectral lines as a criterion to build masks is in progress). However, these are most likely artefacts of fitting noise. In part, this could be due to the smaller depth of the profiles compared to atomic lines, therefore being more sensitive to noise. The residual panel still exhibit prominent vertical bands due to systematic distortions unaccounted in the brightness model. The brightness map reported in Fig. 3.5 is characterised by a dark polar area (about 30% darker than the quiet photosphere) with a bright ring at mid latitudes (about 25% brighter than the quiet photosphere). Dark and bright features overall cover 5% of the surface. These features are usually characterised by errors in the input parameters like limb darkening, $v_{\text{eq}} \sin(i)$, and line width. In fact, if the initial Stokes I model is misrepresented, the maximum entropy algorithm would tend to push the flanks of the line profile downward, resulting in ring-like structures (Vogt et al. 1987; Unruh & Collier Cameron 1995; Donati & Brown 1997); this needs to be investigated further. At the same time, the presence of stationary (i.e. non-rotationally-modulated) distortions can contribute to the ring-like structure, which is not well-constrained and reliable.

When using the atomic+molecular mask, the Stokes I data set is fitted to a S/N of 3340, and the dynamic spectrum reveals dark and bright inhomogeneities at similar location as those shown in the atomic mask case. Once again, the residuals show vertical bands in the far wings symbolising unaccounted systematics (see Fig. 3.4). The brightness map in Fig. 3.5 is a mixture of the previous cases, with the molecular features being more predominant, i.e. a dark polar feature with a ring-like structure at mid latitudes and covering 3% of the surface. Using a combination of atomic and molecular lines is probably unreliable, because we are breaking the self-similarity assumption at the core of Least-Squares Deconvolution (see Sec. 2.2). In fact, as shown already in Fig. 3.3, the line shape associated to atomic and molecular species differ both in width. The analysis of the atomic+molecular mask was kept therefore for completeness.

Compared to the brightness reconstructions of Morin et al. (2008a), the atomic mask yield reasonably consistent results, but we also notice we notice a dark polar feature which was not reported by Morin et al. (2008a) in all the reconstructed maps. For V374 Peg, a polar feature was suggested by Vida et al. (2016), because they reported the presence of flares at all rotational phases. However, this could be equivalently explained by having three active regions displaced at equally separated longitudes, making one of them would always be visible. To check whether the polar spot in our maps stems from unaccounted stationary distortions in our models, we used the method developed to image the surface of slow rotators by Hébrard et al. (2016). The idea is to compute the residuals between the observations and the median observation, and then add the residuals to the optimised line models prior to brightness reconstruction. This way our data will in principle be left only with rotationally modulated distortions. An axisymmetric feature like a polar dark spot would be most likely removed, but this will not impact the ultimate goal of our study, i.e. filtering radial velocity jitter. Indeed, axisymmetric distortions do not contribute to the radial velocity modulation. We performed such correction for the three line masks and the corresponding dynamic spectra and brightness maps are presented in Fig. 3.6 and Fig. 3.7.

For all cases, we observe that the vertical stationary bands in the residuals disappeared, while both the observations and models are unaltered. In parallel, we observe the disappearance of the polar spot from the brightness maps, with a consequent decrease in surface coverage of at most 1% over all cases. For the molecules in particular, we note that the bright ring-like structure vanishes, leaving a highly structured map that is most likely due to fitting noise. This is confirmed when looking at the dynamic spectrum, as the residuals are basically identical to the observations. For the atomic+molecular mask, both the dynamic spectrum and the brightness map are a mixture of the previous cases but the atomic

Figure 3.4: Dynamic spectra built with different line selections for the 2011b SPIRou data of V374 Peg. Each panels row shows the observed Stokes I profiles (left), models (middle) and residuals (right). The observations and the models are median subtracted, hence positive and negative values of the color bar indicate dark and bright features, respectively. The median subtraction removes the stationary bumps as well, which are therefore more evident in the residuals panel. The vertical solid line locates the radial velocity of the star, whereas the two dashed lines are located at $\pm v_{\text{eq}} \sin(i)$. Note that the velocity axis scale for the molecular and atomic+molecular is narrower than the atomic one.

Figure 3.5: Reconstructed brightness maps obtained with different line selections for the 2021b SPIRou data of V374 Peg. The color bar indicates the brightness relative to the quiet photosphere (equal to 1.0).

features seem predominant, contrarily to when the stationary bumps were not corrected for.

To be more quantitative, and understand better what the algorithm is attempting to fit, in Table 3.1 we compare the χ_r^2 between observations and models at the initial iteration of Doppler Imaging (corresponding to a quiet photosphere) and at convergence. We also compute the dispersion of the residuals between the observed Stokes I profiles and the spotted models both inside and outside the velocity range enclosing the line profile, since these residuals represent the signal we are trying to model. The dispersion is scaled by the depth of the profiles for a certain mask, in order to account for effective S/N. We see the smallest difference in χ_r^2 occurs when using molecular lines, being 0.021 and 0.007 for the uncorrected and median-corrected profiles. In comparison, for the atomic and the atomic+molecular masks, the improvement is of 0.027 and 0.041 in the uncorrected case and 0.025 and 0.035 for the corrected case. When looking at the dispersion of the residuals, the molecular case has again the smallest difference within and outside the line, whereas it is moderately larger for the atomic and atomic+molecular mask, suggesting that we may be reconstructing genuine surface inhomogeneities.

Considering these figures, we can conservatively conclude that the Doppler Imaging code mostly fits noise for the molecular profile. For the atomic profile, while it is clear that the code fits genuine distortions, the physical interpretation of the maps may not be straightforward. While we would tend to correlate the atomic profile distortions to the brightness inhomogeneities we see on the map, such interpretation is complicated by Zeeman splitting contribution (see Donati et al., 2023 in press). For strong fields, the validity of weak-field approximation would break, and we would necessarily have to use Unno-Rachkovsky solutions to polarised radiative transfer as a more general model of Stokes I (see Appendix A). The broad wings seen in the atomic LSD line profiles are symbolic of Zeeman broadening, and thus represent another hint to the plausible magnetic nature of the distortions, rather than due to brightness inhomogeneities. The molecular LSD profiles have instead sharper edges, which is typical of a rotationally-dominated profile, and the Doppler Imaging algorithm does not detect clear distortion modulation to fit (even though the larger noise may be responsible of such aspect).

3.5 Radial velocity filtering

Having the brightness maps obtained with different masks at hand, the associated model stokes I profiles can be used to synthesise RV curves and tentatively filter out the activity jitter (Hébrard et al. 2016). In Fig. 3.8, we show the RV curves of the observations, models and residuals for the different line selections, as well as the associated Generalised Lomb-Scargle periodogram to investigate the efficiency of the filtering. These plots in particular refer to the case of Stokes I profiles that are not corrected using the median profile, but the situation is unaltered for median-corrected profiles as reported in Table 3.2

For atomic lines, we observe a clear rotational modulation of the RV curve, with two dips at rotational phase 0.1 and 0.8, and a less clear one at 0.5, as well as three peaks at 0.0, 0.4 and 0.6. Our

Figure 3.6: Dynamic spectra built with different line selections for the 2021b SPIRou data of V374 Peg, and when stationary distortions are corrected. We notice that the residuals are cleaned from the vertical bands in the far wings compared to Fig. 3.4. The format is the same as Fig. 3.4.

Figure 3.7: Reconstructed brightness maps obtained with different line selections for the 2021b SPIRou data of V374 Peg, when stationary bumps are removed. We note that the polar feature disappears compared to Fig. 3.5. The format is the same as Fig. 3.5.

Table 3.1: Statistical properties of the Doppler Imaging reconstructions. The columns are: (1) the line list adopted, (2,3) initial and final χ_r^2 of the brightness reconstructions for the original line profiles (4,5) initial and final χ_r^2 of the brightness reconstructions for the median-corrected profiles, (6) depth of the profiles relative to the continuum, (7,8) dispersion of the residuals outside and inside the velocity range encompassing the line absorption profile.

Mask	Uncorrected		Corrected		depth	σ_{in}	σ_{out}
	$\chi_{r,\text{initial}}^2$	$\chi_{r,\text{final}}^2$	$\chi_{r,\text{initial}}^2$	$\chi_{r,\text{final}}^2$			
Atomic	0.122	0.095	0.084	0.059	0.016	$5.4 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$3.8 \cdot 10^{-6}$
Molecular	0.128	0.107	0.047	0.040	0.013	$3.5 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$3.2 \cdot 10^{-6}$
Atomic + Molecular	0.231	0.190	0.110	0.075	0.017	$4.5 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$3.1 \cdot 10^{-6}$

model reproduces the RV variations with a reasonable match, which is also confirmed by the residuals being rather consistent with white noise, as demonstrated by the periodogram. In particular, the dispersion decreases of a factor of two from observations to residuals, as reported in Table 3.2. This is seen in the Lomb-Scargle periodogram as well, since the peak at the expected stellar rotation period of $P_{\text{rot}}=0.4455$ d is reproduced in the model, but vanishes in the residuals along with the harmonic peaks below P_{rot} . The periodogram of the residuals do not exhibit any particular periodicity, as the remaining peaks are mirrored in the periodogram power of the window function.

For molecular lines, the observed RV time series manifests a large scatter of 3 km s^{-1} , without an evident rotational modulation. Therefore, while the modelled RV variations resemble generally those obtained for the atomic lines, we cannot use them reliably. Indeed, not only the periodogram of the model exhibits a stronger peak at the stellar rotation period, meaning that we are injecting rotational modulation, but the residuals do not see any substantial improvement in dispersion. The atomic+molecular case is in-between the previous two, i.e. the observed RV curve clearly exhibits rotational modulation, which however enhanced in the model. For this reason, the residuals are still rotationally modulated, which is confirmed by the presence of a peak at the stellar rotation period.

3.6 Summary and next steps

This preliminary analysis aimed at linking RV curves and Doppler Imaging maps computed with different line lists, in an attempt to shed more light on the radial velocity content of specific spectral lines. Indeed, activity-filtering techniques for radial velocity have been progressively developed to work on the spectrum, where there is a rich content of RV information, and a better potential to disentangle mag-

Figure 3.8: Radial velocity filtering using reconstructed Doppler Imaging maps. First row: RV curves obtained for an atomic (left), molecular (middle) and atomic+molecular (right) mask. In each panel, the RV curve built from observations, models and residuals is shown. Second row: Generalised Lomb-Scargle periodogram of the observed RV curve for the three masks. Third row: same as second row but for the model RV. Fourth row: same as second row but for the residuals. In each periodogram panel, the expected stellar rotation period of 0.4455 d is illustrated as a vertical solid green line and its harmonics as dashed vertical lines, whereas FAP thresholds of 0.1% and 0.01% are indicated as horizontal lines.

netic activity from genuine planetary signals. Here, the aim is to understand how the stellar surface would appear, if we apply tomographic inversion with selected line masks.

We used three distinct masks, containing only atomic, only molecular and atomic+molecular lines. After computing the time series of Stokes I spectra, we applied Doppler Imaging to reconstruct a brightness map of V374 Peg, as well as to model the associated RV curves. We found that for the atomic lines, the observed RV modulation is well-reproduced by the Doppler Imaging model, and the residuals are indeed flat without featuring any specific periodicity. The RV dispersion is about twice as large as for

Table 3.2: Dispersion properties of the RV curves. The columns are: (1) line mask adopted, (2,3,4) dispersion of the observed, model, and residuals RV for the original line profiles, (5,6,7), dispersion of the observed, model, and residuals RV for the median-corrected Stokes I profiles.

Mask	Uncorrected			Corrected		
	σ_{Observed} [km s ⁻¹]	σ_{Model} [km s ⁻¹]	$\sigma_{\text{Residuals}}$ [km s ⁻¹]	σ_{Observed} [km s ⁻¹]	σ_{Model} [km s ⁻¹]	$\sigma_{\text{Residuals}}$ [km s ⁻¹]
Atomic	0.7	0.6	0.3	0.7	0.5	0.3
Molecular	3.2	0.8	3.0	3.2	0.7	3.0
Atomic + Molecular	1.2	0.8	0.7	1.2	0.8	0.7

the optical data sets (see (Morin 2010)), indeed suggesting that the Stokes I variability is dominated by Zeeman broadening rather than brightness effects (as for EV Lac in Chapter 2). For molecules we do not observe a modulation of the RV curve due to the large dispersion, therefore the modelled variations are likely spurious. For the atomic+molecular mask, we observe rotational modulation, which is boosted in the model curve, resulting in modulated residuals as well. This case is likely unreliable because combining atomic and molecular lines, with clearly distinct shapes, is against the line self-similarity requirement for the validity of LSD.

Naturally, these results are not definitive. There are additional tests to perform and cases to examine. For instance, we can apply a similar analysis to Stokes I profiles obtained with the parametric masks presented in Chapter 2 and with CO lines only, as well as with masks built with our randomised algorithm. Furthermore, we can exploit the temperature dependence of spectral lines to select those whose depth increases or decreases or remains unchanged with increasing temperature. Finally, we plan to apply the method developed by Petit et al. (2015) on both the SPIRou near-infrared and on the optical archival data sets to search for planetary signals.

Chapter 4

Overview on magnetic fields

This Chapter is dedicated to the introduction of spectropolarimetry and the techniques with which to measure stellar magnetic fields. They are at the base of stellar activity phenomena occurring on stars, hence their understanding is fundamental to progress in the exoplanet field as well. I briefly recall the fundamental effects that a magnetic field induce on starlight and how to exploit them in order to estimate the modulus and the orientation of the magnetic field vector. I will touch upon the available instrumentation and describe the SPIRou spectropolarimeter and the associated Legacy Survey which has been pivotal for my doctoral project. Finally, I will briefly summarise the current status of the dynamo theory and its observational constraints, to better contextualise my results. Extensive information on the topics referred here can be found in [Landi Degl’Innocenti \(1992\)](#), [del Toro Iniesta \(2003\)](#), [Donati & Landstreet \(2009\)](#), [Reiners \(2012\)](#), [Brun & Browning \(2017\)](#), and [Rincon \(2019\)](#).

4.1 Spectropolarimetry

Magnetic fields play a crucial role in stellar physics because they impact the formation and evolution of stars, as well as their internal structure and activity. Studying their properties, like strength and geometry, enables us to set constraints on dynamo theories explaining the origin of the field and its preservation over the lifetime of the star. Furthermore, a solid knowledge on the magnetic field underlying the existence of surface features is necessary to comprehend the phenomena inducing RV variability (see [Sec. 1.3](#)). To this end, we perform observations with a specific technique called spectropolarimetry, i.e. we record the irradiance *and* electromagnetic vector properties of starlight as a function of wavelength ([del Toro Iniesta 2003](#)).

4.1.1 Zeeman effect

The principles on which direct stellar magnetic fields measurements are based rely mainly on the Zeeman effect ([Zeeman 1897](#)). Indeed, when atoms and molecules are subject to external magnetic fields, their quantum energy levels split in a certain number of sub-levels. The same follows automatically for the spectral lines, in absorption or emission, associated to electron transitions between the energy levels. From an energy state characterised by a total angular momentum quantum number J , the number of sub-levels is $(2J+1)$, with corresponding magnetic quantum numbers $M = -J, -J+1, \dots, J-1, J$ and energy difference proportional to the magnetic field strength.

Following the selection rule $\Delta M = -1, 0, 1$ between two states, there are three families of transitions named π ($\Delta M = 0$), σ_r ($\Delta M = -1$), and σ_b ($\Delta M = 1$), respectively. The b and r subscripts of the σ components refer to the blueshifted and redshifted photons relative to the unshifted π transition. Considering a normal Zeeman triplet¹ ([Fig. 4.1](#)) the amount of splitting between the π and $\sigma_{b,r}$

¹When the spacing of the upper energy levels is the same as the lower ones. Otherwise, more line components are present, which is known as “anomalous Zeeman effect” ([Landstreet 2009a](#)). The nomenclature is misleading, as the normal Zeeman effect is a particular case of the anomalous one, but they were kept for historical reasons.

Figure 4.1: Sketch depicting the Zeeman effect and the polarisation properties of the split lines. In the absence of a magnetic field there is no splitting, whereas the energy levels, and consequently the spectral lines, split when an external magnetic field is applied. Depending on the orientation of the line of sight with respect to the magnetic field, it is possible to observe circular or linear polarised components. Therefore, collecting the observations at different orientations allow us to determine the magnetic field vector.

components (in nm) is given by

$$\Delta\lambda_{b,r} = \Delta\lambda_B = 4.67 \cdot 10^{-12} \lambda_0^2 g_{\text{eff}} B, \quad (4.1)$$

with B the modulus of the magnetic field [G], λ_0 the central wavelength in the absence of the field [nm] and g_{eff} the Landé factor. The proportionality factor encapsulates fundamental constants such as speed of light, electron mass and electron charge. The Landé factor is a dimensionless number spanning between 0 and 3 and representing the sensitivity to the magnetic field of a particular line. In general, the π and $\sigma_{b,r}$ components are linearly and elliptically polarised, respectively. Two particular cases are shown in Fig.4.1: (i) if the line of sight is perpendicular to the magnetic field, the π component is linearly polarised parallel to the field and the $\sigma_{b,r}$ components perpendicular to the field, (ii) if the line of sight is parallel to the magnetic field, the π component is invisible and the $\sigma_{b,r}$ components are circularly polarised with opposite directions.

There are other quantum mechanical effects resulting in energy changes of atomic levels that reflect in changes of line profiles and polarisation properties (Landstreet 2009a). Depending on the magnetic field strength, there are indeed different regimes: for atomic lines, between 50 and 100 kG we have the Paschen-Back regime (weakly magnetised degenerate stars), whereas above 100 kG (magnetised white dwarfs) we have the quadratic Zeeman effect. Here, we look at non-degenerate stars on the main sequence with fields up to 10 kG, hence these effects are not observable.

4.1.2 Polarised radiative transfer

The starlight polarisation state is typically described with the Stokes vector $\bar{I} = (I, Q, U, V)$ (Stokes 1852; Landi Degl'Innocenti & Landolfi 2004). As illustrated in Fig. 4.2, Stokes I quantifies the amount of unpolarised (integrated) light, Stokes Q and U of net linear polarisation in two orthogonal states and net V of circular polarisation. The Stokes vector is used in the theoretical framework of polarised radiative transfer, expressing the generation and propagation of radiation in stellar atmospheres under

Figure 4.2: Representation of the Stokes vector components. Taken from Kochukhov (2021).

the presence of a magnetic field. Formally,

$$\frac{d}{ds} \begin{pmatrix} I \\ Q \\ U \\ V \end{pmatrix} = - \begin{pmatrix} \eta_I & \eta_Q & \eta_U & \eta_V \\ \eta_Q & \eta_I & \rho_V & -\rho_U \\ \eta_U & -\rho_V & \eta_I & \rho_Q \\ \eta_V & \rho_U & -\rho_Q & \eta_I \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} I \\ Q \\ U \\ V \end{pmatrix}, \quad (4.2)$$

with η_i and ρ_i are the absorption and dispersion coefficients, respectively. There are distinct solutions of this equation depending on the assumptions made (see Appendix A for more details). Two noteworthy and commonly used cases are: 1) the weak-field approximation and 2) Milne-Eddington atmosphere with absence of velocity fields and line formation occurring within negligible optical depth (a uniform field is assumed). The weak-field approximation is valid when the Zeeman splitting $\Delta\lambda_B$ is negligible compared to the intrinsic width of the line. This condition does not hold for fields stronger than ~ 1 kG (Donati & Brown 1997), although its proper usage was reported even for the chemically peculiar stars γ Equ with a typical 5.5 kG field (Donati & Collier Cameron 1997) and V352 Peg with a 9 kG field (Fréour et al. 2022).

Under the weak-field approximation, the expressions for Stokes V , Q , and U have a simple analytical form

$$V = -\Delta\lambda_B \cos\theta \frac{dI}{dv}, \quad (4.3)$$

$$Q = -\frac{1}{4} \Delta\lambda_B^2 \sin^2\theta \cos 2\chi \frac{d^2I}{dv^2}, \quad (4.4)$$

$$U = -\frac{1}{4} \Delta\lambda_B^2 \sin^2\theta \sin 2\chi \frac{d^2I}{dv^2}, \quad (4.5)$$

where θ is the angle between the line of sight and the magnetic field vector, and χ is the angle between the magnetic field vector and a reference direction in a plane orthogonal to the line of sight. Under this approximation, Stokes V is a first order effect while Stokes Q and U are a second order effect. The result assuming a Milne-Eddington atmosphere provides a more general description of the Stokes vector with

any magnetic field strength and is known as Unno-Rachkovsky solution (Unno 1956; Rachkovsky 1967; Landi Degl’Innocenti 1992).

In practice, I used the ZDIPY code described in Folsom et al. (2018). The code performs tomographic inversion under weak-field approximation, hence it was suitably applied for moderately active M dwarfs (e.g., Donati et al. 2008; Klein et al. 2021; Martioli et al. 2022). However, near-infrared observations of stars with intense magnetic fields are more susceptible to spectral line distortions, broadening and even splitting due to an enhanced Zeeman effect (see Eq.4.1), which motivates the need of a more general model for the observed Stokes V profiles. Therefore, we implemented the Unno-Rachkovsky’s solutions and incorporated the filling factor formalism by Morin et al. (2008b).

4.2 Measuring the magnetic field

Spectropolarimetric observations aim at recording Stokes I like in classical spectroscopy, which is sensitive to the total, unsigned magnetic field of the star, and Stokes Q , U , V which also contain information on the field orientation. Properties of the magnetic field are then inferred with two complementary approaches (Reiners 2012): modelling the Zeeman splitting in individual unpolarised spectral lines or applying tomographic techniques like Zeeman-Doppler Imaging to recover the field geometry.

4.2.1 Magnetic field modulus and filling factor

Spectra in unpolarised light allow us to retrieve the total, unsigned stellar magnetic field. Assuming that the instrumental resolution is sufficient to distinguish the Zeeman-split components of individual spectral lines, and that the splitting is larger than the intrinsic line width, the idea is to measure the wavelength separation between the components and invert Eq. 4.1. In practice, a spectral line at 650 nm with $g_{\text{eff}} = 2.5$ under the presence of a 1 kG field is subject to a $\Delta\lambda_B = 4.9 \cdot 10^{-3}$ nm, which is smaller compared to the spectral resolution of modern spectrographs with $R = 110\,000$ ($\Delta\lambda = 5.9 \cdot 10^{-3}$ nm). Therefore, observations of the π and σ components are performed successfully only for intense fields on the order of a few kG, i.e. for chemically peculiar stars or spatially-resolved sunspots.

By virtue of Eq. 4.1, we can start to resolve Zeeman components when exploiting near-infrared lines, which is an additional motivation behind the commissioning of several high-resolution spectrographs in this domain (see Table 1.2). Detailed line shape analyses are executed with instruments such as CARMENES and the upcoming NIRPS operating in the Y , J , and H bands, as well as SPIRou, CRRES+, and iSHELL that extend to the K band.

When observing other stars than the Sun, further complications arise by the lack of spatial resolution, since the components of the Stokes vector convey only average information integrated over the stellar visible hemisphere. For Stokes I , this means that we do not observe the Zeeman triplet clearly, but a more complicated and smeared pattern referred to as Zeeman broadening. Such effect generates further ambiguity with the coexistence of other types of line broadening (rotational, instrumental, thermal, pressure) whose combined action prevents the measurement of weak fields, typically below 100 G (Reiners 2012). This applies to the slowest rotators, but as the projected equatorial velocity increases, the limitation in measuring magnetic fields increases correspondingly.

To disentangle Zeeman broadening, a possibility is to measure the width of atomic spectral lines formed under similar conditions, but with distinct magnetic sensitivities (Saar 1988; Reiners 2012). Otherwise, we can use different sets of diatomic molecules depending on spectral type, and especially for those characterised by forests of molecular lines that restrict the number of unblended atomic lines to only a handful (Berdyugina et al. 2003; Afram & Berdyugina 2015). Observations of cool stars (between G and M type) revealed distinct field intensities, generally on the order of 100 and 500 G for Sun-like stars (Basri et al. 1990; Valenti et al. 1995), and ten times larger for active M dwarfs (Linsky 1985; Shulyak et al. 2019). Among these spectral types, M dwarfs have a greater number of observations because they are favourable targets to capture Zeeman broadening: 1) the lines are overall narrower owing to a weaker temperature broadening, 2) their smaller size translates in a lower rotational broadening even at faster rotation rates, 3) the peak starlight emission is in near-infrared, giving access to a

Figure 4.3: Theoretical modelling of Ti lines in the 965-680 nm wavelength range, with different magnetic sensitivities. These lines are particularly useful because of the $g_{\text{eff}} = 0$ line, which is not magnetically broadened and therefore helps disentangling different broadening agents. A non-magnetic model (dashed blue line) and a magnetic multi-component one (red solid line) is overplotted to the observations (black dots). Taken from [Shulyak et al. \(2019\)](#) for the star V388 Cas.

higher S/N for the measurements, 4) even slower rotators (implying weaker rotational broadening) can host detectable and moderately intense fields (see Sec. 4.4.2) and 5) molecular bands emerge in the spectra and allow reliable measurements.

For M dwarfs in particular, [Reiners & Basri \(2006\)](#) used the FeH band at $1\mu\text{m}$ to interpolate the spectrum of the examined star between an inactive and active stellar benchmark with analogous fundamental properties (effective temperature, surface gravity, metallicity). This methodology was necessary considering that theoretical knowledge of magnetic sensitivity for diatomic molecules is incomplete ([Valenti & Johns-Krull 2001](#); [Reiners & Basri 2006](#)). More recently, spectrum synthesis modelling of the Ti I lines at 964.7-978.8 nm was adopted to perform extensive measurements (see Fig. 4.3), as they are excellent diagnostics for both Zeeman broadening and magnetic intensification ([Kochukhov & Lavail 2017](#); [Shulyak et al. 2017, 2019](#)). The latter effect is identified as an increase in equivalent width of saturated absorption lines under the presence of an intense magnetic field and depending on the Zeeman splitting pattern ([Babcock 1949](#); [Stift & Leone 2003](#); [Kochukhov 2021](#)). Statistical studies of M dwarf magnetic properties revealed extremely intense cases such as WXUMa, with a field of 7.3 kG ([Shulyak et al. 2017](#)).

The output of these analyses is encapsulated in the disk-averaged magnetic flux Bf (measured in Gauss), where B is the modulus of the field and f is the filling factor, i.e. the portion of the stellar surface occupied by magnetic regions. Models postulate either a single value of B and f ([Saar 1988](#)) or a more elaborated multi-component, small-scale scenario ([Johns-Krull et al. 1999](#); [Shulyak et al. 2014](#); [Kochukhov 2021](#)), but in general these two quantities are degenerate. Depending on the field strength (i.e. on the Zeeman broadening relative to the intrinsic width), their estimate is more or less challenging.

4.2.2 Magnetic field vector

Circularly and linearly polarised spectra are sensitive to the magnetic field orientation, so they can be used to infer properties of the field geometry. In this case, the lack of spatial resolution translates into polarisation cancellation effects due to the contribution of areas with opposite field polarity, making the observations sensitive only to largest scales of the field. Therefore, repeated spectropolarimetric measurements are necessary to cover the rotation cycle of a star and eventually observe the magnetic field under different angles, i.e. a modulation of the polarity cancellation. This is a principal distinction with respect to Zeeman broadening analysis.

Stokes V amplitudes are typically on the order of 10^{-3} the level of unpolarised continuum, whereas Stokes Q and U are one order of magnitude smaller ([Kochukhov et al. 2011](#); [Lavail et al. 2018](#)). Observations of cool stars in linear polarisation mode are thus limited to bright stars with strong surface fields and in the following I will mainly focus on circular polarisation. High-S/N observations are generally required to enable polarised Zeeman signatures to emerge from the noise and yield a reliable magnetic detection. In practice, for cool stars, this is achieved condensing the polarimetric information of the

observed spectra in Stokes profiles using LSD (see Sec. 2.2). Owing to the often unknown magnetic sensitivity for molecular lines, atomic absorption lines are used almost exclusively for this purpose. The output Stokes profiles benefit from a S/N gain that scales with the square root of the number of lines used in LSD and varies between 10x and 30x for M and G dwarfs.

In Sec. 4.1.1, I mentioned that circular polarisation is measurable when it has non-zero component parallel to the magnetic field vector, i.e. the longitudinal component (B_l). If we invert the sentence, we can measure B_l from the first order moment of Stokes V ; this is done formally by means of Eq. 2.8. The longitudinal field is a useful quantity for a preliminary evaluation of the magnetic field geometry, because its sign variations could either indicate a predominantly dipolar field (if the it is always positive or negative) or a toroidal axisymmetric field (if it has a symmetrical signature), or a more complex or non-axisymmetric configuration (if the sign changes periodically). Another hint suggesting a misalignment between the magnetic field axis and the stellar rotation axis is a varying amplitude of B_l phase modulation. These aspects will be developed further in the context of magnetic topology evolution in Chapter 5.

Zeeman-Doppler Imaging

A complete reconstruction of the large-scale magnetic field geometry is achieved with a tomographic technique called Zeeman-Doppler Imaging (ZDI; Piskunov & Khokhlova 1983; Semel 1989; Donati & Brown 1997), whose description and principles can be found in Appendix A. The idea is analogous to Doppler Imaging, described in Sec. 3.2, but the iterative algorithm compares observed and synthetic circularly polarised profiles, rather than unpolarised light, and reconstructs a vector quantity instead of a scalar. An example is illustrated in Fig. 4.4.

Contrarily to Doppler Imaging, there is no strict constraint on $v_{\text{eq}} \sin(i)$ for ZDI to be applied. This stems from our knowledge of the intrinsic reference profile, i.e., associated to the quiet photosphere: for unpolarised light, we need to adjust the line parameters (e.g., width and depth) which are unknown a priori, whereas for circularly polarised light the reference profile is simply a constant line at zero, hence perfectly known. In this case, $v_{\text{eq}} \sin(i)$ determines the maximum degree of the spherical harmonic expansion l_{max} in a proportional way, and therefore the amount of complexity we can image (Hussain et al. 2009). In other words, given a complex field topology, a higher value of $v_{\text{eq}} \sin(i)$ will translate in a higher achievable l_{max} and therefore a more structured description of the field. Moreover, faster rotation and thus rotational broadening implies that the Zeeman signatures are more separated in radial velocity space, ultimately limiting polarity cancellation.

The vector magnetic field is modelled as the sum of a poloidal and a toroidal component, both expressed via spherical harmonics decomposition (Donati et al. 2006; Lehmann & Donati 2022). This formal approach is effective at describing the properties of the large-scale magnetic field geometry (e.g., poloidal or toroidal, and axisymmetric or non-axisymmetric) and classify stars accordingly. Zeeman-Doppler Imaging was applied extensively to M dwarfs, especially because they host strong fields compared to other spectral types and thus allow a firm detection of polarimetric Zeeman signatures.

Similarly to Doppler Imaging, cases for which the star is observed pole-on or equator-on yield less reliable magnetic field maps, as the Stokes profiles would not feature rotationally modulated changes in the former scenario, and an ambiguity between north and south hemisphere would appear in the latter scenario. In addition, in the equator-on case the modes with odd l and $m = 0$ cancel out. One important limitation in ZDI is the lack of an intrinsic variability model, i.e. magnetic topologies are assumed to not evolve over time, except for differential rotation. In reality, features on the stellar surface can evolve rapidly, and eventually over shorter time scales than the observations span (see Sec. 1.3). As a result, to maintain coherency of magnetic activity, one has to split the data sets (Yu et al. 2019). First attempts to implement intrinsic variability models have proven successful on simulated data. Finocietty & Donati (2022) recently combined sparse approximation and Gaussian Process Regression to include temporal evolution of the magnetic field topology.

Figure 4.4: Zeeman-Doppler Imaging maps of the large-scale magnetic field at the surface of EQ Peg A (top) and B (bottom). In each column, the radial (left), azimuthal (middle) and meridional (right) components of the magnetic field vector are displayed. The radial ticks are located at the rotational phases when the observations were collected, while the concentric circles represent different stellar latitudes: -30° , $+30^\circ$ and $+60^\circ$ (dashed lines) and equator (solid line). The colour bar range is set by the maximum (in absolute value) of the magnetic field and illustrates the positive (red) and negative (blue) polarity. The field is strong (~ 1 kG), mostly poloidal, dipolar and axisymmetric for both stars. Taken from [Morin et al. \(2008b\)](#).

4.2.3 Limitations of magnetic measurements

Both unpolarised spectroscopy and spectropolarimetry yielded numerous and fundamental results on the magnetic field for low-mass stars, but they are subject to limitations. Here, I summarise the main caveats to consider when the above techniques are applied and their results interpreted.

- To an individual, high S/N Stokes I spectrum, we model the Zeeman effect in unpolarised radiative transfer calculations (in the form of broadening, splitting or intensification) in order to obtain a value of the magnetic field modulus regardless of its complexity. Such value provides partial information to feedback on dynamo theories, and its accuracy stems mostly from our knowledge of the zero-field profile. The latter is determined by overlapping broadening mechanisms which need to be carefully disentangled from magnetically-induced-only effects using low Landé factor lines. For active, slowly rotating stars, Zeeman broadening is more distinguishable from other broadening mechanisms and therefore its modelling is more favourable. For fast-rotating stars instead, magnetic intensification measurements are used ([Shulyak et al. 2017](#)).
- From a time series of high S/N Stokes V spectra, we extract properties of the magnetic field vector. An advantage of polarisation spectra is that the null profile is simply a flat line at zero, hence the confusion with other broadening mechanisms does not appear. The application of tomographic techniques is not constrained by the stellar $v_{\text{eq}} \sin(i)$ (but the larger it is, the more spatial resolution is obtained up to a certain velocity, see Sec. 3.2) and measurements of weak fields on the order of a few G are feasible ([Aurière et al. 2009](#); [Landstreet 2015](#)). Furthermore, the presence of Zeeman signatures reflect unambiguously the existence of a magnetic field, enabling snapshot surveys to be performed ([Grunhut et al. 2010](#); [Alecian et al. 2013](#); [Marsden et al. 2014](#); [Aurière et al. 2015](#); [Wade et al. 2016](#)). However, polarity cancellation effects mask small-scale fields out, making local tangled features on the stellar surface undetected.

Figure 4.5: Ratio of the average magnetic field strength recovered with ZDI to the total magnetic field resulting from Stokes I modelling, taking into account broadening, splitting and intensification. Stars with dipolar and axisymmetric (red circles), and with either multipolar or dipolar, non-axisymmetric (blue squares) fields are shown. The former technique is sensitive only to a portion of the total magnetic field strength, owing to polarity cancellation effects. Taken from Kochukhov (2021).

For both unpolarised spectroscopy and spectropolarimetry one important limitation is that we do not account for brightness distribution or velocity fields (except for global rotation), which are likely structured on small-scale, like the magnetic field.

A crucial aspect to consider is the complementarity of the two approaches: Stokes I conveys information on the total magnetic field, while Stokes V gives the orientation of the field on large-scales only. As a result, the magnetic field strength inferred from Stokes V is systematically lower than that of Stokes I (Reiners 2009; Kochukhov & Shulyak 2019). We therefore lose a significant contribution to the magnetic flux budget of a star. As shown in Fig. 4.5, the ratio of the field intensities (B_V/B) is lower than 20-25% for fully-convective M dwarfs, and lower than 10% for partly convective ones (Morin et al. 2010; Yadav et al. 2015).

One possibility to infer more details of the magnetic surface and increase the fraction of recovered magnetic flux is to perform additional observations in linear polarisation mode (Piskunov & Kochukhov 2002; Kochukhov & Wade 2010; Rosén et al. 2015). An additional benefit is that such observations would also prevent cross-talk between the radial and meridional components of the field. This issue occurs when only circular polarisation observations are acquired, because we would not observe temporal changes associated to the transverse component of the vector field with respect to the line of sight (see Sec. 4.1.1). However, linear polarisation observations are still insensitive to the small-scale field, and subject to phase coverage gaps and noise that make tomographic inversion an ill-posed problem requiring regularisation. Moreover, linear polarisation observations would require longer (a factor of four) exposure times than circular polarisation to achieve similar S/N, which restricts their efficient

usage to bright targets.

We can also perform a combined brightness+magnetic reconstruction with ZDI, i.e. taking into account high-contrast temperature spots (Rosén & Kochukhov 2012). In other words, brightness and magnetic field reconstruction should be performed simultaneously assuming a spatial correlation between brightness and magnetic spots. This would prevent the underestimation of the reconstructed magnetic field strength (Rosén & Kochukhov 2012). However, the correlation between brightness and magnetic field is not always straightforward: a region of strong field could be darker or brighter depending on the stellar properties, but also on the same star.

Obtaining reliable information on stellar magnetic fields is important. On one side, magnetic maps guide dynamo theories towards a complete comprehension of the generation and sustain of magnetic fields with analogous or different conditions than the Sun (more detail in Sec. 4.4.). On the other side, they are necessary to model stellar magnetospheres and winds, which are fundamental to understand the space environment in which exoplanets are embedded as well as the evolution of stellar angular momentum loss. In this sense however, Lang et al. (2014) demonstrated that ignoring small-scale fields has a negligible influence on inferring models for the coronal structure and the spin-down rate. This is sensible considering that higher order modes fall off rapidly with increasing radius.

In summary, capturing a complete view of stellar magnetic fields necessitates the usage of multiple techniques, hence an ideal scenario is when studies encompass both Zeeman broadening and Zeeman-Doppler Imaging analyses. The stellar sample over which this is feasibly performed is restricted by opposite $v_{\text{eq}} \sin(i)$ requirements of the two techniques. For this thesis, I worked on active M dwarfs that allowed both approaches to be adopted, as it will be outlined in Chapter 5.

4.3 Spectropolarimetric instruments

Spectropolarimeters are characterised by a polarimetric unit inserted in the light path going from the telescope to the spectrograph, as illustrated in Fig. 4.6. The purpose is to decompose starlight into two orthogonal polarisation states before it passes through a spectrograph and reaches the detector (Landi Degl’Innocenti & Landolfi 2004; Bagnulo et al. 2009).

First, light travels through a retarder waveplate, which is an optical device characterised by two orthogonal principal axes (i.e., fast and slow). It selects only starlight with a polarisation state parallel to either of the two axes and introduces a phase difference of π (half-wave plate) or $\pi/2$ (quarter-wave plate) between the two polarisation components. Then, the light beam encounters an analyser (a Wollaston prism, for instance) and splits into two beams with orthogonal polarisation states ($I_{//}$ and I_{\perp}), which are carried to the spectrograph and detector via fibre optics.

In case of circularly polarised light, the quarter-wave plate converts the polarisation state into linearly polarised light while keeping directions separate: right circular polarisation becomes linear in one direction and left circular polarisation in the orthogonal direction. The analyser then makes the two beams follow different paths until they reach the detector, where two stellar images are obtained: conveying information on either left or right circularly polarised starlight.

A spectropolarimetric observation (typically called “sequence”) is composed of four sub-exposures taken consecutively with a specific angle of the retarder waveplate relative to the axis of the analyser. For each of the following angles $\{45^\circ, 135^\circ, 225^\circ, 315^\circ\}$ we measure $I_{//}$ and I_{\perp} , for a total of eight spectra. Stokes I and V are obtained by combining the four sub-exposures using the so-called “ratio method” following (Donati et al. 1997; Bagnulo et al. 2009)

$$\begin{cases} I = \sum_{n=1}^4 I_{//,n} + I_{\perp,n}, \\ V = I_{\frac{R-1}{R+1}}, \end{cases} \quad (4.6)$$

where

$$R^4 = \frac{I_{//,45^\circ}/I_{\perp,45^\circ}}{I_{//,135^\circ}/I_{\perp,135^\circ}} \frac{I_{//,315^\circ}/I_{\perp,315^\circ}}{I_{//,225^\circ}/I_{\perp,225^\circ}}, \quad (4.7)$$

Figure 4.6: Schematic view of the main components of a polarimeter. Taken from Bagnulo et al. (2009).

Figure 4.7: Schematic view of the main units of SPIrou (left) and of the Cassegrain Unit (right). Taken from Donati et al. (2020).

Furthermore, it is possible to construct the “Null” profile (Stokes N) using four sub-exposures similarly to Stokes V , but combining them destructively. Stokes N provides a quality check of the observations, since its amplitude is representative of the noise level of the Stokes profiles. A clean polarimetric sequence free from systematic effects and spurious polarisation signals would feature a flat N profile compatible with zero down to the noise level.

4.3.1 SPIrou

As part of my thesis project, I analysed data collected with the SpectroPolarimètre InfraRouge (Donati et al. 2020), the near-infrared spectropolarimeter and high-precision velocimeter installed on the 3.6-m Canada-France-Hawaii Telescope (CFHT) atop Mauna Kea, Hawaii. SPIrou is the successor of previous spectropolarimeters (ESPaDONs and NARVAL) and velocimeters (HARPS) and was developed by an international consortium led by France and involving CFHT, Canada, Switzerland, Brazil, Taiwan and Portugal. In the following, I will summarise its main instrumental components, performances and current results.²

As shown in Fig. 4.7, the entrance beam coming from the telescope mirrors travels through:

- A Cassegrain unit featuring 1) an atmospheric dispersion corrector and a tip-tilt module in the

²More information is available on the SPIrou official website at <https://spirou.omp.eu/>

upper structure for stabilisation of the star’s image with respect to the entrance aperture, and 2) an achromatic polarimeter in the lower structure consisting of two 3/4-wave Fresnel rhombs and a Wollaston prism that separate the input beam into two, with orthogonal polarisation states. By rotating the rhombs, it is possible to obtain either circular or linear polarisation states.

- Two identical science optical fibers that re-direct the two polarised beams toward the spectrograph and a pupil slicer that ensures high throughput while maintaining the resolving power level.
- A cross-dispersed spectrograph capable of recording the wavelength range 0.98-2.35 μm on a 16 megapixel H4RG detector in a single exposure. The spectrograph is contained in a cryogenic dewar under vacuum and maintained at a temperature of 73.5 K to prevent spurious shifts of less than m s^{-1} between science and reference channels.

A separated calibration and RV reference unit is linked to the spectrograph via a third optical fibre, to correct the spectra and reach the highest achievable precision. The fibre conveys light from a halogen lamp (for flat-fielding), a U/Ne hollow-cathode lamp (for absolute wavelength calibration), a Fabry-Perot etalon (for spectrograph drift correction and refined wavelength calibration), and a Laser Frequency Comb (for a RV calibration down to cm s^{-1} , [Hobson et al. 2021](#)) inside the unit. The Laser Frequency Comb covers a spectral range between 1.0 and 2.2 μm , smaller than the nominal domain of the spectrographs, hence its adaptation is ongoing ([Donati et al. 2020](#)).

Performance

The operational spectral range of SPIRou covers the Y, J, H, and K bands, i.e. from 0.95 to 2.5 μm , with a resolving power of 70 000. During commissioning, bright ($H=4.8$) and faint ($H=7.95$) M dwarfs were observed with 60 s and 300 s exposures and led to peak S/N per velocity bin (2.28 km s^{-1}) at 2.1 μm of 250 and 110, respectively. The thermal background was estimated to degrade the S/N in the reddest orders for $H=8$, while becoming dominant for $H=9$. Accounting for instrument, light injection stability, and telluric correction the current RV precision is around 2 m s^{-1} for a mid M dwarf with S/N of 200 ([Donati et al. 2020](#)). As far as the polarimetric capabilities are concerned, SPIRou can detect Zeeman signatures with a sensitivity of 10^{-5} , while cross-talk between circular and linear polarisation was estimated to be only about 1.1% (i.e., within specification).

The reduction pipeline of SPIRou is APERO (A PipelinE to Reduce Observations, [Cook et al. 2022](#)), which performs sequential calibration steps to provide science-ready products. Examples of such steps are: identification of spurious pixels, wavelength calibration, telluric lines and inter-night drift correction, zero-point correction, and Barycentric Earth Radial Velocity (BERV) correction (more details can be found in [Donati et al. 2020](#); [Hobson et al. 2021](#); [Artigau et al. 2022](#); [Cook et al. 2022](#)).

Telluric correction is crucial to remove spurious RV biases and obtain the required sensitivity for the SPIRou science goals ([Moutou et al. 2020](#)). Indeed, near-infrared observations are polluted by numerous and strong telluric bands due to atmospheric absorption of mostly H_2O centered at 0.95, 1.14, 1.40, and 1.90 μm , as well as other molecules like CO_2 , O_2 , CH_4 , and OH. The latter molecule produces a night glow due to atoms recombining after being photoionised by the Sun during the day and it is seen as an emission feature in the spectra ([Rousselot et al. 2000](#)).

In APERO, the correction is performed by means of a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) method developed by [Artigau et al. \(2014\)](#). Basically, by recording spectra of bright telluric standard stars on a nightly basis, we can build a database of observations characterised by distinct atmospheric conditions (e.g., water vapor amount) and generate a master telluric transmission template. Science spectra are matched with the template, allowing telluric lines to be removed.

APERO has been cross-tested with a Libre-Esprit version adapted to SPIRou. During my Ph.D. project, I contributed to perform these tests.

The SPIRou Legacy Survey

The SPIRou Legacy Survey (SLS) is a large programme to which 300 CFHT nights were allocated until end of summer 2022. Its main science drivers have been 1) detecting habitable Earth-like exoplanets around nearby M dwarfs and 2) investigating formation of solar-like stars and their planets. The organisation of SPIRou science is structured in five work packages:³

- WP1: Radial velocity planet search around nearby M dwarfs (Cortes-Zuleta et al. 2023; Carmona et al. 2023, in press).
- WP2: Radial velocity follow-up of interesting candidate systems unraveled by photometric transit surveys like, e.g., *K2*, *TESS* (e.g., Martioli et al. 2022; Cadieux et al. 2022; Kiefer et al. 2022).
- WP3: Spectropolarimetric monitoring of magnetised pre-main-sequence stars with annexed investigation of magnetic field impact on planet formation (e.g., Bouvier et al. 2020; Finocciety et al. 2021; Sousa et al. 2021).
- WP4: Optimisation of theoretical and observational techniques to find and characterise exoplanets around both M dwarfs and young stars (e.g., Bellotti et al. 2021; Artigau et al. 2022)
- WP5: Complementary investigations including spectral analysis improvements, large-scale magnetic field monitoring for M dwarfs, and study of the Earth’s atmosphere modelling (e.g., Petit et al. 2021; Cristofari et al. 2022b,a; Fouqué et al. 2023)

The observations analysed for my Ph.D. project were collected in the framework of WP1, WP2, and WP4.

A new large programme called SPICE has been set up after completion of the SLS, for a total of 174 CFHT nights. The goal is to improve the characterisation of nearby exoplanet systems for a specific sample of late M dwarfs, *TESS* candidates and pre-main-sequence stars, and thus consolidate further the impact of SPIRou science in light of future studies with *JWST*, *Ariel* and ELTs.

4.4 Dynamo theory

What is the origin of magnetic fields in stars? One hypothesis suggests that, during star formation, the gravitational collapse of a molecular clouds drags the magnetic field lines tethered within the clouds (and made of electrically conducting material), leading to steady magnetic configurations. These remnant “fossil” fields have been observed for both chemically peculiar Ap/Bp stars (Landstreet 2009b; Walder et al. 2012). However, this picture has been further developed by Alecian et al. (2019), who showed that many known Ap stars would have passed through a stage in which their interiors were fully or partially convective and hence through a stage in which they had internal dynamo activity. This means that these stars could have potentially hosted more complex magnetic fields before retaining the simpler “fossil” fields observed in 5-10% of A and B-type stars (Grunhut et al. 2017).

This picture does not reconcile with observations of the Sun, since the solar magnetic field manifests temporal variations and induces surface inhomogeneities (see Sec. 1.3). To explain this, we need to invoke the dynamo theory, i.e. the active conversion of kinetic energy associated to hydrodynamical motions of plasma in stellar interiors into magnetic energy, mainly via coupling of rotation and convection.⁴ Such processes can generate and sustain magnetic fields against Ohmic decay over stellar lifetimes (Larmor 1919; Charbonneau 2010). Solar observations represent the main guidelines to a

³More information can be found at <https://spirou-legacy.irap.omp.eu/doku.php?id=start>

⁴Alternatively, a tidally synchronized solar dynamo has been proposed, based on the fact that the orbital period of Jupiter coincides with the solar activity cycle period (Stefani et al. 2019). However, recent studies on exoplanet hosts have found no relation between the gravitational influence of the planet and the stellar cycle, and concluded that a strong gravitational influence may even quench the stellar dynamo completely (Obridko et al. 2022).

Figure 4.8: The butterfly diagram of the Sun. Top: fractional coverage of sunspots as a function of solar latitude and time. Bottom: evolution of the number of sunspots over time. Courtesy of D. Hathaway, Solar Cycle Science, <http://www.solarcyclescience.com/solarcycle.html>

comprehensive dynamo theory, considering the accessible spatial resolution and the possibility to appreciate the wide variety of phenomena occurring on the surface. To this date, however, there is no complete theory that can explain all the observed phenomena (Charbonneau 2020; Petrovay 2020).

4.4.1 The Sun as a benchmark

The long-term evolution of solar surface features (i.e. sunspots) was already noticed by Schwabe (1844), who pointed out an 11-yr cyclic variation in their number, and also by Maunder (1904) who described the spot latitudinal migration by means of the well-known butterfly diagram, presented in Fig. 4.8. These discoveries were later complemented by the polarity reversal law of sunspots over 22 yr (Hale et al. 1919) and the correlated evolution of the large-scale dipolar field (Babcock & Babcock 1955), as well as the oscillation of its tilt angle and poloidal-to-toroidal contribution (Sanderson et al. 2003). Indeed, there is a cyclic regeneration of the large-scale field, for which the poloidal component peaks at sunspot cycle minimum and the toroidal component increases significantly at cycle maximum. These findings set the distinction between the 11-yr *activity* cycle and the 22-yr *magnetic* cycle.

From a theoretical standpoint, the cyclic regeneration is reproduced by the $\alpha\Omega$ dynamo (Parker 1955; Charbonneau 2010), i.e., the interplay between differential rotation (Ω -effect) and cyclonic turbulence (α -effect). Fig. 4.9 illustrates the mechanism: 1) differential rotation stretches poloidal magnetic field lines over latitudes, converting them into a toroidal configuration, and 2) small-scale turbulent plasma motions twist toroidal lines into loops which, on large-scales, result in a toroidal current passing through these loops, ultimately regenerating a poloidal field. A more refined alternative to the $\alpha\Omega$ dynamo is the Babcock-Leighton mechanism (see Fig 4.9), which describes the conversion from toroidal to poloidal field via a poleward migration of bipolar magnetic regions (Babcock 1961; Leighton 1969; Jouve et al. 2010). In practice, sunspots emerge in pairs and tilted relative to the East-West direction, with the leading sunspot (with respect to the solar rotation direction) at a lower latitude; this is known as Joy's law. This phenomenon has a latitudinal dependence, being stronger at higher latitudes (Stenflo & Kosovichev 2012). The tilt of this bipolar magnetic region translates in a non-zero dipole moment,

Figure 4.9: Mechanisms at the base of the solar dynamo model. The Ω -effect transforms a poloidal field into a toroidal field via differential rotation. Restoring a poloidal field from a toroidal field is accomplished in two ways: the α -effect sees cyclonic turbulence twisting toroidal field lines into small-scale poloidal fields which, on average, constitute a global poloidal field. The Babcock-Leighton mechanism sees the formation of bipolar regions on the surface; those close to equator diffuse and reconnect between hemispheres, whereas the remaining ones are transported towards the pole by meridional circulation and produce a large-scale poloidal field. Taken from [Sanchez et al. \(2014\)](#).

which gradually diffuses via surface flows and reconnects with other regions. Taking into account several magnetic regions, their advection towards the pole via meridional circulation ultimately results in a net large-scale poloidal field.

Together with the poloidal-toroidal interplay, an ideal model for solar dynamo should encompass additional aspects that characterise the solar magnetism. For instance, field strength, equatorward migration of sunspots, cyclic polarity reversals, flip-flop cycles, and dominant hemispheric magnetic helicity ([Berdyugina & Usoskin 2003](#); [Charbonneau 2020](#)). This has to be coupled with our knowledge of the internal structure of the Sun.

The Sun has a partly-convective interior, meaning that it has a radiative core surrounded by a convective envelope. The energy produced in the core by hydrogen thermonuclear fusion is initially transported outward, through the densest and hottest regions, by radiation. Then, the energy is also transported by convection: rising cells of hot plasma transport energy to the photosphere, cool down and sink back in a cyclical fashion. The interface between the radiative and convective zone is called *tachocline*, a region of strong shear revealed by helioseismic studies ([Spiegel & Zahn 1992](#)) and the location where magnetic flux tubes are stored and amplified until they eventually rise to the surface and generate spots.

Magnetohydrodynamical (MHD) simulations of solar dynamo in three-dimensional spherical shells corroborated the central role of the tachocline, especially to achieve global-scale ordering of structures ([Brun et al. 2004](#); [Browning et al. 2006](#)). Other simulations, focusing on the bulk of the convection zone, showed the formation of enduring magnetic wreaths coexisting with turbulent convection and in the absence of a tachocline ([Brown et al. 2010](#)), a result that put the role of the latter into question. In terms of cycles, more recent MHD simulations have succeeded at reproducing polarity reversals and quasi-regular oscillations (e.g., [Brown et al. 2011](#); [Guerrero et al. 2016](#); [Strugarek et al. 2018](#)), but our understanding of the cyclic nature of the solar magnetism is still not complete. Indeed, many questions about solar dynamo remain unanswered ([Charbonneau 2020](#)).

4.4.2 Dynamo action in other stars

To obtain a better picture of the solar dynamo and refine its portability, it is important to extend dynamo studies to other stars as well. In particular, it is fundamental to understand how the generation of magnetic fields vary over different stellar temperatures, convective velocities, and rotation rates.

Cool stars are either partly-convective (between mid-F and M3 spectral type) and share similar internal structures as the Sun (with varying aspect ratios), or fully-convective (later than M3) and have no tachocline. In terms of stellar mass, the theoretical limit between the two regimes is $0.35 M_{\odot}$ (Chabrier & Baraffe 1997) and it is in agreement with observations, since it has been used to explain the *Gaia* magnitude gap (Feiden et al. 2021). However, metallicity affects the depth of the convective envelope (van Saders & Pinsonneault 2012; Tanner et al. 2013), and strong magnetic fields quench convection, pushing the boundary towards later spectral type (Mullan & MacDonald 2001), hence it is not a well-defined limit.

In this light, M dwarfs are suitable laboratories to test dynamo theories under similar or different conditions than the Sun, i.e. with partly- and fully-convective interiors. Numerical MHD simulations for early-type, rapidly-rotating M dwarfs performed by Bice & Toomre (2020) indicated that a tachocline is not necessary to achieve strong and organised toroidal wreaths, although its presence would regularise magnetic cycles and allow long-term cycle variations. Generally, a solar-like $\alpha\Omega$ dynamo is adopted to explain the generation of magnetic field in partly-convective stars.

From early ideas on dynamo action in fully convective stars, the Ω -effect cannot apply since the stars exhibit solid body rotation (Küker & Rüdiger 1999), and do not possess a tachocline, where the Ω -effect is supposed to be the most efficient. The generation of magnetic fields is thus explained invoking small-scale dynamo, i.e. at the scale of plasma motions (Durney et al. 1993), or scenarios in which cyclonic turbulence is the sole mechanism at play (i.e. α^2 models, Chabrier & Küker 2006; Yadav et al. 2015). Simulations in this case yield strong (on the order of kG) large-scale magnetic fields with a significant axisymmetric component (Dobler et al. 2006; Browning 2008), but fail at reproducing the observations.

There has been extensive effort to understand the generation of large-scale fields dominated by an axisymmetric dipole, especially for large density contrasts (Gastine et al. 2012; Raynaud et al. 2015; Yadav et al. 2015; Zaire et al. 2022). Fig. 4.10 illustrates an example. Alternatively, mean-field dynamo models are capable of predicting long-term evolution of the field geometry, but provide no information on the global field strength (Kitchatinov et al. 2014; Pipin 2017). Yadav et al. (2016) carried out MHD simulations tailored to be representative of Proxima Cen and predicted a 9-yr cycle of both field strength and topological variations, in accordance with the 7-yr cycle seen with photometry (Suárez Mascareño et al. 2016; Wargelin et al. 2017).

These considerations stress the relevance of a synergistic effort between theoretical self-consistent MHD simulations and long-term observational follow-up of cool stars. In fact, guiding dynamo theories for both partly- and fully-convective stars requires extended observations of stellar magnetic fields across a wide range of properties (mass, rotation period, etc). The following section aims at summarising the current situation in terms of observations, as well as to link specific cases to theoretical simulations.

4.4.3 Observational feedback on dynamo

Activity and rotation

As mentioned in Sec. 1.4.1, the activity level of a star can be quantified by indirect proxies representing a certain amount of chromospheric and coronal emission in specific lines or bandwidths, e.g. CaII H&K lines, H α and X-rays (normalised to bolometric luminosity). Numerous studies have shown that these proxies follow the same trend with stellar rotation (e.g., Noyes et al. 1984; Wright et al. 2011; Reiners et al. 2014; Newton et al. 2017; Wright et al. 2018), which has been conveniently parametrised by the Rossby number ($Ro = P_{\text{rot}}/\tau$): the ratio between the stellar rotation period and the convective turnover time, i.e. the typical timescale for a convective cell to rise in a fluid. As reported in Fig. 4.11, the activity proxies increase with decreasing Rossby number down to $Ro \simeq 0.1$, symbolising a more efficient dynamo for faster rotators, whereas below $Ro \simeq 0.1$ a saturated regime is reached.

Figure 4.10: Magnetohydrodynamic simulations of the radial magnetic field for a fully convective M dwarf with $v_{\text{eq}} \sin(i) = 20 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. From the left, the simulated field, low-pass (degree $l < 10$) filtered map and ZDI reconstruction are shown. This figure helps showing the loss of information of small-scales when ZDI reconstructions are performed, as mentioned in Sec. 4.2.2. Adapted from [Yadav et al. \(2015\)](#).

An analogous behaviour has been found for the magnetic field strength inferred by Zeeman broadening measurements ([Saar 1996](#); [Shulyak et al. 2017](#); [Kochukhov 2021](#)) and which, in turn, exhibited a secondary dependence on magnetic field large-scale field geometry ([Shulyak et al. 2017, 2019](#)). Stars with multipolar fields saturate around $P_{\text{rot}}=4 \text{ d}$ and $B=4 \text{ kG}$, while stars with dipolar fields can sustain stronger fields at faster rotation (see Fig. 4.11). However, the large scatter of the data points at short rotation periods does not allow us to conclude whether a maximum magnetic field is achieved or the field could still increase, which motivates more observations of ultra-rapid rotators. Moreover, the scatter of field strength values for stars with similar Ro indicates that dynamo efficiency is not solely determined by stellar rotation period and mass, as predicted in the [Morin et al. \(2011\)](#) strong field dynamo idea, but an unknown combination of fundamental parameters is at play ([Kochukhov & Shulyak 2019](#)), or the temporal variability is significant enough to blur the relation. Overall, for Bf it seems that a change exists but rather for late M dwarfs, all being fast rotators in the sample examined.

In terms of internal structure, there is no abrupt change in X-ray emission or magnetic field strength at the transition between partly- and fully-convective ([Reiners 2012](#); [Wright et al. 2018](#)), suggesting that the underlying dynamo mechanisms may be similar. Instead, we observe a possible breakdown of the activity-rotation relation around spectral type M7-M9 since, given a Ro value, the distribution of field strength for these stars reaches lower values than the earlier counterparts ([Reiners 2009](#)).

By making a distinction based on age, [Oláh et al. \(2016\)](#) noted that old, slowly-rotating stars tend to have smooth and simple cycles, whereas younger fast-rotating stars exhibit abrupt changes and complex temporal variations. Furthermore, the activity cycles census revealed two populations of stars, named “active” and “inactive”, featuring different scaling laws between cycle period and rotation period ([Saar & Brandenburg 1999](#); [Böhm-Vitense 2007](#); [Metcalf et al. 2016](#)), presumably due to metallicity differences ([Amard & Matt 2020](#); [Bonanno & Corsaro 2022](#)). According to the scaling relations, active stars tend to have longer cycles than inactive ones, for a fixed rotation period. In addition, stars on the active branch tend to have toroidal-dominated topologies, while the inactive ones are mostly poloidal ([See et al. 2016](#)). The cycle period-rotation period relation therefore provides feedback on the time scale over which the toroidal field rises to the surface, following the solar picture, and thus on which shear layer is most crucial to originate activity ([Böhm-Vitense 2007](#)). Originally, the Sun was found to fall amid the two branches, which was interpreted as a transitional evolutionary state ([Metcalf et al. 2016](#)), but more recent studies showed that the region of the plot around the Sun is indeed populated ([Boro Saikia et al. 2018](#)).

Figure 4.11: Rotation-Activity relation for low-mass (later than mid-F) stars seen with different activity proxies. Top left: X-ray-to-bolometric index. Top right: $H\alpha$ index. Bottom left: Magnetic flux density. Sun-like stars (crosses) M0-M6 (black circles), and M7-M9 (red squares) are shown. Bottom right: mean magnetic field obtained from radiative transfer modelling of Zeeman broadening. Symbols are color-coded by stellar spectral type, while the background markers indicate whether the magnetic topology is dipolar, axisymmetric (green diamonds) or multipolar, non-axisymmetric (blue squares). Taken from Wright et al. (2011); Newton et al. (2017); Reiners (2012); Kochukhov (2021).

Results from spectropolarimetry

Zeeman-Doppler Imaging applied to spectropolarimetric data sets has revealed a diversity of magnetic field topologies and properties, as illustrated in Fig. 4.12. Partly-convective stars with mass above $0.5 M_{\odot}$ tend to have weak, predominantly toroidal and non-axisymmetric large-scale fields, whereas between 0.35 and $0.5 M_{\odot}$ they are stronger, poloidal and axisymmetric (Donati et al. 2008; Morin et al. 2008b; Phan-Bao et al. 2009). Recent simulations have successfully reproduced the transition between dipolar and multipolar regimes even at high Ro numbers (Zaire et al. 2022). In terms of magnetic cycles, polarity flips of the large-scale field were detected on sun-like stars: e.g., HD 190771 (Petit et al. 2009), τ Boo (Fares et al. 2009; Jeffers et al. 2018), 61 Cyg A, ε Eri (Boro Saikia et al. 2016; Jeffers et al. 2022), and κ Cet (Boro Saikia et al. 2022). Likewise, photometric and chromospheric activity index campaigns reported periodicities shorter (e.g., τ Boo) or longer ($\simeq 30$ yr) than the solar activity cycle (Wilson 1968; Baliunas et al. 1995; Suárez Mascareño et al. 2016; Boro Saikia et al. 2018).

For stars close to the fully-convective limit, the field topology is dipolar. EV Lac represents an interestingly strange case because of its highly non-axisymmetric topology. For fully-convective stars below approximately $0.2 M_{\odot}$, a dichotomy of topologies has been generally observed to co-exist: weak, complex, non-axisymmetric against strong, simple, axisymmetric (Morin et al. 2008b, 2010). The observed dichotomy is valid also for fully-convective stars with similar fundamental parameters and rotation

Figure 4.12: Magnetic topology diagram for cool stars. The y - and x -axes represent the mass and rotation period of the star, and iso-Rossby number curves are overplotted using the empirical relations of [Wright et al. \(2018\)](#). The symbol size, color and shape encodes the ZDI average field strength, poloidal/toroidal energy fraction and axisymmetry. From the work of this thesis I added CN Leo, and from data I worked on as part of collaborations I added TOI-1759 and GJ 436. Data entering the plot are taken from [Donati et al. 2008](#); [Morin et al. 2008b](#); [Phan-Bao et al. 2009](#); [Morin et al. 2010](#); [Hébrard et al. 2016](#); [Kochukhov & Lavail 2017](#); [Moutou et al. 2017](#); [Kochukhov & Shulyak 2019](#); [Klein et al. 2021](#); [Martioli et al. 2022](#); [Cortes-Zuleta et al. 2023](#); [Bellotti et al.](#), in prep.

periods. An interesting example is the GJ 65 binary system consisting of two M dwarfs (M5.5 and M6) with nearly identical masses, rotation period and evolutionary track, but with two opposite topologies: weak, non-axisymmetric (GJ 65 A) and strong, axisymmetric (GJ 65 B) ([Kochukhov & Lavail 2017](#)).

These findings on fully-convective stars can be explained by either two distinct and independent branches of dynamo (known as bistability, [Morin 2012](#); [Gastine et al. 2013](#)) or by assuming the presence of magnetic cycles for which we reconstruct only a snapshot of a long-term topological variation ([Kitchatinov et al. 2014](#)). In the case of ultracool dwarfs (later than M7), [Route \(2016\)](#) reported changes in the sign of polarised radio emission, suggesting solar-like polarity flips, but no reversal has been detected with spectropolarimetry in the fully-convective regime. This motivates long-term spectropolarimetric monitoring of active stars further, in order to trace any temporal evolution of the large-scale field geometry and shed more light on which of the two hypotheses is more plausible.

Simultaneously, there is increasing interest in making magnetic field maps for slower rotators ([Hébrard et al. 2016](#); [Moutou et al. 2017](#)). On one side, this will fill up the uncharted region of Fig.4.12 and enlarge the parameter space to feed back dynamo theories with, and on the other side it will give access to crucial information to understand the stellar environment in which exoplanets are embedded ([Vidotto et al. 2014](#); [Villarreal D’Angelo et al. 2018](#)), considering that we are able to detect rocky planets around moderately active stars. Indeed, by virtue of the rotation-activity relation, slower rotators are less active, implying a “simplified” detection and characterisation of exoplanets in orbit around them. A lower activity level may also translate in a higher chance of habitability (see Sec. 1.5).

Chapter 5

Hunting for magnetic cycles in M dwarfs

Do partly- and fully-convective M dwarfs manifest magnetic cycles?

In this Chapter, I will outline the long-term monitoring of the large-scale magnetic field of well-known, active M dwarfs. The study was performed by computing distinct magnetic activity proxies, mapping the magnetic field via Zeeman-Doppler Imaging, and applying a new PCA technique to Stokes V profiles. I concatenated optical archival spectropolarimetric data collected with ESPaDOnS and Narval, with recent near-infrared observations collected with SPIRou mostly as part of the Legacy Survey. I sought for secular trends over time scales of 10-15 yr, that may share similarities with the known solar magnetic cycle or exhibit different evolution.

5.1 Motivation

Stellar *activity* cycles for M dwarfs have been reported as a result of photometric and chromospheric activity index campaigns (e.g., [Wilson 1968](#); [Baliunas et al. 1995](#); [Suárez Mascareño et al. 2016](#); [Boro Saikia et al. 2018](#)). However, contrary to solar-like stars, complementary spectropolarimetric monitoring has not grasped polarity reversals and thus the presence of *magnetic* cycles yet. This motivates long-term spectropolarimetric campaigns targeting active M dwarfs on both sides of the fully-convective boundary, in order to sample similar/different interior conditions than the Sun and provide context to the nature of its magnetic field.

The existence of magnetic cycles for fully-convective M dwarfs would shed light on the magnetic topology dichotomy for similar stellar fundamental parameters (see [4.4.3](#)). Besides, the form of the cycle itself, e.g. polarity flips, transition from dipolar to multipolar regimes, and multiplicity of cycles, would provide relevant constraints to dynamo theories, similarly to those found in earlier-type, partly-convective stars ([Petit et al. 2009](#); [Fares et al. 2009](#); [Jeffers et al. 2018](#); [Boro Saikia et al. 2016](#); [Jeffers et al. 2022](#); [Boro Saikia et al. 2022](#)).

In the context of exoplanets, evidence of activity cycles for M dwarfs was found via radial velocity exoplanet searches ([Gomes da Silva et al. 2012](#); [Lopez-Santiago et al. 2020](#)). Studies established that cycles introduce long-term signals in radial velocity data sets that can dominate over planetary signatures ([Meunier et al. 2010](#); [Meunier & Lagrange 2019](#)), as they modulate the appearance and number of heterogeneities on the stellar surface. It is therefore necessary to have an accurate constraint on the temporal variations of the cycle, in order to remove its contamination and allow a more reliable planetary detection and characterisation ([Lovis et al. 2011](#); [Costes et al. 2021](#); [Sairam & Triaud 2022](#)).

Indeed, activity cycles modulate the stellar radiation output and winds in which close-in planets are immersed ([Yeo et al. 2014](#); [Hazra et al. 2020](#)). This leads to a temporal variation in the planetary atmospheric stripping with consequent alteration of the chemical properties and habitability ([Lanza 2013](#); [McCann et al. 2019](#); [Louca et al. 2022](#); [Konings et al. 2022](#)). Details on the occurrence of the cycle

Table 5.1: Properties of the stellar sample examined. The following quantities are listed: 1) and 2) stellar name and alternative identifier, 3) spectral type, 4) mass, 5) radius, 6) rotation period at equator, 7) equatorial projected rotational velocity, 8) inclination, 9) X-ray-to-bolometric luminosity ratio (Wright et al. 2011), and 10) CaII H&K index (Noyes et al. 1984; Boro Saikia et al. 2018). Columns 3), 4), 5), 6), 7) and 8) are extracted from Morin et al. (2008b, 2010) and Hébrard et al. (2016), while columns 9) and 10) from Wright et al. (2011) and Boro Saikia et al. (2018), respectively. The symbol \dagger indicates that parameter was estimated in this work.

Star	ID	Sp Type	M_* [M_\odot]	R_* [R_\odot]	P_{rot} [d]	$v_{\text{eq}} \sin(i)$ [km s^{-1}]	i [deg]	$\log(L_X/L_{\text{bol}})$ [dex]	$\log R'_{\text{HK}}$ [dex]
AD Leo	GJ 388	M3.5	0.42	0.38	$2.23 \pm 0.01^\dagger$	3.0	20	-3.62	-4.00
DS Leo	GJ 410	M0.0	0.58	0.53	$13.91 \pm 0.01^\dagger$	2.0	60	-3.80	-4.16
CN Leo	GJ 406	M5.5	0.10	0.12	$2.70 \pm 0.01^\dagger$	3.2^\dagger	$> 75^\dagger$...	-4.01
EV Lac	GJ 873	M3.5	0.32	0.30	$4.36 \pm 0.01^\dagger$	4.0	60	-3.10	-3.75
V374 Peg	GJ 873	M4.0	0.28	0.28	$0.445 \pm 0.01^\dagger$	37.0	70	-3.15	...

extremes can thus inform the most suitable interpretation framework and observing plans for missions dedicated to transmission spectroscopy like *Ariel* (Tinetti et al. 2021).

Finally, recent LOFAR observations have revealed low-frequency, coherent, highly-circularly polarised radio emission for M dwarfs in a ubiquitous way (Vedantham et al. 2020; Callingham et al. 2021). A plausible explanation for triggering such emission is the presence of a planetary companion (Vedantham et al. 2020; Kavanagh et al. 2021, 2022), whose magnetosphere would have to link to the stellar magnetic field (see Sec. 1.5.1). An accurate modelling of this phenomenon requires updated information on the periodic variations of the stellar large-scale magnetic field geometry, as it affects the visibility of the radio signature.

In the following, I will outline the long-term analysis of the magnetic field for a sample of well-known active M dwarfs. I applied the same techniques for each star, in order to provide converging clues as to whether the star manifest long-term trends/cycles. The description is organised based on whether the stars manifest evident, moderate or weak evolution in the longitudinal field curve, in order to better highlight each case individually. Although not presented here, there are ongoing analyses involving the radiative transfer modelling of Zeeman broadening in individual lines in collaboration with Dr. Colin Folsom. As mentioned in Chapter 4, we can obtain a more complete view on the magnetic field of these stars from the combination of Zeeman broadening modelling and magnetic tomographic inversion, like the link between small- and large-scale fields. A complete description of the analyses will be part of Bellotti et al. 2023a, in prep and Bellotti et al. 2023b, in prep.

5.2 Observations

5.2.1 Active M dwarfs

I look for long-term trends on a selected sample of active M dwarfs: AD Leo, DS Leo, CN Leo, EV Lac, and V374 Peg. Their properties are summarised in Table 5.1. The masses of these stars range between 0.10 and 0.58 M_\odot , and therefore fall on both sides of the fully-convective regime at 0.35 M_\odot (Chabrier & Baraffe 1997). For this reason, they are primary targets to look for cycles, as their internal structure may feature similar or distinct conditions from the Sun. As mentioned in Chapter 3, V374 Peg is not part of the SPIRou Legacy Survey, because its high activity and fast rotation do not make it an optimal target for planet searches, which is one of the main goals of the survey.

5.2.2 Near-Infrared

All SPIRou observations were performed in circular polarisation mode. Optimal extraction of the spectra was carried out with APERO v0.6.132 (v0.7.273 for V374 Peg; Cook et al. 2022). Once again, unpo-

Figure 5.1: Examples of Stokes profiles computed from SPIRou data for AD Leo, DS Leo, CN Leo, EV Lac, and V374 Peg. For each star, Stokes I (top), V (middle), and Null N profile (bottom) are shown. The latter is used to check for any spurious polarimetric signal due to, e.g., light leakage (Donati et al. 1997; Bagnulo et al. 2009). In all panels, the units are relative to the unpolarised continuum.

larised (Stokes I) and circularly polarised (Stokes V) profiles were computed by means of LSD (Donati et al. 1997; Kochukhov et al. 2010).

I used a VALD line list (Ryabchikova et al. 2015; Gustafsson et al. 2008) computed on the Montpellier server¹ with MARCS model atmosphere characterised by $\log g = 5.0$ [cm s⁻²], $v_{\text{micro}} = 1$ km s⁻¹, and $T_{\text{eff}} = 3500$ K. The list contains 1400 atomic lines between 950–2600 nm with known g_{eff} (ranging from 0 to 3) and with depth larger than 3% the continuum level. CN Leo has a later spectral type, hence we

¹<http://vald.oreme.org>

used a similar mask but generated with $T_{\text{eff}} = 3000$ K, and containing 1000 atomic lines.

The near-infrared domain covered by SPIRou is polluted by strong and wide telluric bands due to Earth’s atmospheric absorption (see Sec. 4.3.1). The APERO pipeline has a PCA-based method implemented to handle telluric correction (Artigau et al. 2014), but I conservatively removed the following intervals in order to avoid any imperfection of the method: [950, 979], [1116, 1163], [1331, 1490], [1790, 1985], [1995, 2029], [2250, 2500] nm. These intervals contain deep absorption bands, where the signal would be almost null anyway, thus they would be weighted out by LSD. The final number of spectral lines used in LSD is 588 and 830 for the $T_{\text{eff}} = 3000$ K and $T_{\text{eff}} = 3500$ K line lists, respectively. We show the LSD Stokes profiles for the examined stars in Fig. 5.1.

AD Leo was observed for 77 nights between February 2019 and November 2021, spanning a period of 482 d. I discarded six observations in February 2019 since one optical component of the instrument was not working nominally, one observation in November 2019 because likely affected by a flare (the corresponding radial velocity is >8 sigma lower than the bulk of the measurements) and two observations in 2020 as they led to noisier (by a factor of 10) LSD profiles. The SPIRou observations were performed monthly between 2019 and 2020, except for two gaps of approximately two and three months. There is also a gap of 1.5 month between the end of 2019 and beginning of 2020. I therefore split the entire time series in smaller chunks to maintain coherency of magnetic activity over short time scales: 2019a (15th April 2019 to 21st June 2019), 2019b (16th October 2019 to 12th December 2019) 2020a (26th January 2020 to 12th March 2020), and 2020b (8th May 2020 to 10th June 2020). The S/N at 1650 nm per spectral element ranges between 68 and 220, with a mean of 169, and the mean airmass is 1.3. The average noise level in Stokes V for the entire time series is $1.6 \cdot 10^{-4}$ relative to the unpolarised continuum, similar to previous observations carried out in the optical domain (Morin et al. 2008b). We also note that the profiles are broader than in the optical by more than 10 km s^{-1} , which we attribute to a stronger Zeeman effect in the near-infrared domain (see Sec. 4.1.1).

DS Leo was observed for 130 nights between November 2020 and June 2022, spanning a period of ~ 580 d. The time series is split in two epochs: 2020b2021a (61 observations between 4th November 2020 and 19th July 2021) and 2021b2022a (69 observations between 16th November 2021 and 10th June 2022). The S/N ranges between 51 and 151, with a mean of 125, and the mean airmass is 1.3. The mean noise level in Stokes V is $1.4 \cdot 10^{-4}$.

CN Leo was observed for 169 nights between April 2019 and June 2022, spanning a period of ~ 1150 d. The time series is split in four epochs: 2019a (19 observations between 16th April and 21st June 2019), 2019b2020a (37 observations between 31st October 2019 and 10th June 2020) and 2020b2021a (63 observations between 31st October 2020 and 2nd July 2021) 2021b2022a (45 observations between 16th November 2021 and 10th June 2022). The S/N ranges between 40 and 146, with a mean of 111, and the average airmass is 1.3. Again, February 2019 observations were excluded. The mean noise level in Stokes V is $2.3 \cdot 10^{-4}$.

EV Lac was observed for 163 nights between September 2019 and November 2021, spanning a period of ~ 800 d. I split the time series in three epochs: 2019b (35 obs between 11th September and 13th December 2019), 2020b2021a (67 observations between 27th July 2020 and 8th January 2021) and 2021b (61 observations between 20th June 2021 and 22nd November 2021). We record a S/N at 1650 nm per spectral element between 31 and 165, with a mean of 130, and an average airmass of 1.2. The mean noise level in Stokes V is $1.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$.

V374 Peg was observed 55 times over nine nights in August 2021. The S/N at 1650 nm per spectral element is between 43 and 95, with a mean of 81 and an average airmass of 1.23. The mean LSD noise of the Stokes V profiles is $2 \cdot 10^{-4}$, while the peak-to-peak amplitude is $1.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$. The SPIRou data set of V374 Peg used for this analysis is the same as the one described in Sec. 3.3. The entire journal of observations of the observations for all stars can be found in Appendix C.

5.2.3 Optical

To study long-term trends, we included archival optical observations collected with ESPaDOnS and Narval. The raw data was reduced with LIBRE-ESPRIT (Donati et al. 1997), and the continuum nor-

malised spectra were retrieved from PolarBase (Petit et al. 2014). The extraction of the polarimetric information was performed with LSD similarly to the near-infrared, but using an optical VALD mask containing 3240 lines in range 350-1080 nm and with depths larger than 40% the continuum level, following Bellotti et al. (2021) and as in Chapter 2. The number of lines already accounts for the removal of the following wavelength intervals, which are affected by telluric lines or in the vicinity of $H\alpha$.

For AD Leo, I used 56 observations collected between 2006 and 2016. I also included six new observations taken in November 2019 with ESPaDOnS for CFHT program 19BC06, PI A. Lavail. They are contemporaneous to the SPIRou ones for the same period, hence enabling us to study the dependence of the measured magnetic field strength on the wavelength domain employed (see Sec. 5.3.1). For DS Leo, there are 94 observations between 2006 and 2014. For CN Leo, I have four observations in 2008; since they would not yield substantial additional information, I do not include them in our analysis, but refer back to them when comparisons are possible. For EV Lac, there are 79 observations taken between 2005 and 2016. For V374 Peg, there are 64 observations taken in 2005 and 21 in 2006.

In semester 2021A, I successfully obtained around 120 hour of NEO-Narval observing time to follow-up the stars examined here (except for V374 Peg). The observations are nearly simultaneously to SPIRou, which would allow interesting chromatic studies of activity proxies. However, potential issues during acquisition and reduction occurred, hence the data are not available for analysis at the time of writing.

In the next sections, the observations will be phased with the following ephemeris:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{HJD}_{\text{ADLeo}} &= 2458588.7573 + P_{\text{rot,ADLeo}} \cdot n_{\text{cyc}}, \\
 \text{HJD}_{\text{DSLeo}} &= 2458588.2576 + P_{\text{rot,DSLeo}} \cdot n_{\text{cyc}}, \\
 \text{HJD}_{\text{CNLeo}} &= 2459158.1118 + P_{\text{rot,CNLeo}} \cdot n_{\text{cyc}}, \\
 \text{HJD}_{\text{EVLac}} &= 2458738.0805 + P_{\text{rot,EVLac}} \cdot n_{\text{cyc}}, \\
 \text{HJD}_{\text{V374Peg}} &= 2459440.7902 + P_{\text{rot,V374Peg}} \cdot n_{\text{cyc}},
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{5.1}$$

where we separately used the first SPIRou observation for each star as reference, $P_{\text{rot},i}$ is the stellar rotation period of the i -th star, and n_{cyc} represents the rotation cycle (tabulated in Appendix C).

5.3 Evident long-term evolution

5.3.1 AD Leo

The magnetic field geometry of AD Leo was initially studied by Morin et al. (2008b). They used Narval data collected in 2007 and 2008 to reconstruct ZDI maps, and found a strong (mean field $B_{\text{mean}} = 200$ G), axisymmetric, poloidal and dipolar configuration. Over a time span of 1 yr, i.e. between 2007 and 2008, the topology remained stable.

Later, Lavail et al. (2018) examined ESPaDOnS data from 2012 and 2016, and showed an evolution of the field in the form of a global weakening (about 20%) accompanied by a small-scale enhancement. The latter was quantified by a decrease in magnetic filling factor f_V , from 13% to 7% (see Sec. A). In other words, the local-scale field is more concentrated in certain regions, and therefore intensifies.

The large-scale magnetic polarity has remained stable since spectropolarimetric observations of AD Leo have been initiated (Lavail et al. 2018). The topology is an axial dipole, whose visible pole corresponds to negative radial field (magnetic field vector directed towards the star).

From unpolarised spectra and spectrum synthesis to model Zeeman broadening, strong fields between 2.6-3.3 kG were reported (e.g., Saar 1994; Shulyak et al. 2017, 2019).

Longitudinal field

I measured the line-of-sight component of the magnetic field integrated over the stellar disk (B_l) for all the available observations, in optical (2006–2019) and near-infrared (2019–2020), following the prescription of Donati et al. (1997) reported in Eq. 2.8. For the near-infrared and optical Stokes profiles, the adopted LSD normalisation wavelength and Landé factor are 1700 nm and 1.2144, and 700 nm and

Figure 5.2: Generalized Lomb-Scargle periodogram of the entire SPIRou B_l time series for AD Leo. To prevent perturbations in the period analysis, a long-term variation has been filtered out beforehand. The most significant peak (FAP < 0.01%) is at 2.23 ± 0.01 d, consistently with the literature. The window function of the time series is mirrored with respect to the x axis, to show spurious aliases due to observational cadence and sampling.

Figure 5.3: Evolution of the longitudinal magnetic field of AD Leo. Left: full time series of measurements between 2006 and 2020 with ESPaDOnS, Narval and SPIRou. The shape of the data points corresponds to the wavelength domain, optical (circles) or near-infrared (pluses), and the colour to the epoch in which the observations were performed. Right: SPIRou time series split in four epochs phase-folded according to Eq. 5.1. The least-square sine fit corresponding to [Stibbs \(1950\)](#) formula, to assess the change in magnetic obliquity, is shown as dashed lines. The six ESPaDOnS observations taken in 2019 are plotted as pink circles.

1.1420, respectively. In accordance with the fact that near-infrared lines are broader than optical ones, the integration was carried out within $\pm 50 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ from line centre in the former case and $\pm 30 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ in the latter case, to include the absorption ranges of both Stokes I and V profiles.

As mentioned in Sec. 1.4.1, we know that B_l is a useful diagnostic of surface magnetic features, whose appearance on the visible disk is modulated at the stellar rotation period ([Folsom et al. 2016](#); [Hébrard et al. 2016](#); [Fouqué et al. 2023](#)). I applied a Generalised Lomb-Scargle periodogram ([Zechmeister & Kürster 2009](#)) to the entire time series as well as the individual epochs, and found a sharp peak at

Table 5.2: Best fit values of the polar field and obliquity of Stibb’s formula obtained for optical and near-infrared epochs.

VIS	2006	2007	2008	2012	2016
B_p [G]	-868 ± 20	-842 ± 21	-873 ± 15	-736 ± 19	-555 ± 10
β [°]	13 ± 6	12 ± 4	26 ± 1	7 ± 4	12 ± 1
NIR	2019a	2019b	2020a	2020b	
B_p [G]	-814 ± 17	-882 ± 22	-828 ± 55	-923 ± 70	
β [°]	3 ± 4	23 ± 2	37 ± 4	59 ± 2	

2.23 ± 0.01 d with $FAP < 0.01\%$. The periodogram structure at longer periods is likely due to aliases of the observation window. The results are illustrated in Fig. 5.2, and were used in Carmona et al. (2023, in press), to corroborate further the absence of a co-rotating planetary companion. When the periodogram is applied on the four epochs separately, we observe that the significance of the peak at 2.23 d increases over time, going from $FAP > 1\%$ to $< 0.1\%$. This is not related to a different noise content in the epochs, as the error bar on B_l is consistent throughout the time series. Rather, something occurred in the latest epochs so that the rotational modulation of B_l is more evident, making it a more reliable tracer of stellar rotation period. This is most likely related to the axisymmetry (e.g. obliquity) of the magnetic field with respect to the rotation axis of the star.

The list of measurements is reported in Appendix C. The values are of constant sign (negative), which is expected for a an axial dipole observed nearly pole-on as AD Leo (Morin et al. 2008b; Lavail et al. 2018). The near-infrared measurements range between -263 and -46 G, with an average of -179 G and a median error bar of 15 G. The optical measurements range between -297 and -155 G, with an average of -233 G and a median error bar of 10 G. The lower error bar is likely due to the narrower velocity range over which the optical measurements are performed, since less noise is introduced in Eq. 2.8.

The temporal evolution of B_l is presented in Fig. 5.3, where we note a secular weakening of the field strength over 14 yr, with an oscillation between 2016 and 2019 followed by a rapid decrease in strength (in absolute value). We also note that the intra-epoch dispersion increases for the last two epochs. By phase-folding the near-infrared data at P_{rot} , we observe a systematic increase in the rotational modulation towards 2020b, meaning that the axisymmetry level of the field has likely decreased. To evaluate this, I used the formalism outlined by Stibbs (1950) and Preston (1967) to model the phase variations of the longitudinal field, for a predominantly-dipolar magnetic configuration. The idea is to fit a sine trend parametrised by the polar magnetic field strength of the dipole B_p and the obliquity between magnetic and rotation axes, β . The results are listed in Table 5.2, where I excluded the six optical observations in November 2019 because of their poor coverage, which leads to a less reliable sine fit. Nevertheless, they are compatible with the 2019b fit curve.

Is B_l chromatic?

In Sec. 1.4.1, I mentioned that the radial velocity signal associated to temperature inhomogeneities is chromatic, i.e. it weakens towards longer wavelengths following the decrease of spot-photosphere temperature contrast. However, the Zeeman effect adds complexity to this reasoning, because the phenomenon increases with wavelength (see Sec. 4.1.1). Such effect becomes increasingly important with the activity level of the star, since the number of spots would be correspondingly larger (Reinhold et al. 2019). As a result, the impact of stellar magnetic activity on radial velocity is not easily disentangled in some cases (Reiners et al. 2013). Here, I investigate whether B_l features chromatic properties as well, owing to potentially distinct contributions to the magnetic field strength by different parts of the spectrum, which can then be used to facilitate the modelling of stellar activity.

AD Leo is an interesting target in this sense, because it is a fast rotator observed nearly pole-on. If AD Leo has a polar spot underlying the negative region of the axial dipole (the one we observe

Optical

Near-Infrared

Figure 5.4: Series of Stokes profiles computed with wavelength-base sub-masks. The wavelength intervals of the line subsets are: [350,390], [390,430], [430,480], [480,550], [550,650], [650,1100], [950,1100], [1100,1400], [1400,1600], [1600,1800], [1800,2500] nm. Every panel displays Stokes I (top), V (middle) and N (bottom) for each line subset and vertical dashed lines indicate the adjusted velocity range over which B_l was estimated. The optical profiles are obtained by stacking the ESPaDOnS observations from 2019, and the near-infrared ones from SPIRou 2019b time series, for each panel.

at all times), then the spot chromaticity may eventually reflect in wavelength-dependent longitudinal magnetic field values.

In practice, we use the contemporaneous SPIRou and ESPaDOnS acquired in 2019 and we compute LSD profiles using wavelength-based sub-masks over finer intervals than those of Chapter 2, to prevent large wavelength selections to blur any chromatic effect. Including both optical and near-infrared domains, we considered 11 subsets of lines in the following wavelength ranges: [350,390], [390,430], [430,480], [480,550], [550,650], [650,1100], [950,1100], [1100,1400], [1400,1600], [1600,1800], [1800,2500] nm. The [650,1100] and [950, 1100] nm ranges represent the red end of ESPaDOnS spectra and the blue

Figure 5.5: Test on B_l measurements chromaticity. Shown are B_l measurements obtained with wavelength-based sub-masks in near-infrared (pluses) and optical (circles). The horizontal black lines indicate the values of B_l computed with the full atomic masks and the vertical dashed line separates arbitrarily optical from near-infrared measurements. For visualisation purposes, the [350, 390] nm wavelength bin is not shown since it leads to an outlier data point at around -1 kG, and the [390, 430] nm bin yields a value at -750 G so it is indicated with a downward arrow. Overall, no chromatic trend emerges from the data.

end of SPIRou spectra, respectively. The number of lines used varies between 100 and 1000 in the optical, and between 120 and 300 in the near-infrared (see Fig. 5.4). In addition, we compute LSD using a 50-lines mask in the overlapping wavelength region of ESPaDOnS and SPIRou spectra ([950,1050] nm).

To enhance the S/N of the Stokes I and V profiles and estimate B_l more precisely, the profiles obtained with a specific line list subset and belonging to the same epoch were co-added. This is reasonable considering the marginal amplitude variation in 2019 and the unchanged polarity of Stokes V . The longitudinal field was then computed with Eq. 2.8 using the specific normalisation wavelength and Landé factor of each line subset, and adapting the velocity integration range according to the width of the co-added Stokes V profile.

From Fig. 5.5, we observe no clear chromaticity. The distribution of field strength is flat around -200 G with a scatter of 20 G. Such dispersion is mainly due to LSD computations with a low number of lines, implying Stokes shapes more sensitive to variations in individual lines, blends and residuals of telluric correction. For the same reason, some profiles appear deformed and lead to evident outliers (see Fig.5.4). For the [350,390] nm sub-mask, the ratio of χ^2 (with respect to a flat line at zero) inside and outside ± 20 km s^{-1} is close to 1, for both Stokes V and N . This means that with this wavelength selection the Zeeman signature is not distinguishable from noise. In addition, the Stokes I is also featuring a noisy profile.

The case of [390,430] nm leads to a field value of -750 G, despite the Stokes profiles do not show a particular deformation. There is a small spurious signal in Stokes N in this case, identified by a χ^2 ratio inside and outside Stokes profile of more than 2. This issue was already addressed by Folsom et al. (2016), who attributed the signal to an imperfect background subtraction affecting the blue orders of NARVAL. However, such small signal cannot account for the significant difference in B_l compared to

Figure 5.6: Simulation of the dependence of the magnetic field strength on limb darkening when zero (left) and realistic (right) noise is included. A monotonic decreasing (in absolute value) trend is observed from large (optical) to small (near-infrared) coefficient values, but the effect is small, and negligible compared to noise.

the other sub-masks. We tentatively attributed this behaviour to an imprecise continuum normalisation of the spectra, likely due to a challenging identification of the continuum level in the blue part of the spectrum, where M dwarfs feature forests of spectral lines. The effect is a smaller depth (and equivalent width) of the Stokes I profile relative to the other cases, and it artificially increases the value of the field (in absolute value). Overall, although the [350,390] and [390,430] nm bins contain more than half of the lines in the optical mask, their weight in the LSD computation is small (Kochukhov et al. 2010) making their effect in the computation of B_l with the full mask negligible.

I repeated the same exercise for other SPIRou epochs of AD Leo and found no apparent trend as well, the only difference being 2020b data points shifting upwards because of the field global weakening. A possible implication of the lack of a chromatic trend may be the absence of a polar spot for AD Leo. This would be consistent with other rapidly-rotating M dwarfs like HK Aqr and V374 Peg (Barnes et al. 2004; Morin et al. 2008a).

Previous studies of the Sun have shown that the magnetic field strength measured in individual lines varies significantly (Demidov et al. 2008; Demidov & Balthasar 2012), and differences between optical and near-infrared domains have unveiled a dependence of the field strength on atmospheric height: the field increases while going towards deeper internal layers (Zayer et al. 1989; Solanki 1993). For other stars, Valenti et al. (1995) reported a chromatic difference in magnetic field strength for the moderately active K dwarf ϵ Eri, but attributed its origin to incomplete modelling of the spectral lines used for the Zeeman broadening analysis. No wavelength dependence of the field strength was reported more recently, neither for ϵ Eri (Petit et al. 2021) nor for T Tauri stars (Finocietty et al. 2021). My results on AD Leo are consistent with such conclusions, as well as with the robustness of B_l with respect to the line selections described in Chapter 2.

An additional source of chromaticity for B_l values may come from limb darkening. This radial gradient in stellar brightness over the visible disk can be approximated as a linear function of the angle between the line of sight and the normal to a surface element (θ)

$$\frac{I}{I_0} = 1 - \varepsilon(1 - \cos \theta), \quad (5.2)$$

where I_0 is the brightness at disk centre ($\theta = 0^\circ$) and ε is the limb darkening coefficient. Claret & Bloemen (2011) showed that ε decreases with wavelength, being 0.7 in V band and 0.3 in H band. The linear limb darkening law in Eq.5.2 is the one implemented in the ZDI reconstruction (see Appendix A).

Owing to the stronger limb darkening in optical than in near-infrared, there is the possibility of additional polarity cancellation in the latter domain, which would lead to weaker field measurements. For the specific case of AD Leo, the low stellar inclination makes the equator appear at the limb and near-infrared observations would be more sensitive to this region. In particular, the sign of large-scale

Figure 5.7: Test on the vertical gradient of the field strength between simultaneous SPIRou and ES-PaDOnS observations. The longitudinal magnetic field measurements obtained with subsets based on \mathcal{E} of the near-infrared (squares) and optical (circles) masks. The horizontal black lines indicate the values of B_l computed with the full masks, near-infrared around -100 G and optical around -250 G. Formal error bars are within the data point size. There is no clear trend with \mathcal{E} , and thus with line formation depth.

dipolar magnetic field lines exiting the pole would cancel out more with those at equator, compared to optical observations.

To verify this, I 1) linearly interpolated the limb darkening coefficients in [Claret & Bloemen \(2011\)](#) at the wavelengths examined for the temperature inhomogeneity test (see Fig. 5.5), 2) synthesised Stokes profiles for the same coefficients assuming an axisymmetric dipole of 1 kG seen pole-on (akin to AD Leo in 2019a), and 3) computed the associated field values with Eq. 2.8. The results are illustrated in Fig. 5.6 when adopting infinite and realistic S/N in the synthetic Stokes profiles. I observe a small (7%) weakening of the field from optical to near-infrared, which is most likely overwhelmed by the noise in real observations.

For completeness, I tested whether different line selections could be used to probe distinct layers of magnetic field strength ([Afram & Berdyugina 2019](#)), potentially revealing something similar to the vertical gradient of field strength on the Sun ([Zayer et al. 1989](#); [Solanki 1993](#)). I use the line excitation potential (\mathcal{E}) as a proxy for formation depth ([Grossmann-Doerth 1994](#); [Gurtovenko & Sheminova 2015](#)), and build sub-masks for distinct intervals. The full masks were split using increments of 0.5 in \mathcal{E} , which resulted in 13 and 8 subsets for the near-infrared and optical mask. This way, the progressive average \mathcal{E} of the subset corresponds to a deeper layer of formation.

No clear trend emerges (see Fig. 5.7), neither for the near-infrared mask nor for the optical one. Moreover, spectral lines belonging to different wavelength domains but sharing the same \mathcal{E} bin produce similar B_l values for some bins, whereas they are discrepant for others. The presence of evident outliers in the plot (like a positive B_l) is due to the computation of B_l with Stokes I and V profiles whose shape is completely dominated by noise and blends.

FWHM of Stokes I

Near-infrared lines of stars with intense fields and low equatorial velocity ($v_{\text{eq}} \sin(i)$) such as AD Leo offer the possibility to study variations of their width induced by Zeeman effect (see Sec. 4.2.3). For

Table 5.3: Comparison of a constant line vs a sine fit for the FWHM phase variations. The columns are: 1) subset of the time series, 2) line list used in LSD computation, 3) mean value of FWHM, 4) mean error bar on FWHM, 5) dispersion of the data set, 6) RMS (Root Mean Square) residual of a constant line fit equal to the average of the data set, 7) reduced χ^2 of the constant fit, 8) RMS residual of a sine fit at the stellar rotation period, 9) reduced χ^2 of the sine fit.

Epoch	Mask	Mean [km s ⁻¹]	Mean Error [km s ⁻¹]	STD [km s ⁻¹]	RMS _{const} [km s ⁻¹]	$\chi^2_{r,const}$	RMS _{sine} [km s ⁻¹]	$\chi^2_{r,sine}$
2019a	default	19	0.29	0.40	0.40	1.8	0.39	2.0
	$g_{\text{eff}} > 1.2$	23	0.46	1.16	1.16	6.9	1.13	8.0
2019b	default	21	0.41	0.63	0.63	2.3	0.62	2.5
	$g_{\text{eff}} > 1.2$	27	0.84	1.77	1.77	6.7	1.71	6.9
2020a	default	21	0.41	0.68	0.68	3.2	0.61	3.4
	$g_{\text{eff}} > 1.2$	27	0.82	2.47	2.47	12.2	2.29	13.3
2020b	default	19	0.30	0.47	0.47	3.0	0.47	3.4
	$g_{\text{eff}} > 1.2$	22	0.46	0.83	0.83	5.3	0.79	7.3

the Sun, the rotationally-modulated broadening correlates with the azimuthal distribution of the unsigned small-scale magnetic flux, a useful diagnostic for stellar activity radial velocity contamination, as shown by [Haywood et al. \(2020\)](#). In the stellar context, [Klein et al. \(2021\)](#) adopted a selection of magnetically sensitive lines for AU Mic and saw a correspondence in the variations of RV and FWHM of the Stokes I profiles at the stellar rotation period. This confirmed the sensitivity of the FWHM to the distortions induced by magnetic regions on the stellar surface. In other words, the FWHM of Stokes I can in principle be used as a first approximation of a detailed radiative transfer modelling of Zeeman broadening in individual lines.

I performed a similar analysis to [Klein et al. \(2021\)](#) to connect modulations of the FWHM with variations of the large-scale field. Least-Squares Deconvolution was applied on the SPIRou near-infrared data using a mask of 417 lines characterised by $g_{\text{eff}} > 1.2$ (see Sec. 2.5.1). The rotational phase variations of the FWHM when adopting the full and high- g_{eff} masks are listed in Table 5.3. I inspect whether they are more compatible with a sine fit or a constant fit equal to the mean of the data set. In all cases, there is no clear rotational modulation of the data points, as the sine fit does not provide a better description of the variations than the constant fit. More quantitatively, the reduced χ^2 increases when modelling the variations with a sine function, even though the increase is not statistically significant because the values are within the standard deviation of χ^2 , i.e. $\sqrt{2\nu}$ ([Press et al. 1992](#)). The RMS of the residuals to the sine fit is decreased by at most 5% compared to the constant fit. Therefore, the observed variations are attributable to dispersion, as illustrated in Fig. 5.8. We observed that the FWHM is systematically larger in all epochs for the high- g_{eff} mask, as a consequence of the linear dependence of Zeeman effect to g_{eff} , and the dispersion is between 1.8 and 3.0 times larger. This makes the FWHM a good tracer of the Zeeman effect.

From Fig. 5.8, we also noticed an evident long-term evolution of the mean FWHM, which was already observed for Sun-like stars, e.g. ξ Boo ([Morgenthaler et al. 2012](#)). When using the default mask, the mean FWHM oscillated from 19 km s⁻¹ in 2019a to 21 km s⁻¹ in 2019b and 2020a, and back to 19 km s⁻¹ in 2020b. As expected, such oscillation is enhanced when considering the magnetically sensitive lines and goes from 23 km s⁻¹ in 2019a to 27 km s⁻¹ in 2019b and 2020a, and back to 22 km s⁻¹ in 2020b. I performed the same analysis with low-Landé factor lines ($g_{\text{eff}} < 1.2$, 406 lines) and noticed no appreciable variation of the mean FWHM, since it remained stable at ~ 15 km s⁻¹. The evolution seen for the default mask and high-Landé factor lines has a moderate correlation (Pearson R coefficient of 0.5) with the variations of the epoch-averaged B_l , meaning that the large-scale field (measured by B_l) and the total field (dominated by small-scales, and measured by the FWHM) evolve in a correlated way. This is consistent with [Donati et al. \(2023, submitted\)](#) recent analysis on AU Mic.

By color-coding the data points in Fig. 5.8 according to the date of observations and for the high-

Figure 5.8: Phase variations of the FWHM, folded at a stellar rotation period of 2.23 d. The data sets are computed with the default (black), low- g_{eff} (purple), and high- g_{eff} (either yellow or color-coded by rotational cycles). Each panel represents a near-infrared (2019a, 2019b, 2020a, and 2020b) or optical (2007, 2008, 2012, and 2016) epoch. From all epochs considered and across the two wavelength domains, we notice an evident rotational modulation at the stellar rotation period only in 2007 and 2008. Furthermore, there is a long-term oscillation of the mean FWHM.

Figure 5.9: Secular evolution of the epoch-averaged FWHM of Stokes I for AD Leo. The scale on the left refers to optical data, while on the right to the near-infrared ones, and the colours indicate the use of different masks similarly to Fig. 5.8. Both optical (circles) and near-infrared (pluses) observations feature a long-term variation, which is enhanced (quenched) when using magnetically sensitive (insensitive) lines. Note that the optical data point of 2019 falls behind the near-infrared ones when using magnetically sensitive lines.

Landé factor lines, we can investigate whether the scatter is due to short-term variability. However, this exercise does not reveal particular behaviour, since the scatter is comparable over subsequent rotational cycles. We observe different FWHM values for a few data points located at the same rotational phase, but belonging to distinct rotational cycles, indicating that intrinsic variability likely occurred in-between cycles.

The FWHM analysis was also carried out on the ESPaDOnS and Narval data between 2006 and 2019. When using low- g_{eff} lines, the mean width of Stokes I is reasonably stable around 9.7 km s^{-1} , stressing their potential for precise radial velocity measurements. The difference of the mean FWHM between low- g_{eff} lines in optical and near-infrared can be attributed to lines that have non-zero Landé factor (the average is around 0.9 in both cases). Indeed, the quadratic differential broadening between the two domains is $\sqrt{\text{FWHM}_{\text{NIR}}^2 - \text{FWHM}_{\text{VIS}}^2} = 11.4 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ which, by virtue of Eq. 4.1, corresponds to a magnetic field modulus of 2.5 kG for a line at 1700 nm with $g_{\text{eff}}=0.96$ (the normalisation values of the mask). Such value of magnetic field modulus is 0.5 kG lower than what reported typically in the literature, but still reasonably consistent (Saar 1994; Shulyak et al. 2017, 2019), indicating that the difference in width between optical and near-infrared is mostly accounted by the magnetic field.

The full (high- g_{eff}) mask yields a mean value at 10 km s^{-1} (12 km s^{-1}) between 2006 and 2012, which then increases to 11 km s^{-1} (13 km s^{-1}) in 2016 and 2019. Such long-term evolution is only moderate compared to the one seen in the near-infrared time series. The entire evolution is illustrated in Fig. 5.9. I repeated the quadratic differential broadening computation, but this time using high- and low- g_{eff} lines. The values of the field modulus fall between 3.9-4.7 in optical (with a peak at 5.6 kG in 2016) and 3.6-4.7 kG in near-infrared, larger than the estimates in the literature (Kochukhov 2021), but following the same trend as in Fig. 5.9.

As opposed to the near-infrared phase-folded time series, we observe rotational modulation for

Figure 5.10: Correlation between FWHM and B_l (in absolute value) of AD Leo for optical epochs at which there is an evident rotational modulation of both quantities. We observe a negative correlation in 2007, which increases from low- to high-Landé factor lines. In 2008, the default mask and the high-Landé factor lines show a positive correlation instead.

specific epochs, i.e. in 2007 and 2008 (see Fig. 5.8) and more or less enhanced depending on the adopted line mask. Quantitatively, the χ_r^2 for a sine fit is 0.8 and 0.5, whereas it is 3.3 and 2.0 for a constant fit when using the full mask for the two epochs, respectively. When using the high-Landé factor lines, the χ_r^2 improvement in using a sine model is similar. For the remaining optical epochs, the modulation is either overwhelmed by dispersion (as in 2016) or the number of data points is too low to capture it. A possible explanation for observing rotational modulation of the FWHM in optical but not in near-infrared could be given by the larger contribution of the Zeeman effect in the latter domain, to the point that lines start to split and modulation of the FWHM is ultimately blurred by dispersion. One way to show this would involve the generation of a set of synthetic Stokes profiles with ZDI for an input magnetic topology, and the inspection of the dependence of the FWHM modulation on the field intensity. Such analysis is currently in progress.

Finally, I investigated the correlation between the FWHM of Stokes I and the longitudinal field values, to investigate further the connection between small- and large-scale field. Indeed, we tend to assume that the small-scale field (to which we are insensitive with polarised light, see Sec. 4.2.2) scales with the large-scale field, but we have limited knowledge on this aspect. Here, I used the optical epochs in which rotational modulation is evident for both quantities (i.e. 2007 and 2008). Fig. 5.10 illustrates that FWHM and $|B_l|$ featured a correlation in 2007, and the associated Pearson R coefficient decreased from 0.87 to 0.35 when using high- and low- g_{eff} lines, respectively. This is the expected behaviour, i.e. spectral lines are wider when the field is stronger and the correlation is enhanced when magnetically sensitive lines are adopted. In 2008 the situation is less obvious, because the default mask and the high- g_{eff} lines exhibit an anti-correlation, hence an inverse trend with respect to 2007. The higher dispersion of both FWHM and B_l values when adopting high- g_{eff} lines may be the reason behind the blurring of the positive correlation.

In conclusion, our analyses confirms that the FWHM is capable of tracing secular changes in the total, unsigned magnetic field, which could be used to better understand stellar activity jitter. Activity-mitigating techniques would benefit from this information even for low-inclination stars such as AD Leo, for which the phase modulation of the radial velocity jitter is more difficult to constrain. At the same time, the analysis highlights the presence of rotational modulation that is captured only in certain epochs in optical domain, and that is drowned by dispersion and/or short-term variability otherwise. Finally, the intra-epoch correlation between FWHM and B_l (associated to rotational modulation) is not always detectable, but varies from epoch to epoch, which was also reported by (Morgenthaler et al. 2012).

Figure 5.11: Full SPIRou and 2019 ESPaDOnS time series of Stokes V profiles of AD Leo normalised by the unpolarised continuum intensity. Two panels are present for 2019a (top left), 2019b (top right), one panel for 2019 in optical (bottom left) and 2020a (bottom middle) and two panels for 2020b (bottom right). In all panels, both the observed profiles (black) and Unno-Rachkovsky models (red) are shown. They are shifted vertically for visualisation purposes, and their associated rotational cycle is reported on the right (see Eq. 5.1). A remarkable feature is the increased intermittency of the profiles amplitude towards 2020a and 2020b relative to the previous epochs, suggesting an evolution of the magnetic field tilt.

Zeeman-Doppler Imaging

I applied ZDI to the SPIRou and 2019 ESPaDOnS time series of Stokes V profiles to recover the large-scale magnetic field at the surface of AD Leo. A description of the technique is presented in Sec. 4.2.2, while the implemented algorithm can be found in Appendix A. I used the ZDIPY code described in Folsom

Figure 5.12: Reconstructed ZDI maps in flattened polar view of AD Leo for the SPIRou and 2019 ESPaDOnS time series. The columns correspond to the epochs examined, from the left: 2019a, 2019b, 2019 optical, 2020a, and 2020b. In each column, the radial (top), azimuthal (middle) and meridional (bottom) components of the magnetic field vector are displayed. The radial ticks are located at the rotational phases when the observations were collected, while the concentric circles represent different stellar latitudes: -30° , $+30^\circ$ and $+60^\circ$ (dashed lines) and equator (solid line). The colour bar range is set by the maximum (in absolute value) of the magnetic field and illustrates the positive (red) and negative (blue) polarity for each epoch.

et al. (2018) with my implementation of Unno-Rachkovsky’s solutions to polarised radiative transfer equations in a Milne-Eddington atmosphere (Unno 1956; Rachkovsky 1967; Landi Degl’Innocenti & Landolfi 2004) and of the filling factor formalism outlined in Morin *et al.* (2008b). A comparison with the results obtained under the weak-field approximation are given in Appendix A.

The input parameters of AD Leo are $i = 20^\circ$, $v_{\text{eq}} \sin(i) = 3 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, $P_{\text{rot}} = 2.23 \text{ d}$, and solid body rotation ($d\Omega=0 \text{ rad d}^{-1}$ in Eq. A.33). The line model parameters, i.e. η_0 , β , w_T , and a (see Appendix A for more details), are optimised via χ^2 minimisation applied to the median profile for the epoch examined. I then adopted a linear limb darkening coefficient in H band of 0.3 and V band of 0.7 (Claret & Bloemen 2011). I set the maximum degree of the harmonic expansion $l_{\text{max}} = 8$ (considering the low $v_e \sin(i)$, Morin *et al.* 2008b) and allowed an entropy weighting scheme proportional to l during ZDI inversion, to favour simple geometries as in Folsom *et al.* (2018) and Lavail *et al.* (2018). The Stokes V time series of SPIRou and 2019 ESPaDOnS data are shown in Fig. 5.11.

For the 2019a, 2019b, 2020a and 2020b epochs, I fit the Stokes V profiles to a χ_r^2 level of 1.2, 1.0, 1.1, and 1.1 from an initial value of 10.3, 15.8, 14.7, and 8.5, respectively. For the ESPaDOnS 2019 time series, I fit down to $\chi_r^2 = 2.5$ from an initial value of 156.3. These values are consistent with Morin *et al.* (2008b). The higher target χ_r^2 for the optical data set stems from a higher S/N of the observations, as can be seen from Fig. 5.11. I attempted to merge the 2019b and 2020a epochs and reconstruct a single map, since they are separated by the shortest time gap. The quality of the final model is deteriorated ($\chi_r^2=1.3$) with respect to the two epochs separately, but the corresponding map and magnetic energies are consistently recovered, so I kept 2019b and 2020a data separate.

Fig. 5.11 highlights how the near-infrared Stokes V profiles manifest structures and stochastic variability in both lobes. This is not extended in the continuum, since the residuals with respect to the mean profile are compatible with the noise level and they are not rotationally modulated. The presence of such variability was already suggested by the phase-folded variations in B_l (Fig. 5.3), as some observations featured a departure from a pure rotational modulation. While our ZDI model is capable of describing the general shape of Stokes V profiles, it is limited at reproducing the structures and at capturing all the

Figure 5.13: Evolution of the magnetic field obliquity with respect to the stellar rotation axis. Values estimated from Stibb’s formula (see Sec. 5.3.1) using optical and near-infrared data are illustrated as circles and pluses, color-coded by epoch, whereas values from ZDI are shown as diamonds and crosses. The y axis is expressed in degrees of colatitude. Both approaches show an evident and consistent trend in terms of their long-term evolution.

information present. These considerations are also valid for optical observations in 2019, as the amplitude of Stokes V is not matched exactly by our ZDI model, and overall translate into an underestimate of the field strength. This motivates further the use of the PCA method described in Sec. 5.3.1, which is a data-driven approach offering a complementary view on the magnetic field evolution.

I am able to constrain the filling factor f_V following a χ^2 minimisation prescription similar to (Petit et al. 2002). I found values oscillating between 9% in 2019a, 16% in 2019b and back to $\sim 11\%$ in the remaining epochs, compatible with Morin et al. (2008b), and larger by 70% than Lavail et al. (2018). This would indicate a weakening of the local small-scale field since 2016, on top of a decrease in large-scale field intensity as seen in the reconstructions (Fig. 5.12).

To find the filling factor f_I , I synthesize a time series of Stokes I profiles for increasing values of f_I (each time re-optimising the line model parameters), and I compute the associated time series of χ^2 values with respect to the observations. By phase-folding the χ^2 time series at P_{rot} for each f_I , I can evaluate when such time series manifests artificial rotational modulation. Indeed, the filling factor f_I regulates the amount of magnetic inhomogeneities on the surface, therefore small f_I values would represent a quiet surface, and the rotational modulation should be minimised (and vice versa when f_I is larger). In our case, we notice that values above 30% progressively deteriorate the fit of the profile core, yielding variability and rotational modulation of the Stokes I profiles. In other words, we would be imposing the same structure of variations to Stokes I and V , that is not observed otherwise (see Sec. 5.3.1). Values of $f_I = 30\%$ are three times larger than f_V , in agreement with (Morin et al. 2008b). Considering that the plausible f_I values are consistent with 0% and no appreciable difference results with $f_I = 30\%$, I adopted $f_I = 0\%$ in the ZDI modelling.

The five maps of surface magnetic flux are shown in Figure 5.12 and their properties are reported in Table 5.4. In all cases, the configuration is predominantly poloidal, storing $>95\%$ of the magnetic energy. The main modes are dipolar and quadrupolar, as they account for 70-90% and 10-15% of the

Figure 5.14: Evolution of the magnetic topology of AD Leo over 14 yr. The time series includes optical ESPaDOnS and Narval data between 2008 and 2019, and near-infrared SPIRou data collected between 2019 and 2020. Field strength, level of axisymmetry and dominant field component (poloidal or toroidal) are encoded with the symbol size, shape, and colour, respectively, and were computed using the Unno-Rachkovsky implementation described in this work for consistency. The topology remained predominantly poloidal and dipolar, while the field strength has decreased over time. The most striking change is a decrease in axisymmetry in the most recent epoch.

magnetic energy. I report a weakening of the mean field strength (B_V) of factor of 1.5 and 2.4 relative to the optical maps reconstructed by [Morin et al. \(2008b\)](#) and [Lavail et al. \(2018\)](#), respectively. The most remarkable feature is the reduction of magnetic energy contained in the axisymmetric mode, going from $> 99\%$ in 2019a to 60% in 2020b, translating into an increase of the dipole obliquity relative to the rotation axis, from 3° to 38° .

We note that the maximum field strength reconstructed with ZDI is between 1.2 and 2.4 times smaller than obtained via Stibb’s formula (see Sec.5.3.1). Likewise, the magnetic field obliquity is underestimated, as illustrated in Fig. 5.13. On one side, this difference stems from the limitation of the ZDI model, since the corresponding Stokes V fit does not encompass the full amplitude of the two lobes for some observations. Moreover, the ZDI algorithm will add magnetic features where they are best visible for a certain rotation phase. For a low inclination system like AD Leo, the pole is seen all the time, hence ZDI will tend to push the magnetic regions toward the pole. On the other side, Stibb’s approach assumes a purely dipolar field, contrarily to our reconstructions (the dipole accounts for 70-90% of the energy). Nevertheless, both approaches allow us to observe an evident evolution of the obliquity, featuring a rapid increase in the most recent epochs.

Finally, I merged the 2019b, 2020a and 2020b data sets and attempted a joint rotation period and differential rotation search following [Petit et al. \(2002\)](#). The results were inconclusive, likely due to the significant evolution of the surface magnetic field between each epoch. In addition, the low inclination with which AD Leo is observed is not optimal for differential rotation searches, since I probe less latitudes at which this phenomenon operates. The fact that the large-scale field is dominated by a single strong spot is also not favourable for differential rotation searches.

The summary of the magnetic field’s evolution is illustrated in Fig. 5.14. I performed ZDI reconstructions also for the archival ESPaDOnS and Narval data for consistency, finding compatible results with [Morin et al. \(2008b\)](#) studies. For the 2012 and 2016 maps reconstructed by [Lavail et al. \(2018\)](#), I retrieve lower field strengths (in agreement with the evolution of B_l). However, they are compatible within a factor of two, which has been already attributed to distinct assumptions and implementations between tomographic inversion codes ([Vidotto et al. 2014](#)).

In conclusion, AD Leo features a globally simple geometry (i.e., predominantly poloidal and dipolar) over 14 yr, with a decreasing strength. Our latest SPIRou observations revealed a clear evolution of the dipole obliquity in the form of a reduced axisymmetry, suggesting a potential dynamo magnetic cycle. These features are indeed compatible with the variations observed by [Sanderson et al. \(2003\)](#) and [Lehmann & Donati \(2022\)](#) for the solar cycle.

Table 5.4: Properties of the magnetic maps for the 2019a, 2019b, 2020a, and 2020b near-infrared epochs and the 2007, 2008, 2012, 2016, and 2019 optical data set of AD Leo. The following quantities are listed: filling factor, mean magnetic strength, maximum magnetic strength, poloidal and toroidal magnetic energy as a fraction of the total one, dipolar, quadrupolar and octupolar magnetic energy as a fraction of the poloidal one, axisymmetric magnetic energy as a fraction of the total one, and tilt of the magnetic axis relative to the rotation axis.

	2007	2008	2012	2016	2019a	2019b	2019 (VIS)	2020a	2020b
f_V	11%	13%	16%	4%	9%	16%	12%	12%	11%
B_{mean} [G]	169.0	176.5	152.2	143.1	111.2	132.3	158.0	115.3	93.4
B_{max} [G]	1083.0	957.8	672.7	469.1	481.2	764.0	577.2	555.1	434.3
B_{pol} [%]	99.2	94.2	95.3	80.0	100.0	99.9	95.0	99.3	98.7
B_{tor} [%]	0.8	5.8	4.7	20.0	0.0	0.1	5.0	0.7	1.3
B_{dip} [%]	72.8	77.0	78.1	83.1	81.3	71.1	81.7	75.7	70.1
B_{quad} [%]	13.9	13.5	16.2	13.1	14.9	19.0	14.6	17.7	21.2
B_{oct} [%]	23.4	3.4	3.9	2.1	2.8	6.2	2.7	4.4	5.9
B_{axisym} [%]	95.5	83.5	88.3	92.6	99.8	94.5	77.0	85.8	58.3
Obliquity [°]	9.5	13.5	12.5	8.5	2.5	12.5	21.5	19.5	38.0

PCA reconstruction

Recently, [Lehmann & Donati \(2022\)](#) showed that fundamental properties of the large-scale field topology can be derived directly from the circularly polarised Stokes V time series using Principal Component Analysis (PCA), without prior assumptions. This data-driven method allows us to qualitatively infer the predominant component of the field topology, as well as its complexity, axisymmetry, and evolution. This analysis was performed in collaboration with Dr. L. T. Lehmann, and only on near-infrared data, because the number of optical 2019 observations is not sufficient.

First, I study the axisymmetric component of the large-scale magnetic field as shown in Fig. 5.15. I compute the mean Stokes V profile (\bar{V}) using the full time series, and I decompose it into its symmetric and antisymmetric components (see [Lehmann & Donati 2022](#))

$$\text{sym} = 0.5 \cdot (\bar{V} + \bar{V}), \quad (5.3)$$

$$\text{antisym} = 0.5 \cdot (\bar{V} - \bar{V}), \quad (5.4)$$

which convey information on the axisymmetric toroidal and poloidal components of the magnetic field, respectively. Working on mean profiles follows the necessity to have high S/N and trace shape changes of the profiles, but in principle the method could be applied to individual lines as well. For AD Leo, the mean profile is primarily antisymmetric, i.e. the axisymmetric field is poloidal. The symmetric part is at the level of the noise, and most likely due to an uneven phase coverage ([Lehmann & Donati 2022](#)).

Second, I study the non-axisymmetric component of the large-scale magnetic field, by subtracting \bar{V} to the time series of observed Stokes V profiles. I indicate the mean-subtracted residuals as \tilde{V} . If we track the amplitude of \tilde{V} over time, we observe that it increases towards 2020a and 2020b, symbolising a less axisymmetric configuration. The idea now is to apply PCA to \tilde{V} . In general, PCA is used to find a coordinate system where most of the variance of the data can be described. The initial variables (\tilde{V} in our case) are then expressed as a linear combination of eigenvectors and associated eigenvalues, and the eigenvectors are sorted according to their importance to the variance. The aim here is to find the contribution of each eigenvector (and therefore magnetic field component) to the observed data and how it evolves with time. For this reason, the mean profile \bar{V} is computed across epochs. This allows us to capture variations of the PCA coefficients (and in particular their amplitude and mean value) epoch-by-epoch. Otherwise, if we compute \bar{V} for each epoch individually, we would lose such information, as the mean of the coefficients would be zero.

The first three eigenvectors and their corresponding coefficients are presented in Fig. 5.16. The first eigenvector displays an antisymmetric shape proportional to the first derivative of the Stokes I profile

Figure 5.15: The mean profile \bar{V} (solid red line) of all Stokes V profiles observed for AD Leo and their antisymmetric (dash dotted blue line) and symmetric (dashed yellow line) parts related to the poloidal and toroidal components of the axisymmetric large-scale field, respectively.

and, together with the associated coefficient, scales mainly with the longitudinal magnetic field (Landi Degl’Innocenti & Landolfi 2004). The second eigenvector shows a more symmetric shape, closer related to the second derivative of the Stokes I profile, and describes the temporal evolution of the Stokes V profiles between the maxima of the longitudinal field. According to Lehmann & Donati (2022), a strongly antisymmetric eigenvector traces the radial component and a symmetric eigenvector the azimuthal component for a dipole-dominated, strongly poloidal field, akin to AD Leo’s. The third eigenvector features an approximately antisymmetric signal, related to the third derivative of the Stokes I profile, and which is detectable due to the high S/N of the data set. The other eigenvectors are dominated by noise. The number of eigenvectors for which we observe a signal correlates with the non-axisymmetry of the magnetic field relative to the rotation axis (Lehmann & Donati 2022). The presence of three eigenvectors allows us to describe the non-axisymmetric field in detail, even though the axisymmetric component is likely to be dominant.

When we look at the coefficients split by epoch, we note a temporal evolution of the non-axisymmetric component of the field (Fig. 5.16). Focusing on the coefficients of the first eigenvector, we see how their rotational modulation increases from zero in 2019a to clearly sinusoidal in 2020b. Moreover, we see sine-like variations from 2019b to 2020b also in the coefficients of the second eigenvector, and in 2020b even in the coefficients of the third. This corroborates the temporal increase magnetic field obliquity relative to the rotation axis. It is important to remember that with PCA we are finding eigenvectors and eigenvalues that can be used in a linear combination to express the mean-subtracted Stokes V profile, \tilde{V} . When the coefficients are mostly zero like in 2019a, the linear combination will lead to an expression of \tilde{V} that is flat around zero. This is consistent with the fact that the *mean-subtracted* Stokes V profile at that epoch is flat at zero.

The extremes of the coefficients associated to the first and second eigenvector, for the same epoch, feature an apparent phase shift of ≈ 0.25 , meaning that the dipolar component has little to no toroidal contribution (Lehmann & Donati 2022). The extremes occur at the same rotational phase throughout the whole observation run, designating a stable pointing phase of the dipole, in agreement with the B_ℓ measurements (see middle panel of Fig. 5.3). For 2019b, 2020a, and 2020b, the maximum of the coefficients variation occurs at a pointing phase of ≈ 0.3 for the northern pole of the dipole, and the sign of the eigenvector implies a negative polarity.

Figure 5.16: Principal Component Analysis applied to the mean-subtracted Stokes V profiles. The first three eigenvectors (top row) and their corresponding coefficients (2nd-4th row) are shown. The vertical line in the eigenvector panels indicates the radial velocity offset for AD Leo, of approximately 12.4 km s^{-1} , while the horizontal dotted line in all panels represents the null line. The coefficients are displayed by epoch: 2019a (2nd row), 2019b (3rd row), 2020a (4th row) and 2020b (5th row). They are phase folded Eq. 5.1 and colour-coded by rotation cycle.

Figure 5.17: The Generalised Lomb-Scargle periodogram for the coefficients of the first three eigenvectors of all the epochs together. Top: periodograms over a 1 - 500 d grid. Bottom: periodograms zoom around the peak at the stellar rotation period. The red, green and yellow dashed lines indicate the False-Alarm-Probability (FAP) of 1 %, 5 %, 10 %, respectively. The stellar rotation period is marked by a vertical dotted line.

The time series of coefficients obtained with the PCA analysis are amenable to periodicity searches, similarly to an activity proxy. Fig. 5.17 shows the Generalised Lomb-Scargle periodogram (Zechmeister & Kürster 2009) of the first three coefficients. For the first two coefficients, I find a significant signal at the stellar rotation period, around 2.23 d. Only for the coefficients of the first eigenvector, the most significant peak is at 123.88 d, which is an alias of the observational sampling.

In conclusion, with the application of the PCA method on the time series of Stokes V , I confirm AD Leo features a secular evolution of the field in the form of an increased obliquity towards the most recent SPIRou observations. As the large-scale field became more non-axisymmetric, the pointing phase of the dipole remained stable.

New DDT observations

The results of our analyses on AD Leo converge toward the same conclusion: the large-scale magnetic field of the star may be approaching polarity reversal. Consequently, re-observing the star even for a handful of nights becomes time-critical, as it may reveal an opposite shape of the Stokes V profiles and an opposite polarity sign. I successfully obtained some Director Discretionary Time (DDT) at CFHT with ESPaDOnS and SPIRou under the program 22BD009 (P.I. Julien Morin). The journal of observations is reported in Appendix C, and consists of four ESPaDOnS visits between 16 and 19 October 2022 (indicated as 2022b VIS) and 19 SPIRou visits between 10 November 2022 and 13 January 2023 (indicated as 2020b2032a).

Looking at the time series of Stokes V profiles in Fig. 5.18, we already notice that the shape of the profile implies a negative polarity, hence the reversal has not occurred yet. The radial velocity shown in Fig. 5.18 is not the correct one because of a known bug in the APERO version with which the DDT observations were reduced, and affecting the correction of the barycentric motion of the Earth (BERV).

Figure 5.18: Stokes V time series for the DDT observations collected in October 2022 with ESPaDOnS (left) and between November 2022 and January 2023 with SPIRou.

Figure 5.19: Time series of B_l measurements updated with the new estimates from the DDT time series of ESPaDOnS and SPIRou data. The format is the same as Fig. 5.3.

I measure the longitudinal magnetic field following the same steps as in Sec. 5.3.1. For the ESPaDOnS

data, the values range between -120 and -180 G, with a median error bar of 9 G, whereas for the SPIRou data they range between -86 G and -251 G, with a median error bar of 24 G. Once again, the larger error bar is explained because the integration to compute B_l is carried out over a larger velocity range in near-infrared than in optical. I then updated the secular evolution plot, as illustrated in Fig. 5.19. It seems that the large-scale magnetic field is gaining strength (in absolute values) compared to the 2021b SPIRou epoch, by approximately 50-100 G, and therefore moving away from a potential polarity reversal. However, we cannot exclude that the magnetic field of the star is featuring a temporary strengthening, similarly to what happened between 2016 and 2019, only to lead to a potential reversal later on. These findings make AD Leo stand out as a particularly interesting target, and therefore additional monitoring is foreseen. As mentioned in Sec. 5.2, I obtained Neo-Narval data in 2021. Such data set will bridge between the latest SPIRou observations in 2021b and the first ESPaDOnS nights in 2022, ultimately shedding more light on the secular evolution of AD Leo's magnetic field.

5.3.2 EV Lac

For EV Lac, Morin et al. (2008b) used optical 2006 and 2007 data collected with ESPaDOnS and Narval, and reconstructed ZDI maps featuring a strong ($B_{\text{mean}} = 500$ G), non-axisymmetric, mostly dipolar field, composed mainly by two magnetic spots of distinct polarity at opposite longitudes. They were able to constrain a differential rotation rate of 1.7 mrad d^{-1} which was consistent with solid body rotation within 3σ . In 2006, the field was globally stronger of about 100 G and the negative magnetic spot was split into two structures, which appeared merged in 2007. A strong magnetic flux in range 3.7-4.2 kG was measured from modelling of Zeeman broadening in unpolarised spectra (e.g., Saar 1994; Shulyak et al. 2017, 2019).

Longitudinal field

I computed B_l using Eq. 2.8 within $\pm 50 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ and $\pm 30 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ from line centre, respectively for near-infrared and optical Stokes profiles, and I adopted 1700 nm, 1.191 and 700 nm, 1.154 as LSD normalisation wavelength and Landé factor. I then applied a Generalised Lomb-Scargle periodogram to the entire time series as well as the individual epochs for all the examined stars. The results are illustrated in Fig. 5.20. The peak at the expected rotation period is unambiguously higher than a FAP of 0.01% when analysing the full time series and also the separate epochs, which emphasises the dominant stellar activity signal. I retrieved a rotation period of 4.36 ± 0.01 d, in agreement with the literature (Morin et al. 2008b).

The long-term evolution of the longitudinal field is presented in Fig. 5.21. The near-infrared measurements lie between 270 and -470 G, with a mean of -50 G and a median error bar of 19 G. In comparison, the optical data have a larger spread in strength, ranging between 380 and -540 G with a mean of -90 G and a median error bar of 16 G. The near-infrared data seem to progressively restore the amplitude of B_l variations with time, after a potential minimum in 2016, making the overall trend look like a beating signal. However, the dearth of data between 2010 and 2019 prevents us from constraining the phenomenon further. I phase-folded the near-infrared data at $P_{\text{rot, EV Lac}} = 4.36$ d and note a clear rotational modulation for the three epochs (see Fig. 5.21). In particular, we observe that the amplitude of variations in 2019b is lower than for the most recent epochs, likely indicating a decrease in field axisymmetry.

FWHM of Stokes I

I computed Stokes I profiles with the full, high- g_{eff} and low- g_{eff} masks, and the associated FWHM to seek for time variability in terms of rotational modulation or long-term variations. The results are reported in Table 5.5 and illustrated in Fig. 5.22.

We note that, analogously to AD Leo (see Sec. 5.3.1), the near-infrared data do not reveal evident rotational modulation, since the change in χ_r^2 between a constant and a sine model is less than one. In some cases, like 2021b using high- g_{eff} lines, the χ_r^2 increases when using a sine model, but it is not

Figure 5.20: Generalised Lomb-Scargle periodogram of the longitudinal field values extracted from the SPIRou near-infrared time series for EV Lac. The format is similar to Fig. 5.37.

Figure 5.21: Evolution of the longitudinal magnetic field of EV Lac. Left: full time series of measurements between 2006 and 2022 with ESPaDOnS, Narval and SPIRou. Right: phase-folded B_l curves obtained with $P_{\text{rot,EVLac}} = 4.36$ d for SPIRou time series split in specific epochs based on target visibility and telescope scheduling. The format is similar to Fig. 5.3.

statistically significant (similarly to some near-infrared epochs of AD Leo). Only in 2020b2021a we observe a χ_r^2 improvement of about 2 when using the sine model for either of the chosen masks, and we correspondingly visualise a hint of rotational modulation especially for the full mask (see Fig. 5.22). If we perform the same exercise for the optical observations, we observe a clear rotational modulation in 2006, 2007, and 2010 (the other epochs have too few data points) for all line selections. Overall, the modulation is evident for the optical epochs and for the near-infrared ones when the default mask is used, as opposed to the near-infrared observations when the high-Landé factor lines are adopted. As for AD Leo, this most likely stems from an enhanced Zeeman effect in the latter case, which increases scatter and dilutes the modulation.

I also checked the correlation between FWHM values for the three different masks and the longitudinal field values, for the optical epochs in which the rotational modulation is evident, similarly to AD Leo. As illustrated in Fig. 5.23, we see a positive correlation for 2006 which increases when adopting low-Landé lines (Pearson $R = 0.19$) to high-Landé lines (Pearson $R = 0.59$). A positive correlation

Figure 5.22: Phase-folded variations of the FWHM for EV Lac, using a stellar rotation period of 4.36 d (see Eq. 5.1). The data sets are computed with the default (black), high- g_{eff} (yellow), and low- g_{eff} (purple) mask for the three SPIRou epochs (2019b, 2020b2021a, and 2021b in first three panels) and three optical epochs (2006, 2007, and 2010 in last three panels). For the near-infrared epochs, the high- g_{eff} data points are color-coded by rotational cycle. The format is similar to Fig. 5.8.

Table 5.5: Comparison of a constant line vs a sine fit for the FWHM phase variations for EV Lac. The columns are the same as Table 5.3.

Epoch	Mask	Mean [km s ⁻¹]	Mean Error [km s ⁻¹]	STD [km s ⁻¹]	RMS _{const} [km s ⁻¹]	$\chi^2_{r,const}$	RMS _{sine} [km s ⁻¹]	$\chi^2_{r,sine}$
2019b	default	22	0.65	1.68	1.68	6.91	1.45	5.89
	$g_{\text{eff}} > 1.2$	29	1.12	4.39	4.39	19.73	4.17	19.66
2020b2021a	default	21	0.44	1.00	1.00	6.18	0.82	4.37
	$g_{\text{eff}} > 1.2$	28	0.87	2.62	2.62	12.91	2.45	10.66
2021b	default	21	0.46	0.98	0.98	4.80	0.90	4.46
	$g_{\text{eff}} > 1.2$	28	0.74	2.57	2.57	13.02	2.44	16.11

Figure 5.23: Correlation between FWHM and $|B_l|$ of EV Lac for optical epochs at which there is an evident rotational modulation of both quantities. We observe a positive correlation in 2006 and 2007 (top left and right panels), which increases from low- to high-Landé factor lines in the first case, while it remains stable in the second case. The situation is analogous for 2010 (bottom panel), but with an anti-correlation, i.e. the FWHM is at maximum when B_l is at minimum.

is also seen in 2007, but its strength does not vary according to the line selection. In 2010, we see an anti-correlation implying that the FWHM maximum lies where $|B_l|$ is at minimum and vice versa, and its strength decreases marginally from low- to high-Landé factor lines. While not straightforward to interpret, these results suggest an underlying complexity in the link between small- and large-scale field, which may not be encapsulated in a simple scaling. Therefore, additional work in this direction is required.

When the near-infrared data points obtained with the high- g_{eff} lines are color-coded by rotational cycle, we do not observe any specific feature, as the dispersion within a certain epoch but over different cycles is comparable. Possible hints of short-term variability can be seen for specific rotational phases

Figure 5.24: Secular evolution of the epoch-averaged FWHM of Stokes I of EV Lac. The y axis is different for optical (left) and near-infrared data (right). The colours indicate the use of different masks similarly to Fig. 5.8. The long-term oscillation of the values is anti-correlated with the B_l variations, and it is enhanced (quenched) when using magnetically sensitive (insensitive) lines.

belonging to distinct rotational cycles, for which the FWHM are significantly different (e.g., phase 0.05 or 0.30 of 2020b2021a epoch).

Both the mean FWHM and the dispersion of a certain epoch are larger for magnetically sensitive lines than the full and the magnetically insensitive lines, owing to a larger influence of the Zeeman effect. The computation of the quadratic differential broadening results in field modulus values of 4.2-4.8 kG (optical) and 4.9-5.4 kG (near-infrared), similar to the estimates reported in the literature (Saar 1994; Shulyak et al. 2017, 2019). Fig. 5.24 illustrates the evolution of the epoch-averaged FWHM using different line masks, but it is not straightforward to extract clear trends from it. The average FWHM from near-infrared observations has decreased from 22 to 21 km s^{-1} for the default mask, while it was stable around 16 km s^{-1} for the low- g_{eff} mask. For high- g_{eff} , there is a slight decrease over time from 29 km s^{-1} to below 28 km s^{-1} . In optical, we observe the same slight oscillation when adopting the three line masks, around 14 km s^{-1} , above 12 km s^{-1} and below 12 km s^{-1} for the high- g_{eff} , default, and low- g_{eff} masks, respectively.

Zeeman-Doppler Imaging

I reconstructed the large-scale magnetic field at the surface of EV Lac with ZDI, for the 2019b, 2020b2021a, and 2021b epochs. The input parameters are $i = 60^\circ$, $v_{\text{eq}} \sin(i) = 4.0 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, $P_{\text{rot}} = 4.36 \text{ d}$, and solid body rotation (Morin et al. 2008b). I set the maximum degree of the harmonic expansion $l_{\text{max}} = 10$, and adopted a linear limb darkening coefficient in H band of 0.3 (Claret & Bloemen 2011).

The Stokes V time series is shown in Fig. 5.25, and cut at $\pm 50 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ from line centre. The profiles are fit down to a χ_r^2 level of 0.9, 1.2, and 1.4 from an initial value of 1.2, 5.0, and 6.5 for 2019b, 2020b2021a, and 2021b, respectively. I am able to constrain filling factor f_V values to be 9% and 19% for 2020b2021a and 2021b, while we cannot for 2019b, hence we set it to 100%. Using either 9% or 19% on 2019b has only marginal effects on the map and the magnetic energy repartition, and the same level of χ^2 is achieved. This could result from a lower effective S/N at this epoch, which prevents us from reliably constraining

Figure 5.25: SPIRou time series of Stokes V profiles of EV Lac normalised by the unpolarised continuum intensity. Top left: 2019b. Top right: 2020b2021a. Bottom: 2021b. The format is the same as Fig. 5.11

f_V . Hence, weak-field approximation could be used equivalently and without invoking the use of f_V . For the two remaining epochs, it is not straightforward to claim an evolution of the small-scale features represented by a change in f_V from 9% to 19%. In fact, if we set f_V to the median value of the two epochs (i.e., 14%), we observe only slight differences in the reconstructed maps: the field is more axisymmetric (additional 4%) and in 2020b2021a the field is also more octupolar (additional 4%). While still limited, a variation of f_V has more impact on 2020b2021a than 2021b because of the stronger constraint on f_V in the former epoch. The optimisation of f_I proceeded analogously as that of AD Leo, i.e. for values up to 30-40% there is not artificial rotational modulation of the χ_r^2 between observations and models, hence we fixed it to 0%.

The maps of the magnetic field and their characteristics are shown in Fig. 5.26 and Table 5.6. In all epochs, most of the magnetic energy is stored in the poloidal ($> 99\%$) and dipolar ($> 65\%$) components, with a substantial contribution from the quadrupolar modes ($> 13\%$). The field is non-axisymmetric, and the axisymmetric energy fraction decreases over time from 25% to 4%. Likewise, the obliquity of the field increases from 53° to 87° , as illustrated in Fig. 5.27. Compared to archival ZDI reconstruction in optical described by Morin et al. (2008b), we observe an even less axisymmetric field, with the negative pole of the predominantly dipolar geometry lying approximately at equator.

Table 5.6: Properties of the magnetic map for EV Lac. The same quantities as Table 5.4 are listed.

	2019b	2020b2021a	2021b
f_V [%]	...	9	19
B_{mean} [G]	56.8	193.8	204.6
B_{max} [G]	143.4	620.0	693.6
B_{pol} [%]	99.7	99.9	96.6
B_{tor} [%]	0.3	0.1	3.4
B_{dip} [%]	64.3	85.5	76.4
B_{quad} [%]	26.3	12.9	17.7
B_{oct} [%]	8.4	1.4	4.9
B_{axisym} [%]	24.8	10.5	4.2
Obliquity [$^\circ$]	53.5	69.5	86.5

Figure 5.26: Reconstructed ZDI maps in flattened polar view of EV Lac for (from left to right) 2019b, 2020b2021a, and 2021b. The format is the same as Fig. 5.12.

The field strength rises from 57 G in 2019b to around 200 G in 2020b2021a and 2021b, following a similar evolution with respect to B_l . The values for 2019b are at least one order of magnitude lower than optical observations (Morin et al. 2008b), partly due to the limitations of the ZDI model in reproducing the shape of the Stokes V profiles. I attempted a differential rotation search but the results were inconclusive.

Figure 5.27: Evolution of the magnetic topology of EV Lac over 15 yr for the time series of near-infrared SPIRou data. The format of the plot is the same as Fig. 5.14.

5.4 Moderate long-term evolution

5.4.1 CN Leo

There is no reconstruction of the magnetic field in the literature for this star. From the collected spectropolarimetric data, [Morin et al. \(2010\)](#) detected strong Zeeman signatures corresponding to longitudinal fields of 600 G (as large as the maximum of EV Lac). The shape of Stokes V profiles and the absence of intermittency suggested an axisymmetric, poloidal dipole, while the low dispersion of B_l and RV data indicated likely pole-on geometry of the observations. Their four observations did not cover the rotation of the star densely enough to produce reliable maps. From unpolarised spectral analysis, previous studies revealed unsigned magnetic flux on the order of 2-3 kG ([Reiners 2009](#); [Shulyak et al. 2017](#)).

Longitudinal field

I computed B_l using Eq. 2.8 within $\pm 60 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ from line centre and adopting 1700 nm and 1.223 as LSD normalisation wavelength and Landé factor. The interpretation of the generalised Lomb-Scargle periodogram is more elaborated with respect to the previous stars (see Fig. 5.29). The presence of strong aliases of the observational cadence ($\sim 1 \text{ d}$), the gap between instrument runs ($\sim 30 \text{ d}$), and the time span of the time series ($\sim 1000 \text{ d}$) contributes significantly to the periodogram power. By ignoring these features, the periodogram shows a clear and unique peak at the expected stellar rotation period, for which there is no correspondence with the observing window function. If I restrict the periodogram analysis to the four epochs individually (see Sec 5.2), only the last one (2021b2022a) does not show a peak at the expected rotation period. I retrieve $P_{\text{rot,CNLeo}} 2.7 \pm 0.01 \text{ d}$, consistently with the literature ([Reinhold & Hekker 2020](#); [Lafarga et al. 2021](#)).

As shown in Fig. 5.29, the B_l measurements range from -626 to -238 G with a median error bar of 40 G, implying that we observe only the negative polarity of the large-scale field, similarly to AD Leo. These are compatible with the average B_l reported in [Morin et al. \(2010\)](#) of $-691 \pm 54 \text{ G}$. The field values exhibit a sine-like oscillation of about 1000 d as well as fluctuations within each epoch. Although the scatter of the global and epoch-by-epoch time series is lower or compatible with the respective median error bar, which would make the oscillations dubious, the time series is dense, hence we are more sensitive to the epoch-to-epoch variability. When phase-folded at the stellar rotation period, we do not note any evident rotational modulation, except for the 2019b2020a and 2021b2022a epochs. However, the variations are not strong enough to exclude a model without intra-epoch variations. With these clues, we could expect the field topology to be a dipole with negative polarity, and with the magnetic axis almost aligned with the rotation axis of the star.

Figure 5.28: Generalised Lomb-Scargle periodogram of the longitudinal field values extracted from the SPIRou near-infrared time series for CN Leo. The only peak that does not match with an alias of the observing window is at 2.7 d, which is compatible with the stellar rotation period reported in the literature. The format is similar to Fig. 5.2.

Figure 5.29: Evolution of the longitudinal magnetic field of CN Leo. Left: full time series of measurements between 2019 and 2022 with SPIRou. Right: phase-folded B_l curves obtained with $P_{\text{rot,CNLeo}} = 2.7$ d split in specific epochs based on target visibility and telescope scheduling. A Levenberg-Marquardt least-square fit is illustrated as a solid line for each epoch. The format is similar to Fig. 5.3.

FWHM of Stokes I

I computed the FWHM of Stokes I profiles with high- g_{eff} and low- g_{eff} masks, to investigate any rotational modulation and long-term trends as for the previous stars. The results are reported in Table 5.7 and illustrated in Fig. 5.30. Once again, the average FWHM correlates with the choice of g_{eff} -based mask, as I obtain wider lines when high- g_{eff} lines are selected. At the same time, the dispersion increases when adopting these lines because of the Zeeman effect contribution.

Similarly to AD Leo and EV Lac, I cannot choose a sine model to explain the phase variations against a constant model, as the associated χ_r^2 varies only marginally. At the same time, color-coding the data points by rotational cycle does not reveal any specific structure that could be associated to short-term variability. The only effect we observe is an increased dispersion at phases larger than 0.5 for almost all epochs when using high- g_{eff} lines, which could bias the measurement of the average FWHM. Looking

Table 5.7: Comparison of a constant line vs a sine fit for the FWHM phase variations for CN Leo. The columns are the same as Table 5.3.

Epoch	Mask	Mean [km s ⁻¹]	Mean Error [km s ⁻¹]	STD [km s ⁻¹]	RMS _{const} [km s ⁻¹]	$\chi^2_{r,\text{const}}$	RMS _{sine} [km s ⁻¹]	$\chi^2_{r,\text{sine}}$
19a	default	15	0.34	1.27	1.27	16.7	1.22	19.7
	$g_{\text{eff}} > 1.2$	21	1.19	3.73	3.73	19.8	3.44	22.5
19b20a	default	17	0.359	1.41	1.41	19.1	1.35	16.6
	$g_{\text{eff}} > 1.2$	25	1.57	4.44	4.44	15.3	4.27	13.6
20b21a	default	16	0.37	1.69	1.69	45.8	1.61	39.8
	$g_{\text{eff}} > 1.2$	22	1.51	5.08	5.08	26.8	4.74	23.1
21b22a	default	17	0.34	1.37	1.37	25.7	1.29	24.7
	$g_{\text{eff}} > 1.2$	22	1.41	4.94	4.94	16.3	4.65	15.8

Figure 5.30: Phase variations of the FWHM, folded at a stellar rotation period of 2.7 d using Eq. 5.1. The data sets are computed with the default (black), high- g_{eff} (yellow), and low- g_{eff} (purple) mask for the four SPIRou epochs: 2019a, 2019b2020a, 2020a2021b and 2021b2022a. We do not observe a rotational modulation of the FWHM, but some sporadic variability due to the magnetic field, and especially at phases larger than 0.5 when high- g_{eff} lines are adopted.

at the quality of the observations, I did not identify Stokes I observations with a remarkably low S/N due to, e.g. weather conditions. Low- g_{eff} lines maintain a constant behaviour throughout the entire time series, suggesting that the sporadic variability we observe in the data (i.e., distinct FWHM values for the same rotational phase) is most likely due to the magnetic field.

The time series of Stokes I profiles for 2019b2020a computed with the default mask is given in Fig. 5.31, where we clearly note variability from one observation to the next, that acts as a distortion of the red part of the line profile. We also note more evident structures in the red wing of the profile than in the blue. We exclude imperfections in the telluric correction as origin of this effect, because statistically

Figure 5.31: Time series of Stokes I profiles of CN Leo for 2019b2020a. The data points are colored based on their rotational phase, but there is no clear trend or systematic difference across different rotational cycles. We note also that some profiles manifest distortions in their shape, regardless of the rotational phase. Similar features are seen also for the 2019a, 2020b2021a and 2021b2022a epochs. The vertical line indicates the radial velocity of the star, at around 21 km s^{-1} .

such imperfections should act on both wings of the Stokes I profile. A plausible source could be the low-temperature synthetic mask I used in LSD, which may not model properly the spectrum. I tested this by computing Stokes I profiles with the same mask for GJ 1002, which is a slower rotator with similar spectral type to CN Leo (Fouqué et al. 2023), and found the same structure on the red wing, indicating that the synthetic line list may be the culprit. However, the reason why this should influence the red wing more than the blue one is not obvious and will be further investigated, since perhaps a certain molecular band becomes predominant at this spectral type. If this is not related to the star, it could contribute to spurious FWHM and B_l variability.

In Fig. 5.32, I show the epoch-averaged evolution of the FWHM using different line masks. While the low- g_{eff} lines are stable around 12 km s^{-1} , the full mask values evolve from 15 km s^{-1} to 17 km s^{-1} and then back to 16 km s^{-1} , while the high- g_{eff} mask values from 21 km s^{-1} to 25 km s^{-1} and back to 22 km s^{-1} . The quadratic differential broadening computation leads to magnetic field modulus values of 3.7, 4.7, 3.8, and 3.9 kG for the four epochs, respectively, which are larger than the literature (Shulyak et al. 2011). Such temporal variation is somehow anti-correlated with the long-term sine oscillation of B_l (in absolute value), the FWHM being largest when the B_l is smallest. The conclusions are generally

Figure 5.32: Secular evolution of the epoch-averaged FWHM of Stokes I of CN Leo. The colours indicate the use of different masks similarly to Fig. 5.8. The long-term oscillation of the values is anti-correlated with the B_l variations, and it is enhanced (quenched) when using magnetically sensitive (insensitive) lines.

analogous to AD Leo: the FWHM is capable of tracing long-term evolution of the field strength, but the rotational modulation may be drowned by intrinsic variability.

Zeeman-Doppler Imaging

I reconstructed the large-scale magnetic field at the surface of CN Leo with ZDI, for the 2019a, 2019b, 2020a, 2020b, 2021a and 2021b epochs. The input parameters are $i = 75^\circ$, $v_{\text{eq}} \sin(i) = 3.2 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, $P_{\text{rot}} = 2.7 \text{ d}$, and solid body rotation. I set the maximum degree of the harmonic expansion $l_{\text{max}} = 10$, and adopted a linear limb darkening coefficient in H band of 0.3 (Claret & Bloemen 2011).

I refined the values of i and $v_{\text{eq}} \sin(i)$ as a consistency check with the literature, and considering that i was not estimated in Morin et al. (2010). Starting with $v_{\text{eq}} \sin(i)$, I followed Reiners & Basri (2007) and computed Stokes I profiles for GJ 1002, which is the slowest rotator within the SLS target list with similar spectral type to CN Leo. For both stars, I used a line list containing CO lines between 2.2 and 2.5 μm , since they are the most insensitive to activity distortions and Zeeman broadening (Reiners et al. 2013). This is similar to the mask yielding low RV jitter and employed in the analysis described in Chapter 2. The idea, as illustrated in Fig. 5.33, is to broaden the Stokes I profiles of GJ 1002 using a dense grid of $v_{\text{eq}} \sin(i)$ and depth scaling factors, and compare them with CN Leo Stokes I profiles until a minimum χ^2 is found. I obtained $v_{\text{eq}} \sin(i) = 3.2 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ over a 50-point grid between 2 and 5 km s^{-1} , which is compatible with the literature (Reiners & Basri 2007; Fouqué et al. 2018), since the error bar is typically of 1 km s^{-1} . At this point, I compare the stellar radius $R = 0.15 R_\odot$ (Demory et al. 2009; Mamajek 2016) with $R \sin(i) = P_{\text{rot}} v_{\text{eq}} \sin(i) / 50.6145 = 0.16 R_\odot$ (the denominator accounts for the unit conversion of the variables involved). This implies that the star is likely observed equator-on, so I set the input inclination for ZDI to 60° (Morin et al. 2010), to conservatively prevent mirroring effects

Figure 5.33: Measurement of the projected equatorial velocity of CN Leo. The median Stokes I profile of a template slow rotator (GJ 1002) is broadened until a best match with the observed median Stokes I of CN Leo is found. The minimum χ^2 in this case is found at 3.2 km s^{-1} , in agreement with (Reiners & Basri 2007).

between the northern and southern hemisphere.

I fit the profiles to a χ_r^2 level of 0.9, 1.0, 1.3, and 1.2 from an initial value of 2.9, 3.5, 6.8, 6.7 for 2019a, 2019b2020a, 2020b2021a, and 2021b2022a, respectively. The algorithm converges successfully, but we note once again the limitation in modelling completely the profile lobes. The f_V values are constrained to be 16%, 13%, 19% and 16% for the same epochs. The optimisation of f_I did not yield conclusive results. Indeed, as we increase f_I from 0% to 100% in our models, we observe a progressively significant distortion of the profiles shape, making the line parameter optimisation rather challenging. For this reason, and to be consistent with the previous stars, we set $f_I = 0\%$. The Stokes V time series is shown in Fig. 5.34 within $\pm 60 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ from line centre.

The maps of the magnetic field and their characteristics are shown in Fig. 5.35 and Table 5.8. In all epochs, most of the magnetic energy is stored in the poloidal ($> 99\%$), dipolar ($> 95\%$) and axisymmetric ($> 99\%$) components, without any significant variation over time. If we increased the inclination to 75° , the quadrupolar component would account for 15% of the energy, therefore providing a more complex topology. The decrease of the dipolar-to-quadrupolar energy ratio while increasing the inclination was already pointed out by Aurière et al. (2011) for the study on EK Eri.

The field strength follows the sine-like long-term oscillation exhibited by B_l , i.e. it starts from an average field of 460 G, it decreases to 370 G, then increases to 580 G and finally decreases to 520 G. The limitations of the ZDI model at reproducing the lobes of the Stokes V profiles completely leads most likely to an underestimated field strength. As illustrated in Fig. 5.36, the evolution of the field over 4 yr is noted only in the field intensity, as it remains consistently poloidal, dipolar and axisymmetric throughout. I attempted a differential rotation search but the results are inconclusive, which is not surprising given the geometry of the field and the high inclination observations.

Table 5.8: Properties of the magnetic map for CN Leo. The same quantities as Table 5.4 are listed.

	2019a	2019b2020a	2020b2021a	2021b2022a
f_V [%]	16	13	19	16
B_{mean} [G]	458.8	370.5	578.0	520.1
B_{max} [G]	779.0	621.6	993.6	894.2
B_{pol} [%]	99.8	99.9	99.8	99.8
B_{tor} [%]	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.2
B_{dip} [%]	95.7	96.7	96.3	95.8
B_{quad} [%]	0.7	0.5	0.7	0.9
B_{oct} [%]	3.1	2.5	2.7	2.9
B_{axisym} [%]	99.6	99.3	99.9	99.9
$B_{\text{axisym,pol}}$ [%]	99.6	99.3	99.9	99.9
$B_{\text{axisym,tor}}$ [%]	97.4	97.9	99.5	99.7
Obliquity [$^\circ$]	2.5	4.5	1.5	1.5

Figure 5.34: SPIRou time series of Stokes V profiles of CN Leo normalised by the unpolarised continuum intensity. Top left: 2019a. Top right: 2019b2020a. Bottom left: 2020b2021a. Bottom right: 2021b2022a. The format is the same as Fig. 5.11

Figure 5.35: Reconstructed ZDI maps in flattened polar view of CN Leo for (from left to right) 2019a, 2019b2020a, 2020b2021a, and 2021b2022a. The format is the same as Fig. 5.12.

Figure 5.36: Evolution of the magnetic topology of CN Leo over 4 yr for the time series of near-infrared SPIRou data. The format of the plot is the same as Fig. 5.14.

5.4.2 DS Leo

The large-scale magnetic field map for DS Leo was reconstructed initially by [Donati et al. \(2008\)](#) using Narval data collected in 2007 and 2008. They obtained a predominantly toroidal field geometry encircling the star, whereas the remaining poloidal component is mainly dipolar. The average field strength is 100 G, following the slower rotation and only moderate activity level. They reported an axisymmetry variation between 2007 and 2008 of the poloidal component, for which the field was aligned and then misaligned with the rotation axis, respectively. At the same time, the toroidal field featured two spots in 2007 at opposite longitudes, while only one spot in 2008.

Later, [Hébrard et al. \(2016\)](#) applied ZDI to HARPS-Pol and Narval observations collected in 2014, and consistently found a toroidal, axisymmetric geometry, with the poloidal component accounting for less than half the magnetic energy and mostly dipolar. Compared to the previous reconstructions, the average field strength decreased down to 80 G and the dipolar component increased from 50% to 88%. Finally, from unpolarised light studies and modelling of the Zeeman broadening, [Shulyak et al. \(2019\)](#)

Figure 5.37: Generalised Lomb-Scargle periodogram of the longitudinal field values extracted from the SPIRou near-infrared time series for DS Leo. The format is similar to Fig. 5.2.

Figure 5.38: Evolution of the longitudinal magnetic field of DS Leo. Left: full time series of measurements between 2006 and 2022 with ESPaDOnS, Narval and SPIRou. Right: phase-folded B_l curves obtained with $P_{\text{rot,DSL}_{\text{Leo}}} = 13.91$ d for SPIRou time series split in specific epochs based on target visibility and telescope scheduling. A Levenberg-Marquardt least-square fit is illustrated as a solid line for each epoch. The format is similar to Fig. 5.3.

reported an average magnetic flux of 900 G.

Longitudinal field

The longitudinal field was computed adopting LSD normalisation wavelength of 1700 nm and 700 nm, and a Landé factor of 1.181 and 1.086 for near-infrared and optical data, respectively. The integration range of Eq. 2.8 was set to ± 25 km s $^{-1}$ and ± 20 km s $^{-1}$ from line centre, since it is a slower rotator and the least magnetically active star of the M dwarf sample I studied. A Generalised Lomb-Scargle periodogram applied to the near-infrared B_l time series reveal an unambiguous (FAP < 0.01%) peak at $P_{\text{rot,DSL}_{\text{Leo}}} = 13.91 \pm 0.01$ d, which is the expected one from the literature (e.g., Hébrard et al. 2016). This is illustrated in Fig. 5.37.

The near-infrared B_l measurements fall within ± 56 G with a median error bar of 7 G, whereas the optical ones range between -25 and 80 G, with a median error of 7 G (excluding a visible outlier). The

Table 5.9: Comparison of a constant line vs a sine fit for the FWHM phase variations for DS Leo. The columns are the same as Table 5.3.

Epoch	Mask	Mean [km s ⁻¹]	Mean Error [km s ⁻¹]	STD [km s ⁻¹]	RMS _{const} [km s ⁻¹]	$\chi^2_{r,const}$	RMS _{sine} [km s ⁻¹]	$\chi^2_{r,sine}$
2020b2021a	default	13	0.18	0.29	0.29	2.8	0.16	0.9
	$g_{\text{eff}} > 1.2$	14	0.21	0.47	0.47	6.2	0.33	2.9
2021b2022a	default	13	0.18	0.21	0.21	1.5	0.20	1.3
	$g_{\text{eff}} > 1.2$	14	0.20	0.32	0.32	3.1	0.30	2.7

dispersion is comparable to the optical (20 G against 24 G) and the mean of near-infrared B_l values shifts toward zero by 16 G with respect to the optical one. The phase-folded curves of the two epochs (2020b2021a and 2021b2022a) reveal a slight decrease in the amplitude of the modulation in the second epoch, likely suggesting an increase in axisymmetry as shown in Fig. 5.38.

FWHM of Stokes I

I computed the FWHM of Stokes I profiles with high- g_{eff} and low- g_{eff} masks, to investigate any rotational modulation and long-term trends. The results of the rotational modulation analysis are reported in Table 5.9. In the 2020b2021a epoch, the phase-folded data points vary with the stellar rotation, quantified by a decrease in χ^2 from 2.8 to 0.9 (for the default mask) and from 6.2 to 2.9 (for the high- g_{eff} mask) when using a sine model rather than a constant. The sine model for the default mask fits the data approximately down to noise level. In 2021b2022a, there is no clear rotational modulation instead as the variations can be equivalently explained by a constant model. When present, such modulation is enhanced or quenched based when high- g_{eff} or low- g_{eff} lines are adopted.

Color-coding the high- g_{eff} by cycle number reveals short-term variability, as distinct modulations for different rotational cycles can be extracted. This is more evident for 2020b2021a, as the variations of the data points appear “stacked”, i.e. FWHM values belonging to different rotational cycles exhibit an offset. In particular, we observe that observations within the first 5 cycles tend to fall at high FWHM values, then progressively at lower FWHM between cycle number 5 and 11, and at higher FWHM values again in the latest cycles. This feature could be explained by the presence of differential rotation, whose shear would have displaced magnetic regions on the surface during the time span of our observations, making the cycle-averaged FWHM oscillate.

In both epochs, the mean FWHM is 13 km s^{-1} , 14 km s^{-1} and 11 km s^{-1} for the full, high- g_{eff} and low- g_{eff} mask, respectively, as expected from the Zeeman effect contribution to the broadening. For the same reason, the dispersion is higher for magnetically sensitive lines than the insensitive ones. The magnetic field modulus as computed by quadratic differential broadening is stable around 2 kG, twice the estimate reported in the literature from theoretical Zeeman broadening modelling (Shulyak et al. 2019). Over time, the mean FWHM does not manifest particular changes, even though the field becomes weaker from 2020b2021a to 2021b2022a (see Sec. 5.4.2).

When computed for archival optical ESPaDOnS and Narval observations, the mean FWHM is stable around 8.0 km s^{-1} , 9.0 km s^{-1} and 8.4 km s^{-1} for the full, high- g_{eff} and low- g_{eff} mask, respectively. The quadratic differential broadening reveals values of the field modulus at 2 kG, similarly to the near-infrared observations. As shown in Fig. 5.39, the FWHM is still able to catch the rotational modulation in most of the epochs, especially when using magnetically sensitive lines. Once again this could be attributable to the weak-field considerations, since the contribution of Zeeman effect to the line shape is less important for DS Leo than for the other stars, in this case both in near-infrared and in optical.

Finally, I inspected the correlation between FWHM and $|B_l|$ for the optical epochs, as shown in Fig. 5.40. We observe a variety of correlations: there is a positive correlation that increases going from magnetically insensitive to sensitive lines for 2007 (Pearson R from 0.1 to 0.3) and 2011 (R from 0.2 to 0.8), whereas in 2012 and 2014, there is an anti-correlation that increases for magnetically insensitive

Figure 5.39: Phase variations of the FWHM, folded at a stellar rotation period of 13.91 d using Eq. 5.1. The data sets are computed with the default (black), high- g_{eff} (yellow), and low- g_{eff} (purple) mask for the two SPIRou epochs: 2020a2021b and 2021b2022a, as well as for the optical ESPaDOnS and Narval epochs: 2007, 2008, 2010, 2011, 2012, and 2014. While no long-term evolution is observed of the epoch-averaged FWHM, we observe evident rotational modulation (especially when using high- g_{eff} lines) in almost all epochs. The SPIRou values obtained with high- g_{eff} lines are color-coded by cycle number, which reveal a “stacking” feature in 2020b2021a. This is attributable to short-term variability.

lines (down to $R=0.6$). For 2008 and 2010, there is one outlying data point at large B_l values that likely biases the correlation coefficient, as the bulk of the data points do not manifest particular correlations. For the near-infrared epoch in which we observe rotational modulation of FWHM (i.e. 2020b2021a), there is no significant correlation, the Pearson R coefficient being smaller than 0.2 for the three masks. The variety of correlations for different epochs may stem from the fact that, for early M dwarfs like DS Leo, the ratio of magnetic field recovered with polarised light relative to unpolarised light is only a few percent (and it increases to dozens of percents for mid-M, [Morin et al. 2008b](#); [Kochukhov 2021](#)), hence there is an even less obvious scaling between small- and large-scale fields. Besides, we have to consider that the Pearson R coefficient does not take into account measurement uncertainties, which are become important when they are compatible with dispersion.

Zeeman-Doppler Imaging

I reconstructed the large-scale magnetic field at the surface of DS Leo with ZDI, for the 2020b2021a and 2021b2022a epochs. The input parameters are $i = 60^\circ$, $v_{\text{eq}} \sin(i) = 2 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, $P_{\text{rot}} = 13.91 \text{ d}$, and I started assuming solid body rotation. I set the maximum degree of the harmonic expansion $l_{\text{max}} = 8$, and adopted a linear limb darkening coefficient in H band of 0.3 ([Claret & Bloemen 2011](#)). I adopted Unno-Rachkovsky solutions to radiative transfer, but in this case weak-field approximation would have been an equally valid choice (see Appendix A).

[Fig. 5.41](#) illustrates the time series of SPIRou Stokes V cut at $\pm 25 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ from line centre. Analogously to the other stars, the observations exhibit a complex structure predominantly within the Stokes profile range, but it is not straightforward to discern whether or not it is rotationally modulated, since the field is more structured than, e.g., AD Leo. The residuals of Stokes I with respect to the median profile do not manifest evident variability, contrarily to the previous stars. I fit the profiles to a χ_r^2 level of 1.4 and 1.2 from an initial value of 2.7 and 1.6 for 2020b2021a and 2021b2022a, respectively. I also constrain f_V values of 10% and 6% for the two epochs, and we set $f_I = 0\%$ similarly to AD Leo, as values up to approximately 50% do not introduce artificial rotational modulation of the profiles.

I then searched for differential rotation using the method of [Donati et al. \(2000\)](#) and [Petit et al. \(2002\)](#). Basically, I fix the entropy at a certain level and scour a dense grid of $(P_{\text{rot,eq}}, d\Omega)$ pairs to find the combination that minimise the χ_r^2 between observations and synthetic models, as illustrated in [Fig. 5.42](#). The variable $d\Omega$ is the differential rotation rate, as implemented in [Eq. A.33](#). The best parameters are measured by fitting a 2D paraboloid to the χ^2 distribution, and the error bars are obtained from a variation of $\Delta\chi^2 = 1$ away from the minimum ([Press et al. 1992](#); [Petit et al. 2002](#)). I found $P_{\text{rot,eq}} = 13.836 \pm 0.016 \text{ d}$ and $d\Omega = 0.0192 \pm 0.0020 \text{ rad d}^{-1}$ for 2020b2021a, meaning that the rotation period of at the pole is $14.447 \pm 0.069 \text{ d}$, by virtue of [Eq. A.33](#). For 2021b2022a, I have $P_{\text{rot,eq}} = 13.469 \pm 0.054 \text{ d}$ and $d\Omega = 0.0448 \pm 0.0045 \text{ rad d}^{-1}$, and the rotation period at the pole is $14.899 \pm 0.172 \text{ d}$. Assuming the $(P_{\text{rot,eq}}, d\Omega)$ pairs as input parameters for ZDI, I am able to improve the fit down to χ_r^2 level of 1.25 and 1.10 for 2020b2021a and 2021b2022a, respectively.

Likely, I obtained tighter constraints on 2020b2021a relative to 2021b2022a because the field is less complex in the second epoch, hence I have a lower number of magnetic features with which I can track differential rotation. More generally, the error bars are smaller than the literature measurements because our time series contain a larger number of observations. Also, these error bars are only statistical and do not account for systematics, hence they are likely underestimated. One possible way to estimate systematics is to vary input parameters like inclination and $v_{\text{eq}} \sin(i)$ and check how the minimum χ_r^2 varies accordingly. The values of equator/pole period I estimated encompass the measurement obtained from the periodogram analysis of B_l , and fall within the range of literature values ([Donati et al. 2008](#); [Hébrard et al. 2016](#)). Our $d\Omega$ values are generally lower than estimated in the literature, but compatible within 3σ from [Donati et al. \(2008\)](#), and 1σ from [Hébrard et al. \(2016\)](#). Such difference could be due to an evolution of the shear at the surface of the star, as studied also by [Donati et al., \(2023, submitted\)](#) for AU Mic, but deciphering the exact mechanism is not a straightforward task. [Fig. 5.42](#) also shows that there is an anti-correlation between $P_{\text{rot,eq}}$ and $d\Omega$ (or equivalently an $\Omega_{\text{eq}} - d\Omega$ correlation), likely due to the fact that I mainly trace one latitude when searching for differential rotation.

Figure 5.40: Correlation between FWHM and $|B_l|$ of DS Leo for optical epochs. Depending on the epoch examined, we observe both positive correlation (2006 and 2011), negative correlation (2012 and 2014) and lack of correlation (2007 and 2010). The increase or decrease in correlation depending on the line selection is also not straightforward, overall suggesting an underlying complexity of the scaling between small- and large-scale field.

The maps are shown in Figure 5.43 and their properties are reported in Table 5.10. In 2020b2021a, the magnetic energy is distributed almost equally in poloidal and toroidal components, with the dipolar mode accounting for most of the energy (66%). While the toroidal component is mostly axisymmetric (90%), the poloidal component is largely non-axisymmetric (4%). In 2021b2022a, the poloidal component takes over the toroidal one, counting 74% of the magnetic energy against 26%. The dipolar mode remains the dominant one (82%), featuring a moderate increase similarly to the one reported in Hébrard et al. (2016). In terms of axisymmetry, the toroidal component is stable, while the poloidal one increases axisymmetry to 15%. Between the two epochs, the average field strength has halved, from 30 to 15 G.

Figure 5.41: SPIRou time series of Stokes V profiles of DS Leo normalised by the unpolarised continuum intensity. Top: 2020b2021a. Bottom: 2021b2022a. The cycles in this plot are computed with Eq. 5.1 while using the median HJD for each epoch. The format is the same as Fig. 5.11.

Figure 5.42: Differential rotation search for DS Leo for 2020b2021a (left) and 2021b2022a (right). The plot shows the χ_r^2 landscape over a grid of $(P_{\text{rot,eq}}, d\Omega)$ pairs, with the 1σ and 3σ contours centered on the minimum. The best values are obtained by fitting a 2D paraboloid around the minimum, while their error bars are the projection of the 1σ contour on the respective axis (Press et al. 1992).

Table 5.10: Properties of the magnetic maps for the 2020b2021a and 2021b2022a SPIRou epochs for DS Leo. The same quantities as Table 5.4 are listed.

	2020b2021a	2021b2022a
f_V	10%	6%
B_{mean} [G]	33.4	14.2
B_{max} [G]	80.3	38.6
B_{pol} [%]	50.9	73.6
B_{tor} [%]	49.1	26.4
B_{dip} [%]	66.5	82.1
B_{quad} [%]	23.2	13.7
B_{oct} [%]	4.5	2.6
B_{axisym} [%]	46.9	35.7
$B_{\text{axisym,pol}}$ [%]	4.3	15.0
$B_{\text{axisym,tor}}$ [%]	91.0	93.3

To assess whether we can detect differential rotation on shorter time scales, the ZDI reconstruction and differential rotation search were also carried out for two subsets of the 2020b2021a and 2021b2022a epochs. I used 17 observations from 21st February to 1st of April 2021 and 19 observations from the 6th January to 1st February 2020, respectively. These subsets contain three times less observations than the full epochs, but span between two and three rotational cycles of the star, without long gaps between individual observations. For this reason, they represent a trade-off between considering long time spans, over which the field may have evolved significantly, and short time spans, over which I could not capture the shear of differential rotation. The reconstructed maps are reasonably similar to those obtained with the full epochs: the subset of 2020b2021a leads to a map with 10% more energy in the poloidal component (and correspondingly 10% less in the toroidal component) as well as in the dipolar one. The field is also stronger, owing to a better ZDI fit given the smaller number of observations. Instead, the map is basically unchanged for the 2021b2022a subset. The situation is somehow reversed when searching for differential rotation, the subset of 2020b2021a being consistent within uncertainties with the full epoch, and the subset of 2021b2022a yielding unconstrained values. The maps presented here are therefore those obtained using the two full epochs, allowing the differential rotation to act in a consistent way for a longer time scale as shown also in Donati et al. 2023, submitted.

The inverse of the differential rotation rate represents the pole-equator lap time ($t_{\text{lap}} = 2\pi/d\Omega$): if I suppose to have two points, one at the pole and one at equator, connected by the same longitude at one initial instant, the t_{lap} represents how much time it takes for the two points to share the same

Figure 5.43: Reconstructed ZDI maps in flattened polar view of DS Leo for 2020b2021a (left) and 2021b2022a (right), and accounting for the constrained differential rotation. The format is the same as Fig. 5.12.

longitude again. For 2020b2021a (time span of 256 d) and 2021b2022a (time span of 205 d) respectively, I obtain a lap time of 327 ± 34 d and 140 ± 14 d. During this time, magnetic regions on the surface are presumably distorted by the shear of differential rotation.

It is interesting to compare these values with the evolution time scale of a Gaussian Process defined with a quasi-periodic covariance function, and applied to longitudinal field values. I used the formalism outlined in Appendix B, while including an excess of white noise parameter (S), to account for additional noise that is not represented by the error bars on B_l . I applied the Gaussian Process to 2020b2021a and 2021b2022a individually, as well as the full time series. The results are reported in Table 5.11 and shown in Fig. 5.44. For 2020b2021a, I constrain a decay time which is compatible with t_{lap} for the same epoch within uncertainties, whereas for 2021b2022a, the decay time is $4\text{-}5\sigma$ lower than the lap time. This means that differential rotation was the predominant contributor to the variability of the field in 2020b2021a, while not as much in 2021b2022a, and is indicative that differential rotation may evolve

Figure 5.44: Gaussian Process Regression applied to B_l values for DS Leo, for 2020b2021a (left) and 2021b2022a (right), respectively. Top: Gaussian Process with a 1σ confidence region using the optimised hyperparameters in Table 5.11. Bottom: corner plots with the 2D posterior distributions and the marginalised 1D distributions on the diagonal for the hyperparameters of the GP (see Table 5.11) and excess of uncorrelated noise (S). Vertical lines represent the 50th (solid), 16th and 84th (dashed) percentiles.

Table 5.11: Gaussian Process hyperparameters applied to B_l time series of DS Leo. The columns are: (1) hyperparameter identifier (see Eq. B.2) or statistical variable, (2) injected uniform prior with boundaries within parenthesis, (3,4,5) best values and uncertainties when applied to 2020b2021a, 2021b2022a, and the full time series.

Hyperparameter	Prior	Best Value		
		2020b2021a	2021b2022a	Full
Amplitude (θ_1) [G]	$\mathcal{U}(0, 1000)$	$52.9^{+34.7}_{-20.5}$	$16.4^{+6.1}_{-3.4}$	$20.1^{+4.9}_{-3.3}$
Evolution (θ_2) [d]	$\mathcal{U}(0, 500)$	$261.2^{+117.8}_{-85.2}$	$55.6^{+23.8}_{-14.5}$	$81.9^{+17.6}_{-15.9}$
Rotation (θ_3) [d]	$\mathcal{U}(1, 20)$	$13.840^{+0.065}_{-0.051}$	$14.248^{+0.232}_{-0.212}$	$13.974^{+0.086}_{-0.089}$
Smoothness (θ_4)	$\mathcal{U}(0.0, 1.2)$	$0.75^{+0.26}_{-0.24}$	$0.47^{+0.24}_{-0.13}$	$0.48^{+0.13}_{-0.09}$
Uncorrelated noise (S) [G]	$\mathcal{U}(0, 100)$	$5.4^{+2.0}_{-2.2}$	$4.9^{+2.1}_{-2.3}$	$6.1^{+1.3}_{-1.4}$
RMS residuals [G]		10.3	7.3	8.9
χ_r^2		1.4	1.1	1.3

Figure 5.45: Evolution of the magnetic topology of DS Leo over 15 yr. The time series includes optical (Donati et al. 2008; Hébrard et al. 2016), and near-infrared SPIRou data. The format of the plot is the same as Fig. 5.14.

over time. The amplitude of the Gaussian process reflects the weakening of the field strength seen in ZDI maps, and the values for the full time series are intermediate between the two individual epochs. The stellar rotation period is recovered consistently. By virtue of the differential rotation law (see Eq. A.33), we see that the periodicity retrieved by the Gaussian Process in 2020b2021a is associated to low latitudes, whereas in 2021b2022a to intermediate latitudes. Finally, the GP is also able to capture a decrease in field complexity (of the radial field in particular), as we note that the variations in 2020b2021a are described by a “double-peaked” trend, and in 2021b2022a by a more sine-like oscillation.

We observe a correlation between the reconstructed maps and the rotational modulation of the FWHM of Stokes I for the 2020b2021a epoch. Indeed, the positive polarity of the predominantly-dipolar configuration is located at around phase 0.2, whereas the negative polarity at phase 0.6. Correspondingly, the FWHM modulation exhibits the maximum and the minimum of the oscillation at these phases, confirming its capability as a magnetic activity and stellar rotation tracer. Furthermore, the short-term variability emerging from the SPIRou time series of FWHM values (see Fig. 5.39) can be attributed to differential rotation since the equator-pole lap time is comparable to the time span of the epochs considered, meaning that differential rotation could have shifted the magnetic regions on the surface affecting the mean level of FWHM for that specific cycle.

The magnetic field’s evolution over 15 yr is illustrated in Fig. 5.45. We observe how the field in the latest epochs has a progressively dominant poloidal component (the color of the data point is changing), but that remained highly non-axisymmetric throughout (the shape is more ‘star-like’), except for 2007 (Donati et al. 2008). The complexity of the poloidal component of the field has also decreased in the same time scale, being the field predominantly dipolar. On top of that, the average reconstructed field strength has decreased, from an initial 100 G to 15 G in the latest SPIRou epoch. We caution that, owing to the limitation of the ZDI model at reproducing the shape of the Stokes V lobes, the field strength reported may be underestimated. Indeed, both from the Stokes V profiles themselves and the FWHM analysis, we notice that short-term variability is present, but it is not completely accounted for by the ZDI model.

5.5 Weak long-term evolution

5.5.1 V374 Peg

The large-scale magnetic field of V374 Peg was reconstructed by Morin et al. (2008a), using ESPaDOnS data from 2005 and 2006. The geometry is mostly poloidal, dipolar and axisymmetric, with the visible hemisphere featuring the positive polarity of the radial component (field lines are coming out of the hemisphere). The field has a mean strength of 780 G and overall it did not manifest evident evolution over 1 yr. The magnetic flux measured from theoretical modelling of Zeeman broadening is between 4.4

Figure 5.46: Generalised Lomb-Scargle periodogram of the longitudinal field values extracted from the SPIRou near-infrared time series for V374 Peg. I found the most significant peak at 0.445 ± 0.018 d, which is consistent with the literature, but the periodogram power is spread over many high-frequency peaks representing the aliases of the observational cadence. The format is similar to Fig. 5.2, but we added vertical dash-dot lines to indicate the first harmonics of the stellar rotation period.

and 5.3 kG (Shulyak et al. 2017, 2019).

Longitudinal field

I applied Eq. 2.8 to compute B_l from the SPIRou time series of Stokes LSD profiles. The integration was carried out within $\pm 70 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ from line centre and adopting 1700 nm and 1.184 as LSD normalisation wavelength and Landé factor, respectively. As illustrated in Fig. 5.46, the Generalised Lomb-Scargle periodogram on B_l is contaminated by a forest of aliases of real rotation period and observations cadence. The most significant peak is found at $P_{\text{rot}, \text{V374Peg}} = 0.445 \pm 0.018$ d, consistent with Morin et al. (2008a) within uncertainties, and without a corresponding peak in the window function.

To further corroborate such periodicity, I used photometric data collected with *TESS*. In particular, there are two light curves publicly available at the Mikulski Archive for Space Telescope (MAST)²: one covers between 15th August and 10th September 2019, when *TESS* monitored sector 15, and one between 2nd and 30th September 2022 while monitoring sector 56. I selected the Pre-search Data Conditioning Single Aperture Photometry (PDC-SAP) light curve, in which the flux has been corrected already for systematics and I removed data points whose quality flag was different than zero, symbolising data conditions outside nominal values. Fig. 5.47 illustrates the light curve and the application of a periodogram to the data. There is a sharp and highly significant ($\text{FAP} < 0.01\%$) peak at $P_{\text{rot}, \text{V374Peg}} = 0.4455 \pm 0.0002$ d in 2019 and $P_{\text{rot}, \text{V374Peg}} = 0.4455 \pm 0.0001$ d in 2022. Such time scale is consistent with previous determinations based on ZDI analysis of spectropolarimetric data (Morin et al. 2008a), and could be noticed directly from the smooth periodic variations of the light curves.

The long-term behaviour of B_l is illustrated in Fig. 5.48. The B_l measurements range from 80 to 620 G with a median error bar of 67 G. As opposed to AD Leo and CN Leo, we are observing only the positive polarity of the magnetic field. There is no peculiarity in the long-term behaviour, the average and scatter being approximately 300 G and 100 G at each epoch. When phase-folded at the stellar rotation period,

²<https://dx.doi.org/10.17909/T9RP4V>

Figure 5.47: Analysis of *TESS* photometric data taken in 2019 (top) and 2022 (bottom). Left: PDC-SAP light curve with data points. The inset shows a portion of the light curve, where a periodicity of nearly half a day can be noticed. Right: Generalised Lomb-Scargle periodogram of the light curve. The strongest peak is at $P_{\text{rot},V374\text{Peg}} = 0.4455 \pm 0.0002$ d for 2019, and at $P_{\text{rot},V374\text{Peg}} = 0.4455 \pm 0.0001$ d for 2022, both compatible with [Morin et al. \(2008a\)](#).

Figure 5.48: Evolution of the longitudinal magnetic field of V374 Peg. Left: full time series of measurements between 2005 and 2021 with SPIRou, Narval and ESPaDOnS. The time series does not reveal particular trends, as both the mean and dispersion of the data remain stable. Right: phase-folded B_l curves obtained with $P_{\text{rot},V374\text{Peg}} = 0.446$ d and color-coded based on the rotational cycle of the observation (see Eq. 5.1). A Levenberg-Marquardt least-square sine fit at $P_{\text{rot},V374\text{Peg}}$ is illustrated as a dashed line.

we notice that the B_l exhibit modulation, even though a simple sine model does not account entirely the variability.

Figure 5.49: Median Stokes I profile of SPIRou 2021b observations of V374 Peg computed with the full (top), high- g_{eff} (middle), and low- g_{eff} (bottom) mask. The width of all this profiles is comparable, and dominated by rotational broadening, hence the contribution from Zeeman effect cannot be captured easily.

FWHM of Stokes I

V374 Peg is a fast rotator compared to the other stars I have examined, which is quantified by a projected rotational velocity $v_{\text{eq}} \sin(i)$ of about 37 km s^{-1} . For this reason, despite the star manifests an intense field (Morin et al. 2008a; Shulyak et al. 2017), the shape of spectral lines is dominated by rotational broadening and likely overwhelms the contribution of Zeeman splitting. I proceeded analogously to the other stars and computed Stokes I profiles with the full, high- g_{eff} and low- g_{eff} masks.

Regardless of the selection of magnetically sensitive or insensitive lines, there are only negligible differences in the time series of FWHM values, confirming that rotation is the dominant broadening agent shaping the line profiles, as presented in Fig. 5.49. For this reason, I cannot infer a reliable value of the small-scale magnetic flux from the quadratic differential broadening between the two line selections

Figure 5.50: Phase variations of the FWHM computed from the 2011b SPIRou data, folded at the stellar rotation period of 0.4455 d using Eq. 5.1. Top: the data sets are computed with the default (black), high- g_{eff} (yellow), and low- g_{eff} (purple) mask. Middle: correlation plot between the time series of FWHM values computed with the three different masks and the longitudinal magnetic field. Bottom: Phase-folded time series of FWHM values computed with the full mask and color-coded by rotational cycle.

similarly to the other stars. Quantitatively, the mean of the measured FWHM is around 72 km s^{-1} , with a standard deviation of 3.0 km s^{-1} .

In Fig. 5.50, we observe evident rotational modulation of the FWHM, with a complex structure of the variations: at phases 0.2, 0.6 and 0.9 the curve exhibit a dip, whereas at phases 0.0, 0.3 and 0.8 there is a peak. Such behaviour correlates with the location of dark and bright surface inhomogeneities that I reconstructed via Doppler Imaging, as outlined in Chapter 3. If color-coded by rotational cycle, we do not observe substantial intra-cycle variability of the FWHM, since the dispersion is comparable for distinct cycles. Such stability of the modulation is in agreement with the absence of an evident evolution over three years of the brightness oscillations as shown by the *TESS* light curves (see Fig. 5.47).

Finally, I looked for correlations between FWHM and the longitudinal field values (see Fig. 5.50), and found Pearson R coefficients between 0.3-0.4 when adopting different spectral line selections. The positive sign of the correlation implies wider spectral lines for stronger field values, as expected if the Zeeman effect drives the FWHM variability, and the lack of variation of the correlation coefficient according to the line list chosen likely stems from the dominance of rotational broadening over magnetic broadening. Such positive correlation is however only moderate, and the scatter in FWHM values for a certain longitudinal field values (e.g., around 300 G) is large, hence it is not straightforward to claim that larger values of FWHM correspond to larger values of the field. Indeed, the Pearson R coefficient does not take into account measurement uncertainties, which become dominant in this case.

Zeeman-Doppler Imaging

I reconstructed the large-scale magnetic field at the surface of V374 Peg with ZDI, adopting $i = 70^\circ$, $v_{\text{eq}} \sin(i) = 37 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, $P_{\text{rot}} = 0.4455 \text{ d}$, and solid body rotation as input parameters. In this case, $v_{\text{eq}} \sin(i)$ was optimised along with the other line model parameters as described in Sec. 5.12. I set the maximum degree of the harmonic expansion $l_{\text{max}} = 15$, and set the linear limb darkening coefficient to 0.3 (Claret & Bloemen 2011). The LSD profiles analysed here were obtained with a complete atomic mask, similarly to the one used for the brightness imaging analysis in Chapter 3.

Fig. 5.51 illustrates the time series of SPIRou Stokes V within $\pm 70 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ from line centre. We do not observe an evident horizontal separation between the two lobes of the profiles, as expected for a high $v_{\text{eq}} \sin(i)$ value, hence we set $f_V = 100\%$ and adopt Unno-Rachkovsky solutions. The optimisation of this parameter is in fact inconclusive, and adopting values between 10% and 20% similarly to the other stars would lead to negligible differences in the magnetic field maps. For this reason, I could also assume weak-field approximation similarly to Morin et al. (2008a), because the Zeeman splitting effect is smeared out compared to the rotational broadening, and I would obtain results consistent with the ones adopting Unno-Rachkovsky solutions. I fit the profiles to a χ_r^2 level of 1.0 from an initial value of 1.9. I attempted to constrain f_I as well, but changing this quantity did not yield significant differences to the models of the line profiles. Indeed, we could not observe any artificial rotational modulation of the χ_r^2 variations when going from $f_I = 0\%$ to 100%. For this reason, and consistency with the previous stars, we set $f_I = 0\%$.

The ZDI map is shown in Figure 5.52 and its properties are reported in Table 5.12. The field is mostly poloidal (99% of the magnetic energy), dipolar (88%) and axisymmetric (89%). Although the dipolar energy fraction is large, the map appears more complex, i.e. with a visible octupolar contribution. I reconstructed the map using an entropy weighting scheme based on l^2 rather than l (see Appendix A), and obtained a purely dipolar configuration. For consistency with the other stars, the map presented here is obtained with an l -based entropy weighting scheme. The strength of the field is approximately half of that reported in Morin et al. (2008a), but we attribute this to a limitation of the ZDI model (either Unno-Rachkovsky or weak-field approximation) to encompass the lobes of the Stokes V profiles, rather than actual evolution of the field.

We finally note that the three structures of the positive radial field located at rotational phases 0.15, 0.40 and 0.80, which correlate reasonably with the occurrence of the peaks of the FWHM variations, as well as the position of brightness features reconstructed in Chapter 3. This likely reflects Zeeman effect associated with magnetic regions rather than brightness effects, as pointed out in Sec 3.4. In terms of

Figure 5.51: SPIRou time series of Stokes V profiles of V374 Peg normalised by the unpolarised continuum intensity. The format is the same as Fig. 5.11.

Table 5.12: Properties of the magnetic map for V374 Peg. The same quantities as Table 5.4 are listed.

B_{mean} [G]	337.5
B_{max} [G]	758.8
B_{pol} [%]	98.7
B_{tor} [%]	1.3
B_{dip} [%]	88.5
B_{quad} [%]	6.8
B_{oct} [%]	4.3
B_{axisym} [%]	89.7
$B_{\text{axisym,pol}}$ [%]	89.8
$B_{\text{axisym,dip}}$ [%]	93.0
Tilt angle [°]	15.5

Figure 5.52: Reconstructed ZDI map in flattened polar view of V374 Peg. The format is the same as Fig. 5.12.

Figure 5.53: Evolution of the magnetic topology of V374 Peg over 16 yr. The time series includes optical (Morin et al. 2008a), and near-infrared SPIRou data. The format of the plot is the same as Fig. 5.14.

long-term trend, V374 Peg features a magnetic topology that is highly consistent with that reported by Morin et al. (2008a) after 16 yr, as shown in Fig. 5.53. The gap of the observations does not allow us, however, to conclude whether the field has been stable for the entire time or if we are coincidentally seeing the same configuration as the past maps.

Finally, I attempted a differential rotation search, but the SPIRou observations span only two weeks, preventing us from probing the appropriate time scales over which differential rotation has had an effect on the surface distribution of the field (Morin et al. 2008a). The result is a χ^2 landscape featuring a long valley without any particular minimum.

5.6 Summary of magnetic field monitoring

I investigated the evolution of the large-scale magnetic field for a sample of well-studied M dwarfs: AD Leo, DS Leo, CN Leo, EV Lac, and V374 Peg. I combined optical archival spectropolarimetric data collected with ESPaDOnS and Narval, and analysed by Donati et al. (2008); Morin et al. (2008a,b, 2010); Hébrard et al. (2016); Lavail et al. (2018), with new near-infrared SPIRou data collected between 2019 and 2022, mostly as part of the SPIRou Legacy Survey. This way, the time baseline to seek for secular evolution is around 15 yr.

Distinct techniques were applied consistently to all stars. More precisely, I computed and analysed the time series of longitudinal magnetic field and FWHM of Stokes I , and I reconstructed the magnetic field topology at the stellar surface by means of Zeeman-Doppler Imaging. For AD Leo, I additionally presented the application of a Principal Component Analysis in collaboration with Dr. Lisa Lehmann. For this reason, AD Leo represents the most complete case, for which we can appreciate the convergence of the results from techniques to the same conclusions. For this reason, although the other examined stars do not have an associated section on PCA analysis, the conclusions are not expected to differ significantly. A complete description of these results will be part of Bellotti et al. 2023a, in prep and Bellotti et al. 2023b, in prep.

5.6.1 Longitudinal field

The time series of B_l values revealed an exciting variety of long-term trends:

- AD Leo manifested a long-term decrease (in absolute value) from -300 to -50 G, with a temporary increase in strength between 2016 and 2019, and without reaching polarity reversal in our time frame. Additional DDT observations were obtained, but the field has a negative sign still, and seemed to have re-gained strength at around -150 G.
- EV Lac showed a “pulsating” trend, which saw variations between ± 400 G around 2007, then between ± 200 G in 2016, and finally between ± 300 G around 2020. However, the dearth of observations between 2010 and 2019 prevent us from being conclusive on this behaviour.
- CN Leo exhibited a sine-like trend, characterised by a period of 1000 d, an amplitude of 100 G, and an average of -500 G.
- DS Leo did not manifest any specific trend, as the mean field remained reasonably stable around 0 G, within ± 50 G.
- V374 Peg also did not show evident evolution, the longitudinal field falling between 200 G and 600 G, with a reasonably stable mean at 350 G.

In all cases, the rotational modulation of B_l is clear, confirming its role as an excellent magnetic activity tracer. Indeed, a Lomb-Scargle periodogram shows a significant peak at the expected stellar rotation period. When there are several aliases of the observing cadence and time span, the periodogram power can leak at the corresponding time scales, creating a distribution of peaks from which it is more complicated to disentangle the stellar rotation period. Also, the increased spatial resolution, associated with high $v_{\text{eq}} \sin(i)$, results in a clearly non-sinusoidal curve, and therefore the periodogram power at some harmonics of the stellar rotation period is stronger. This was the case for V374 Peg, but the retrieved stellar rotation period was supported by a similar analysis on *TESS* photometric time series.

5.6.2 FWHM of Stokes I

The FWHM of Stokes profiles in unpolarised light can serve as a low-resolution proxy for measuring Zeeman broadening and making a first-order estimate of the total, unsigned field at the stellar surface, owing to the FWHM sensitivity to small-scale fields. Except for V374 Peg, the low $v_{\text{eq}} \sin(i)$ of the M dwarfs examined here is suitable for studying magnetic-induced broadening. We can obtain a lot of information by comparing time series of FWHM while adopting magnetically sensitive (high-Landé factor) and insensitive (low-Landé factor) line lists. In particular, I investigated distinct temporal behaviour of the FWHM, such as rotational modulation and long-term trends, and looked for correlations with the longitudinal magnetic field and ZDI maps. Ultimately, this information has the potential to shed more light on the yet-understood connection between small- and large-scale field, and obtain a global picture of the magnetic field of the star.

General features emerging from our analyses are:

- Not surprisingly, we noticed that the FWHM computed with high- g_{eff} lines was systematically larger than with low- g_{eff} lines, whereas the full line list represented an intermediate case, clearly reflecting the linear dependence of Zeeman splitting on the Landé factor (see Eq. 4.1). For every star, the quadratic differential broadening between high- and low-Landé factor lines allowed us to infer values of the magnetic field modulus that were larger, but reasonably compatible with the literature. Whenever present, such values exhibited the same long-term trends as the FWHM, eventually correlating with the evolution of the field topology.
- The scatter affecting FWHM estimates with near-infrared observations can be attributed to short-term variability, especially when adopting high- g_{eff} lines. Indeed, by color-coding the time series based on the rotational cycle, we noticed for AD Leo, EV Lac and CN Leo that some data points sharing the same rotational phase (but different rotational cycle) were falling at distinct FWHM values. For DS Leo instead, we observed a structured “stacking” of the data points depending on the rotational cycle, possibly due to the action of differential rotation or intrinsic variability of active regions.
- On the rotation period time scale, for AD Leo, EV Lac, and DS Leo, we observed rotational modulation of the FWHM for some epochs of the optical observations and regardless the line lists adopted. In near-infrared, the rotational modulation was more challenging to capture. A possible explanation stems from the larger contribution of Zeeman effect in near-infrared relative to the optical domain, as it introduces more line shape distortions and results in a larger scatter, overwhelming rotational modulation. We noticed the latter clearly only for one epoch of EV Lac when using the full or low- g_{eff} line list, or for DS Leo epochs for all line lists. Such modulation correlates with the ZDI maps of the radial field, the FWHM being minimum when the negative polarity is along the line of sight and maximum when the positive polarity is.
- Because the longitudinal field is sensitive to the large-scale field and the FWHM is sensitive to small-scale fields, seeking a correlation between these two quantities could shed more light on the link between the scales. I mostly used optical archival data sets of AD Leo, EV Lac and DS Leo for this analysis, for which the rotational modulation at the stellar rotation period of FWHM was evident. I found a variety of behaviours depending on the epoch considered. In some cases, there is a positive correlation between $|B_l|$ and FWHM, meaning that the spectral lines are on average wider when the field is stronger, as expected. In other cases, I recorded a lack of correlation or even an anti-correlation, which is not straightforward to explain, and therefore requires further work in this direction.
- On longer time scales, I observed trends of the epoch-averaged FWHM (an aspect already reported by [Morgenthaler et al. 2012](#)), reflecting more or less the behaviour exhibited by the longitudinal field and/or the magnetic topology evolution. This is enhanced in particular when high-

g_{eff} lines are used, whereas low- g_{eff} tend to lead to the same value throughout. This suggests that the FWHM of a specific set of lines may be used as a first-order tracer of magnetic field evolution.

The case of V374 Peg deserves a separate comment. For this star, the FWHM did not change significantly when the Stokes I profiles were computed with high- or low-Landé factor lines, because of the dominance of rotational broadening. Nevertheless, I was able to capture rotational modulation with all the masks used, revealing a complex behaviour that may correlated with the brightness reconstructed with DI and the magnetic map reconstructed with ZDI. Interpreting the distortions of Stokes I profile as caused by genuine brightness inhomogeneities or Zeeman effect is not straightforward (Donati et al., 2023 submitted)

Finally, these conclusions are drawn while using a Landé factor threshold of 1.2, to be consistent with the studies I described in Chapter 2. However, these analyses can be refined by selecting magnetically insensitive lines with $g_{\text{eff}} < 1.0$ and sensitive ones with $g_{\text{eff}} > 1.5$. The number of lines and consequently the signal-to-noise ratio of the LSD profiles would inexorably decrease, but this exercise could help understand the differential broadening between high- and low-Landé factor lines further.

5.6.3 ZDI

I have detected evident secular variations in the topology of the large-scale magnetic field for some of our stars. The results are summarised in Fig. 5.54. The main features are the following:

- AD Leo’s magnetic field remained predominantly poloidal and dipolar, with a clear decrease in axisymmetry (or correspondingly, an increase in magnetic axis obliquity) in the most recent epoch, i.e. late 2020. The reconstructed field is also weaker compared to the optical maps (Morin et al. 2008b; Lavail et al. 2018).
- EV Lac’s field remained mainly poloidal, dipolar and with a significant contribution of quadrupolar field. The axisymmetry has decreased almost to 0% in the most recent epoch, i.e. the large-scale topology is dominated by an equatorial dipole, and the strength is also diminished relative to optical reconstructions (Morin et al. 2008b).
- CN Leo’s field did not show variations from a poloidal, dipolar, axisymmetric configuration. The only evolution seems to be in the field strength, which follows a similar fluctuating trend as the longitudinal field.
- DS Leo’s field saw a systematic increase in poloidal energy fraction over time, accompanied by a decrease in poloidal axisymmetry. The toroidal components contributes significantly to the energy budget still, and its mainly axisymmetric, similarly to the optical reconstructions (Donati et al. 2008; Hébrard et al. 2016).
- V374 Peg’s field remained predominantly poloidal, dipolar and axisymmetric, with a slightly weaker field than in optical maps (Morin et al. 2008a,b).

If I group the long-term trends according to spectral type, I see that the field of DS Leo (early M-type) has more rapid variations than the other types, i.e. on shorter time scales. For AD Leo and EV Lac instead (mid M-type), I can still appreciate evident topological changes of the field, but the time scales appear to be longer. Then, for CN Leo and V374 Peg (late M-type), I lack a substantial evolution over 15 yr. Such phenomenon could be correlated to the magnetic field intensity, with stronger fields (i.e., later spectral types) being able to quench surface shear and yield intrinsic stability, as already pointed out in Donati et al. (2008); Morin et al. (2008b). The decrease in cyclic variability toward later spectral types was also reported by Fuhrmeister et al. (2022) from a long-term monitoring campaign of activity indicators.

A word of caution is necessary regarding the magnetic field strength. For each star, we noticed that the ZDI model had limitations at reproducing the lobes of the Stokes V , owing to evident and

Figure 5.54: Evolution of the magnetic topology of all stars over 15-16 yr. The time series includes reconstructions from optical archival data with ESPaDOnS and Narval, as well as from near-infrared SPIRou data. The format of the plot is the same as Fig. 5.14.

unaccounted variability. Since the reconstructed field strength scales with the amplitude of the model fit, we emphasize that the values obtained in near-infrared are likely underestimates.

An additional information we could infer from the magnetic reconstructions is the helicity, which quantifies the linkage between poloidal and toroidal field lines and thus describes the complexity of the magnetic topology (Lund et al. 2020, 2021). For the Sun, Pipin et al. (2019) reported a temporal variation of the quantity correlated to the magnetic cycle. Indeed, helicity maxima and minima occur when the axis of symmetry of the poloidal and toroidal field components are aligned and orthogonal, respectively. The case of DS Leo is worth mentioning, as the poloidal axisymmetric energy fraction increases from 4% to 15%, whereas the toroidal axisymmetric fraction remains around 90% between the two epochs considered. Since both the total poloidal and toroidal magnetic energies account for a significant portion of the total energy in both epochs, the field is characterised by a presumably high level of helicity, i.e. more tangled fields. From the first epoch to the second, the helicity decreases as the poloidal field is slightly more aligned with the toroidal one. Analogous comments on the field linkage can be done for the other stars, but we have to consider that the toroidal energy fraction in most of these cases accounts for less than 5%. Therefore, although the alignment between poloidal and toroidal components may have evolved in time, the overall effect on helicity is likely negligible.

In collaboration with Dr. Lisa Lehmann, we applied a Principal Component Analysis on the median subtracted Stokes V profiles of AD Leo SPIRou time series (Lehmann & Donati 2022). Despite the PCA technique does not output quantitative information like ZDI, our analysis corroborated its efficiency at capturing the general evolution of the large-scale field, i.e. the decrease in axisymmetry of the dipolar configuration. For this reason, and along with the fact that it can be easily applied to many large data sets in a fast way, such PCA technique can be a resourceful tool to accompany spectropolarimetric campaigns and investigate the presence of magnetic evolution (and cycles, eventually) to first-order. In addition, this technique is not affected by imperfect modelling of LSD profile features that are not modulated at the stellar rotation period.

Conclusions and outlook

This thesis was centered on understanding stellar magnetic activity further, and how we can exploit its knowledge to inform observing strategies and time series analysis of exoplanet surveys, especially for the radial velocity method. Indeed, as long as precise mass (and bulk density) estimates and/or accurate planetary characterisation are sought, we have to necessarily deal with stellar activity to some extent. I tackled this from two distinct points of view, which are nevertheless intertwined: i) I investigated how the radial velocity content of a data set changes based on the spectral lines selected and how this correlates with brightness inhomogeneities on the stellar surface, and ii) I monitored the evolution of the large-scale magnetic field across 15 yr of observations, looking for long-term trends that may or may not resemble a solar-like magnetic cycle. Naturally, the output of this work is twofold because it feeds back on the exoplanet field and the quest of finding small, potentially habitable worlds, but also on stellar astrophysics, since we can observe dynamo-powered phenomena influencing the stellar magnetic field.

High-precision planetary mass measurements

The mass of a planet is a diagnostic of its nature, and it is a pivotal parameter because it allows us to assess the origin and the evolution of a planet. For instance, the capability of a planet to retain an atmosphere after formation depends primarily on its surface gravity, and ultimately its mass. Likewise, spectral retrievals of exoplanet atmospheres need to be informed about the planetary mass in order to discern details such as the presence of clouds and the existence of a primary, secondary or even a tertiary (life-related) atmosphere (Di Maio et al. 2023), which is relevant for space-based missions like *JWST* and *Ariel* as well as direct imaging campaigns. For these reasons, understanding planets as celestial objects is strictly tethered to our precision in estimating their masses. The radial velocity method has been the most prolific approach in this sense and it will probably be for the foreseeable future, even though transit time variations in compact, multi-planet systems or astrometric campaigns can also be used to infer planetary masses.

Achieving precise planetary mass estimates is even more important in light of the fleet of space-based missions that have been deployed (or that will be) to study exoplanets as one of their primary purposes. The inflow of thousands of exoplanet candidates from the collective power of photometric missions like *Kepler*, *TESS*, *CHEOPS*, and *PLATO* will need a corresponding radial velocity follow-up from the ground, in order to ensure an accurate characterisation of the newly-discovered objects. Doing so will give access to statistical studies of planetary bulk densities and their dependence on distinct factors like stellar age, mass, and composition, as well as the orbital separation of the planet.

At the moment, we are witnessing the era of extreme precision radial velocity (EPRV), with detections of planetary signals at the m s^{-1} level or below (Demangeon et al. 2021). Reaching this level of precision is an instrumental challenge (Fischer et al. 2016), and has been a substantial driver for the commissioning of new high-resolution ultra-precise spectrographs operating at optical wavelengths such as ESPRESSO (Pepe et al. 2021; Suárez Mascareño et al. 2020), EXPRESS (Petersburg et al. 2020), and NEID (Schwab et al. 2016). Indeed, a precision on the cm s^{-1} level is required to reliably detect Earth analogs around Sun-like stars. For M dwarfs, a bunch of Earth-like planets have been detected (Anglada-Escudé et al. 2016; Astudillo-Defru et al. 2017b,a; Robertson 2018; Zechmeister et al. 2019; Suárez Mascareño

et al. 2020), given the more favourable dynamics of the system for which the planetary signal is on the order of m s^{-1} . To reach this result, the community has only recently designed high-resolution, near-infrared spectrographs and spectropolarimeters such as SPIRou and its twin instrument SPIP (to be installed atop Pic du Midi at Telescope Bernard-Lyot, France), CARMENES, CRIRES+, and NIRPS, owing mostly to the fact that the emission energy distribution of low-mass M dwarfs peaks in the near-infrared.

Ever-improving instrumental precision is a double-edge sword for an indirect method like radial velocity, since we are also more sensitive to phenomena associated to stellar variability. This is where a collaborative framework between exoplanet hunters and stellar astrophysicists is needed (Wright & Sigurdsson 2019): to understand the contamination that the star induces, define new metrics to identify stellar activity and variability, find efficient ways to correct such contributions, and ultimately disentangle genuine planetary signatures. A valuable laboratory to carry out these tasks is the Sun, as its observations enable us to correlate RV signals with surface variability and magnetic activity proxies at a highly refined level. This should also be complemented by 3D simulations of the photosphere, for a comparative study on which activity proxy is best suited for diagnosing solar-like variability. In practice, this requires synergies between instrumentation, survey planning, follow-up strategies and development of data analysis techniques. Clearly, efforts in monitoring stars other than the Sun are still essential to obtain a full picture of stellar variability (e.g., Meunier et al. 2010; Haywood et al. 2020).

Switching from optical to near-infrared observations is already beneficial for RV searches around M dwarfs, as the stellar activity contribution is supposedly lower (Baroch et al. 2020), which has been an additional driver behind the choice of developing near-infrared instruments. However, the near-infrared is a relatively uncharted domain in this context, both in terms of activity proxies (e.g., Fuhrmeister et al. 2019; Cortes-Zuleta et al. 2023) and predominance of Zeeman broadening on the radial velocity estimate against a chromatic thermal contrast (Reiners et al. 2013). For this reason, during my Ph.D. project I analysed high-resolution spectropolarimetric data sets collected both in optical with ESPaDOnS and Narval, and in near-infrared with SPIRou. The well-studied optical measurements served as benchmarks to understand several of the features and results encountered in the near-infrared.

Line-by-line techniques have proven to be quite successful to obtain high-precision RV data sets (Dumusque 2018; Cretignier et al. 2020), exploiting the rich RV content in the spectrum itself rather than averaging information in RV time series, and reaching RV precision on the m s^{-1} level even for active M dwarfs (Artigau et al. 2022; Carmona et al. 2023, in press). What we are lacking at the moment is a firm understanding of *which lines* specifically are used to obtain such RV improvement and especially *why*, i.e. the physics behind their choice. Some of the questions that arise are: what properties do these lines have? Can their benefit be transferred across different spectral types? What do the “discarded” lines tell us about the sources of noise among which stellar magnetic activity?

The analyses and the filtering technique developed in the course of this thesis have the potential to shed more light on these aspects. Compared to the line-by-line approaches, my technique has a “lower resolution” because I inspect combinations of a certain number of lines instead of individual ones, but we can study the characteristics of the lines associated to the combinations that yield the best RV improvement. I showed that this can be done in a straightforward way by analysing the distribution of line parameters and, although there is a tendency to prefer deep, magnetically insensitive and short wavelength lines (at least in the near-infrared domain), the answer is not completely clear. An important confirmation of my work is the substantial RV improvement obtained using CO lines at $2.2 \mu\text{m}$, as already pointed out by Reiners et al. (2013). Despite the RV precision is around $20\text{--}30 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ for the active M dwarfs I studied, hence not at the same level of the line-by-line output, they could represent an initial step toward understanding the results of line-by-line approaches.

In this direction, I showed a preliminary analysis aimed at connecting specific line selections with the brightness image of a star. I employed Doppler Imaging to reconstruct such images using an atomic, molecular and atomic+molecular line mask, finding distinct surface inhomogeneities in each case. On one side, the validation of these results is conditional to the assessment of the noise level in our observations, which should also be complemented by a thorough analysis of alternative physical phenomena

that could mimic the presence of surface inhomogeneities, i.e. Zeeman splitting, for which we are particularly sensitive in near-infrared for magnetically active stars. On the other side, I will continue the analysis by refining the grid of masks with which to carry out the brightness reconstructions, investigating parametric and randomised selections, as well as specific chemical species like CO.

Magnetometry of low-mass stars

Advancements in understanding stellar activity are inexorably tethered to the characterisation of the star's magnetic field. Spectropolarimetry is an efficient observational technique for this purpose, since it relies on the Zeeman effect, i.e. the splitting of spectral lines in distinct components characterised by specific polarisation properties when an external magnetic field is applied. Exploiting the enhanced sensitivity to the Zeeman effect at near-infrared wavelengths, SPIRou is an excellent instrument to survey M dwarfs on both sides of the fully-convective interior threshold and characterise their magnetic field, ultimately providing tight observational constraints to dynamo theories.

Over the years, studies based on radiative transfer modelling of Zeeman broadening of individual spectral lines in unpolarised light (e.g., Kochukhov & Lavail 2017; Shulyak et al. 2017, 2019) and on tomographic inversion of time series of circularly polarised spectra via Zeeman-Doppler Imaging (e.g., Donati et al. 2008; Morin et al. 2008b, 2010) have set constraints on stellar magnetic field properties such as intensity, topology and temporal evolution. I analysed the latter aspect further, concatenating well-studied optical spectropolarimetric data collected with ESPaDOnS and Narval, and near-infrared SPIRou data obtained as part of the SPIRou Legacy Survey. With a baseline of approximately 15 yr, I presented an exciting diversity of long-term trends, some of which share similarities with the solar magnetic cycle and others featuring a more stable behaviour. We observed a tendency to manifest intrinsic stability for late-type stars with strong magnetic fields, while earlier-types showcased an evident evolution. Although these results bring new observational insights on the dynamo processes operating in stellar interiors with different conditions (i.e. either partly- or fully-convective), we cannot be tightly conclusive on whether the dichotomy of magnetic field topologies for fully-convective M dwarfs is due to magnetic cycles or dynamo bistability. For instance, the interior of both EV Lac and CN Leo is expected to be dominated by convection, but they clearly manifest two distinct temporal variations of the large-scale field. Therefore, is there a mass threshold below which bistability overcomes cyclic evolution? Is it related to the break point of the activity-rotation relation seen in X-ray for cool, M7-M9 dwarfs?

Predicting the cycle behaviour or when the polarity reversal may occur is not a trivial task. For a solar-like trend as the one exhibited by AD Leo, the axisymmetric level of the large-scale topology is a suitable proxy (Lehmann et al. 2021), but we recorded its change only in the most recent SPIRou observations. While less adequate, the longitudinal magnetic field can give a general direction of the long-term behaviour, but the observational gaps affecting our time series and the lack of clear minima or maxima in some cases prevent us from estimating a putative evolution time scale. When comparing our time series to the literature, we note some differences. For AD Leo, previous studies based on photometric observations reported either two co-existing timescales, i.e. 7 yr and 2 yr (Buccino et al. 2014), or an individual one of about 11 yr (Tuomi et al. 2018), which are both not compatible with the variations of B_l . Likewise, Suárez Mascareño et al. (2016) reported an activity cycle of 8.9 yr for CN Leo, which is longer than our B_l sine fluctuation of about 2.7 yr. For these two stars, campaigns dedicated to the long-term behaviour of chromospheric activity indexes did not record cyclic trends (Fuhrmeister et al. 2022). This is not somehow surprising considering that, even for Sun-like stars featuring regular chromospheric oscillations, there is no straightforward polarimetric counterpart (Boro Saikia et al. 2022). Other Sun-like stars instead manifest magnetic cycles and polarity reversals in phase with chromospheric cycles (Boro Saikia et al. 2016; Jeffers et al. 2017). Therefore, it is interesting to study these distinct time scales further, in order to understand what the different quantities are tracing.

Naturally, addressing these questions/considerations advocates for a continuous spectropolarimetric monitoring of these stars, as well as an expansion of the stellar parameter space over which these

phenomena are probed. This could be conducted in a collaborative manner as part of a multi-wavelength effort. Indeed, magnetic cycles and polarity reversals can be captured also by means of surveys at radio wavelengths, as outlined in [Route \(2016\)](#).

In this direction, and driven by the existence of coherent, low-frequency radio emission discovered recently with LOFAR ([Vedantham et al. 2020](#); [Callingham et al. 2020](#)), a fruitful coordination can be initiated between radio and spectropolarimetric observations. While the source mechanism has been in fact attributed to electron cyclotron maser instability, it is not obvious whether it is triggered by reconnection processes in the outer stellar magnetosphere ([Linsky et al. 1992](#); [Owocki et al. 2022](#)) or by means of star-planet sub-Alfvénic interactions ([Kavanagh et al. 2021, 2022](#)). Understanding which case leads to the observed radio emission could give access to a new independent method to detect exoplanets; if confirmed, it will be used to direct RV observational effort, especially around active M dwarfs for which all other techniques are limited. The magnetic field maps of M dwarfs reconstructed with Zeeman-Doppler Imaging are a necessary input in this context, as they allow an accurate modelling of the radio signatures and their interpretation.

Stellar activity and exoplanet atmospheric characterisation

Modelling the stellar environment in which exoplanets are embedded is an essential step to understand the evolution of star-planet interactions and requires a detail model of the stellar magnetic field. In fact, the high-energy output of a star correlates with its magnetic activity level, hence with spectropolarimetry we can actively participate in getting a better interpretation of the different features in exoplanet spectra. For instance the atmospheric chemistry is altered by near- and far-ultraviolet radiation via photodissociation of molecules such as H₂O and CO, while the upper regions of the atmosphere can be heated and inflated by means of photoionisation induced by extreme ultraviolet radiation. This, combined with the energetic particles composing the stellar wind, would ultimately lead to atmospheric escape ([Lammer et al. 2003](#)) and could jeopardise the planetary habitability. The situation is somehow worse for planets closer-in to the host star, as the extent of their habitable zone would inevitably be affected ([Vidotto et al. 2013](#)). The existence of a planetary magnetic field acting as a shield to deflect energetic particles is a well-studied phenomenon in the Solar System ([Zarka 1998](#); [Shkolnik & Llama 2018](#)), and present a more optimistic scenario in terms of finding potentially habitable planets around other stars. However, measuring planetary fields is not a straightforward task, especially for rocky planets, which makes it a very active research field ([Grießmeier 2015](#)).

Characterising the magnetic field of host stars and its activity features is also key for the success of transmission spectroscopy campaigns. With transmission spectroscopy, we aim at identifying the atmospheric composition of a transiting exoplanet, by measuring the wavelength-dependent radius as the planet crosses the stellar disk ([Seager & Sasselov 2000](#)). Surface inhomogeneities induced by magnetic activity hinder such goal: occulted and unocculted dark spots can result in a shallower and deeper transits, respectively ([Pont et al. 2013](#)), and the situation is reversed for bright regions like faculae and plages. These are manifestations of a more general problem named “transit light source effect” ([Rackham et al. 2018, 2019](#)), which stems from the approximation that the disk-integrated spectrum is the same as the light impinging on the planetary atmosphere. Instead, the planet is occulting only a portion of the stellar disk along the transit chord, which represents the actual light source of the transmission spectrum. Identifying and studying for these effects is of paramount importance for not only correcting planetary radius estimates from systematics, but also for interpreting the chemical signatures in transmission spectra of planetary atmospheres, and especially for M dwarfs. For instance, unocculted spots can lead to false positive of H₂O ([Rackham et al. 2018](#)). The ANDES instrument for E-ELT will be primarily designed for atmospheric characterisation and stellar activity studies, producing high-resolution spectra over a wavelength domain overlapping ESPaDOnS and SPIRou ([Maiolino et al. 2013](#)). In this sense, it is directly tied to the work presented here. Considering the impact of stellar activity, developing efficient stellar activity-filtering techniques is not central only for radial velocity, but transmission spectroscopy as well ([Cracchiolo et al. 2021](#); [Thompson et al. 2023](#)). Overall, this work finds evident

application in the preparation and optimisation of observing strategies of planetary atmospheres for missions like *JWST* and *Ariel*.

Long-term prospects for exoplanetology

From current research, to upcoming developments in ground-based observatories, to the launch of dedicated space-based missions, our knowledge on the nature and diversity of exoplanetary systems will continue to progress. The detection output of transit surveys undertaken by means of flagship space missions like *TESS* and *PLATO* (to be launched in 2026) is expected to reach a few tenths of thousands of exoplanets, each with their peculiar features to characterise. With a coordinated effort involving efficient radial velocity follow-up, the community will be able to populate the mass-radius diagram substantially, and obtain tighter constraints on the frequency of planets according to their mass. *Gaia* is expected to detect a large number of planets through astrometry, which is sensitive to planets at a few AU from their stars, adding a population of cold planets to our current catalogue. The *Nancy Grace Roman Space Telescope*, whose launch is planned for 2027, will include an exoplanet microlensing survey mapping a representative sample of the Galactic stellar population. This will allow the community to define the mass and orbital distance distribution for planets located beyond the snow line, as well as the mass function of free-floating planets, ultimately yielding an outstanding planetary census with which to validate planet formation models.

In terms of exoplanet atmospheres, *JWST* and *Ariel* going to revolutionize our understanding of exoplanets. *JWST* will carry out detailed observations of a specific sample of temperate super-Earth atmospheres and a larger sample of mini-Neptune atmospheres, with unprecedented sensitivity, searching for the presence of, e.g., water, carbon dioxide, and oxygen as well as building blocks of life in the Universe. *Ariel* will enable the statistical understanding of warm and hot exoplanets, as it will make a reconnaissance survey of approximately 1000 transiting exoplanets and a spectroscopic characterisation for most of them. The combination of such observations will allow the community to probe the variety of exoplanet atmospheres and establish trends of composition and cloud properties based on both planetary and stellar properties. Ultimately, this will feed back on our understanding of planetary formation and evolution.

With the advent of the next generation of large ground-based telescopes like E-ELT and GMT, whose scientific operations are expected to start in 2027 and 2025, respectively, we will then be able to follow-up and characterise the most promising targets close to Earth with direct imaging. Indeed, with the equipped adaptive optics systems, we will perform high-contrast coronagraphic imaging of a modest sample of warm giant planets, reaching a contrast level no better than 10^{-8} in near-infrared due to Earth's atmosphere. Finally, although this work will pave the way for the deep exploration of potentially habitable planets around low-mass, M dwarf in the solar neighborhood, spectral characterization of the reflected light from rocky planets will only be possible with the launch of flagship space-based laboratories like *Habex* and *LUVVOIR*.

Altogether, there are exciting discoveries coming in the future.

Conclusions et perspectives

Cette thèse était centrée sur une meilleure compréhension de l'activité magnétique stellaire et sur la façon dont nous pouvons exploiter cette connaissance pour informer les stratégies d'observation et l'analyse des séries temporelles des études d'exoplanètes, en particulier pour la méthode des vitesses radiales. En effet, tant que l'on cherche à obtenir des estimations précises de la masse (et de la densité apparente) et/ou une caractérisation précise des planètes, il faut nécessairement traiter de l'activité stellaire dans une certaine mesure. J'ai abordé cette question de deux points de vue distincts, mais néanmoins liés : i) j'ai étudié comment le contenu en vitesse radiale d'un ensemble de données change en fonction des raies spectrales sélectionnées et comment cela est corrélé avec les inhomogénéités de luminosité sur la surface stellaire, et ii) j'ai suivi l'évolution du champ magnétique à grande échelle sur 15 millions d'années d'observations, à la recherche de tendances à long terme qui peuvent ou non ressembler à un cycle magnétique de type solaire. Naturellement, le résultat de ce travail est double car il se répercute sur le domaine des exoplanètes et la recherche de petits mondes potentiellement habitables, mais aussi sur l'astrophysique stellaire, puisque nous pouvons observer des phénomènes dynamo influençant le champ magnétique stellaire.

Mesures de haute précision de la masse des planètes

La masse d'une planète conditionne sa nature, et c'est un paramètre central car il nous permet d'évaluer l'origine et l'évolution d'une planète. Par exemple, la capacité d'une planète à conserver une atmosphère après sa formation dépend principalement de sa gravité de surface et, en fin de compte, de sa masse. De même, les analyses spectrales de l'atmosphère des exoplanètes doivent être informées de la masse de la planète afin de discerner des détails tels que la présence de nuages et l'existence d'une atmosphère primaire ou secondaire (Di Maio et al. 2023), ce qui est important pour les missions spatiales telles que *JWST* et *Ariel*, ainsi que pour les campagnes d'imagerie directe. Pour ces raisons, la compréhension des planètes en tant qu'objets célestes est strictement liée à notre précision dans l'estimation de leur masse. La méthode des vitesses radiales a été l'approche la plus prolifique en ce sens et le restera probablement dans un avenir proche, même si les variations du temps de transit dans les systèmes compacts et multiplanétaires ou les campagnes astrométriques peuvent également être utilisées pour déduire les masses planétaires.

Il est d'autant plus important d'obtenir des estimations précises de la masse des planètes que des missions spatiales ont été déployées (ou le seront) pour étudier les exoplanètes, ce qui est l'un de leurs principaux objectifs. L'afflux de milliers de candidats exoplanètes provenant de la puissance collective des missions photométriques telles que *Kepler*, *TESS*, *CHEOPS*, et *PLATO* nécessitera un suivi correspondant de la vitesse radiale depuis le sol, afin d'assurer une caractérisation précise des objets nouvellement découverts. Cela permettra d'accéder à des études statistiques des densités planétaires et de leur dépendance vis-à-vis de facteurs distincts tels que l'âge, la masse et la composition stellaires, ainsi que la séparation orbitale de la planète.

Nous assistons actuellement à l'ère de la vitesse radiale d'extrême précision, avec des détections de signaux planétaires au niveau m s^{-1} ou en dessous (Demangeon et al. 2021). Atteindre ce niveau de précision est un défi instrumental (Fischer et al. 2016), et a été un moteur important pour la mise en service de nouveaux spectrographes ultra-précis à haute résolution fonctionnant à des longueurs

d'onde optiques, tels que ESPRESSO (Pepe et al. 2021; Suárez Mascareño et al. 2020), EXPRESS (Petersburg et al. 2020), et NEID (Schwab et al. 2016). En effet, une précision de l'ordre de cm s^{-1} est nécessaire pour détecter de manière fiable des analogues de la Terre autour d'étoiles semblables au Soleil. Pour les naines M, plusieurs planètes semblables à la Terre ont été détectées (Anglada-Escudé et al. 2016; Astudillo-Defru et al. 2017b,a; Robertson 2018; Zechmeister et al. 2019; Suárez Mascareño et al. 2020), compte tenu de la dynamique plus favorable du système pour lequel le signal planétaire est de l'ordre du m s^{-1} . Pour parvenir à ce résultat, la communauté n'a conçu que récemment des spectrographes et des spectropolarimètres à haute résolution dans le proche infrarouge, tels que SPIRou et son instrument jumeau SPIP (qui sera installé au sommet du Pic du Midi au télescope Bernard-Lyot, France), CARMENES, CRIRES+ et NIRPS, principalement en raison du fait que la distribution de l'énergie d'émission des naines M de faible masse atteint son maximum dans le proche infrarouge.

L'amélioration constante de la précision instrumentale est une arme à double tranchant pour une méthode indirecte comme la vitesse radiale, puisque nous sommes également plus sensibles aux phénomènes associés à la variabilité stellaire. C'est ici qu'un cadre de collaboration entre les chasseurs d'exoplanètes et les astrophysiciens stellaires est nécessaire (Wright & Sigurdsson 2019) : pour comprendre la contamination induite par l'étoile, définir de nouvelles métriques pour identifier l'activité et la variabilité stellaires, trouver des moyens efficaces pour corriger ces contributions, et finalement démêler les signatures planétaires authentiques. Le Soleil est un laboratoire précieux pour mener à bien ces tâches, car ses observations nous permettent de corrélérer les signaux VR avec la variabilité de surface et les indicateurs de l'activité magnétique à un niveau très raffiné. Cela devrait également être complété par des simulations en 3D de la photosphère, pour une étude comparative de l'indicateur d'activité le mieux adapté pour diagnostiquer la variabilité de type solaire. En pratique, cela nécessite des synergies entre l'instrumentation, la planification des relevés, les stratégies de suivi et le développement de techniques d'analyse des données. Il est clair que les efforts de surveillance des étoiles autres que le Soleil restent essentiels pour obtenir une image complète de la variabilité stellaire.

Le passage des observations optiques aux observations dans le proche infrarouge est déjà bénéfique pour les recherches VR autour des naines M, car la contribution de l'activité stellaire est supposée plus faible (Baroch et al. 2020), ce qui a été un moteur supplémentaire pour le choix de développer des instruments dans le proche infrarouge. Cependant, le proche infrarouge est un domaine relativement inexploité dans ce contexte, à la fois en termes d'indicateurs d'activité (e.g., Fuhrmeister et al. 2019; Cortes-Zuleta et al. 2023) et de prédominance de l'élargissement Zeeman sur l'estimation de la vitesse radiale par rapport à un contraste thermique chromatique (Reiners et al. 2013). C'est pourquoi, au cours de mon projet de doctorat, j'ai analysé des ensembles de données spectropolarimétriques à haute résolution recueillies à la fois en optique avec ESPaDOnS et Narval, et dans le proche infrarouge avec SPIRou. Les mesures optiques bien étudiées ont servi de référence pour comprendre plusieurs des caractéristiques et des résultats rencontrés dans le proche infrarouge.

Les techniques raie par raie se sont avérées très efficaces pour obtenir des ensembles de données VR de haute précision (Dumusque 2018; Cretignier et al. 2020), en exploitant le riche contenu VR dans le spectre lui-même plutôt que l'information intégrée dans les séries temporelles VR, et en atteignant une précision VR au niveau du m s^{-1} même pour les naines M actives (Artigau et al. 2022 ; Carmona et al. 2023, accepté). Ce qui nous manque pour l'instant, c'est une bonne compréhension de *quelles lignes* sont spécifiquement utilisées pour obtenir une telle amélioration de la VR et surtout *pourquoi*, c'est-à-dire la physique qui sous-tend leur choix. Certaines des questions qui se posent sont les suivantes : quelles sont les propriétés de ces raies ? Leurs avantages peuvent-ils être transférés dans différents types de spectres ? Qu'est-ce que les raies "rejetées" nous apprennent sur les sources de bruit, parmi lesquelles l'activité magnétique stellaire ?

Les analyses et la technique de filtrage développées au cours de cette thèse ont le potentiel d'éclairer davantage ces aspects. Par rapport aux approches raie par raie, ma technique a une "résolution plus faible" parce que j'inspecte des combinaisons d'un certain nombre de lignes au lieu de lignes individuelles, mais nous pouvons étudier les caractéristiques des raies associées aux combinaisons qui donnent la meilleure amélioration de la VR. J'ai montré que cela pouvait être fait de manière simple en analysant

la distribution des paramètres des raies et, bien qu'il y ait une tendance à préférer les raies profondes, insensibles au magnétisme et de courte longueur d'onde (au moins dans le domaine du proche infrarouge), la réponse n'est pas tout à fait claire. Une confirmation importante de mon travail est l'amélioration substantielle de la VR obtenue en utilisant les raies de CO à $2,2 \mu\text{m}$, comme l'a déjà souligné [Reiners et al. \(2013\)](#). Bien que la précision de la VR soit d'environ 20 à $30 \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ pour les naines M d actives que j'ai étudiées, donc pas au même niveau que la sortie raie par raie, elles pourraient représenter une première étape vers la compréhension des sélections des approches raie par raie.

Dans cette direction, j'ai montré une analyse préliminaire visant à relier des sélections de lignes spécifiques à l'image de luminosité d'une étoile. J'ai utilisé l'imagerie Doppler pour reconstruire de telles images en utilisant un masque de lignes atomiques, moléculaires et atomiques+moléculaires, et j'ai trouvé des inhomogénéités de surface distinctes dans chaque cas. D'une part, la validation de ces résultats est conditionnée par l'évaluation du niveau de bruit dans nos observations, qui devrait également être complétée par une analyse approfondie des phénomènes physiques alternatifs qui pourraient imiter la présence d'inhomogénéités de surface, par exemple le dédoublement Zeeman, pour lequel nous sommes particulièrement sensibles dans l'infrarouge proche pour les étoiles magnétiquement actives. D'autre part, je poursuivrai l'analyse en affinant la grille des masques avec lesquels nous effectuons les reconstructions de luminosité, en étudiant les sélections paramétriques et aléatoires, ainsi que des espèces chimiques spécifiques comme le CO.

Magnétométrie des étoiles de faible masse

Les progrès dans la compréhension de l'activité stellaire sont inexorablement liés à la caractérisation du champ magnétique de l'étoile. La spectropolarimétrie est une technique d'observation efficace à cette fin, puisqu'elle repose sur l'effet Zeeman, c'est-à-dire la division des raies spectrales en composantes distinctes caractérisées par des propriétés de polarisation spécifiques lorsqu'un champ magnétique externe est appliqué. En exploitant la sensibilité accrue à l'effet Zeeman dans les longueurs d'onde du proche infrarouge, SPIRou est un excellent instrument pour étudier les naines M de part et d'autre du seuil intérieur entièrement convectif et pour caractériser leur champ magnétique, ce qui, en fin de compte, apporte des contraintes observationnelles strictes aux théories dynamo.

Au fil des ans, des études basées sur la modélisation du transfert radiatif de l'élargissement Zeeman des raies spectrales individuelles dans la lumière non polarisée ont été réalisées (e.g., [Kochukhov & Lavail 2017](#); [Shulyak et al. 2017, 2019](#)) et sur l'inversion tomographique de séries temporelles de spectres polarisés circulairement via l'imagerie Zeeman-Doppler (e.g., [Donati et al. 2008](#); [Morin et al. 2008b, 2010](#)) ont établi des contraintes sur les propriétés des champs magnétiques stellaires telles que leur force, leur topologie et leur évolution temporelle. J'ai analysé ce dernier aspect plus en détail, en concaténant des données spectropolarimétriques optiques bien étudiées collectées avec ESPaDOnS et Narval, et des données SPIRou dans le proche infrarouge obtenues dans le cadre du SPIRou Legacy Survey. Avec une base de référence d'environ 15 ans, j'ai mis en évidence une diversité passionnante de tendances à long terme, dont certaines présentent des similitudes avec le cycle magnétique solaire et d'autres un comportement plus stable. Nous avons observé une tendance à manifester une stabilité intrinsèque pour les étoiles de type tardif avec des champs magnétiques forts, tandis que les types plus précoces ont montré une évolution évidente. Bien que ces résultats apportent de nouvelles contraintes sur les processus dynamo opérant dans les intérieurs stellaires avec des conditions différentes (c'est-à-dire partiellement ou totalement convectives), nous ne pouvons pas être très concluants sur la question de savoir si la dichotomie des topologies de champ magnétique pour les naines M totalement convectives est due aux cycles magnétiques ou à la bistabilité de la dynamo. Par exemple, l'intérieur de EV Lac et de CN Leo devrait être dominé par la convection, mais ils manifestent clairement deux variations temporelles distinctes du champ à grande échelle. Par conséquent, existe-t-il un seuil de masse en dessous duquel la stabilité l'emporte sur l'évolution cyclique? Est-elle liée au point de rupture de la relation activité-rotation observée en rayons X pour les naines froides M7-M9 ?

Prévoir le comportement du cycle ou le moment où l'inversion de polarité peut se produire n'est

pas une tâche triviale. Pour une tendance de type solaire comme celle présentée par AD Leo, le niveau d'axisymétrie de la topologie à grande échelle est un indicateur approprié (Lehmann et al. 2021), mais nous n'avons enregistré son changement que dans les observations SPIRou les plus récentes. Bien que moins adéquat, le champ magnétique longitudinal peut donner une orientation générale du comportement à long terme, mais les lacunes observationnelles affectant nos séries temporelles et l'absence de minima ou de maxima clairs dans certains cas nous empêchent d'estimer une échelle temporelle d'évolution putative. En comparant nos séries temporelles à la littérature, nous notons quelques différences. Pour AD Leo, des études antérieures basées sur des observations photométriques ont rapporté soit deux échelles de temps coexistantes, à savoir ~ 7 ans et ~ 2 ans (Buccino et al. 2014), soit une échelle individuelle d'environ 11 ans (Tuomi et al. 2018), qui ne sont toutes deux pas compatibles avec les variations de B_l . De même, Suárez Mascareño et al. (2016) a rapporté un cycle d'activité de 8-9 ans pour CN Leo, qui est plus long que notre fluctuation sinusoïdale de B_l d'environ 2,7 ans. Pour ces deux étoiles, les campagnes consacrées au comportement à long terme des indices d'activité chromosphérique n'ont pas enregistré de tendances cycliques (Fuhrmeister et al. 2022). Cela n'est pas vraiment surprenant si l'on considère que, même pour les étoiles semblables au Soleil qui présentent des oscillations chromosphériques régulières, il n'existe pas de contrepartie polarimétrique directe (Boro Saikia et al. 2022). D'autres étoiles semblables au Soleil manifestent au contraire des cycles magnétiques et des inversions de polarité en phase avec les cycles chromosphériques (Boro Saikia et al. 2016; Jeffers et al. 2017). Il est donc intéressant d'étudier plus avant ces échelles de temps distinctes, afin de comprendre ce que les différentes quantités tracent.

Naturellement, pour répondre à ces questions/considérations, il faut un suivi spectropolarimétrique continu de ces étoiles, ainsi qu'un élargissement de l'espace des paramètres stellaires sur lequel ces phénomènes sont sondés. Ces travaux pourraient être menés en collaboration dans le cadre d'un effort portant sur plusieurs longueurs d'onde. En effet, les cycles magnétiques et les inversions de polarité peuvent également être détecté au moyen d'études aux longueurs d'onde radio, comme indiqué dans Route (2016).

Dans cette direction, et poussé par l'existence d'une émission radio cohérente à basse fréquence découverte récemment avec LOFAR (Vedantham et al. 2020; Callingham et al. 2020), une coordination fructueuse peut être initiée entre les observations radio et spectropolarimétriques. Bien que le mécanisme de la source ait été attribué à l'instabilité du maser cyclotronique électronique, il n'est pas évident de savoir s'il est déclenché par des processus de reconnexion dans la magnétosphère stellaire externe (Linsky et al. 1992; Owocki et al. 2022) ou par le biais d'interactions sous-alphabétiques étoile-planète (Kavanagh et al. 2021, 2022). Comprendre quel cas conduit à l'émission radio observée pourrait donner accès à une nouvelle méthode indépendante pour détecter les exoplanètes ; si elle est confirmée, elle sera utilisée pour orienter l'effort d'observation de la VR, en particulier autour des naines M actives pour lesquelles toutes les autres techniques sont limitées. Les cartes du champ magnétique des naines M reconstruites avec l'imagerie Zeeman-Doppler sont nécessaires dans ce contexte, car elles permettent une modélisation précise des signatures radio et leur interprétation.

Activité stellaire et caractérisation atmosphérique des exoplanètes

La modélisation de l'environnement stellaire dans lequel les exoplanètes sont intégrées est une étape essentielle pour comprendre l'évolution des interactions étoile-planète et nécessite un modèle détaillé du champ magnétique stellaire. En fait, la rayonnement de haute énergie d'une étoile est en corrélation avec son niveau d'activité magnétique. Grâce à la spectropolarimétrie, nous pouvons donc participer activement à une meilleure interprétation des différentes caractéristiques des spectres des exoplanètes. Par exemple, la chimie atmosphérique est modifiée par le rayonnement ultraviolet proche et lointain via la photodissociation de molécules telles que H_2O et CO , tandis que les régions supérieures de l'atmosphère peuvent être chauffées et dilatées au moyen de la photoionisation induite par le rayonnement ultraviolet extrême. Ces phénomènes, combinés aux particules énergétiques composant le vent stellaire, conduiraient finalement à un échappement atmosphérique (Lammer et al. 2003) et pourraient

mettre en péril l’habitabilité de la planète. La situation est encore pire pour les planètes plus proches de l’étoile hôte, car l’étendue de leur zone habitable serait inévitablement affectée (Vidotto et al. 2013). L’existence d’un champ magnétique planétaire agissant comme un bouclier pour dévier les particules énergétiques est un phénomène bien étudié dans le système solaire (Zarka 1998; Shkolnik & Llama 2018), et présente un scénario plus optimiste en termes de découverte de planètes potentiellement habitables autour d’autres étoiles. Cependant, la mesure des champs planétaires n’est pas une tâche simple, en particulier pour les planètes rocheuses, ce qui en fait un domaine de recherche très actif (Grießmeier 2015). Les résultats de notre travail seront finalement pris en compte dans les théories de formation des planètes et les études de caractérisation de l’atmosphère.

La caractérisation du champ magnétique des étoiles hôtes et de ses caractéristiques d’activité est également essentielle au succès des campagnes de spectroscopie en transmission. Avec la spectroscopie en transmission, nous cherchons à identifier la composition atmosphérique d’une exoplanète en transit, en mesurant le rayon dépendant de la longueur d’onde lorsque la planète traverse le disque stellaire (Seager & Sasselov 2000). Les inhomogénéités de surface induites par l’activité magnétique empêchent d’atteindre cet objectif : les taches sombres occultées et non occultées peuvent donner lieu à des transits moins profonds et plus profonds, respectivement (Pont et al. 2013), et la situation est inversée pour les régions brillantes comme les facules et les plages. Ce sont des manifestations d’un problème plus général appelé ”effet de source lumineuse de transit” (Rackham et al. 2018, 2019), qui découle de l’approximation selon laquelle le spectre intégré au disque est le même que la lumière qui frappe l’atmosphère planétaire. Au contraire, la planète n’occulte qu’une partie du disque stellaire le long de la corde de transit, qui représente la source lumineuse réelle du spectre de transmission. L’identification et l’étude de ces effets sont d’une importance capitale non seulement pour corriger les estimations du rayon planétaire à partir des systématiques, mais aussi pour interpréter les signatures chimiques dans les spectres de transmission des atmosphères planétaires, et en particulier pour les naines M d. Par exemple, les taches non occultées peuvent conduire à des faux positifs de H₂O (Rackham et al. 2018). L’instrument ANDES pour l’E-ELT sera principalement conçu pour la caractérisation de l’atmosphère et les études de l’activité stellaire, produisant des spectres à haute résolution sur un domaine de longueur d’onde qui couvre celle de ESPaDOnS et SPIRou (Maiolino et al. 2013). En ce sens, il est directement lié au travail présenté dans cette thèse. Pour ces raisons, le développement de techniques efficaces de filtrage de l’activité stellaire n’est pas seulement central pour la vitesse radiale, mais aussi pour la spectroscopie de transmission (Cracchiolo et al. 2021; Thompson et al. 2023). Dans l’ensemble, ce travail trouve une application évidente dans la préparation et l’optimisation des stratégies d’observation des atmosphères planétaires pour des missions telles que *JWST* et *Ariel*.

Perspectives à long terme pour l’exoplanétologie

De la recherche actuelle au lancement de missions spatiales spécialisées, en passant par les développements à venir dans les observatoires terrestres, nos connaissances sur la nature et la diversité des systèmes exoplanétaires vont continuer à progresser. Les résultats des relevés de transit effectués par des missions spatiales phares telles que *TESS* et *PLATO* (qui seront lancées en 2026) devraient permettre de détecter quelques dizaines de milliers d’exoplanètes, chacune présentant des caractéristiques particulières à caractériser. Grâce à un effort coordonné impliquant un suivi efficace des vitesses radiales, la communauté sera en mesure de peupler considérablement le diagramme masse-rayon et d’obtenir des contraintes plus strictes sur la fréquence des planètes en fonction de leur masse. Le télescope spatial Nancy Grace Roman, dont le lancement est prévu pour 2027, comprendra une étude de microlentille d’exoplanètes cartographiant un échantillon représentatif de la population stellaire galactique. Cela permettra à la communauté de définir la distribution de la masse et de la distance orbitale des planètes situées au-delà de la limite des glaces, ainsi que la fonction de masse des planètes flottant librement, ce qui aboutira à un recensement planétaire exceptionnel permettant de valider les modèles de formation des planètes.

En ce qui concerne les atmosphères des exoplanètes, *JWST* et *Ariel* vont révolutionner notre

compréhension des exoplanètes. *JWST* effectuera des observations détaillées d'un échantillon spécifique d'atmosphères de super-Terres tempérées et d'un échantillon plus large d'atmosphères de mini-Neptunes, avec une sensibilité sans précédent, à la recherche de la présence, par exemple, d'eau, de dioxyde de carbone et d'oxygène, ainsi que des éléments constitutifs de la vie dans l'Univers. *Ariel* permettra une compréhension statistique des exoplanètes chaudes et tièdes, puisqu'il effectuera une étude de reconnaissance d'environ 1000 exoplanètes en transit et une caractérisation spectroscopique de la plupart d'entre elles. La combinaison de ces observations permettra à la communauté de sonder la variété des atmosphères des exoplanètes et d'établir les tendances de la composition et des propriétés des nuages en fonction des propriétés planétaires et stellaires. En fin de compte, cela nous permettra de mieux comprendre la formation et l'évolution des planètes.

Avec l'arrivée de la prochaine génération de grands télescopes terrestres tels que l'E-ELT et le GMT, dont les opérations scientifiques devraient débiter respectivement en 2027 et 2025, nous serons alors en mesure de suivre et de caractériser les cibles les plus prometteuses proches de la Terre grâce à l'imagerie directe. En effet, avec les systèmes d'optique adaptative équipés, nous réaliserons une imagerie coronographique à fort contraste d'un échantillon modeste de planètes géantes chaudes, atteignant un niveau de contraste ne dépassant pas 10^{-8} dans le proche infrarouge en raison de l'atmosphère de la Terre. Enfin, bien que ces travaux ouvrent la voie à l'exploration approfondie de planètes potentiellement habitables autour de planètes de masse faible, naines M dans le voisinage solaire, la caractérisation spectrale de la lumière réfléchiée par les planètes rocheuses ne sera possible qu'avec le lancement de laboratoires spatiaux phares tels que *Habex* et *LUVVOIR*.

Dans l'ensemble, l'avenir nous réserve des découvertes passionnantes.

Appendix A

Zeeman-Doppler Imaging

In this appendix, I outline the principles of Zeeman-Doppler Imaging, which has been used extensively for the thesis project. I used the ZDPY code developed by [Folsom et al. \(2018\)](#), which represents the python translation of the code used in [Donati et al. \(2006\)](#). The code reconstructs a brightness and/or magnetic map of a star from a time series of Stokes I and/or V profiles. I did not analysed observations of linear polarisation, hence we only concentrate on circular polarisation. The map resulting from the inversion process is the one that best matches the data, while featuring the lowest information content ([Skilling & Bryan 1984](#)).

A.1 Forward problem

From a brightness or magnetic field image, we can synthesize a time series of associated line profiles with the so-called “forward problem”. This is expressed in matrix form as

$$\mathbf{D} = \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{M}) + \varepsilon, \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where \mathbf{D} is the vector (time series) of line profiles, \mathbf{M} is the image, \mathbf{R} is the response function, and ε is gaussian noise. The response function contains the derivatives of Stokes I and V with respect the parameters we have to fit, i.e. brightness or magnetic coefficients (see Eq. A.2-A.4), depending on whether we perform Doppler or Zeeman-Doppler Imaging.

A star is simulated as a number of surface cells with equal area arranged in latitude rings and viewed under a user-defined input inclination (see Fig. A.1). Each cell is located at (colatitude, longitude)=(θ_i, φ_i) and encapsulates a value of brightness relative to a quiet, immaculate photosphere. The cells are also associated to a magnetic field vector expressed in spherical coordinates, i.e. radial (B_r), azimuthal (B_θ) and meridional (B_φ), which are described via spherical harmonics formalism ([Donati et al. 2006](#); [Vidotto 2016](#))

$$B_r(\theta, \varphi) = \sum_{l=0}^{l_{\max}} \sum_{m=0}^l \Re [\alpha_{lm} Y_{lm}(\theta, \varphi)], \quad (\text{A.2})$$

$$B_\theta(\theta, \varphi) = - \sum_{l=0}^{l_{\max}} \sum_{m=0}^l \Re [\beta_{lm} Z_{lm}(\theta, \varphi) + \gamma_{lm} X_{lm}(\theta, \varphi)], \quad (\text{A.3})$$

$$B_\varphi(\theta, \varphi) = - \sum_{l=0}^{l_{\max}} \sum_{m=0}^l \Re [\beta_{lm} X_{lm}(\theta, \varphi) - \gamma_{lm} Z_{lm}(\theta, \varphi)], \quad (\text{A.4})$$

Figure A.1: Sketch depicting the numerical implementation of tomographic reconstruction of Zeeman-Doppler Imaging. The number of phases is equivalent to the number of observations examined, and the number of iterations indicates when the code has converged, i.e. when the χ^2 and entropy gradients are sufficiently anti-parallel (see Sec A.2).

where

$$Y_{lm} = c_{lm} P_{lm}(\cos \theta) e^{im\varphi}, \quad (\text{A.5})$$

$$X_{lm} = \frac{c_{lm}}{l+1} \frac{im}{\sin \theta} P_{lm}(\cos \theta) e^{im\varphi}, \quad (\text{A.6})$$

$$Z_{lm} = \frac{c_{lm}}{l+1} \frac{\partial P_{lm}}{\partial \theta} e^{im\varphi}, \quad (\text{A.7})$$

and

$$c_{lm} = \sqrt{\frac{2l+1}{4\pi} \frac{(l-m)!}{(l+m)!}}, \quad (\text{A.8})$$

$P_{lm}(\cos \theta)$ is the Legendre polynomial of degree l and order m , and l_{\max} is the maximum degree l over which the decomposition is considered. The global magnetic field is expressed as the sum of a poloidal and toroidal component $\vec{B} = \vec{B}_{\text{pol}}(r, \theta, \varphi) + \vec{B}_{\text{tor}}(0, \theta, \varphi)$. The coefficients α_{lm} , β_{lm} , and γ_{lm} are complex numbers used to describe the radial poloidal, tangential poloidal, and toroidal field, respectively.

A local line model for Stokes I and V is assigned to each cell. When weak-field approximation is assumed (see Sec.4.1.2), a Voigt profile and its derivative are used for Stokes I and V , respectively, using the numerical prescription of Humlíček (1982). A more general model is necessary when near-infrared observations of stars with intense magnetic fields are dealt with, since they are more susceptible to distortions and broadening due to an enhanced Zeeman effect, as described in Sec. 4.1.1. In addition, M dwarfs have been reported to manifest fields on the order of the kG (Shulyak et al. 2017, 2019), hence Zeeman patterns in individual lines are more likely to be visible. I have implemented the Unno-Rachkovsky's solutions to polarised radiative transfer equations in a Milne-Eddington atmosphere (Unno 1956; Rachkovsky 1967; Landi Degl'Innocenti & Landolfi 2004) in ZDIPY and incorporated

the filling factor formalism outlined by [Morin et al. \(2008b\)](#). Formally, we have

$$I = f_I \cdot I_{\text{UR}}(v_B) + (1 - f_I) \cdot I_q, \quad (\text{A.9})$$

$$V = f_V \cdot V_{\text{UR}}(v_B), \quad (\text{A.10})$$

$$v_B = 4.67 \cdot 10^{-12} \cdot g_{\text{eff}} \cdot \frac{\lambda_0^2}{\Delta \lambda_D} \cdot \frac{B}{f_V}, \quad (\text{A.11})$$

where $\Delta \lambda_D$ is the Doppler width in wavelength units and I_q is the unpolarised light profile for the quiet photosphere ($B = 0$).

In practice, the filling factors f_I and f_V are assumed constant over the stellar grid, and represent the fraction of each cell covered by general magnetic regions and magnetic regions inducing net circular polarisation, respectively. Using two filling factors reflects the fact that Stokes I and V have different sensitivities to magnetic fields and cancellation effects (see Sec. 4.2.2). This way, the large-scale magnetic field does not possess a global, monolithic structure anymore but features small-scale structures (due to, e.g., convection and turbulence) with strong field and distributed according to a large-scale geometry. In terms of modelling, including f_V enables the code to reproduce the amplitude of Stokes V (which scales with the magnetic field B) and the splitting at zero-crossing point (scaling with B/f_V).

The Unno-Rachkovsky's solutions are given by

$$I_{\text{UR}} = \left(1 + \frac{\beta \mu}{\Delta} [\eta_I(\eta_I^2 + \rho_Q^2 + \rho_U^2 + \rho_V^2)] \right) \cdot \frac{1}{1 + \beta \mu} \quad (\text{A.12})$$

$$Q_{\text{UR}} = \left(-\frac{\beta \mu}{\Delta} [\eta_I^2 \eta_Q + \eta_I(\eta_V \rho_U - \eta_U \rho_V) + \rho_Q(\eta_Q \rho_Q + \eta_U \rho_U + \eta_V \rho_V)] \right) \cdot \frac{1}{1 + \beta \mu}, \quad (\text{A.13})$$

$$U_{\text{UR}} = \left(-\frac{\beta \mu}{\Delta} [\eta_I^2 \eta_U + \eta_I(\eta_Q \rho_V - \eta_V \rho_Q) + \rho_U(\eta_Q \rho_Q + \eta_U \rho_U + \eta_V \rho_V)] \right) \cdot \frac{1}{1 + \beta \mu}, \quad (\text{A.14})$$

$$V_{\text{UR}} = \left(-\frac{\beta \mu}{\Delta} [\eta_I^2 \eta_V + \eta_I(\eta_U \rho_Q - \eta_Q \rho_U) + \rho_V(\eta_Q \rho_Q + \eta_U \rho_U + \eta_V \rho_V)] \right) \cdot \frac{1}{1 + \beta \mu}, \quad (\text{A.15})$$

$$\Delta = \eta_I^2 [\eta_I^2 - \eta_Q^2 - \eta_U^2 - \eta_V^2 + \rho_Q^2 + \rho_U^2 + \rho_V^2] - (\eta_Q \rho_Q + \eta_U \rho_U + \eta_V \rho_V)^2, \quad (\text{A.16})$$

where β is the ratio of the linear and constant term in the Planck source function, μ is the limb darkening angle, and the absorption/dispersion coefficients are given by

$$\eta_I = 1 + \frac{\eta_0}{2} \left[\phi_p \sin^2 \theta + \frac{\phi_b + \phi_r}{2} (1 + \cos^2 \theta) \right], \quad (\text{A.17})$$

$$\eta_Q = \frac{\eta_0}{2} \left[\phi_p - \frac{\phi_b + \phi_r}{2} \right] \sin^2 \theta \cos 2\chi, \quad (\text{A.18})$$

$$\eta_U = \frac{\eta_0}{2} \left[\phi_p - \frac{\phi_b + \phi_r}{2} \right] \sin^2 \theta \sin 2\chi, \quad (\text{A.19})$$

$$\eta_V = \frac{\eta_0}{2} [\phi_r - \phi_b] \cos \theta, \quad (\text{A.20})$$

$$\rho_Q = \frac{\eta_0}{2} \left[\psi_p - \frac{\psi_b + \psi_r}{2} \right] \sin^2 \theta \cos 2\chi, \quad (\text{A.21})$$

$$\rho_U = \frac{\eta_0}{2} \left[\psi_p - \frac{\psi_b + \psi_r}{2} \right] \sin^2 \theta \sin 2\chi, \quad (\text{A.22})$$

$$\rho_V = \frac{\eta_0}{2} [\psi_r - \psi_b] \cos \theta \quad (\text{A.23})$$

where χ is the angle between the magnetic field vector and a reference direction in a plane orthogonal to the line of sight. This is used for linear polarisation, as circular polarisation is not affected by differences

in χ . In turn, the absorption/dispersion profiles

$$\phi_p = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{1}{\Delta\nu_D} H(v - v_M, a) \quad (\text{A.24})$$

$$\phi_b = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{1}{\Delta\nu_D} H(v - v_M + v_B, a) \quad (\text{A.25})$$

$$\phi_r = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{1}{\Delta\nu_D} H(v - v_M - v_B, a) \quad (\text{A.26})$$

$$\psi_p = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{1}{\Delta\nu_D} L(v - v_M, a) \quad (\text{A.27})$$

$$\psi_b = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{1}{\Delta\nu_D} L(v - v_M + v_B, a) \quad (\text{A.28})$$

$$\psi_r = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{1}{\Delta\nu_D} L(v - v_M - v_B, a) \quad (\text{A.29})$$

$$(\text{A.30})$$

where the subscripts p, b, r correspond to the unshifted, blueshifted and redshifted components of Zeeman splitting (see Sec. 4.1.1). Then, $\Delta\nu_D$ is the Doppler width in frequency units, v_M is the radial velocity, a is the damping constant, and the absorption (H) and dispersion (L) functions are given by

$$H(v, a) = \frac{a}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-y^2} \frac{1}{(v - y)^2 + a^2} dy \quad (\text{A.31})$$

$$L(v, a) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-y^2} \frac{v - y}{(v - y)^2 + a^2} dy \quad (\text{A.32})$$

From a coding point of view, computing the integrals in Eq. A.31-A.32 is the most time consuming step. While it is a simple operation, this has to be performed for each point of the velocity array v , two times for $v, v + v_B$, and $v - v_B$, for both profiles and derivatives. Indeed, contrarily to weak-field approximation, the response function is not constant, but the derivatives contained within must be updated at every ZDI iteration (Folsom et al. 2018). The integrations are repeated for all observations for a number of ZDI iterations until convergence, leading to a large multiplicative factor. To perform ZDI in a reasonable amount of time, I made extensive use of the NUMPY (van der Walt et al. 2011) and SCIPY (Virtanen et al. 2020) packages, and parallelised the code with respect to the observations by means of the MULTIPROCESSING package. This way, the computation time scale is on the order of a few minutes for a grid of 100-200 cells, with $v_{\text{eq}} \sin(i)$ on the order of 2-3 km s⁻¹, l_{max} up to 20 and about 60 rotational phases. I also tested parallelisations over the number of grid cells or the number of points constituting the local Stokes profiles for each cell, but the corresponding speed-up was not as efficient. Tests with Unno-Rachkovsky solutions implemented in ZDPY were performed with synthetic data and real observations. In the latter case, the output maps are compatible with those in the literature (Morin et al. 2008a,b). Some of the tests are reported in Sec. A.3.

The local Stokes I and V profiles of each cell are Doppler shifted according to the line-of-sight projected rotational velocity of the cell. Then, disk integration is carried out by summing all the surface cells while scaling them by their projected area, brightness, and limb darkening (a linear law is used, Gray 2005; Claret & Bloemen 2011). Implementing an adequate limb darkening law is important for reliable reconstruction, although the effects are less severe than, e.g., blends (Unruh & Collier Cameron 1995). There is also the possibility to include differential rotation with the form

$$\Omega(\theta) = \Omega_{\text{eq}} - d\Omega \cdot \sin^2(\theta), \quad (\text{A.33})$$

with Ω_{eq} the rotational frequency, and $d\Omega$ the equator-pole rotation rate difference. Finally, the integrated profile is convolved with a Gaussian instrumental profile to emulate the finite resolution of the spectropolarimeter. The synthetic profiles generated with this procedure can be compared to the observed ones.

A.2 Inverse problem

To proceed in the opposite direction and retrieve a brightness or magnetic map from a time series of Stokes I or V profiles, we need to invert the response function \mathbf{R} in Eq. A.1. Such inversion is however not possible, because of degeneracies created by measurement noise, the fact that each velocity pixel of the Stokes profile encapsulates the information of an entire longitude, and by our limited knowledge on the intrinsic line profile, which has to be disentangled from the instrumental profile. To circumvent this issue, the algorithm seeks for a solution by iteratively applying the forward approach. Basically, ZDI generates synthetic Stokes profiles, compares them to the observations via χ^2 , and adjusts the brightness or magnetic coefficients to produce a new set of profiles. The iteration is carried out until a user-defined target value of χ^2 is reached.

The χ^2 minimisation alone is ill-posed, because there are multiple brightness or magnetic field configurations that can reproduce the observations. This is due to the number of free parameters exceeding the observational constraints, a poor phase coverage of the observations, and sometimes a low S/N. Following Skilling & Bryan (1984), we use a maximum entropy regularisation scheme based on the conjugate gradient method (Press et al. 1992) to break such ambiguity and find a unique solution. This way, the iterative algorithm stops when the χ^2 and entropy gradients are anti-parallel. By maximising the entropy (or minimising the information content) in the maps, we ensure that the features ZDI finds are actually required by the data to reproduce the observations.

Formally, Shannon's definition of entropy ($S = -\sum n \ln n$) is not used because we require both positive and negative values. We report here the expression used in ZDIPY for completeness, but a detailed explanation can be found in Folsom et al. (2018). For Doppler Imaging, if we reconstruct both bright and dark features, we use Hobson & Lasenby (1998) formalism

$$S_{\text{bri}} = -\sum_{i=1}^N w_i \left[m_i + f_i \left(\ln \frac{f_i}{m_i} - 1 \right) \right], \quad (\text{A.34})$$

where w_i is a weight given by the i -th cell surface area, and f_i and m_i are the relative and default (set to 1) brightness values assigned to the i -th cell. In case we only allow dark spots on the surface, the entropy becomes (Hussain et al. 2001)

$$S_{\text{bri,dark}} = -\sum_{i=1}^N w_i \left[f_i \ln \left(\frac{f_i}{m} \right) + (m_{\text{lim}} - f_i) \left(\ln \frac{m_{\text{lim}} - f_i}{m_{\text{lim}} - m} \right) \right], \quad (\text{A.35})$$

where m is a constant brightness value across all cells (typically just below 1), while m_{lim} is the maximum value (typically equal to 1) that the f_i values can have. This way f_i is interpreted as a spot filling factor. Finally, the entropy for Zeeman-Doppler Imaging is (Hobson & Lasenby 1998)

$$S_{\text{mag}} = \sum_{i=1}^N \left[\psi_i - (m_f)_i - (m_g)_i - h_i \ln \left(\frac{\psi_i + h_i}{2(m_f)_i} \right) \right], \quad (\text{A.36})$$

with $\psi_i = (h_i^2 + 4(m_f)_i(m_g)_i)^{1/2}$, while h_i contains the spherical harmonic coefficients that the ZDI algorithm fits, and $(m_f)_i$ and $(m_g)_i$ are the default values for positive and negative entropy distributions, respectively. To penalise positive and negative values in the same fashion, the latter variables are assumed to be equal and called entropy slope $(m_f)_i = (m_g)_i = E_{\text{slope}}$ (Folsom et al. 2018; Fréour et al. 2022). This is a control parameter of the entropy regularisation scheme and encapsulates prior information on the positive/negative entropy distributions.

The magnetic entropy is further weighted by the degree of spherical harmonics l , to obtain the simplest map possible and prevent spurious complex structuring of the field. In other words, we weight against small structures, since they are mostly due to noise in Stokes V . When both Doppler and Zeeman-Doppler Imaging are performed, the overall entropy is simply the sum of the two corresponding formulas.

Table A.1: Properties of the magnetic maps obtained using weak-field approximation or Unno-Rachkovsky solutions for the 2019a, 2019b, 2020a, and 2020b near-infrared epochs of AD Leo. The following quantities are listed: magnetic filling factor, mean magnetic strength, maximum magnetic strength, poloidal and toroidal magnetic energy as a fraction of the total one, dipolar, quadrupolar and octupolar magnetic energy as a fraction of the poloidal one, axisymmetric magnetic energy as a fraction of the total one, and tilt of the magnetic axis relative to the rotation axis.

	Weak-Field Approximation				Unno-Rachkovsky solutions			
	2019a	2019b	2020a	2020b	2019a	2019b	2020a	2020b
B_{mean} [G]	105.2	128.9	116.2	112.2	111.2	132.3	115.3	93.4
B_{max} [G]	221.5	316.3	311	396.7	481.2	764	555.1	434.3
B_{pol} [%]	98.7	99.2	95.7	90.6	100.0	99.9	99.3	98.7
B_{tor} [%]	1.3	0.8	4.3	9.4	0.0	0.1	0.7	1.3
B_{dip} [%]	87.4	85.9	81.9	68.1	81.3	71.1	75.7	70.1
B_{quad} [%]	11.2	12.7	14.9	21.6	14.9	19.0	17.7	21.2
B_{oct} [%]	0.8	1.1	2.5	7.0	2.8	6.2	4.4	5.9
B_{axisym} [%]	97.1	90.7	74.4	48.5	99.8	94.5	85.8	58.3
Obliquity [$^{\circ}$]	5.5	15.5	24.5	48.5	2.5	12.5	19.5	38.0

Zeeman-Doppler Imaging requires input stellar parameters such as rotation period, projected rotational velocity, inclination, radial velocity, and differential rotation rate as input. Small errors on these parameters would lead to spurious maps with unrealistic features (Vogt et al. 1987; Rice et al. 1989; Donati & Brown 1997). Based on this, we can search for the stellar parameters yielding the map that best matches the observations. In practice, we execute a χ^2 minimisation at a fixed entropy over a grid of possible stellar parameter values. We indeed build a χ^2 landscape that we fit with a multi-dimensional paraboloid (usually no more than 3D) around the minimum, in order to find the value of the stellar parameters corresponding to this minimum and their associated error bars. This prescription was introduced by Donati et al. (2000) and Petit et al. (2002) to find, e.g., differential rotation rates. Alternatively, it is possible to let entropy be unconstrained and fix the χ^2 , since the results should be reasonably compatible.

A.3 Tests of the Unno-Rachkovsky implementation

A.3.1 Comparison to weak-field approximation

It is interesting to reconstruct magnetic field topologies using both weak-field approximation and the Unno-Rachkovsky' solution to radiative transfer, in order to compare the information gain or lost when making the choice. I start by performing tests on the near-infrared SPIRou data set of AD Leo used in Chapter 5, while splitting the time series in a similar way: 2019a, 2019b, 2020a, and 2020b. Here I will describe mainly the weak-field approximation maps, as a description of the Unno-Rachkovsky maps is found in Sec. 5.3.1

The input parameters are $i = 20^{\circ}$, $v_{\text{eq}} \sin(i) = 3 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, $P_{\text{rot}} = 2.23$ days, and solid body rotation. Considering weak-field approximation, I fit Stokes V profiles down to χ_r^2 of 2.2, 2.1, 1.9, 1.4 for 2019a, 2019b, 2020a, and 2020b, respectively. The quality of the fit is systematically worse than when using Unno-Rachkovsky models, the χ^2 being 30-80% times larger. This is not surprising since the latter has more flexibility to model Zeeman signatures. For instance, near-infrared Stokes V profiles of AD Leo may feature additional horizontal separation at zero crossing point, which is not part of the weak-field approximation model (Landi Degl'Innocenti & Landolfi 2004). A visual comparison of the models is presented in Fig. A.2.

Both models are capable of capturing the long-term evolution of the magnetic field, because the magnetic properties of the map are retrieved consistently, i.e. decreasing strength and axisymmetry

Figure A.2: Stokes V models obtained with weak-field approximation (blue) and Unno-Rachkovsky solutions (red) compared to the observations (black).

(see Table A.1). The value of field strength is reasonably similar between the two models, as well as the repartition of the magnetic energy in the poloidal, toroidal and various degrees l . However, when using weak-field approximation, we observe more leakage of magnetic field in the meridional component, of which we do not have constraints from Stokes V observations only. Moreover, the axisymmetry of the field is lower, and correspondingly its obliquity is higher, but still not reaching the values obtained with Stibb's formula in Table 5.2. The discrepancy between the retrieved obliquity values is likely due to the limitations of the models combined with the low inclination with which AD Leo is observed, which makes ZDI push magnetic features poleward, i.e. the region observed at all times. Indeed such low inclination is at the edge of the applicability of ZDI (Donati et al. 1997).

Figure A.3: Reconstructed ZDI maps in flattened polar view of AD Leo for 2020b SPIRou time series. Left: using weak-field approximation, Right: using Unno-Rachkovsky models. The plot format is the same as Fig. 5.12. We notice that weak-field approximation results in maps with a lower axisymmetry level.

To test inclination effects on the reconstruction, we generated synthetic Stokes V profiles from an artificial map of a tilted dipole at 35° (67% of energy in axisymmetric mode) and then reconstructed it assuming $i = 20^\circ$ and 60° (the other input parameters are fixed to those of AD Leo). When using $i = 20^\circ$, the output field map is indeed more axisymmetric than the synthetic one (79%, and obliquity of 26°), whereas with $i = 60^\circ$ the map is recovered consistently regardless of the model.

The reconstruction of the field maps with weak-field approximation and Unno-Rachkovsky solutions were also carried out for DS Leo, as shown in Fig. A.4 and reported in Table A.2, which is a less magnetically active star compared to AD Leo, therefore the choice of using Unno-Rachkovsky models is less obvious.

Using the same input parameters of Sec. 5.4.2 and assuming solid body rotation, we fit the profiles down to χ^2 of 1.45 and 1.27 for 2020b201a and 2021b2022a, slightly larger than those used with Unno-Rachkovsky solutions (1.2 and 1.4, respectively). We then carried out a differential rotation search adopting weak-field approximation and found $P_{\text{rot,eq}} = 13.848 \pm 0.020$ d and $d\Omega = 0.0174 \pm 0.0023$ rad d $^{-1}$ for 2020b201a and $P_{\text{rot,eq}} = 13.648 \pm 0.019$ d and $d\Omega = 0.0424 \pm 0.0021$ rad d $^{-1}$ for 2021b2022a. Accounting for differential rotation improves the fit, as we achieve a target χ^2 of 1.25 and 1.15, which is equal and 0.05 larger than the one reached with Unno-Rachkovsky for 2020b201a and 2021b2022a, re-

Figure A.4: Reconstructed ZDI maps in flattened polar view of DS Leo for 2020b2021a SPIRou time series. Left: using weak-field approximation, Right: using Unno-Rachkovsky models. The plot format is the same as Fig. 5.12. Adopting the Unno-Rachkovsky solutions leads to a slightly improved fit of the Stokes V , and visually the maps are nearly identical.

spectively. At the same time, the equatorial rotation period and differential rotation rate obtained with the Unno-Rachkovsky models were $(13.836 \pm 0.016 \text{ d}, 0.0192 \pm 0.0020 \text{ rad d}^{-1})$ and $(13.469 \pm 0.054 \text{ d}, 0.0448 \pm 0.0045 \text{ rad d}^{-1})$ for the two epochs, hence mostly consistent within 1σ . A comparison of the χ_r^2 landscape over which the differential rotation search is performed is illustrated in Fig. A.5.

The maps in Fig. A.4 for the same epoch but different model choice do not manifest substantial changes. An average field strength of 30 G and 15 G is retrieved regardless of the model for 2020b2021a and 2021b2022a, respectively. Likewise, the large-scale topology was almost equally poloidal and toroidal in 2020b2021a and mostly poloidal (80% of the magnetic energy) in 2021b2022a. The poloidal component is consistently non-axisymmetric (4% in 2020b2021a and 15% in 2021b2022a), whereas the toroidal one is largely axisymmetric ($\sim 90\%$). The dipolar mode is the dominant one, with more than 60% of the energy in 2020b2021a and more than 80% in 2021b2022a.

In conclusion, when the magnetic field is weak enough so that the Stokes profiles do not exhibit visible deformations induced by the Zeeman effect, the weak-field approximation is a totally valid choice. The marginal difference in the reconstructed magnetic features can be thought of as an error bar associated to the choice of the model. The Unno-Rachkovsky model tends to perform better, i.e. we achieve lower χ^2 of the Stokes V fit because it has more flexibility at capturing the shape of the profiles. A posteriori, this is the reason why Unno-Rachkovsky solutions were implemented in ZDIPY and used for all the ZDI reconstructions carried out during the Ph.D. project.

A.3.2 Entropy slope tests

One of the user-defined input parameters for ZDI is the entropy slope (E_{slope}), entering the definition of the magnetic entropy in Eq. A.36. As explained by Folsom et al. (2018) and Fréour et al. (2022), this parameter acts as prior information on the positive and negative parts of the entropy distribution and takes part in the regularisation scheme. In practice, it sets a threshold below which spherical harmonic coefficients are less regularised, since they would contribute less to the entropy. The choice of E_{slope} has thus consequences on the magnetic field reconstructions: a large value would imply a weak regularisation, more magnetic energy in high-degree spherical harmonic coefficients, and ultimately

Table A.2: Properties of the magnetic maps obtained using weak-field approximation or Unno-Rachkovsky solutions for the 2019a, 2019b, 2020a, and 2020b near-infrared epochs of AD Leo. The listed quantities are the same as Table A.1, with the two additional last rows being the fraction of magnetic energy in the poloidal and toroidal components.

	Weak-Field Approximation		Unno-Rachkovsky	
	2020b2021a	2021b2022a	2020b2021a	2021b2022a
B_{mean} [G]	35.3	12.1	33.4	14.2
B_{max} [G]	81.5	25.8	80.3	38.6
B_{pol} [%]	52.3	79.6	50.9	73.6
B_{tor} [%]	47.7	20.4	49.1	26.4
B_{dip} [%]	66.5	85.8	66.5	82.1
B_{quad} [%]	23.3	11.9	23.2	13.7
B_{oct} [%]	3.9	1.5	4.5	2.6
B_{axisym} [%]	42.8	27.4	46.9	35.7
$B_{\text{axisym,pol}}$ [%]	4.1	10.7	4.3	15.0
$B_{\text{axisym,tor}}$ [%]	85.2	92.8	91.0	93.3

Figure A.5: Differential rotation search comparison between weak-field approximation (left panels) and Unno-Rachkovsky models (right panels), for 2020b2021a (top panels) and 2021b2022a (bottom panels).

overfitting. Vice versa, a small value would lead to underfitting. For synthetic data associated with a non-axisymmetric dipole of 500 G, 5 kG and 10 kG, Fréour et al. (2022) showed that E_{slope} is optimised when it is 50 times smaller than the dipolar magnetic field strength.

We tested this for the SPIRou observations of AD Leo in 2019a and 2020b, i.e. when it is presumably most axisymmetric and non-axisymmetric throughout the entire time series. Morin et al. (2008b) used $E_{\text{slope}} = 1000$ for the optical observations, which is of the same order of magnitude as the maximum radial field. We reconstructed the field with $E_{\text{slope}} = 10$ and 1000, as illustrated in Fig. A.6. The characteristics of the magnetic maps are listed in Table A.3.

In both epochs, we observe that the $E_{\text{slope}} = 1000$ choice yields a marginally stronger average field, whereas the difference in maximum field is more substantial, owing to a more concentrated dipolar region as can be seen from the maps. Indeed, the hemisphere with the negative polarity is more “diffuse” when $E_{\text{slope}} = 10$ is selected. While the poloidal/toroidal energy fractions are retrieved reasonably

Table A.3: List of magnetic energies for E_{slope} tests for AD Leo.

Quantity	2019a		2020b	
	$E_{\text{slope}} = 10$	$E_{\text{slope}} = 1000$	$E_{\text{slope}} = 10$	$E_{\text{slope}} = 1000$
$\langle B \rangle$ [G]	119.9	135.9	75.5	81.4
B_{max} [G]	281.5	380.8	296.1	345.5
B_{pol}	100.0%	100.0%	99.6%	99.7%
B_{tor}	0.0%	0.0%	0.4%	0.7%
B_{dip}	99.2%	97.4%	76.8%	73.0%
B_{quad}	0.7%	2.2%	18.4%	20.4%
B_{oct}	0.05%	0.3%	4.0%	5.3%
B_{axisym}	99.9%	99.9%	66.5%	60.9%
$B_{\text{axisym,pol}}$	99.9%	99.9%	66.7%	61.3%
$B_{\text{axisym,dip}}$	99.9%	99.9%	73.9%	68.5%
Obliquity [$^{\circ}$]	0.5	0.5	30.5	34.5

Figure A.6: Tests on E_{slope} for AD Leo observations of 2019a and 2020b. First two columns: $E_{\text{slope}}=10$, and $E_{\text{slope}}=1000$ for 2019a. Second two columns: First two columns: $E_{\text{slope}}=10$, and $E_{\text{slope}}=1000$ for 2020b.

consistently, the $E_{\text{slope}} = 1000$ choice leads to a higher fraction of energy in the quadrupolar and octupolar modes for both epochs, as predicted by Fréour et al. (2022). The axisymmetric level is not affected by E_{slope} in 2019a, and in 2020b we see that $E_{\text{slope}} = 1000$ produces a less axisymmetric map than $E_{\text{slope}} = 10$.

In conclusion, we note that E_{slope} influences the final magnetic field reconstructions. However, the difference in the maps is only marginal regardless of the evolution of the field. Therefore, we adopted $E_{\text{slope}} = 1000$ for the ZDI analysis carried out for this thesis. This choice allows us also to compare the new maps with the literature ones in a consistent way.

A.3.3 Distinct spherical harmonics formalism

In our ZDI implementation and analyses, we adopted Eq. A.2 to describe the radial, azimuthal and meridional components of the magnetic field vector. A slight modification of Eq. A.2 consists in replac-

Table A.4: List of magnetic energies for spherical harmonics formalism tests for AD Leo.

Quantity	2019a		2020b	
	β_{lm}	$\alpha_{lm} + \beta_{lm}$	β_{lm}	$\alpha_{lm} + \beta_{lm}$
$\langle B \rangle$ [G]	135.9	161.1	81.4	150.5
B_{\max} [G]	380.8	638.8	345.5	469.1
B_{pol}	100.0%	100.0%	99.3%	99.5%
B_{tor}	0.0%	0.0%	0.7%	0.5%
B_{dip}	97.4%	81.6%	73.0%	80.0%
B_{quad}	2.2%	12.5%	20.4%	15.5%
B_{oct}	0.3%	3.7%	5.3%	3.1%
B_{axisym}	99.9%	99.8%	60.9%	70.5%
$B_{\text{axisym,pol}}$	99.9%	99.8%	61.3%	70.7%
$B_{\text{axisym,dip}}$	99.9%	99.8%	68.5%	75.4%
Obliquity [$^{\circ}$]	0.5	1.5	34.5	29.5

ing β_{lm} by $\alpha_{lm} + \beta_{lm}$ as follows (Lehmann & Donati 2022)

$$B_r(\theta, \varphi) = \sum_{l=0}^{l_{\max}} \sum_{m=0}^l \Re[\alpha_{lm} Y_{lm}(\theta, \varphi)], \quad (\text{A.37})$$

$$B_{\theta}(\theta, \varphi) = - \sum_{l=0}^{l_{\max}} \sum_{m=0}^l \Re[(\alpha_{lm} + \beta_{lm}) Z_{lm}(\theta, \varphi) + \gamma_{lm} X_{lm}(\theta, \varphi)], \quad (\text{A.38})$$

$$B_{\varphi}(\theta, \varphi) = - \sum_{l=0}^{l_{\max}} \sum_{m=0}^l \Re[(\alpha_{lm} + \beta_{lm}) X_{lm}(\theta, \varphi) - \gamma_{lm} Z_{lm}(\theta, \varphi)], \quad (\text{A.39})$$

and with the propagation of such modification also in the derivatives included in the response function \mathbf{R} . With this modification, the description of the meridional field is linked to the radial one, hence we can prevent the tangential poloidal component, encapsulated by β_{lm} , to assume unnecessarily large values, owing to the fact that with circular polarisation we are not sensitive to the tangential component of the field.

We tested whether such difference in the usage of the magnetic coefficients would influence the maps substantially, for both 2019a and 2020b epochs of near-infrared SPIRou data of AD Leo. The results are presented in Fig. A.7 and Table A.4. Overall, the two maps are similar and exhibit analogous features. However, the repartition of the magnetic energy depends on the chosen formalism. For 2019a, the reconstructed magnetic field has a larger quadrupolar contribution (13%) when the $\alpha_{lm} + \beta_{lm}$ is adopted, at the expenses of the dipolar component. At the same time, the ZDI concentrates the field in a smaller area, and we see a corresponding increase in maximum field strength, but the average field is reasonably consistent. In 2020b, the main difference is in the axisymmetric level, since with the $\alpha_{lm} + \beta_{lm}$ formalism it stores 70% of the magnetic energy, 10% more than with β_{lm} only. To allow a consistent comparison with maps in the literature, we proceeded with the β_{lm} formalism, i.e. Eq. A.2.

Figure A.7: Tests on spherical harmonics formalism for AD Leo observations of 2019a and 2020b. First two columns: β_{lm} , and $\alpha_{lm} + \beta_{lm}$ for 2019a. Second two columns: First two columns: β_{lm} , and $\alpha_{lm} + \beta_{lm}$ for 2020b.

Appendix B

Gaussian Process Regression

B.1 Definition

A Gaussian process (GP) is “a collection (finite or infinite) of random variables, any finite subset of which has a joint Gaussian distribution” (Rasmussen & Williams 2006). A GP can be efficiently used both for classification and regression problems. During my Ph.D. project, I used GPs for the second category, aiming to fit radial velocity or photometric or longitudinal field data sets over some observational time span, and eventually predict values at unknown times (see Sec. 5.4.2). Compared to Lomb-Scargle periodograms, GPs enable us to model the intrinsic variability of activity features over long time scales (e.g. spots decay and emergence, and coherency loss of stellar activity) and are therefore more powerful at extracting periodic information from the data sets. Indeed periodograms adopt only sinusoidal models and uncorrelated (white) noise, while GP can work with multiple non-sinusoidal, quasi-periodic signals and correlated (red) noise.

A GP is a non-parametric (i.e., Bayesian) approach to fitting data, as we do not force any specific shape to the analytical model before having performed the measurements (resulting in more freedom and less assumptions). The choice of the model is in fact data-driven, meaning that our measurements determine the shape of the model. In practice, when applying GPs, we infer a probability distribution over random functions, while injecting some prior information (Aigrain & Foreman-Mackey 2022).

Formally, a GP is denoted $\mathcal{GP}(m, k)$ and it is completely characterized by a mean function $m = m(t, \bar{\phi})$ and a covariance function $k = k(t, t', \bar{\theta})$ (commonly called kernel), in the same manner as a Gaussian distribution is characterized by a mean and a standard deviation, and a Gaussian multivariate by a mean vector and a covariance matrix. In a one-dimensional GP framework, any point $t \in \mathbb{R}$ is associated to a random variable $f(t)$ which, in our case, could describe the temporal behaviour of RV, B_l or photometric flux. By definition, a finite set of these variables $f(t_1), \dots, f(t_N)$ has a Gaussian joint distribution

$$p(f|\bar{t}) = \mathcal{N}(f|\bar{\mu}, \bar{K}), \quad (\text{B.1})$$

where $\bar{t} = (t_1, \dots, t_N)$ are the time stamps of the time series, $\bar{\mu} = (m(t_1), \dots, m(t_N), \bar{\phi})$ and \bar{K} is the covariance matrix, whose elements are $K_{ij} = k(t_i, t_j, \bar{\theta})$. The diagonal elements of the covariance matrix express the variance of individual variables (independent), whereas the off-diagonal elements the joint variability (correlated variables). The quantities $\bar{\phi}$ and $\bar{\theta}$ are vectors containing the hyperparameters of the GP.

The mean function m encapsulates the deterministic part of the GP, i.e. it is used to express the behaviour of the model when there is no stochastic variation. For instance, this could be a Keplerian model, if the GP is applied on RV, or the mean variation of B_l . The function k describes the covariance between any two data points, and encapsulates the stochastic part of the GP. For our purposes, k accounts for the nuisance signals, i.e. stellar activity. The analytical choice of k depends on the problem

Figure B.1: Steps defining a Gaussian Process. Top left: true function $f(t)$ (red) and synthetic data points with random noise. The latter is what it observed usually. Top right: covariance matrix obtained for a quasi-periodic kernel, where we see that off-diagonal elements have values different than zero. This is representative of correlated noise. Bottom left: true function and sample functions (blue) from the prior distribution. Bottom right: true function and Gaussian process (green) with confidence intervals.

at hand; in my work, I used a quasi-periodic function

$$k(t, t', \bar{\theta}) = \theta_1^2 \cdot \exp \left[-\frac{(t - t')^2}{\theta_2^2} - \frac{\sin^2 \left(\frac{\pi(t - t')}{\theta_3} \right)}{\theta_4^2} \right], \quad (\text{B.2})$$

where $\bar{\theta} = (\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3, \theta_4)$ are the hyperparameters, and determine the shape of the function $f(t)$ we want to infer. They represent specific physical quantities: θ_1 is the amplitude of the curve (and it may be associated with, e.g., spot coverage or field strength), θ_2 is the evolution timescale (it determines how rapidly the function evolves, e.g., the spots lifetime), θ_3 is the recurrence timescale (e.g., the rotation period of the star), and θ_4 is the smoothness factor (determining whether there is harmonic or high-frequency structure in the curve).

When modelling stellar activity, a quasi-periodic kernel like in Eq. B.2 is a suitable choice (Nicholson & Aigrain 2022). In fact, its formalism allows us to efficiently probe periodicity (rotation period), variable periodicity (spots decay) and long time scales (evolution). It also accounts for stationarity given by the Euclidean distance ($|t - t'|$), i.e. the fact that points closer in time are more informative than distant ones.

B.2 Inference

Our observations collected at times t_i can be written as

$$\bar{y} = f(\bar{t}, \bar{\phi}) + \bar{\varepsilon}, \quad (\text{B.3})$$

with $\bar{\varepsilon}$ the vector of measurement errors associated to \bar{y} . Each element of $\bar{\varepsilon}$ is drawn from a Gaussian distribution centered at zero and with variance σ_i^2 , namely $\mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_i^2)$. The likelihood is then

$$\log \mathcal{L}(\bar{\theta}, \bar{\phi}) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi|\bar{K}|}} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}(\bar{y} - \bar{m})^T \bar{K}^{-1}(\bar{y} - \bar{m})\right), \quad (\text{B.4})$$

\bar{m} is the vector with elements $m_i = m(t_i, \bar{\phi})$ and \bar{K} is the covariance matrix with elements $k(t_i, t_j, \bar{\theta}) + \delta_{ij}\sigma_i^2$, i.e. including both red and white noise, respectively. The term δ is a Kronecker delta function.

By incorporating prior information, we can then exploit the Bayes framework to obtain the posterior distribution. For our purposes, a prior distribution over functions encodes a blind guess of the unknown function f , before any measurement is performed, and aims at giving general properties we believe the function f has. This reduces the possibilities to a single or a group of functions to be searched for.

According to Bayes theorem, we the posterior probability is given by

$$p(\phi, \bar{\theta}|\bar{y}) = \frac{p(\bar{\phi}, \bar{\theta})p(\bar{y}|\bar{\phi}, \bar{\theta})}{p(\bar{y})}, \quad (\text{B.5})$$

where the $p(\bar{y}) = \int p(\bar{\phi}, \bar{\theta})p(\bar{y}|\bar{\phi}, \bar{\theta})d\bar{\theta}d\bar{\phi}$ is the evidence (or marginal likelihood), which is used to quantitatively assess the choice of distinct models. The GP regression problem consists in optimising the posterior to find the best kernel hyperparameters and mean parameters. An illustration of Gaussian Process Regression is illustrated in Fig. B.1. This is practically performed by exploring the posterior landscapes with sampling algorithms, like MCMC, nested sampling and cross-validation.

B.2.1 Nested sampling

To perform Gaussian Process Regression, I mainly used the CPNEST package (Del Pozzo & Veitch 2022) which performs Bayesian inference via nested sampling algorithm (Skilling 2004). The choice was relatively arbitrary, considering that there are several implementations and techniques to converge toward more or less consistent results (Nelson et al. 2020). It could happen that MCMC-based methods sample the posterior while focusing mainly on its peak, therefore undersampling the tails of the distribution, or getting trapped in case of multi-modal distributions. Nested sampling represents a robust alternative to counter these cases.¹

With nested sampling, we progressively probe the prior mass above a given likelihood threshold (see Fig. B.2). In practice, we draw a set of points (called live points or active points) from the prior distribution and evaluate their likelihood. We identify the point with smallest likelihood (the threshold), remove it from the computation and draw another point with the constraint that it has a likelihood larger than the removed one. Drawing a new point under this constraint is typically carried out with an MCMC process. The discarded data point is stored because it will be used for the computation of the evidence. The sampling-removal process continues iteratively and the examined prior mass shrinks accordingly by a constant factor. The algorithm stops when the mass is small and the likelihood flat enough that their contribution to the evidence is negligible. The output is a sequence of discarded points with increasing likelihood and decreasing associated prior volume: with these an estimate of the final evidence can be obtained (Fig. B.2). The speed at which the volume shrinks depends on the selected number of live points. For an extensive explanation of nested sampling algorithm, see Skilling (2004).

¹A really insightful lecture on nested sampling has been provided by Dr. Brewer at the University of Auckland during Astro Hack Week 2015. It can be found here <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5bO2JwsJY1M&list=WL&index=21>.

Figure B.2: Sketch representing the principle of nested sampling. After selecting the point with likelihood L_1 , we draw a new point under the constrain $L > L_1$, which is equivalent to draw a new point inside the iso-likelihood contour L_1 . While the process is iterated, the prior mass shrinks and the algorithm stops when the likelihood varies only marginally (i.e. it is flat) when a new point in a smaller prior mass is drawn. The evidence is computed as the integral of the likelihood over the prior mass.

Appendix C

Journal of observations and measurements

In this Appendix, I list the observations collected with SPIRou for the stars examined in the thesis: AD Leo, DS Leo, CN Leo, EV Lac and V374 Peg. For the optical observations acquired with ESPaDOnS and Narval, the journal of the observations can be found in the corresponding literature (Donati et al. 2008; Morin et al. 2008a,b, 2010; Hébrard et al. 2016). Here, I will also provide the measurements of relevant quantities that have been used in the analyses of Chapter 5, i.e. the longitudinal magnetic field (B_l) and the mean magnetic flux from radiative transfer modelling of Zeeman broadening.

C.1 AD Leo

Table C.1: List of AD Leo observations collected with SPIRou. The columns are: (1 and 2) date and universal time of the observations, (3) rotational cycle of the observations found using Eq. 5.1, (4) exposure time of a polarimetric sequence, (5) signal-to-noise ratio at 1650 nm per spectral element, (6) RMS noise level of Stokes V signal in units of unpolarised continuum.

Date	UT [hh:mm:ss]	n_{cyc}	t_{exp} [s]	S/N	σ_{LSD} [$10^{-4}I_c$]
2019					
April 15	06:11:02.35	0.00	4x61	151	1.9
April 16	12:03:07.61	0.56	4x61	130	1.8
April 18	09:00:59.77	1.40	4x61	138	1.9
April 19	10:36:14.55	1.88	4x61	143	1.8
April 20	08:56:19.44	2.29	4x61	143	1.8
April 21	05:42:43.43	2.68	4x61	165	1.5
April 22	08:58:10.67	3.19	4x61	147	1.9
April 23	07:01:28.73	3.60	4x61	154	1.9
April 24	06:04:06.74	4.03	4x61	147	1.9
April 25	09:41:45.90	4.55	4x61	152	1.9
April 26	08:13:21.75	4.97	4x61	162	1.9
April 27	08:17:48.22	5.42	4x61	139	2.1
May 01	08:59:11.25	7.23	4x61	153	1.8
May 15	06:11:38.01	13.45	4x61	165	1.6
June 13	06:30:59.49	26.46	4x61	186	2.1
June 14	05:44:29.79	26.89	4x61	193	2.0
June 15	06:04:31.16	27.35	4x61	192	2.1
June 16	05:44:52.21	27.79	4x61	173	1.8

Table C.1: continued.

Date	UT [hh:mm:ss]	n_{cyc}	t_{exp} [s]	S/N	σ_{LSD} [$10^{-4}I_c$]
June 17	06:08:46.48	28.25	4x61	150	1.8
June 19	05:47:00.42	29.14	4x61	175	1.5
June 21	06:18:29.14	30.05	4x61	169	1.7
October 16	15:31:29.14	82.69	4x61	180	1.4
October 31	15:32:56.51	89.41	4x61	169	1.6
November 01	15:22:10.08	89.86	4x61	159	1.5
November 02	15:36:52.90	90.31	4x61	170	1.4
November 03	14:53:22.07	90.75	4x61	151	1.5
November 04	15:43:18.06	91.21	4x61	137	1.9
November 05	15:33:34.93	91.66	4x61	164	1.3
November 06	15:37:27.47	92.10	4x61	190	1.5
November 07	15:01:11.73	92.54	4x61	165	1.5
November 09	14:03:02.38	93.42	4x61	116	1.6
November 10	15:51:32.68	93.90	4x61	151	1.5
November 13	14:47:09.89	95.22	4x61	201	1.8
November 14	14:13:58.20	95.66	4x61	197	1.4
December 05	15:12:55.68	105.10	4x61	116	1.4
December 05	15:35:03.10	105.10	4x61	68	1.5
December 07	15:08:39.83	105.99	4x61	133	2.2
December 08	14:29:19.93	106.43	4x61	181	1.8
December 09	14:21:48.74	106.88	4x61	193	1.5
December 10	13:15:39.48	107.31	4x61	194	1.5
December 11	14:58:07.44	107.79	4x61	189	3.0
December 12	14:33:27.45	108.23	4x61	190	3.6
2020					
January 26	12:11:48.90	128.36	4x61	218	2.0
January 27	12:07:16.45	128.81	4x61	166	1.5
January 28	12:06:25.46	129.26	4x61	193	1.5
February 05	08:18:51.61	132.78	4x61	174	1.4
February 16	07:39:02.87	137.70	4x61	193	1.8
February 17	09:20:45.46	138.18	4x61	171	1.9
February 18	07:39:13.56	138.59	4x61	191	1.2
February 19	08:37:09.84	139.06	4x61	210	1.5
March 12	09:16:56.32	148.94	4x61	217	2.0
May 08	05:59:01.58	174.43	4x61	194	1.4
May 09	09:42:30.22	174.95	4x61	206	1.5
May 12	09:39:45.19	176.30	4x61	177	1.4
May 13	09:43:17.10	176.75	4x61	204	1.4
May 14	07:46:35.66	177.16	4x61	208	1.5
May 15	09:50:31.27	177.65	4x61	164	1.6
May 31	06:22:44.29	184.76	4x61	215	1.2
June 01	07:29:57.32	185.23	4x61	189	1.3
June 02	06:23:31.70	185.65	4x61	202	1.4
June 03	07:38:43.10	186.13	4x61	196	1.3
June 04	06:32:43.13	186.55	4x61	197	1.3
June 05	06:42:42.88	187.01	4x61	139	1.8
June 06	07:53:54.53	187.48	4x61	167	1.2

Table C.1: continued.

Date	UT [hh:mm:ss]	n_{cyc}	t_{exp} [s]	S/N	σ_{LSD} [$10^{-4}I_c$]
June 07	06:58:07.88	187.91	4x61	154	1.6
June 08	06:03:47.85	188.34	4x61	135	1.3
June 08	06:10:09.48	188.34	4x61	143	1.4
June 09	06:31:50.17	188.79	4x61	120	1.3
June 10	06:57:13.44	189.25	4x61	200	1.8
October 31	15:06:44.49	253.75	4x61	205	1.5
November 03	15:29:52.78	255.11	4x61	220	1.5

Table C.2: List of AD Leo observations collected with ESPaDOnS in 2019. The columns are: (1 and 2) date and universal time of the observations, (3) rotational cycle of the observations found using Eq. 5.1, (4) exposure time of a polarimetric sequence, (5) signal-to-noise ratio at 650 nm per spectral element, (6) RMS noise level of Stokes V signal in units of unpolarised continuum.

Date	UT [hh:mm:ss]	n_{cyc}	t_{exp} [s]	S/N	σ_{LSD} [$10^{-4}I_c$]
November 15	13:24:01.40	96.32	4x300	234	1.7
November 16	14:20:01.30	96.79	4x300	230	1.9
November 19	14:08:04.00	98.13	4x300	151	3.6
November 19	14:33:03.00	98.14	4x300	159	3.2
November 19	14:56:04.00	98.15	4x300	180	2.8
November 21	15:43:01.00	99.06	4x300	265	1.8

Table C.3: List of optical and near-infrared measurements of longitudinal magnetic field and magnetic flux. The columns are: (1) Heliocentric Julian date of the observation, (2) B_l with formal error bar (see Eq. 2.8), and (3) magnetic flux from Zeeman broadening modelling, when a reliable measurement was possible, and (4) the instrument used.

HJD [−2450000]	B_l [G]	Bf [kG]	Instrument
3747.0876	-269.4 ± 26.4	$3.65^{+0.07}_{-0.08}$	ESPaDOnS
3748.8868	-272.4 ± 15.1	$3.52^{+0.09}_{-0.10}$	ESPaDOnS
3780.0705	-280.7 ± 13.1	$3.55^{+0.10}_{-0.10}$	ESPaDOnS
3895.8047	-291.2 ± 10.7	$3.62^{+0.08}_{-0.09}$	ESPaDOnS
3896.8124	-260.1 ± 7.6	$3.61^{+0.08}_{-0.09}$	ESPaDOnS
3897.8005	-266.7 ± 7.4	$3.63^{+0.08}_{-0.09}$	ESPaDOnS
3898.7785	-294.2 ± 8.1	$3.58^{+0.08}_{-0.10}$	ESPaDOnS
4127.5975	-294.6 ± 16.5	...	Narval
4128.6088	-248.6 ± 10.8	$2.95^{+0.16}_{-0.16}$	Narval
4129.5717	-296.2 ± 11.8	$2.85^{+0.21}_{-0.22}$	Narval
4130.6084	-253.8 ± 9.4	$2.65^{+0.21}_{-0.20}$	Narval
4133.6312	-274.8 ± 10.4	...	Narval
4134.6112	-271.7 ± 11.4	...	Narval
4135.6217	-231.4 ± 10.4	...	Narval
4136.5925	-294.9 ± 13.0	...	Narval
4276.7715	-261.0 ± 8.2	...	ESPaDOnS
4485.5177	-290.1 ± 13.2	$3.18^{+0.17}_{-0.20}$	Narval

Table C.3: continued.

HJD [−2450000]	B_l [G]	B_f [kG]	Instrument
4489.5683	-248.6 ± 10.3	$3.10^{+0.17}_{-0.18}$	Narval
4492.5379	-285.3 ± 10.7	...	Narval
4493.5486	-204.6 ± 10.6	$3.03^{+0.18}_{-0.19}$	Narval
4495.5611	-227.2 ± 12.6	$2.81^{+0.19}_{-0.19}$	Narval
4499.5675	-256.8 ± 11.1	...	Narval
4501.5473	-288.6 ± 12.1	...	Narval
4502.5475	-202.8 ± 9.7	...	Narval
4506.5576	-218.9 ± 10.0	$2.84^{+0.19}_{-0.20}$	Narval
4508.5516	-265.5 ± 11.0	...	Narval
4509.5564	-219.6 ± 12.2	$2.90^{+0.18}_{-0.20}$	Narval
4510.5523	-286.6 ± 15.3	...	Narval
4511.5694	-200.2 ± 10.5	$2.86^{+0.17}_{-0.17}$	Narval
4512.5537	-296.7 ± 10.8	$2.99^{+0.16}_{-0.16}$	Narval
5896.7560	-249.3 ± 11.5	$3.22^{+0.15}_{-0.16}$	Narval
5934.6407	-247.0 ± 9.5	$3.39^{+0.11}_{-0.12}$	Narval
5935.6765	-225.9 ± 9.3	$3.50^{+0.09}_{-0.11}$	Narval
5936.6050	-241.7 ± 10.9	$3.38^{+0.09}_{-0.10}$	Narval
5937.7575	-254.6 ± 11.2	$3.44^{+0.08}_{-0.10}$	Narval
5938.6659	-243.9 ± 8.8	$3.31^{+0.08}_{-0.10}$	Narval
5939.6031	-234.2 ± 10.6	$3.34^{+0.08}_{-0.10}$	Narval
5940.6416	-203.8 ± 9.1	$3.31^{+0.09}_{-0.09}$	Narval
5941.6411	-232.7 ± 9.7	$3.36^{+0.11}_{-0.13}$	Narval
5942.6256	-220.5 ± 10.2	$3.30^{+0.09}_{-0.10}$	Narval
7435.7957	-177.0 ± 5.5	$3.68^{+0.07}_{-0.08}$	ESPaDOnS
7436.8831	-165.8 ± 5.3	$3.67^{+0.08}_{-0.09}$	ESPaDOnS
7441.8954	-181.4 ± 5.3	$3.57^{+0.06}_{-0.07}$	ESPaDOnS
7443.0074	-166.1 ± 5.3	$3.60^{+0.09}_{-0.10}$	ESPaDOnS
7447.9103	-160.7 ± 6.4	$3.65^{+0.14}_{-0.16}$	ESPaDOnS
7449.0011	-182.9 ± 7.7	$3.66^{+0.11}_{-0.13}$	ESPaDOnS
7449.9154	-154.6 ± 6.5	$3.66^{+0.12}_{-0.15}$	ESPaDOnS
7450.8328	-190.5 ± 6.9	$3.70^{+0.09}_{-0.11}$	ESPaDOnS
7495.8253	-192.9 ± 8.8	$3.66^{+0.12}_{-0.15}$	ESPaDOnS
7498.7442	-170.6 ± 5.8	$3.68^{+0.09}_{-0.09}$	ESPaDOnS
8588.7573	-194.7 ± 17.2	$3.40^{+0.08}_{-0.09}$	SPIRou
8590.0016	-212.3 ± 19.9	...	SPIRou
8592.9410	-206.5 ± 17.4	$3.33^{+0.09}_{-0.11}$	SPIRou
8593.8715	-202.5 ± 16.5	$3.37^{+0.11}_{-0.11}$	SPIRou
8594.7370	-234.3 ± 16.8	$3.42^{+0.10}_{-0.11}$	SPIRou
8595.8726	-211.7 ± 16.4	$3.47^{+0.10}_{-0.13}$	SPIRou
8596.7915	-217.9 ± 16.0	$3.37^{+0.09}_{-0.09}$	SPIRou
8597.7516	-219.1 ± 18.6	$3.33^{+0.10}_{-0.09}$	SPIRou
8598.9026	-240.0 ± 16.9	$3.49^{+0.09}_{-0.09}$	SPIRou
8599.8411	-263.6 ± 17.6	$3.36^{+0.09}_{-0.10}$	SPIRou
8600.8441	-182.9 ± 16.7	$3.36^{+0.10}_{-0.11}$	SPIRou
8604.8725	-190.5 ± 16.3	$3.27^{+0.11}_{-0.12}$	SPIRou
8618.7549	-216.5 ± 15.1	$3.27^{+0.08}_{-0.09}$	SPIRou
8647.7665	-217.0 ± 12.9	$3.26^{+0.09}_{-0.09}$	SPIRou

Table C.3: continued.

HJD [−2450000]	B_l [G]	B_f [kG]	Instrument
8648.7341	-221.3 ± 13.1	$3.38^{+0.09}_{-0.09}$	SPIRou
8649.7480	-230.0 ± 15.3	$3.23^{+0.10}_{-0.10}$	SPIRou
8650.7343	-194.7 ± 13.6	$3.49^{+0.09}_{-0.10}$	SPIRou
8651.7509	-209.4 ± 16.0	$3.49^{+0.08}_{-0.10}$	SPIRou
8653.7357	-227.2 ± 13.6	$3.38^{+0.09}_{-0.09}$	SPIRou
8655.7575	-250.3 ± 20.3	$3.42^{+0.09}_{-0.10}$	SPIRou
8773.1472	-223.6 ± 14.4	$3.39^{+0.10}_{-0.10}$	SPIRou
8788.1497	-223.7 ± 13.4	$3.32^{+0.09}_{-0.10}$	SPIRou
8789.1423	-184.8 ± 13.7	$3.43^{+0.10}_{-0.09}$	SPIRou
8790.1526	-245.2 ± 15.4	$3.50^{+0.09}_{-0.10}$	SPIRou
8791.1225	-192.7 ± 13.8	$3.50^{+0.12}_{-0.12}$	SPIRou
8792.1572	-256.3 ± 16.3	$3.46^{+0.09}_{-0.10}$	SPIRou
8793.1506	-204.8 ± 13.6	$3.50^{+0.09}_{-0.10}$	SPIRou
8794.1534	-246.5 ± 13.5	$3.53^{+0.09}_{-0.09}$	SPIRou
8795.1283	-209.1 ± 15.4	$3.48^{+0.09}_{-0.09}$	SPIRou
8797.0881	-189.3 ± 25.7	$3.51^{+0.10}_{-0.09}$	SPIRou
8798.1635	-202.8 ± 17.8	$3.63^{+0.10}_{-0.10}$	SPIRou
8801.1190	-254.3 ± 14.6	$3.56^{+0.11}_{-0.12}$	SPIRou
8802.0961	-186.1 ± 14.1	$3.58^{+0.08}_{-0.09}$	SPIRou
8803.0577	-208.3 ± 7.0	$3.67^{+0.13}_{-0.14}$	ESPaDOnS
8804.0967	-189.1 ± 7.2	$3.58^{+0.10}_{-0.11}$	ESPaDOnS
8807.0890	-178.9 ± 12.9	$3.65^{+0.07}_{-0.09}$	ESPaDOnS
8807.1062	-198.8 ± 11.5	$3.61^{+0.08}_{-0.09}$	ESPaDOnS
8807.1223	-169.3 ± 10.1	$3.63^{+0.07}_{-0.07}$	ESPaDOnS
8809.1547	-161.1 ± 6.4	$3.57^{+0.08}_{-0.09}$	ESPaDOnS
8823.1385	-254.6 ± 30.7	$3.48^{+0.08}_{-0.09}$	SPIRou
8823.1539	-242.9 ± 42.2	$3.69^{+0.10}_{-0.09}$	SPIRou
8825.1357	-193.2 ± 22.1	$3.60^{+0.08}_{-0.08}$	SPIRou
8826.1084	-236.2 ± 14.4	$3.41^{+0.09}_{-0.09}$	SPIRou
8827.1033	-178.9 ± 13.7	$3.42^{+0.09}_{-0.09}$	SPIRou
8828.0574	-249.2 ± 13.9	$3.40^{+0.11}_{-0.11}$	SPIRou
8829.1286	-152.6 ± 14.4	$3.44^{+0.10}_{-0.10}$	SPIRou
8830.1115	-248.1 ± 14.8	$3.35^{+0.10}_{-0.09}$	SPIRou
8875.0136	-176.0 ± 12.2	$3.43^{+0.09}_{-0.10}$	SPIRou
8876.0104	-118.6 ± 13.3	$3.54^{+0.08}_{-0.09}$	SPIRou
8877.0098	-238.7 ± 14.5	$3.40^{+0.10}_{-0.11}$	SPIRou
8884.8515	-122.9 ± 12.6	$3.42^{+0.10}_{-0.11}$	SPIRou
8895.8233	-132.6 ± 11.9	$3.40^{+0.10}_{-0.10}$	SPIRou
8896.8939	-219.3 ± 13.7	$3.44^{+0.11}_{-0.10}$	SPIRou
8897.8233	-157.3 ± 12.7	$3.43^{+0.09}_{-0.11}$	SPIRou
8898.8635	-216.3 ± 13.3	$3.44^{+0.10}_{-0.11}$	SPIRou
8920.8895	-176.4 ± 12.6	$3.42^{+0.09}_{-0.10}$	SPIRou
8977.7467	-177.7 ± 11.8	$3.27^{+0.09}_{-0.10}$	SPIRou
8978.9018	-114.9 ± 11.5	$3.33^{+0.09}_{-0.08}$	SPIRou
8981.8996	-214.6 ± 14.0	$3.28^{+0.10}_{-0.11}$	SPIRou
8982.9020	-81.2 ± 11.5	$3.43^{+0.11}_{-0.10}$	SPIRou
8983.8209	-190.0 ± 11.2	$3.27^{+0.08}_{-0.09}$	SPIRou

Table C.3: continued.

HJD [−2450000]	B_l [G]	Bf [kG]	Instrument
8984.9069	-100.5 ± 16.8	$3.44^{+0.11}_{-0.11}$	SPIRou
9000.7614	-50.4 ± 10.5	$3.26^{+0.12}_{-0.11}$	SPIRou
9001.8080	-217.7 ± 17.7	$3.32^{+0.09}_{-0.10}$	SPIRou
9002.7618	-61.7 ± 11.9	$3.20^{+0.09}_{-0.11}$	SPIRou
9003.8140	-199.2 ± 12.7	$3.18^{+0.10}_{-0.11}$	SPIRou
9004.7681	-110.4 ± 11.8	$3.26^{+0.09}_{-0.09}$	SPIRou
9005.7750	-96.4 ± 15.5	$3.30^{+0.09}_{-0.09}$	SPIRou
9006.8244	-119.8 ± 14.9	$3.30^{+0.09}_{-0.10}$	SPIRou
9007.7856	-70.0 ± 15.1	$3.30^{+0.10}_{-0.10}$	SPIRou
9008.7478	-178.4 ± 16.2	$3.28^{+0.10}_{-0.10}$	SPIRou
9008.7522	-185.2 ± 16.6	$3.30^{+0.09}_{-0.10}$	SPIRou
9009.7672	-64.5 ± 18.5	$3.35^{+0.10}_{-0.11}$	SPIRou
9010.7848	-194.7 ± 13.2	$3.17^{+0.10}_{-0.09}$	SPIRou
9154.1315	-62.2 ± 10.1	$3.31^{+0.07}_{-0.07}$	SPIRou
9157.1479	-46.1 ± 9.9	$3.28^{+0.08}_{-0.09}$	SPIRou

C.2 CN Leo

Table C.4: List of CN Leo observations collected with SPIRou. The columns are the same as Table C.1.

Date	UT [hh:mm:ss]	n_{cyc}	t_{exp} [s]	S/N	σ_{LSD} [$10^{-4}I_c$]
2019					
April 16	12:13:42.22	22.56	4x128	176	2.5
April 18	9:09:19.88	23.25	4x117	171	2.8
April 19	10:44:28.81	23.65	4x128	163	2.8
April 20	9:35:28.57	24.00	4x128	171	2.7
April 21	11:35:37.16	24.40	4x128	170	2.8
April 22	9:19:34.48	24.74	4x111	172	2.6
April 23	9:33:44.59	25.11	4x111	172	2.7
April 24	8:19:40.68	25.46	4x111	174	2.7
April 25	9:49:38.88	25.86	4x105	173	2.9
April 26	8:22:17.22	26.20	4x128	192	2.5
April 27	8:25:34.09	26.58	4x128	175	2.4
May 01	9:09:09.90	28.07	4x117	171	2.7
May 15	6:56:10.26	33.22	4x83	172	2.7
June 13	6:21:17.73	43.95	4x72	170	2.6
June 14	5:53:42.23	44.31	4x66	173	2.6
June 16	6:04:10.29	45.06	4x83	179	2.7
June 17	5:47:17.17	45.42	4x89	173	2.4
June 19	6:03:42.60	46.17	4x89	178	2.8
June 21	6:26:25.16	46.92	4x105	175	2.4
October 31	15:11:53.11	95.94	4x128	214	1.9
November 01	15:29:15.11	96.31	4x128	184	2.2
November 02	15:44:00.94	96.69	4x128	214	2.2
November 03	15:03:29.07	97.05	4x128	204	2.2
November 07	15:23:03.22	98.53	4x128	175	2.5

Table C.4: continued.

Date	UT [hh:mm:ss]	n_{cyc}	t_{exp} [s]	S/N	σ_{LSD} [$10^{-4}I_c$]
November 09	14:49:54.88	99.27	4x128	155	2.7
November 11	15:43:55.63	100.02	4x128	171	2.9
November 13	14:54:25.58	100.75	4x105	233	2.1
November 14	14:48:53.61	101.12	4x105	232	2.4
December 07	15:35:36.87	109.65	4x128	196	2.2
December 08	14:55:34.82	110.01	4x117	228	2.2
December 09	14:45:15.59	110.38	4x117	229	2.0
December 10	13:54:07.22	110.73	4x117	235	2.4
December 11	15:20:36.69	111.13	4x117	229	2.1
December 12	14:56:48.41	111.49	4x128	229	2.1
2020					
January 26	12:28:07.86	128.12	4x111	233	2.3
January 27	12:23:43.97	128.49	4x117	230	2.2
January 28	13:14:47.18	128.87	4x128	219	2.0
February 05	8:54:48.40	131.77	4x111	228	2.1
February 09	8:19:52.83	133.24	4x128	182	2.5
February 16	7:47:00.30	135.82	4x111	227	2.1
February 17	9:28:00.93	136.22	4x128	206	2.2
February 18	7:46:31.47	136.57	4x128	229	2.0
February 19	10:11:34.85	136.97	4x105	233	2.2
March 11	12:52:11.14	144.79	4x111	233	1.8
March 12	11:12:15.25	145.14	4x100	236	2.2
May 07	10:50:12.93	165.87	4x128	218	2.2
May 09	9:49:53.90	166.60	4x111	231	2.0
May 12	9:47:44.18	167.71	4x128	222	2.1
May 13	9:52:29.17	168.08	4x100	231	2.2
May 14	7:54:40.23	168.42	4x94	229	1.9
May 15	9:57:54.46	168.82	4x128	196	2.3
June 05	6:51:51.44	176.55	4x128	197	2.1
June 07	7:06:16.26	177.30	4x128	175	2.7
June 08	6:17:14.27	177.65	4x128	179	3.2
June 09	6:43:04.47	178.03	4x128	174	2.6
June 10	7:04:25.72	178.41	4x128	230	1.9
October 31	15:20:34.06	231.50	4x111	226	2.1
November 02	15:34:13.01	232.24	4x128	211	2.1
November 03	15:43:02.82	232.61	4x89	225	2.1
November 04	14:48:35.82	232.97	4x83	222	2.3
November 05	14:39:48.09	233.34	4x78	220	2.3
December 24	13:17:50.80	251.47	4x78	228	2.2
December 25	14:34:01.34	251.86	4x83	225	2.4
December 26	13:02:53.07	252.20	4x117	223	2.4
December 29	14:57:23.81	253.34	4x128	158	2.5
December 30	14:59:32.48	253.71	4x128	223	2.4
December 31	14:19:08.41	254.07	4x100	226	2.4
2021					
January 02	15:33:42.40	254.83	4x111	222	2.3
January 03	13:49:08.56	255.18	4x78	223	2.2

Table C.4: continued.

Date	UT [hh:mm:ss]	n_{cyc}	t_{exp} [s]	S/N	σ_{LSD} [$10^{-4}I_c$]
January 04	13:17:16.19	255.54	4x78	226	2.2
January 05	13:07:42.22	255.91	4x83	220	2.3
January 06	14:05:29.70	256.29	4x89	222	2.1
January 07	13:34:08.29	256.65	4x94	225	2.2
January 07	16:17:06.35	256.70	4x100	220	2.5
January 08	13:41:17.96	257.03	4x100	225	2.6
January 08	16:03:57.25	257.06	4x105	222	2.3
February 21	10:53:47.13	273.28	4x111	165	2.8
February 21	11:04:02.34	273.28	4x111	188	2.5
February 22	10:05:46.91	273.64	4x100	226	2.3
February 23	12:41:09.81	274.05	4x111	203	2.5
February 26	8:09:09.92	275.09	4x111	245	2.4
February 28	14:12:09.33	275.92	4x111	275	2.1
March 02	13:44:02.27	276.66	4x111	238	2.4
March 03	11:50:58.30	277.00	4x111	254	2.1
March 04	13:32:04.78	277.40	4x111	276	2.0
March 20	12:37:22.22	283.31	4x111	269	1.9
March 21	11:38:33.18	283.66	4x111	240	2.2
March 23	11:30:39.62	284.40	4x111	261	2.1
March 24	12:44:32.17	284.79	4x111	263	2.1
March 26	11:52:50.95	285.52	4x111	247	2.3
March 27	6:45:37.02	285.81	4x111	248	2.1
March 31	10:54:04.65	287.35	4x111	219	2.4
April 01	12:02:33.87	287.74	4x111	254	2.1
April 22	10:28:06.67	295.50	4x111	187	2.3
April 23	7:56:25.52	295.83	4x111	264	2.2
April 24	10:38:50.47	296.24	4x111	220	2.6
April 25	9:34:48.36	296.59	4x111	218	2.7
April 26	9:44:56.28	296.97	4x111	204	2.9
April 27	10:43:10.75	297.35	4x111	242	2.2
April 28	10:40:26.84	297.72	4x111	257	2.1
April 30	8:57:35.34	298.44	4x111	269	2.0
May 01	9:25:34.23	298.81	4x111	266	2.1
May 02	9:55:38.98	299.19	4x111	201	2.5
May 03	9:26:51.13	299.55	4x111	136	2.5
May 03	9:36:37.40	299.56	4x111	207	2.5
June 19	6:03:13.60	316.91	4x111	141	4.2
June 19	6:12:45.43	316.91	4x111	132	3.0
June 20	6:15:05.26	317.28	4x111	245	2.2
June 21	6:09:04.48	317.65	4x111	277	2.1
June 23	5:41:33.33	318.39	4x111	269	2.1
June 24	5:38:03.01	318.75	4x111	249	2.2
June 25	5:49:08.47	319.13	4x111	241	2.3
June 26	5:46:41.96	319.50	4x111	247	2.4
June 27	5:46:00.34	319.87	4x111	284	2.1
June 28	5:44:57.25	320.24	4x111	287	2.2
June 29	5:38:28.52	320.61	4x111	244	2.7

Table C.4: continued.

Date	UT [hh:mm:ss]	n_{cyc}	t_{exp} [s]	S/N	σ_{LSD} [$10^{-4}I_c$]
June 30	5:39:01.55	320.98	4x111	207	2.8
July 01	5:39:05.12	321.35	4x111	239	2.2
July 02	5:39:06.12	321.72	4x111	156	3.2
November 16	14:51:17.17	372.60	4x111	258	1.9
November 18	15:09:21.21	373.35	4x111	252	2.1
November 19	15:41:46.14	373.72	4x111	292	2.0
November 20	15:25:28.03	374.09	4x111	269	2.2
November 21	15:18:29.94	374.46	4x111	270	1.9
November 22	15:01:19.45	374.83	4x111	251	2.0
2022					
December 09	14:43:38.22	381.12	4x111	169	2.2
December 10	14:16:08.87	381.48	4x111	197	2.4
December 11	15:16:43.27	381.87	4x111	239	2.6
December 12	14:49:26.03	382.23	4x111	270	2.0
December 13	14:19:35.10	382.59	4x111	281	2.1
December 17	15:21:34.66	384.09	4x111	221	2.2
January 08	16:08:05.82	392.25	4x111	237	2.1
January 09	14:54:37.52	392.60	4x111	290	2.2
January 10	15:11:57.75	392.98	4x111	268	2.0
January 11	15:15:49.27	393.35	4x111	228	1.9
January 13	15:15:45.97	394.09	4x111	273	2.0
January 14	14:57:46.42	394.45	4x111	275	1.9
January 15	14:30:58.09	394.82	4x111	217	2.5
January 15	16:24:18.06	394.85	4x111	248	2.0
January 16	16:17:06.12	395.22	4x111	208	2.1
January 17	14:48:47.16	395.56	4x111	259	1.9
January 18	16:14:14.92	395.96	4x111	281	1.9
January 19	16:03:54.92	396.32	4x111	242	2.0
January 20	16:19:00.43	396.70	4x111	275	2.0
January 22	14:51:44.64	397.42	4x111	197	2.1
January 23	12:33:17.06	397.75	4x111	253	1.8
January 24	15:39:39.54	398.17	4x111	278	1.9
January 25	14:54:38.57	398.53	4x111	268	2.1
January 26	15:22:06.80	398.90	4x111	258	2.1
January 27	15:04:51.26	399.27	4x111	251	1.6
January 31	15:25:45.41	400.76	4x111	264	1.8
February 01	15:16:42.73	401.13	4x111	224	2.4
March 11	8:37:55.01	415.10	4x111	287	1.8
March 12	8:40:28.21	415.47	4x111	289	2.0
March 13	8:01:40.95	415.83	4x111	292	1.8
March 15	10:37:12.00	416.61	4x111	281	2.1
March 17	8:44:34.57	417.32	4x111	244	2.1
March 20	9:52:07.34	418.45	4x111	270	1.8
March 22	9:46:22.44	419.19	4x111	226	2.4
April 12	11:02:15.07	426.99	4x111	246	2.2
April 18	11:23:26.56	429.21	4x111	251	2.1
May 11	9:17:57.19	437.70	4x111	230	2.4

Table C.4: continued.

Date	UT [hh:mm:ss]	n_{cyc}	t_{exp} [s]	S/N	σ_{LSD} [$10^{-4}I_c$]
May 14	9:36:00.15	438.82	4x111	198	2.4
June 10	6:03:21.25	448.76	4x111	281	2.2

Table C.5: List of optical and near-infrared measurements of longitudinal magnetic field for CN Leo. The columns are the same as Table C.3.

JD [-2450000]	B_l [G]	Instrument
8590.0095	-486.0±56.3	SPIRou
8591.8815	-526.2±54.5	SPIRou
8592.9476	-502.4±59.5	SPIRou
8593.8996	-469.9±55.4	SPIRou
8594.9831	-557.7±59.6	SPIRou
8595.8886	-469.7±53.9	SPIRou
8596.8984	-523.5±55.7	SPIRou
8597.8470	-511.4±53.0	SPIRou
8598.9095	-452.3±58.1	SPIRou
8599.8488	-482.1±50.9	SPIRou
8600.8511	-475.8±51.2	SPIRou
8604.8814	-571.8±57.6	SPIRou
8618.7890	-494.9±59.1	SPIRou
8647.7648	-560.4±59.8	SPIRou
8648.7456	-522.5±63.9	SPIRou
8650.7529	-505.2±59.6	SPIRou
8651.7412	-358.4±59.5	SPIRou
8653.7526	-550.5±61.4	SPIRou
8655.7683	-432.6±58.7	SPIRou
8788.1333	-385.7±40.1	SPIRou
8789.1453	-408.6±48.2	SPIRou
8790.1556	-361.5±41.6	SPIRou
8791.1274	-436.4±44.4	SPIRou
8795.1410	-342.0±56.9	SPIRou
8797.1180	-512.4±84.4	SPIRou
8799.1555	-413.4±71.1	SPIRou
8801.1211	-273.0±48.8	SPIRou
8802.1173	-412.2±51.8	SPIRou
8825.1497	-361.3±52.4	SPIRou
8826.1219	-481.6±46.5	SPIRou
8827.1148	-441.2±44.5	SPIRou
8828.0792	-388.2±44.6	SPIRou
8829.1393	-388.8±44.8	SPIRou
8830.1228	-376.4±43.9	SPIRou
8875.0195	-515.9±43.1	SPIRou
8876.0165	-450.3±40.2	SPIRou
8877.0519	-444.9±42.4	SPIRou
8884.8714	-454.0±40.5	SPIRou
8888.8471	-506.5±47.8	SPIRou

Table C.5: continued.

JD [−2450000]	B_l [G]	Instrument
8895.8243	-401.4 ± 39.4	SPIRou
8896.8945	-487.5 ± 47.3	SPIRou
8897.8240	-381.7 ± 41.0	SPIRou
8898.9247	-523.8 ± 43.6	SPIRou
8920.0362	-408.7 ± 40.0	SPIRou
8920.9668	-390.5 ± 39.7	SPIRou
8976.9515	-480.5 ± 47.0	SPIRou
8978.9097	-384.2 ± 40.1	SPIRou
8981.9082	-431.0 ± 40.5	SPIRou
8982.9114	-465.3 ± 41.7	SPIRou
8983.8296	-373.3 ± 38.8	SPIRou
8984.9152	-407.7 ± 52.9	SPIRou
9005.7860	-420.1 ± 44.6	SPIRou
9007.7960	-450.6 ± 54.6	SPIRou
9008.7620	-497.0 ± 69.5	SPIRou
9009.7799	-600.3 ± 68.3	SPIRou
9010.7947	-421.1 ± 37.0	SPIRou
9154.1393	-436.4 ± 38.5	SPIRou
9156.1488	-435.4 ± 37.4	SPIRou
9157.1549	-440.1 ± 40.3	SPIRou
9158.1171	-577.5 ± 44.7	SPIRou
9159.1110	-434.8 ± 42.7	SPIRou
9208.0541	-406.4 ± 42.3	SPIRou
9209.1070	-528.8 ± 43.5	SPIRou
9210.0437	-517.6 ± 44.2	SPIRou
9213.1232	-393.4 ± 48.2	SPIRou
9214.1247	-547.2 ± 42.8	SPIRou
9215.0966	-539.9 ± 44.1	SPIRou
9217.1484	-566.1 ± 42.6	SPIRou
9218.0758	-474.9 ± 43.0	SPIRou
9219.0537	-451.0 ± 42.0	SPIRou
9220.0470	-506.1 ± 44.9	SPIRou
9221.0871	-457.7 ± 40.7	SPIRou
9222.0654	-462.0 ± 42.0	SPIRou
9222.1785	-573.1 ± 42.9	SPIRou
9223.0703	-545.8 ± 43.9	SPIRou
9223.1694	-531.2 ± 43.8	SPIRou
9266.9540	-500.9 ± 53.5	SPIRou
9266.9611	-529.6 ± 52.8	SPIRou
9267.9207	-533.6 ± 45.0	SPIRou
9269.0286	-626.1 ± 54.3	SPIRou
9271.8397	-494.0 ± 44.5	SPIRou
9274.0918	-581.2 ± 41.1	SPIRou
9276.0722	-500.7 ± 42.1	SPIRou
9276.9937	-557.0 ± 40.3	SPIRou
9278.0639	-500.5 ± 34.5	SPIRou
9294.0260	-537.0 ± 37.8	SPIRou

Table C.5: continued.

JD [−2450000]	B_l [G]	Instrument
9294.9851	-497.7 ± 37.6	SPIRou
9296.9796	-444.7 ± 35.9	SPIRou
9298.0309	-563.4 ± 38.1	SPIRou
9299.9950	-577.8 ± 37.4	SPIRou
9300.7817	-518.5 ± 41.5	SPIRou
9304.9542	-491.1 ± 39.5	SPIRou
9306.0018	-561.0 ± 37.2	SPIRou
9326.9362	-493.5 ± 43.9	SPIRou
9327.8309	-583.6 ± 40.2	SPIRou
9328.9436	-617.5 ± 46.7	SPIRou
9329.8992	-573.3 ± 45.7	SPIRou
9330.9062	-583.3 ± 49.8	SPIRou
9331.9467	-540.6 ± 39.8	SPIRou
9332.9448	-579.8 ± 42.1	SPIRou
9334.8733	-560.0 ± 38.1	SPIRou
9335.8928	-568.8 ± 39.5	SPIRou
9336.9136	-597.1 ± 53.4	SPIRou
9337.8936	-545.6 ± 43.1	SPIRou
9337.9004	-545.6 ± 43.1	SPIRou
9384.7522	-512.6 ± 98.5	SPIRou
9384.7589	-498.6 ± 67.9	SPIRou
9385.7605	-528.3 ± 40.8	SPIRou
9386.7563	-559.7 ± 38.0	SPIRou
9388.7372	-435.1 ± 33.6	SPIRou
9389.7348	-551.9 ± 39.2	SPIRou
9390.7425	-592.0 ± 43.5	SPIRou
9391.7408	-560.8 ± 42.0	SPIRou
9392.7403	-545.1 ± 37.7	SPIRou
9393.7396	-534.8 ± 40.0	SPIRou
9394.7351	-589.4 ± 42.7	SPIRou
9395.7354	-616.2 ± 49.6	SPIRou
9396.7355	-544.4 ± 42.5	SPIRou
9397.7355	-592.5 ± 60.9	SPIRou
9535.1189	-483.4 ± 40.2	SPIRou
9537.1315	-508.2 ± 39.4	SPIRou
9538.1540	-549.0 ± 39.0	SPIRou
9539.1427	-562.0 ± 38.0	SPIRou
9540.1378	-511.6 ± 36.6	SPIRou
9541.1259	-488.8 ± 37.9	SPIRou
9558.1136	-477.6 ± 50.5	SPIRou
9559.0945	-466.2 ± 45.8	SPIRou
9560.1366	-516.8 ± 43.3	SPIRou
9561.1177	-489.7 ± 37.9	SPIRou
9562.0969	-501.7 ± 36.9	SPIRou
9566.1400	-446.5 ± 47.7	SPIRou
9588.1723	-420.3 ± 37.8	SPIRou
9589.1213	-494.5 ± 36.3	SPIRou

Table C.5: continued.

JD [−2450000]	B_l [G]	Instrument
9590.1333	-448.6 ± 35.1	SPIRou
9591.1360	-464.2 ± 40.4	SPIRou
9593.1359	-480.1 ± 36.0	SPIRou
9594.1235	-425.0 ± 34.1	SPIRou
9595.1048	-360.6 ± 53.9	SPIRou
9595.1835	-462.7 ± 38.3	SPIRou
9596.1785	-455.2 ± 41.4	SPIRou
9597.1172	-470.3 ± 36.7	SPIRou
9598.1766	-418.6 ± 33.7	SPIRou
9599.1694	-513.6 ± 38.5	SPIRou
9600.1799	-447.4 ± 36.2	SPIRou
9602.1193	-460.9 ± 44.5	SPIRou
9603.0231	-413.9 ± 37.8	SPIRou
9604.1525	-428.8 ± 35.2	SPIRou
9605.1213	-478.9 ± 37.2	SPIRou
9606.1404	-418.5 ± 37.3	SPIRou
9607.1284	-444.8 ± 36.4	SPIRou
9611.1429	-477.3 ± 36.8	SPIRou
9612.1366	-495.6 ± 44.4	SPIRou
9649.8597	-462.7 ± 35.1	SPIRou
9650.8614	-488.6 ± 36.3	SPIRou
9651.8345	-431.4 ± 35.1	SPIRou
9653.9425	-465.3 ± 34.2	SPIRou
9655.8643	-431.1 ± 38.3	SPIRou
9658.9112	-443.5 ± 34.1	SPIRou
9660.9072	-392.5 ± 44.5	SPIRou
9681.9599	-512.1 ± 40.1	SPIRou
9687.9746	-440.6 ± 39.5	SPIRou
9710.8875	-531.8 ± 43.2	SPIRou
9713.9000	-496.4 ± 47.6	SPIRou
9740.7523	-450.7 ± 34.6	SPIRou

C.3 DS Leo

Table C.6: List of DS Leo observations collected with SPIRou. The columns are the same as Table C.1.

Date	UT [hh:mm:ss]	n_{cyc}	t_{exp} [s]	S/N	σ_{LSD} [$10^{-4} I_c$]
2020					
November 04	14:41:01.65	0.00	4x66	242	1.3
November 05	14:32:49.50	0.07	4x66	248	1.3
December 24	13:11:16.12	3.59	4x55	250	1.5
December 25	14:26:36.37	3.67	4x66	255	1.4
December 26	12:54:42.75	3.73	4x83	221	1.4
December 29	14:46:25.61	3.95	4x83	172	2.0
December 30	14:48:29.36	4.03	4x78	241	1.5
December 31	14:11:29.98	4.10	4x61	246	1.4

Table C.6: continued.

Date	UT [hh:mm:ss]	n_{cyc}	t_{exp} [s]	S/N	σ_{LSD} [$10^{-4}I_c$]
2021					
January 02	15:25:19.11	4.24	4x83	249	1.5
January 03	13:41:59.49	4.31	4x61	251	1.3
January 04	13:10:27.14	4.38	4x61	250	1.5
January 05	13:00:23.34	4.45	4x66	243	1.4
January 06	13:57:54.22	4.53	4x61	249	1.3
January 07	14:05:48.84	4.60	4x61	247	1.3
January 08	14:15:30.20	4.67	4x66	243	1.4
February 21	11:23:11.74	7.83	4x72	234	1.5
February 22	12:44:47.36	7.90	4x72	250	1.5
February 23	14:13:45.11	7.98	4x72	113	3.5
February 23	14:56:45.73	7.98	4x72	206	1.6
February 26	10:15:48.22	8.18	4x72	269	1.3
February 28	14:29:34.27	8.34	4x72	280	1.0
March 02	14:02:39.82	8.48	4x72	235	1.5
March 03	12:08:50.87	8.55	4x72	240	1.3
March 04	13:42:07.40	8.62	4x72	285	1.2
March 20	12:54:55.01	9.77	4x72	275	1.2
March 21	11:56:28.50	9.84	4x72	232	1.5
March 22	13:26:55.90	9.92	4x72	224	1.5
March 23	11:52:40.55	9.98	4x72	273	1.1
March 24	13:02:40.05	10.06	4x72	277	1.3
March 26	12:24:48.47	10.20	4x72	175	2.0
March 27	7:03:51.09	10.26	4x72	233	1.3
March 31	11:11:31.74	10.56	4x72	252	1.4
April 01	12:19:51.08	10.63	4x72	269	1.2
April 22	10:49:28.41	12.14	4x72	246	1.5
April 23	8:52:58.20	12.20	4x72	269	1.4
April 24	10:56:14.16	12.28	4x72	241	1.5
April 25	9:52:11.19	12.35	4x72	173	1.8
April 26	10:03:37.95	12.42	4x72	157	2.5
April 26	10:52:46.47	12.43	4x72	183	2.8
April 27	11:01:16.31	12.50	4x72	240	1.4
April 28	10:58:29.76	12.57	4x72	257	1.2
April 30	10:17:36.74	12.71	4x72	280	1.2
May 01	10:26:10.76	12.78	4x72	261	1.4
May 02	10:13:59.09	12.86	4x72	224	1.7
May 03	9:56:11.36	12.93	4x72	234	1.3
June 19	6:32:04.07	16.29	4x72	182	1.6
June 19	6:38:49.98	16.30	4x72	171	1.7
June 20	6:32:32.52	16.37	4x72	241	1.3
June 21	6:27:02.17	16.44	4x72	280	1.4
June 23	6:00:08.67	16.58	4x72	258	1.3
June 24	5:57:16.62	16.65	4x72	283	1.2
June 25	6:06:01.63	16.72	4x72	235	1.4
June 26	5:57:21.88	16.80	4x72	293	1.3
June 27	5:59:26.04	16.87	4x72	286	1.5

Table C.6: continued.

Date	UT [hh:mm:ss]	n_{cyc}	t_{exp} [s]	S/N	σ_{LSD} [$10^{-4}I_c$]
June 28	6:02:42.25	16.94	4x72	295	1.4
June 29	5:56:45.44	17.01	4x72	242	1.6
June 30	5:58:09.69	17.08	4x72	220	1.6
July 01	5:58:11.25	17.16	4x72	241	1.6
July 02	5:57:49.39	17.23	4x72	195	2.0
July 17	5:56:11.39	18.31	4x72	271	1.3
July 19	5:46:33.47	18.45	4x72	239	1.4
November 16	15:08:48.28	27.10	4x72	273	1.3
November 17	15:38:53.47	27.18	4x72	236	1.3
November 18	15:01:36.89	27.25	4x72	280	1.3
November 19	15:34:03.76	27.32	4x72	302	1.1
November 20	15:17:58.29	27.39	4x72	260	1.3
November 20	15:55:15.68	27.39	4x72	273	1.4
November 21	15:10:49.20	27.46	4x72	278	1.4
November 22	14:53:39.28	27.53	4x72	293	1.2
December 09	15:17:03.16	28.76	4x72	284	1.3
December 10	14:49:25.95	28.83	4x72	233	1.5
December 11	15:49:49.61	28.90	4x72	217	1.4
December 13	14:59:58.41	29.04	4x72	287	1.1
December 15	14:37:49.46	29.19	4x72	256	1.4
December 17	15:55:58.97	29.34	4x72	203	2.0
December 18	15:05:25.50	29.40	4x72	248	1.5
2022					
January 06	15:05:19.45	30.77	4x72	265	1.3
January 08	15:34:42.78	30.92	4x72	279	1.3
January 09	14:22:30.48	30.98	4x72	291	1.3
January 10	15:03:28.46	31.06	4x72	295	1.3
January 12	16:22:44.45	31.21	4x72	263	1.3
January 13	14:39:32.63	31.27	4x72	250	1.4
January 14	14:23:12.69	31.34	4x72	285	1.1
January 15	16:16:39.50	31.42	4x72	261	1.3
January 16	14:47:37.30	31.49	4x72	163	1.9
January 17	15:00:18.40	31.56	4x72	263	1.2
January 18	16:06:47.82	31.64	4x72	288	1.4
January 19	16:21:07.15	31.71	4x72	277	1.2
January 20	16:11:30.66	31.78	4x72	277	1.4
January 22	15:03:23.65	31.92	4x72	193	1.7
January 24	15:01:19.06	32.06	4x72	295	1.2
January 25	15:30:10.81	32.14	4x72	266	1.2
January 26	14:25:07.09	32.21	4x72	277	1.4
January 31	14:50:19.86	32.57	4x72	265	1.3
February 01	15:01:09.68	32.64	4x72	150	2.1
February 01	15:08:29.53	32.64	4x72	162	1.8
March 11	8:48:01.68	35.35	4x72	292	1.1
March 12	10:53:43.46	35.43	4x72	256	1.2
March 13	11:22:40.32	35.50	4x72	288	1.3
March 14	8:28:17.21	35.57	4x72	295	1.2

Table C.6: continued.

Date	UT [hh:mm:ss]	n_{cyc}	t_{exp} [s]	S/N	σ_{LSD} [$10^{-4}I_c$]
March 15	12:22:54.90	35.65	4x72	286	1.1
March 16	13:16:17.50	35.73	4x72	251	1.3
March 17	11:09:30.70	35.79	4x72	267	1.5
March 18	13:20:13.72	35.87	4x72	218	1.6
March 19	13:06:09.07	35.94	4x72	270	1.3
March 20	11:47:25.79	36.01	4x72	293	1.2
March 22	11:42:33.77	36.15	4x72	244	1.5
March 23	11:05:20.41	36.22	4x72	102	1.2
March 23	11:55:50.39	36.22	4x72	275	1.2
April 09	11:37:18.90	37.45	4x72	271	1.4
April 12	11:20:02.08	37.66	4x72	265	1.4
April 13	11:46:22.06	37.73	4x72	267	1.3
April 14	12:06:31.61	37.81	4x72	172	2.1
April 15	11:32:16.57	37.88	4x72	266	1.5
April 18	11:33:35.81	38.09	4x72	262	1.4
April 19	11:06:39.63	38.16	4x72	262	1.2
April 20	10:47:12.72	38.23	4x72	281	1.3
April 21	10:45:48.61	38.31	4x72	289	1.3
May 11	9:35:49.87	39.74	4x72	247	1.4
May 12	9:47:34.23	39.81	4x72	245	1.4
May 13	9:11:53.37	39.88	4x72	235	1.4
May 16	8:31:03.28	40.10	4x72	267	1.5
May 17	8:38:05.11	40.17	4x72	285	1.4
June 02	6:33:44.50	41.31	4x72	280	1.3
June 03	6:29:45.48	41.38	4x72	273	1.3
June 05	6:38:13.26	41.53	4x72	277	1.2
June 06	8:16:18.89	41.61	4x72	262	1.4
June 08	6:00:13.71	41.74	4x72	266	1.4
June 09	6:01:26.80	41.81	4x72	281	1.2
June 10	7:06:39.01	41.89	4x72	278	1.2

Table C.7: List of optical and near-infrared measurements of longitudinal magnetic field for DS Leo. The columns are the same as Table C.3.

HJD [-2450000]	B_l [G]	Instrument
3748.1023	4.7 ± 5.9	ESPaDOnS
3748.9053	23.6 ± 13.1	ESPaDOnS
3774.0359	9.8 ± 6.0	ESPaDOnS
3781.1526	-7.9 ± 9.1	ESPaDOnS
4126.6502	-16.5 ± 8.9	NARVAL
4127.6349	-4.5 ± 7.3	NARVAL
4128.6469	1.7 ± 5.9	NARVAL
4129.6107	22.4 ± 5.7	NARVAL
4130.6536	23.1 ± 5.4	NARVAL
4133.6704	20.2 ± 5.5	NARVAL
4134.6568	14.0 ± 5.5	NARVAL

Table C.7: continued.

HJD [−2450000]	B_l [G]	Instrument
4135.6695	12.6±5.3	NARVAL
4136.6303	30.1±10.0	NARVAL
4462.6760	5.0±6.0	NARVAL
4463.7049	7.8±5.3	NARVAL
4465.7095	27.0±7.2	NARVAL
4466.7091	25.0±5.4	NARVAL
4468.7075	74.6±11.7	NARVAL
4472.6258	16.4±13.3	NARVAL
4473.6232	1.5±7.2	NARVAL
4484.5805	17.1±11.7	NARVAL
4485.5564	−6.5±10.5	NARVAL
4487.5839	−0.8±8.6	NARVAL
4489.5328	19.8±7.6	NARVAL
4491.5490	13.4±7.5	NARVAL
4492.5717	2.9±5.8	NARVAL
4493.5834	1.7±6.4	NARVAL
4499.6016	−10.8±6.8	NARVAL
4501.5834	6.5±7.7	NARVAL
4502.5820	12.2±6.0	NARVAL
4503.5804	4.3±6.2	NARVAL
4506.5933	18.7±6.1	NARVAL
4507.5570	6.3±5.7	NARVAL
4508.5856	29.6±6.3	NARVAL
4509.5907	28.6±6.7	NARVAL
4510.5857	27.9±8.4	NARVAL
4511.6026	−0.9±6.2	NARVAL
4512.5883	−0.5±6.8	NARVAL
4513.5876	−2.1±6.0	NARVAL
4862.6428	46.2±14.1	NARVAL
5266.4448	29.3±7.0	NARVAL
5268.4569	55.1±6.5	NARVAL
5269.4287	41.6±6.8	NARVAL
5270.5521	22.8±7.5	NARVAL
5271.5597	9.2±5.3	NARVAL
5272.5173	−5.3±11.5	NARVAL
5278.4970	−16.0±5.7	NARVAL
5284.4554	61.1±9.6	NARVAL
5292.4695	163.2±27.1	NARVAL
5293.3366	22.5±6.2	NARVAL
5295.5424	38.9±6.1	NARVAL
5296.4579	44.9±5.7	NARVAL
5297.3607	33.0±5.7	NARVAL
5302.5069	−10.0±5.9	NARVAL
5303.4522	−9.5±5.8	NARVAL
5304.3913	−17.4±5.6	NARVAL
5310.3818	19.8±6.6	NARVAL
5311.4403	21.0±6.5	NARVAL

Table C.7: continued.

HJD [−2450000]	B_l [G]	Instrument
5312.3920	35.1±5.9	NARVAL
5586.5978	18.2±7.0	NARVAL
5587.5790	18.5±6.0	NARVAL
5588.5849	25.8±5.6	NARVAL
5589.5985	44.9±7.0	NARVAL
5593.5929	−3.9±6.1	NARVAL
5596.5681	−0.3±6.5	NARVAL
5597.5715	−0.8±5.4	NARVAL
5598.5820	18.2±6.3	NARVAL
6048.3494	−4.6±7.2	NARVAL
6050.3464	34.7±13.0	NARVAL
6084.3812	61.7±17.4	NARVAL
6092.3807	12.1±13.0	NARVAL
6093.3758	68.2±19.5	NARVAL
6094.3724	46.5±19.9	NARVAL
6095.3935	3.3±12.2	NARVAL
6100.3997	32.7±10.3	NARVAL
6101.3914	23.4±8.9	NARVAL
6102.4207	16.7±10.5	NARVAL
6103.4078	24.9±14.6	NARVAL
6667.6945	0.1±5.9	NARVAL
6669.6203	4.5±6.7	NARVAL
6744.3769	31.2±14.3	NARVAL
6754.4270	33.0±8.1	NARVAL
6756.4720	24.4±5.7	NARVAL
6757.4436	14.9±5.7	NARVAL
6759.5429	7.3±7.0	NARVAL
6760.4614	16.6±6.2	NARVAL
6761.4555	10.6±5.9	NARVAL
6762.4030	17.1±8.0	NARVAL
6763.4675	13.5±5.9	NARVAL
6764.4372	1.0±5.7	NARVAL
6765.4610	4.6±7.1	NARVAL
6786.3669	18.8±6.7	NARVAL
6787.3714	3.9±6.0	NARVAL
9158.1132	−23.1±7.1	SPIRou
9159.1076	0.1±7.1	SPIRou
9208.0545	1.3±7.5	SPIRou
9209.1069	−3.3±7.3	SPIRou
9210.0431	−17.6±7.6	SPIRou
9213.1208	−10.8±10.0	SPIRou
9214.1222	−10.7±8.1	SPIRou
9215.0966	8.5±7.1	SPIRou
9217.1479	50.3±7.2	SPIRou
9218.0762	30.9±7.3	SPIRou
9219.0543	25.0±7.2	SPIRou
9220.0473	7.9±7.4	SPIRou

Table C.7: continued.

HJD [−2450000]	B_l [G]	Instrument
9221.0873	19.4±7.4	SPIRou
9222.0928	0.5±7.2	SPIRou
9223.0996	−25.3±7.2	SPIRou
9266.9790	−26.9±8.0	SPIRou
9268.0356	−34.3±6.9	SPIRou
9269.0974	−10.1±21.6	SPIRou
9269.1272	−10.5±9.9	SPIRou
9271.9320	24.7±7.1	SPIRou
9274.1081	28.4±6.2	SPIRou
9276.0892	8.3±8.1	SPIRou
9277.0101	19.6±7.6	SPIRou
9278.0748	5.7±6.0	SPIRou
9294.0409	−22.1±6.3	SPIRou
9295.0002	−28.7±7.6	SPIRou
9296.0629	−16.8±8.1	SPIRou
9296.9974	−17.8±6.2	SPIRou
9298.0459	−15.9±6.3	SPIRou
9300.0194	13.8±10.0	SPIRou
9300.7965	17.5±7.2	SPIRou
9304.9681	24.8±7.1	SPIRou
9306.0155	3.7±6.5	SPIRou
9326.9507	21.8±7.5	SPIRou
9327.8698	24.1±7.1	SPIRou
9328.9553	24.1±7.5	SPIRou
9329.9107	8.5±10.4	SPIRou
9330.9185	5.0±14.0	SPIRou
9330.9527	56.5±16.7	SPIRou
9331.9585	31.4±7.2	SPIRou
9332.9564	20.3±6.7	SPIRou
9334.9279	4.2±6.4	SPIRou
9335.9337	−22.0±7.1	SPIRou
9336.9252	−34.0±8.0	SPIRou
9337.9127	−26.9±7.2	SPIRou
9384.7675	−16.4±10.6	SPIRou
9384.7722	−8.1±10.1	SPIRou
9385.7677	−4.6±7.5	SPIRou
9386.7639	39.9±6.2	SPIRou
9388.7451	27.9±6.9	SPIRou
9389.7431	17.5±6.3	SPIRou
9390.7491	−16.2±7.2	SPIRou
9391.7430	−36.3±6.2	SPIRou
9392.7444	−48.3±6.7	SPIRou
9393.7467	−53.5±6.2	SPIRou
9394.7425	−33.7±7.6	SPIRou
9395.7435	−19.6±8.5	SPIRou
9396.7434	−15.0±7.9	SPIRou
9397.7432	38.1±10.3	SPIRou

Table C.7: continued.

HJD [−2450000]	B_l [G]	Instrument
9412.7417	2.6±6.8	SPIRou
9414.7350	30.3±7.6	SPIRou
9535.1336	8.1±6.7	SPIRou
9536.1546	0.6±7.2	SPIRou
9537.1288	17.3±6.7	SPIRou
9538.1514	3.0±5.9	SPIRou
9539.1403	−3.0±7.2	SPIRou
9539.1662	11.7±6.8	SPIRou
9540.1354	−7.2±6.7	SPIRou
9541.1236	−2.4±6.4	SPIRou
9558.1411	−20.4±6.7	SPIRou
9559.1219	−5.6±8.1	SPIRou
9560.1639	−10.5±8.4	SPIRou
9562.1294	−2.2±6.1	SPIRou
9564.1142	23.9±7.1	SPIRou
9566.1686	26.4±11.7	SPIRou
9567.1335	2.1±7.6	SPIRou
9586.1341	−15.5±6.4	SPIRou
9588.1546	−16.4±6.2	SPIRou
9589.1044	−25.0±6.1	SPIRou
9590.1329	−30.8±5.9	SPIRou
9592.1880	31.6±6.6	SPIRou
9593.1163	36.9±6.9	SPIRou
9594.1050	33.5±6.0	SPIRou
9595.1838	29.1±6.4	SPIRou
9596.1219	19.4±9.9	SPIRou
9597.1307	−4.8±6.3	SPIRou
9598.1769	−1.7±6.2	SPIRou
9599.1869	−22.7±6.2	SPIRou
9600.1802	−22.5±6.5	SPIRou
9602.1329	11.4±10.1	SPIRou
9604.1314	−14.0±5.8	SPIRou
9605.1515	−5.9±6.5	SPIRou
9606.1063	10.3±6.2	SPIRou
9611.1237	14.3±6.7	SPIRou
9612.1312	−15.2±10.5	SPIRou
9612.1363	2.1±9.6	SPIRou
9649.8702	28.7±5.8	SPIRou
9650.9574	15.3±6.9	SPIRou
9651.9774	28.7±6.2	SPIRou
9652.8562	23.9±6.0	SPIRou
9654.0191	−7.1±6.1	SPIRou
9655.0560	−3.6±7.0	SPIRou
9655.9679	−14.7±6.7	SPIRou
9657.0586	−14.8±8.5	SPIRou
9658.0488	−20.6±6.7	SPIRou
9658.9940	−19.4±6.0	SPIRou

Table C.7: continued.

HJD [−2450000]	B_l [G]	Instrument
9660.9905	5.4 ± 7.6	SPIRou
9661.9645	9.8 ± 6.3	SPIRou
9661.9996	9.8 ± 6.3	SPIRou
9678.9852	12.5 ± 6.7	SPIRou
9681.9729	-10.0 ± 7.1	SPIRou
9682.9911	-34.1 ± 6.7	SPIRou
9684.0050	-18.1 ± 11.7	SPIRou
9684.9812	-15.7 ± 7.0	SPIRou
9687.9818	-5.8 ± 7.6	SPIRou
9688.9630	8.6 ± 6.9	SPIRou
9689.9494	7.2 ± 6.5	SPIRou
9690.9483	2.5 ± 6.6	SPIRou
9710.8979	-5.0 ± 7.4	SPIRou
9711.9059	-22.3 ± 7.1	SPIRou
9712.8811	-13.4 ± 7.7	SPIRou
9715.8525	-20.7 ± 6.9	SPIRou
9716.8573	12.9 ± 6.7	SPIRou
9732.7697	3.7 ± 6.6	SPIRou
9733.7668	9.3 ± 6.8	SPIRou
9735.7726	-1.8 ± 6.7	SPIRou
9736.8406	-15.7 ± 6.9	SPIRou
9738.7460	-4.2 ± 6.9	SPIRou
9739.7468	-2.2 ± 6.5	SPIRou
9740.7920	6.2 ± 6.5	SPIRou

C.4 EV Lac

Table C.8: List of EV Lac observations collected with SPIRou. The format is the same as Table C.1.

Date	UT [hh:mm:ss]	n_{cyc}	t_{exp} [s]	S/N	σ_{LSD} [$10^{-4} I_c$]
2019					
September 11	13:55:51.10	0.00	4x61	177	1.5
September 18	9:14:04.52	1.56	4x61	258	1.5
September 19	8:18:23.93	1.78	4x61	273	1.6
September 20	11:55:01.36	2.04	4x61	219	1.8
September 24	8:10:20.29	2.93	4x61	277	1.5
September 25	10:26:04.22	3.18	4x61	274	1.5
September 26	8:19:18.57	3.39	4x61	279	1.8
October 02	8:44:59.95	4.77	4x61	208	1.8
October 05	8:01:27.77	5.45	4x61	271	1.8
October 06	7:41:48.50	5.67	4x61	279	2.0
October 07	10:11:10.32	5.93	4x61	235	1.8
October 09	9:39:22.98	6.38	4x61	262	1.6
October 12	10:46:51.96	7.08	4x61	237	1.6
October 14	8:56:36.72	7.52	4x61	248	1.6
October 16	8:59:26.66	7.98	4x61	240	1.6

Table C.8: continued.

Date	UT [hh:mm:ss]	n_{cyc}	t_{exp} [s]	S/N	σ_{LSD} [$10^{-4}I_c$]
October 31	8:22:51.21	11.41	4x61	192	1.7
November 01	8:45:36.02	11.65	4x61	222	1.3
November 02	7:17:00.73	11.86	4x61	242	1.5
November 03	8:05:36.05	12.10	4x61	217	1.6
November 04	7:12:06.27	12.32	4x61	167	2.1
November 05	10:10:50.67	12.58	4x61	214	1.7
November 07	8:39:07.45	13.02	4x61	196	1.9
November 09	8:40:23.42	13.48	4x61	213	1.8
November 10	9:19:14.54	13.72	4x61	208	1.9
November 11	9:11:19.59	13.95	4x61	171	2.0
November 12	7:45:35.45	14.16	4x61	232	1.7
November 13	8:19:17.48	14.40	4x61	206	1.7
November 14	7:44:47.84	14.62	4x61	230	1.8
December 05	6:51:09.99	19.43	4x61	188	1.9
December 08	7:17:20.12	20.12	4x61	220	1.7
December 09	7:39:53.15	20.35	4x61	204	2.1
December 10	6:23:03.35	20.57	4x61	221	1.8
December 11	6:43:05.45	20.80	4x61	244	1.6
December 12	5:41:28.65	21.02	4x61	265	1.5
December 13	6:46:22.38	21.26	4x61	229	1.6
2020					
July 27	14:59:58.04	73.40	4x61	238	1.5
July 29	11:20:47.34	73.83	4x61	259	1.3
July 30	11:14:11.73	74.06	4x61	257	1.3
July 31	14:56:34.88	74.32	4x61	245	1.3
August 01	11:55:22.15	74.52	4x61	267	1.5
August 02	11:19:59.63	74.75	4x61	265	1.4
August 03	12:13:13.60	74.98	4x61	261	1.3
August 04	10:42:02.97	75.20	4x61	281	1.5
August 06	12:38:28.82	75.68	4x61	139	2.3
August 06	12:44:56.78	75.68	4x61	129	2.2
August 08	12:36:54.83	76.13	4x61	182	1.9
August 09	13:04:12.53	76.37	4x61	229	1.5
August 10	12:26:01.62	76.59	4x61	276	1.4
August 11	13:28:42.14	76.83	4x61	270	1.2
August 26	11:49:46.00	80.26	4x61	227	1.5
August 27	11:20:50.23	80.48	4x61	262	1.5
August 28	10:03:49.00	80.70	4x61	305	1.4
August 29	12:07:39.46	80.95	4x61	279	1.2
August 30	12:10:25.30	81.18	4x61	240	1.4
August 31	11:56:19.84	81.40	4x61	284	1.3
September 01	10:23:01.42	81.62	4x61	283	1.3
September 02	10:16:13.69	81.85	4x61	285	1.2
September 03	12:27:38.73	82.10	4x61	277	1.4
September 04	12:28:09.24	82.33	4x61	270	1.6
September 05	12:12:24.68	82.55	4x61	233	1.4
September 06	11:50:38.31	82.78	4x61	253	1.3

Table C.8: continued.

Date	UT [hh:mm:ss]	n_{cyc}	t_{exp} [s]	S/N	σ_{LSD} [$10^{-4}I_c$]
September 08	10:55:48.32	83.23	4x61	285	1.2
September 09	10:11:06.99	83.45	4x61	297	1.6
September 10	10:13:11.62	83.68	4x61	299	1.3
September 18	9:25:02.88	85.51	4x61	255	1.5
September 19	10:05:48.40	85.74	4x61	194	1.7
September 20	11:48:32.60	85.99	4x61	288	1.3
September 21	8:20:51.79	86.19	4x61	216	1.7
September 22	8:35:31.66	86.42	4x61	281	1.2
September 23	8:13:19.93	86.64	4x61	277	1.6
September 25	9:15:08.47	87.11	4x61	313	1.4
September 26	7:33:25.24	87.32	4x61	246	1.4
September 27	7:42:07.90	87.56	4x61	306	1.5
September 28	7:41:26.06	87.78	4x61	306	1.4
September 29	7:38:29.25	88.01	4x61	304	1.4
September 30	8:40:14.19	88.25	4x61	299	1.2
October 01	9:45:52.92	88.49	4x61	261	1.4
October 03	8:12:28.39	88.94	4x61	256	1.5
October 04	8:57:10.35	89.17	4x61	280	1.5
October 05	8:29:39.33	89.40	4x61	270	1.5
October 06	10:31:49.98	89.65	4x61	267	1.4
October 07	8:22:05.70	89.86	4x61	305	1.2
November 01	8:15:35.26	95.59	4x61	307	1.4
November 03	9:05:33.11	96.05	4x61	313	1.1
November 04	8:50:23.57	96.28	4x61	280	1.3
November 05	6:47:10.96	96.49	4x61	307	1.4
December 24	6:12:25.23	107.72	4x61	292	1.4
December 25	4:53:19.85	107.94	4x61	286	1.3
December 26	5:33:37.73	108.18	4x61	299	1.2
December 29	6:13:56.63	108.87	4x61	254	1.3
December 30	4:44:03.71	109.09	4x61	237	1.4
December 31	5:48:42.91	109.33	4x61	261	1.6
2021					
January 01	4:37:16.34	109.54	4x61	253	1.6
January 02	5:09:55.69	109.78	4x61	269	1.3
January 03	5:47:29.85	110.01	4x61	278	1.3
January 04	5:00:26.60	110.24	4x61	291	1.2
January 05	5:17:26.10	110.47	4x61	261	1.4
January 06	5:01:25.17	110.69	4x61	289	1.3
January 07	5:21:18.80	110.93	4x61	275	1.5
January 07	6:08:01.35	110.93	4x61	257	1.3
January 08	5:29:10.80	111.16	4x61	251	1.4
January 08	6:17:39.99	111.17	4x61	272	1.3
June 20	12:20:33.62	148.61	4x61	300	1.4
June 21	12:09:03.29	148.84	4x61	253	1.4
June 22	10:34:16.22	149.05	4x61	170	3.2
June 22	10:40:11.40	149.05	4x61	133	2.8
June 23	12:19:50.11	149.30	4x61	311	1.1

Table C.8: continued.

Date	UT [hh:mm:ss]	n_{cyc}	t_{exp} [s]	S/N	σ_{LSD} [$10^{-4}I_c$]
June 24	13:12:53.35	149.53	4x61	287	1.5
June 25	13:02:56.56	149.76	4x61	285	1.8
June 26	13:28:16.27	150.00	4x61	308	1.4
June 27	13:07:23.34	150.22	4x61	324	1.3
June 28	13:48:12.59	150.46	4x61	292	1.4
June 29	12:23:06.45	150.67	4x61	304	1.6
June 30	14:57:58.81	150.93	4x61	248	1.4
July 01	12:53:56.69	151.14	4x61	266	1.4
July 02	12:38:58.59	151.36	4x61	280	1.3
July 17	13:01:17.98	154.81	4x61	222	1.4
July 18	12:56:59.07	155.04	4x61	244	1.6
July 19	10:45:04.51	155.24	4x61	255	1.8
July 20	12:29:36.88	155.49	4x61	305	1.3
July 21	13:44:44.47	155.73	4x61	276	1.4
July 25	14:01:52.56	156.65	4x61	201	2.1
July 27	13:32:52.79	157.11	4x61	280	1.3
August 13	12:41:46.76	161.00	4x61	293	1.4
August 14	9:26:02.95	161.20	4x61	302	1.3
August 15	8:41:13.87	161.42	4x61	301	1.2
August 16	8:27:44.94	161.64	4x61	305	1.3
August 17	9:59:38.41	161.89	4x61	275	1.4
August 18	12:25:00.60	162.14	4x61	312	1.3
August 19	7:49:01.33	162.33	4x61	303	1.2
August 20	9:48:31.18	162.58	4x61	194	2.0
August 21	10:45:00.86	162.81	4x61	220	1.7
August 22	10:23:55.51	163.04	4x61	277	1.5
August 23	9:57:29.39	163.26	4x61	308	1.4
August 24	13:07:34.34	163.52	4x61	255	1.6
August 25	9:05:11.93	163.72	4x61	286	1.3
August 26	8:53:03.17	163.94	4x61	309	1.3
September 15	9:41:58.73	168.54	4x61	304	1.4
September 17	9:37:52.17	169.00	4x61	308	1.2
September 18	8:05:34.97	169.21	4x61	323	1.3
September 19	7:42:11.87	169.44	4x61	310	1.0
September 20	8:37:10.74	169.67	4x61	316	1.3
September 21	8:14:05.06	169.90	4x61	259	1.4
September 22	8:09:20.14	170.13	4x61	328	1.3
September 23	7:50:05.57	170.35	4x61	322	1.3
September 24	7:57:29.68	170.59	4x61	327	1.4
October 15	7:00:00.33	175.39	4x61	329	1.2
October 16	7:58:44.35	175.63	4x61	306	1.4
October 17	7:39:54.74	175.86	4x61	265	1.3
October 19	11:41:55.58	176.35	4x61	317	1.3
October 20	7:14:06.57	176.54	4x61	292	1.3
October 21	8:04:58.67	176.78	4x61	277	1.5
October 22	6:47:00.27	177.00	4x61	260	1.6
October 23	7:23:28.60	177.23	4x61	302	1.1

Table C.8: continued.

Date	UT [hh:mm:ss]	n_{cyc}	t_{exp} [s]	S/N	σ_{LSD} [$10^{-4}I_c$]
October 24	8:28:04.13	177.47	4x61	261	1.6
October 25	6:06:35.30	177.68	4x61	300	1.3
October 26	7:02:29.73	177.92	4x61	305	1.2
October 27	9:46:41.47	178.17	4x61	295	1.1
November 19	6:45:55.17	183.42	4x61	309	1.2
November 20	6:27:30.27	183.64	4x61	286	1.1
November 21	6:25:45.70	183.87	4x61	240	1.4
November 22	7:03:53.33	184.11	4x61	177	2.4

Table C.9: List of optical and near-infrared measurements of longitudinal magnetic field for EV Lac. The format is the same as Table C.3.

JD [−2450000]	B_l [G]	Instrument
3569.1119	144.4±8.3	ESPaDOnS
3606.1478	−305.9±20.4	ESPaDOnS
3631.9065	23.9±9.4	ESPaDOnS
3631.9447	−106.2±11.0	ESPaDOnS
3631.9828	−82.9±9.6	ESPaDOnS
3953.0731	−529.5±20.6	ESPaDOnS
3955.0663	319.8±15.1	ESPaDOnS
3956.0600	−354.3±13.8	ESPaDOnS
3957.0597	−422.4±18.1	ESPaDOnS
3958.0723	−282.6±15.9	ESPaDOnS
3959.0728	290.1±15.0	ESPaDOnS
3960.0761	−161.0±15.2	ESPaDOnS
4309.5464	76.7±11.4	NARVAL
4310.5661	−410.9±17.8	NARVAL
4311.5937	−543.7±23.3	NARVAL
4312.5937	41.5±16.1	NARVAL
4313.5958	265.1±21.5	NARVAL
4315.6018	−462.3±23.1	NARVAL
4316.5998	−273.2±18.9	NARVAL
4317.6712	350.3±22.7	NARVAL
4322.5952	88.4±17.6	NARVAL
4323.5977	−367.3±24.1	NARVAL
4327.5882	−311.3±19.7	NARVAL
4330.5813	382.1±20.8	NARVAL
4331.5149	−28.1±14.7	NARVAL
4340.5300	−214.6±20.0	NARVAL
4343.5212	228.4±22.1	NARVAL
4986.5995	264.8±18.4	NARVAL
4994.6321	0.5±20.9	NARVAL
4995.5842	251.6±38.6	NARVAL
5059.3898	48.0±18.3	NARVAL
5370.5520	92.9±16.7	NARVAL
5384.6114	−49.5±13.4	NARVAL

Table C.9: continued.

JD [−2450000]	B_l [G]	Instrument
5385.5601	-176.2 ± 15.1	NARVAL
5388.5822	23.4 ± 14.6	NARVAL
5390.5888	-203.6 ± 25.4	NARVAL
5392.5938	-73.6 ± 14.2	NARVAL
5396.5771	22.4 ± 13.2	NARVAL
5401.5894	76.7 ± 14.0	NARVAL
5402.5222	-87.1 ± 14.5	NARVAL
5403.5208	-270.5 ± 18.7	NARVAL
5411.5386	-194.8 ± 15.6	NARVAL
5414.5135	93.9 ± 14.1	NARVAL
5415.5838	-105.8 ± 16.3	NARVAL
5416.5916	-297.6 ± 16.2	NARVAL
5419.5954	-58.9 ± 14.3	NARVAL
5420.5813	-306.3 ± 19.1	NARVAL
5425.6210	-231.6 ± 14.9	NARVAL
5426.5908	-143.6 ± 14.6	NARVAL
5429.5743	-355.4 ± 21.8	NARVAL
5430.6048	-168.5 ± 16.1	NARVAL
7584.5642	-97.8 ± 15.2	NARVAL
7585.5742	-107.6 ± 20.7	NARVAL
7588.5683	5.1 ± 13.9	NARVAL
7595.5856	-93.8 ± 15.0	NARVAL
7608.4675	-61.2 ± 15.2	NARVAL
7612.5894	-50.4 ± 17.5	NARVAL
8738.0805	120.8 ± 26.4	SPIRou
8744.8848	-151.5 ± 22.6	SPIRou
8745.8461	47.1 ± 22.6	SPIRou
8746.9965	57.1 ± 28.9	SPIRou
8750.8405	130.8 ± 21.0	SPIRou
8751.9348	-14.5 ± 22.0	SPIRou
8752.8467	-82.0 ± 21.9	SPIRou
8758.8646	-42.6 ± 34.0	SPIRou
8761.8343	-71.1 ± 22.1	SPIRou
8762.8207	-114.5 ± 22.0	SPIRou
8763.9244	201.6 ± 26.9	SPIRou
8765.9023	-23.3 ± 22.3	SPIRou
8768.9492	64.0 ± 24.4	SPIRou
8770.8726	-160.7 ± 24.0	SPIRou
8772.8746	113.7 ± 25.4	SPIRou
8787.8492	-43.4 ± 28.4	SPIRou
8788.8650	-171.5 ± 22.8	SPIRou
8789.8035	121.3 ± 21.6	SPIRou
8790.8372	82.6 ± 23.3	SPIRou
8791.8001	18.3 ± 29.9	SPIRou
8792.9242	-136.4 ± 25.1	SPIRou
8794.8605	149.6 ± 31.5	SPIRou
8796.8614	-126.4 ± 34.2	SPIRou

Table C.9: continued.

JD [−2450000]	B_l [G]	Instrument
8797.8884	−66.1±37.9	SPIRou
8798.8829	182.5±42.1	SPIRou
8799.8233	−57.3±29.1	SPIRou
8800.8467	−53.9±31.4	SPIRou
8801.8228	−101.7±31.7	SPIRou
8822.7855	−164.5±33.4	SPIRou
8825.8037	6.6±28.6	SPIRou
8826.8194	9.1±32.7	SPIRou
8827.7660	−205.7±29.1	SPIRou
8828.7799	−5.1±25.3	SPIRou
8829.7371	201.0±24.4	SPIRou
8830.7822	−30.8±28.0	SPIRou
9058.1250	−173.8±20.7	SPIRou
9059.9728	54.1±17.8	SPIRou
9060.9682	222.0±18.8	SPIRou
9062.1226	−45.8±18.8	SPIRou
9062.9968	−355.7±19.6	SPIRou
9063.9722	−119.3±18.8	SPIRou
9065.0092	175.9±18.9	SPIRou
9065.9459	119.8±18.6	SPIRou
9068.0267	−329.2±43.3	SPIRou
9068.0312	−293.3±42.1	SPIRou
9070.0256	206.8±30.3	SPIRou
9071.0446	−137.7±21.0	SPIRou
9072.0181	−381.7±19.1	SPIRou
9073.0616	21.9±16.9	SPIRou
9087.9929	−13.6±24.4	SPIRou
9088.9728	−315.0±19.7	SPIRou
9089.9193	−304.9±17.8	SPIRou
9091.0053	116.5±17.4	SPIRou
9092.0072	160.0±19.9	SPIRou
9092.9975	−237.8±17.2	SPIRou
9093.9327	−305.1±18.7	SPIRou
9094.9279	12.8±16.2	SPIRou
9096.0192	217.5±18.1	SPIRou
9097.0196	−95.4±18.3	SPIRou
9098.0086	−387.9±22.0	SPIRou
9098.9935	−92.1±18.3	SPIRou
9100.9554	71.0±17.0	SPIRou
9101.9244	−258.0±20.4	SPIRou
9102.9258	−273.3±18.2	SPIRou
9110.8924	−327.2±21.0	SPIRou
9111.9207	−166.5±26.8	SPIRou
9112.9920	137.9±18.2	SPIRou
9113.8478	184.2±25.4	SPIRou
9114.8580	−227.5±18.5	SPIRou
9115.8426	−338.7±19.5	SPIRou

Table C.9: continued.

JD [−2450000]	B_l [G]	Instrument
9117.8855	254.0±18.3	SPIRou
9118.8149	−30.6±21.3	SPIRou
9119.8209	−469.1±19.2	SPIRou
9120.8204	−94.8±18.3	SPIRou
9121.8184	191.1±18.3	SPIRou
9122.8613	82.0±17.2	SPIRou
9123.9069	−364.0±20.7	SPIRou
9125.8420	120.7±18.7	SPIRou
9126.8730	250.2±20.7	SPIRou
9127.8539	−223.5±18.6	SPIRou
9128.9388	−320.2±19.2	SPIRou
9129.8487	−8.8±17.2	SPIRou
9154.8442	−388.4±17.2	SPIRou
9156.8789	216.9±16.9	SPIRou
9157.8683	43.0±18.3	SPIRou
9158.7828	−323.0±17.3	SPIRou
9207.7586	−227.0±18.1	SPIRou
9208.7037	23.9±17.9	SPIRou
9209.7317	153.5±17.7	SPIRou
9212.7597	−15.4±20.3	SPIRou
9213.6973	136.5±22.7	SPIRou
9214.7422	−29.1±21.0	SPIRou
9215.6925	−355.8±21.3	SPIRou
9216.7152	−173.8±18.7	SPIRou
9217.7413	78.8±17.1	SPIRou
9218.7086	130.8±17.2	SPIRou
9219.7204	−293.7±19.6	SPIRou
9220.7093	−357.7±18.6	SPIRou
9221.7231	12.6±19.5	SPIRou
9221.7556	36.1±19.4	SPIRou
9222.7286	140.4±18.7	SPIRou
9222.7623	163.7±18.7	SPIRou
9386.0143	−370.1±17.9	SPIRou
9387.0063	−83.9±18.7	SPIRou
9387.9405	143.6±55.6	SPIRou
9387.9446	120.0±42.8	SPIRou
9389.0138	155.7±16.8	SPIRou
9390.0506	−314.4±19.2	SPIRou
9391.0437	−240.4±19.7	SPIRou
9392.0613	194.9±18.0	SPIRou
9393.0468	86.5±18.1	SPIRou
9394.0751	−180.9±17.8	SPIRou
9395.0160	−360.0±19.2	SPIRou
9396.1236	174.1±19.3	SPIRou
9397.0375	72.0±20.9	SPIRou
9398.0271	105.6±20.4	SPIRou
9413.0426	−174.6±20.2	SPIRou

Table C.9: continued.

JD [−2450000]	B_l [G]	Instrument
9414.0396	216.1±24.3	SPIRou
9414.9480	171.8±28.5	SPIRou
9416.0206	−264.2±17.3	SPIRou
9417.0727	−321.1±19.7	SPIRou
9421.0846	−442.5±28.9	SPIRou
9423.0645	177.7±17.9	SPIRou
9440.0290	249.7±18.8	SPIRou
9440.8931	104.1±17.2	SPIRou
9441.8620	−22.3±16.3	SPIRou
9442.8526	−455.8±20.0	SPIRou
9443.9164	82.2±18.8	SPIRou
9445.0174	112.8±18.5	SPIRou
9445.8257	167.7±17.7	SPIRou
9446.9087	−405.0±32.7	SPIRou
9447.9479	−164.1±24.4	SPIRou
9448.9333	259.2±19.3	SPIRou
9449.9149	111.8±18.2	SPIRou
9451.0469	−294.0±23.0	SPIRou
9451.8786	−367.3±19.4	SPIRou
9452.8702	194.3±16.7	SPIRou
9472.9042	−272.5±19.6	SPIRou
9474.9013	272.7±17.4	SPIRou
9475.8372	137.8±16.7	SPIRou
9476.8210	−9.3±16.3	SPIRou
9477.8592	−394.8±18.4	SPIRou
9478.8431	17.4±22.1	SPIRou
9479.8398	173.0±17.4	SPIRou
9480.8265	154.8±17.5	SPIRou
9481.8316	−340.5±18.2	SPIRou
9502.7917	104.2±16.0	SPIRou
9503.8325	−371.1±18.2	SPIRou
9504.8194	−106.2±18.7	SPIRou
9506.9874	85.4±16.6	SPIRou
9507.8015	−239.0±17.9	SPIRou
9508.8368	−242.1±19.3	SPIRou
9509.7826	226.4±21.8	SPIRou
9510.8080	87.4±17.0	SPIRou
9511.8528	−92.6±20.2	SPIRou
9512.7546	−363.7±17.6	SPIRou
9513.7934	28.4±16.6	SPIRou
9514.9074	129.1±17.7	SPIRou
9537.7819	−25.7±17.8	SPIRou
9538.7691	−330.5±18.8	SPIRou
9539.7679	−43.1±20.1	SPIRou
9540.7944	152.8±35.0	SPIRou

C.5 V374 Peg

Table C.10: List of V374 Peg observations collected with SPIRou. The format is the same as Table C.1.

Date	UT [hh:mm:ss]	n_{cyc}	t_{exp} [s]	S/N	σ_{LSD} [$10^{-4}I_c$]
2019					
August 14	6:57:49.49	0.00	4x100	178	1.8
August 14	7:30:58.80	0.05	4x100	186	1.8
August 14	9:16:44.06	0.22	4x100	187	1.8
August 14	10:35:33.47	0.34	4x100	178	1.7
August 14	11:11:49.73	0.40	4x100	157	1.8
August 14	12:46:18.85	0.54	4x100	163	1.8
August 14	13:22:01.20	0.60	4x100	150	1.9
August 14	14:28:20.57	0.70	4x100	146	2.1
August 16	6:19:28.34	4.42	4x100	189	1.5
August 16	7:14:20.93	4.51	4x100	184	1.8
August 16	8:03:33.62	4.59	4x100	179	1.7
August 16	8:42:23.54	4.65	4x100	187	1.8
August 16	9:25:00.04	4.71	4x100	169	1.9
August 16	10:10:27.33	4.78	4x100	175	1.7
August 16	10:54:42.21	4.85	4x100	173	1.7
August 16	11:43:39.33	4.93	4x100	162	2.0
August 17	6:16:08.47	6.66	4x100	172	2.1
August 17	6:58:20.23	6.73	4x100	167	1.8
August 17	7:50:23.44	6.81	4x100	184	1.8
August 17	9:07:30.40	6.93	4x100	177	1.8
August 17	9:50:16.61	6.99	4x100	178	1.6
August 17	10:33:16.01	7.06	4x100	169	1.8
August 17	11:20:59.43	7.14	4x100	146	2.3
August 17	12:09:46.87	7.21	4x100	150	2.2
August 20	6:06:45.26	13.37	4x100	168	1.9
August 20	6:50:38.79	13.44	4x100	155	2.1
August 20	7:26:51.78	13.50	4x100	172	2.1
August 20	8:14:10.99	13.57	4x100	161	2.0
August 20	9:29:52.77	13.69	4x100	106	2.5
August 20	10:05:36.35	13.75	4x100	118	3.1
August 20	11:33:59.06	13.88	4x100	128	3.0
August 20	12:19:20.61	13.95	4x100	124	2.4
August 21	6:54:34.48	15.69	4x100	150	1.9
August 21	7:41:44.13	15.76	4x100	173	1.9
August 21	8:17:44.29	15.82	4x100	178	1.9
August 21	9:12:20.80	15.90	4x100	186	1.5
August 21	10:28:37.68	16.02	4x100	86	3.1
August 21	11:10:31.26	16.09	4x100	154	2.2
August 21	12:07:31.67	16.18	4x100	145	2.3
August 21	12:58:38.35	16.26	4x100	167	2.0
August 22	6:44:30.64	17.92	4x100	121	2.4
August 22	7:24:01.95	17.98	4x100	123	2.7
August 22	7:58:51.70	18.03	4x100	132	2.3
August 22	8:52:52.15	18.12	4x100	156	2.1

Table C.10: continued.

Date	UT [hh:mm:ss]	n_{cyc}	t_{exp} [s]	S/N	σ_{LSD} [$10^{-4}I_c$]
August 22	10:14:18.03	18.24	4x100	159	2.0
August 22	10:58:24.09	18.31	4x100	162	1.9
August 22	11:51:18.61	18.39	4x100	173	2.0
August 22	12:35:16.19	18.46	4x100	173	1.9
August 23	6:28:23.06	20.13	4x100	176	1.7
August 23	7:07:08.09	20.19	4x100	182	2.0
August 23	7:40:43.06	20.25	4x100	182	1.9
August 23	8:33:30.83	20.33	4x100	180	2.0
August 23	9:47:38.32	20.44	4x100	184	1.8
August 23	10:22:11.97	20.50	4x100	166	2.0
August 23	11:17:33.79	20.58	4x100	155	1.7

Table C.11: List of optical and near-infrared measurements of longitudinal magnetic field for V374 Peg. The format is the same as Table C.3.

JD [-2450000]	B_l [G]	Instrument
9440.7902	288.1±66.9	SPIRou
9440.8132	317.0±63.7	SPIRou
9440.8866	386.7±62.7	SPIRou
9440.9414	646.2±65.6	SPIRou
9440.9665	566.9±68.3	SPIRou
9441.0322	196.6±69.8	SPIRou
9441.0570	284.1±76.2	SPIRou
9441.1030	170.8±81.2	SPIRou
9442.7635	419.4±61.8	SPIRou
9442.8016	181.8±64.3	SPIRou
9442.8358	157.1±64.3	SPIRou
9442.8628	333.5±62.1	SPIRou
9442.8924	268.3±67.7	SPIRou
9442.9239	192.7±64.8	SPIRou
9442.9547	206.1±67.0	SPIRou
9442.9887	154.2±74.0	SPIRou
9443.7612	220.4±69.0	SPIRou
9443.7905	262.8±66.2	SPIRou
9443.8267	302.2±64.8	SPIRou
9443.8802	113.3±65.3	SPIRou
9443.9099	318.1±74.4	SPIRou
9443.9398	360.5±70.1	SPIRou
9443.9729	312.1±73.2	SPIRou
9444.0068	394.1±75.2	SPIRou
9446.7547	486.2±72.1	SPIRou
9446.7852	284.5±80.0	SPIRou
9446.8103	299.9±71.8	SPIRou
9446.8432	209.4±79.9	SPIRou
9446.8958	220.6±108.2	SPIRou
9446.9206	381.6±131.8	SPIRou

Table C.11: continued.

JD [−2450000]	B_l [G]	Instrument
9446.9819	68.2 ± 116.5	SPIRou
9447.0134	268.3 ± 102.2	SPIRou
9447.7879	284.2 ± 73.7	SPIRou
9447.8207	301.8 ± 67.4	SPIRou
9447.8457	113.2 ± 66.8	SPIRou
9447.8836	111.8 ± 62.4	SPIRou
9447.9365	307.3 ± 130.1	SPIRou
9447.9656	394.8 ± 83.3	SPIRou
9448.0052	345.6 ± 77.6	SPIRou
9448.0407	407.2 ± 73.9	SPIRou
9448.7809	227.4 ± 105.2	SPIRou
9448.8084	481.5 ± 121.0	SPIRou
9448.8325	381.8 ± 93.8	SPIRou
9448.8700	339.2 ± 85.3	SPIRou
9448.9266	444.5 ± 75.3	SPIRou
9448.9572	591.8 ± 71.2	SPIRou
9448.9940	449.7 ± 67.0	SPIRou
9449.0245	316.9 ± 66.1	SPIRou
9449.7697	310.9 ± 65.5	SPIRou
9449.7966	449.6 ± 64.9	SPIRou
9449.8199	443.3 ± 63.7	SPIRou
9449.8566	322.5 ± 68.3	SPIRou
9449.9081	358.5 ± 64.5	SPIRou
9449.9321	261.7 ± 67.6	SPIRou
9449.9705	159.6 ± 70.2	SPIRou

Appendix D

List of publications and contributions

Here I provide a list of my contributions to peer-reviewed papers, and my first-author papers that are in preparation or published in the *Astronomy & Astrophysics* journal.

- Bellotti et al. (2023a, in prep.): study of the long-term evolution of the magnetic field of AD Leo. This paper contains part of the work presented in this thesis.
- Bellotti et al. (2023b, in prep.): study of the long-term evolution of the magnetic field of CN Leo, DS Leo, and EV Lac. This paper contains part of the work presented in this thesis.
- Bellotti et al. (2023c, in prep.): study of the correlation between specific spectral line selections and brightness reconstruction by means of Doppler Imaging on SPIRou data of V374 Peg, with application to the filtering of radial velocity jitter for exoplanet detection and characterisation. In addition we analyse the long-term evolution of the magnetic field. This paper contains part of the work presented in this thesis.
- Bellotti et al. (2023d, in prep.): investigation of the stellar magnetic environment in which the planet GJ 436 b is immersed. I reconstructed the large-scale field map of GJ 436 using archival optical data of Narval, and performed a longitudinal field and periodicity analysis. In collaboration with Prof. Aline Vidotto and Prof. Rim Fares.
- Tsvetkova et al. (2023, in prep.): characterisation of the large-scale magnetic field of the double-line spectroscopic binary FK Aqr. I provided scripts for the optimisation of line parameters for the Zeeman-Doppler Imaging model, target χ_r^2 and best fit stellar parameters.
- Carmona et al. (2023, in press): analysis of velocimetric data sets of AD Leo to investigate the existence of a planetary companion. I provided the longitudinal magnetic field analysis, to further corroborate the presence of a unique activity signal at the stellar rotation period.
- Fouqué et al. (2023): analysis of the temporal behaviour of longitudinal magnetic field data for all targets of the SPIRou Legacy Survey, mainly via Gaussian Process Regression. I performed complementary tests to compute Stokes profiles in circular polarisation mode and measure stellar rotation period, by using a different recipe to perform Least-Square Deconvolution, longitudinal field estimation and Gaussian Process Regression.
- Cortes-Zuleta et al. (2023): characterisation of the M dwarf Gl 205 with focus on the investigation of near-infrared activity proxies. I discovered and fixed a bug affecting the computation of circularly polarised spectra in the APERO pipeline, that resulted in Stokes V amplitudes quenched by a factor of two.
- Martioli et al. (2022): RV follow-up and characterisation of the TOI-1759 system with SPIRou. I performed the magnetic field reconstruction of the host star by means of Zeeman-Doppler Imaging, using data reduced with the APERO pipeline.

Mitigating stellar activity jitter with different line lists for least-squares deconvolution

Analysis of a parametric and a randomised line selection

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Received 16 July 2021 / Accepted 19 October 2021

ABSTRACT

Context. Stellar activity limits the radial velocity (RV) search and characterisation of exoplanets, as it introduces spurious noise (called jitter) in the data sets and prevents the correct retrieval of a planetary signal. This is key for M dwarfs, considering that they manifest high activity levels and are primary targets for present and future searches of habitable Earth-like planets. To perform precise RV measurements, multi-line numerical techniques like cross-correlation and least-squares deconvolution (LSD) are typically employed.

Aims. Effective filtering of activity is crucial to achieving the sensitivity required for small planet detections. Here we analyse the impact of selecting different line lists for LSD on the dispersion in our RV data sets, to identify the line list that most effectively reduces the jitter.

Methods. We employ optical spectropolarimetric observations of the active M dwarf EV Lac collected with ESPaDOnS and NARVAL, and study two line down-selection approaches: a parametric method based on line properties (depth, wavelength, magnetic sensitivity) and a randomised algorithm that samples the line combination space. We test the latter further to find the line list that singles out the activity signal from other sources of noise, and on AD Leo and DS Leo to examine its consistency at mitigating jitter for different activity levels. The analysis is complemented with planetary injection tests.

Results. The parametric selection yields a RV RMS reduction of less than 10%, while the randomised selection yields a systematic improvement (>50%) regardless of the activity level of the star examined. Furthermore, if activity is the dominant source of noise, this approach allows the construction of lists containing mainly activity-sensitive lines, which could be used to enhance the rotational modulation of the resulting data sets and determine the stellar rotation period more robustly. Finally, the output line lists allow the recovery of a synthetic planet ($0.3\text{--}0.6 M_{\text{Jup}}$ on a 10 d orbit) in the presence of both moderate (20 m s^{-1} semi-amplitude) and high (200 m s^{-1}) activity levels, without substantially affecting the planet signal (between 60 and 120 m s^{-1}).

Key words. stars: activity – methods: data analysis – techniques: polarimetric – techniques: radial velocities

1. Introduction

The principal scientific objective of exoplanetary sciences is to find and characterise habitable Earth-like planets, and then to scrutinise their atmospheres and search for potential biomarkers; it is the main driver for current space-based missions such as TESS and CHEOPS (Ricker et al. 2015; Benz et al. 2021), and for future ones like JWST, PLATO, and ARIEL (Gardner et al. 2006; Rauer et al. 2014; Tinetti et al. 2018) and ground-based facilities like ESO ELT (Marconi et al. 2021). Radial velocity (RV) measurements are fundamental to infer physical properties such as mass and density of the planets detected by the transit method, therefore providing a deeper characterisation.

The success of velocimetric surveys relies on the instrumental precision and on the ability of numerical techniques to remove the effects of stellar activity from the data sets. Considering

that modern instruments such as ESPRESSO (Pepe et al. 2013) and EXPRES (Jurgenson et al. 2016) reach a precision of a few dozen cm s^{-1} , just above the precision required for a habitable Earth-like planet around a Sun-like star, the remaining fundamental limitation is the activity-induced variability (Meunier 2021). Stellar activity produces surface inhomogeneities that distort the spectral line profiles and result in spurious Doppler shifts that reach a few m s^{-1} in solar-like stars (Dumusque et al. 2021); (Collier Cameron et al. 2021) and over 1 km s^{-1} for young ($\sim 1 \text{ Myr}$) T Tauri stars (Donati et al. 2016). The RV signal of a habitable Earth-like planet is consequently drowned and its detection severely hampered.

M dwarfs are attractive targets for low-mass planet detections: they outnumber the other stars in the solar neighbourhood, have high occurrence rates of Earth-like planets (Kopparapu 2013; Gaidos et al. 2016), and have closer habitable zones

(implying magnified RV reflex motion and higher transit probability). Furthermore, because the habitable zone of M dwarfs is more compact, the orbital period of a habitable planet cannot be mistaken with long-term evolution of the stellar magnetic cycle, contrarily to active Sun-like stars (Meunier et al. 2010). However, M dwarfs exhibit high levels of activity that persist on gigayear (Gyr) timescales (West et al. 2008), hence robust activity-filtering techniques are essential to ensure precise RV measurements and reliable planet detections.

Radial velocity measurements are commonly performed with numerical techniques such as cross-correlation (Baranne et al. 1996; Pepe et al. 2002), least-squares deconvolution (LSD, Donati et al. 1997; Kochukhov et al. 2010), and least-squares template matching (e.g. Anglada-Escudé & Butler 2012; Astudillo-Defru et al. 2015; Zechmeister et al. 2018). The last technique gives precise results for M dwarfs because it makes use of a master spectrum template with high signal-to-noise ratio (S/N) and with a richer RV content than a synthetic spectrum with a lower number of absorption lines. However, both cross-correlation and LSD produce a high S/N line profile from which we can compute the FWHM and bisector. These are known to correlate with stellar activity (Queloz et al. 2001; Boisse et al. 2009; Queloz et al. 2009) and can therefore be used to disentangle activity signatures from genuine planetary signals. A comparison of the performance between cross-correlation and LSD will be investigated in a forthcoming paper (Bellotti et al., in prep.).

Dumusque (2018) and Cretignier et al. (2020) employed the fact that spectral lines have different sensitivities to activity (e.g. Davis et al. 2017; Lisogorskyi et al. 2019), and designed a line-by-line RV extraction method for α Cen B with which the activity signal is either enhanced or mitigated by a factor of two. The precision with which to robustly identify individual lines is limited by blends and photon noise, however, an aspect that becomes more relevant when considering cooler stars since they are fainter and feature dense spectra. To date, no line-by-line method has been applied to M dwarfs in the visible domain as its extension is not straightforward.

In this paper we analyse different line selection approaches to build synthetic line lists (hereafter called masks) for LSD, with the intention of developing a new activity-mitigating procedure tailored for active M dwarfs observed in the optical. Its extension to the near-infrared regime is also planned (Bellotti et al., in prep.). We test a parametric selection based on line properties (depth, wavelength, and magnetic sensitivity) and a randomised selection that samples the line combination space. We assess the extracted subsets of lines by looking at the resulting dispersion of the RV data sets in order to find a mask that reduces the activity jitter. Overall, our approach benefits from the multi-line nature of LSD since it produces a high S/N profile cleared from line blends.

The paper is structured as follows. In Sect. 2 we describe the spectropolarimetric data sets that are used in this study. Sections 3 and 4 are respectively dedicated to the description of the parametric and randomised selection used to create the line subsets, and in Sect. 5 we present our conclusions.

2. Data sets

The analysis presented here focuses mainly on EV Lac (GJ 873), an active M 4.0 star whose magnetic field properties have been extensively studied (e.g. Morin et al. 2008; Shulyak et al. 2019). This star has a rotation period of 4.38 days and is

Fig. 1. Numerical mask generated with a LTE model atmosphere from VALD showing atomic lines for M dwarfs such as EV Lac.

notoriously active, with an X-ray-to-bolometric luminosity ratio ($\log(L_X/L_{\text{bol}})$) of -3.10 (Wright et al. 2011) and a CaII H&K chromospheric activity index ($\log R'_{\text{HK}}$) of -3.75 (Boro Saikia et al. 2018; Noyes et al. 1984). The high activity level of EV Lac makes it an optimal target for our study because it is the dominant source of noise in the RV data sets and it allows us to compare the performance of different line selection approaches.

We use 57 spectropolarimetric observations in the visible collected between 2005 and 2016 with the twin spectropolarimeters ESPaDOnS on the 3.6 m Canada–France–Hawaii Telescope (CFHT) located atop Mauna Kea in Hawaii, and NARVAL on the 2 m Telescope Bernard Lyot (TBL) at the Pic du Midi Observatory in France (Donati 2003). The continuum normalised spectra were retrieved from PolarBase (Petit et al. 2014).

We derived Stokes I (unpolarised) and V (circularly polarised) profiles via LSD. This numerical technique combines the information from thousands of spectral lines to obtain a mean high S/N line profile (Donati et al. 1997; Kochukhov et al. 2010). With LSD the spectrum is regarded as the convolution between a mean profile and a line mask; the latter is basically a weighted Dirac comb reproducing the arrangement of lines in the stellar spectrum with the associated wavelengths, depths, and Landé factors (i.e. sensitivities to the Zeeman effect at a given wavelength). Compared to cross-correlation, LSD removes the auto-correlation function of the mask to provide a cleaner mean profile.

For stars like EV Lac, we employed the same line mask used in Morin et al. (2008). It is generated using the Vienna Atomic Line Database (VALD) with a local thermodynamic equilibrium model (Gustafsson et al. 2008) and corresponds to $T_{\text{eff}} = 3500$ K, $\log g = 5.0$ [cm s^{-2}], and $v_{\text{micro}} = 2$ km s^{-1} , and contains 4216 atomic lines in the range 350–1080 nm (Fig. 1) with depths greater than 40% of the continuum level. The number of lines in the range used for our observations is 3300. This is referred to as ‘full mask’ and the extracted subsets as ‘sub-masks’. To extract precise radial velocities, we note that an empirical mask with a rich content of spectral lines is generally used, rather than a synthetic one.

To compute the RV values, we simultaneously fitted a Voigt function and a linear continuum to each Stokes I profile within a ± 20 km s^{-1} velocity interval from the profile centre. The additional linear continuum fit is a precaution to prevent biases of the RV measurement due to an imperfect spectrum normalisation. In addition, we computed the longitudinal magnetic field as

$$B_l [G] = \frac{-2.14 \times 10^{11}}{\lambda_0 g_{\text{eff}} c} \frac{\int v V(v) dv}{\int (I_c - I) dv}, \quad (1)$$

Fig. 2. Generalised Lomb-Scargle periodogram of the longitudinal magnetic field of EV Lac, for the 2010 data set (20 observations). The data set is preliminarily detrended with a quadratic fit in order to remove long-term variations. The normalisation of the periodogram power and the false alarm probability (FAP) levels are computed with the prescription in Zechmeister & Kürster (2009). We find a significant (FAP < 0.011%) peak at a rotation period of 4.36 ± 0.05 d, which is consistent with previous studies.

where λ_0 and g_{eff} are respectively the normalisation wavelength and Landé factor of the LSD profiles, I_c is the continuum level, v is the radial velocity associated with a point in the spectral line profile in the star’s rest frame, and c the speed of light in vacuum (Donati et al. 1997). The B_l measurements were performed within a velocity interval of ± 30 km s⁻¹ to include the absorption ranges of both Stokes I and V profiles.

The quantity B_l is a known magnetic activity tracer as its temporal variation is modulated at the stellar rotation period. Both Folsom et al. (2016) and Hébrard et al. (2016) showed that it performs better than RVs, for example, at retrieving the stellar rotation period, especially because it is not expected to be influenced by the presence of a planet. We therefore carried out a preliminary period analysis on the B_l 2010 data set using the generalised Lomb-Scargle (GLS) periodogram (Zechmeister & Kürster 2009; Czesla et al. 2019), and find a significant peak at a rotation period of 4.36 ± 0.05 d (Fig. 2) consistent with previous studies (e.g. Wright et al. 2011; Morin et al. 2008). This value is used in the following analysis.

In the following sections, the performance of the sub-masks is quantified primarily by the dispersion of the associated data sets (for RV and B_l). We use ‘stable’ and ‘unstable’ to identify sub-masks leading respectively to an improvement and a degradation in RMS relative to the full mask case, respectively. We also performed contemporaneous Monte Carlo simulations to determine the RV precision associated with each sub-mask and used it as a metric to discern whether the line selection is photon noise limited. More precisely, for each time series examined we performed the following: (1) selected the spectrum corresponding to the Stokes I profile with S/N closest to the S/N of the median Stokes I profile, (2) injected white noise into the spectrum in the form $\mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_i)$ (with σ_i the error bar for each data point of the chosen spectrum), (3) applied LSD with the examined sub-mask, and (4) measured RV. The RV RMS of 100 iterations is representative of the photon noise level associated with the sub-mask. Given that spectra are collected individually, it is not surprising that some estimates of the photon noise are

lower than the stability of the instrument (30 m s⁻¹, Moutou et al. 2007).

3. Parametric selection

For this first approach the full mask was cleaned of lines close to H α or belonging to telluric windows in the ranges [627,632], [655.5,657], [686,697], [716,734], [759,770], [813,835], and [895,986] nm; hence, we conservatively used 3240 lines in total. The RV time series obtained using the full mask and all the observations has a RMS dispersion of 165 m s⁻¹ and a RV precision of 8 m s⁻¹.

The line selection consists in splitting the full mask based on the following line parameters: depth (d), wavelength (λ), and Landé factor (g_{eff}). The parametric threshold is set so that the S/N distribution of the observed Stokes V profiles for the two sub-masks is compatible; this way we ensure the same S/N and a consistent comparison of the effects of different sub-masks. For each sub-mask, we perform a three-parameter (semi-amplitude K , phase correction, and offset) Levenberg-Marquardt least-squares sinusoidal fit to both the RV and B_l data sets, assuming the stellar rotation period obtained in Sect. 2. The inclusion of higher order harmonics of the stellar rotation period (Boisse et al. 2011) does not lead to a substantial improvement in the results throughout. The results are illustrated in Fig. 3 and summarised in Table 1 for different parametric selections.

3.1. Depth case

We selected lines with depths lower than 0.6, between 0.6 and 0.8, and larger than 0.8, resulting in three sub-masks of 926, 1231, and 1058 lines, respectively. For RV the RMS dispersion is decreased only in the $d > 0.8$ case by 6%, while it is deteriorated by up to 25% in the other cases. The semi-amplitude follows a similar trend, but with a more moderate deterioration in the $d < 0.6$ case. Depending on the sub-mask considered, the RV data sets show systematic shifts up to 100 m s⁻¹ relative to the full-mask data set, likely due to a different line sensitivity to convective motions and corresponding velocity fields (Gray 2005; Morgenthaler et al. 2012; Beeck et al. 2013; Meunier et al. 2017). Another reason could be instrumental systematics affecting specific spectral lines (Cretignier et al. 2021).

For B_l , no significant improvement in either RMS or semi-amplitude is observed. The $d < 0.6$ case yields the least precise estimates, resulting in deviant magnetic field measurements (with respect to the full mask) and a poorer sinusoidal fit (increased χ^2_ν). This suggests that deeper lines have a stabilising effect on the time series (also given their higher effective S/N) in agreement with Reiners et al. (2016) and Cretignier et al. (2020).

3.2. Wavelength case

Activity signatures induced by spots are strongly chromatic (Reiners et al. 2010), hence a wavelength selection may help locate spectral regions with reduced RV dispersion. We select lines with wavelength above and below 550 nm, resulting in two sub-masks of 314 and 2872 lines, respectively. The RV values exhibit a loss of precision up to 3.6% for both sub-masks, and the B_l values feature a negligible <4% improvement in RMS only when using red lines (>550 nm). Likewise, the semi-amplitude of the sinusoidal fit for both quantities shows either a degradation or marginal improvement. We note that despite the different number of lines in the sub-masks (due to the higher S/N in the

Fig. 3. Comparison of RV and B_1 data sets obtained with a parametric selection of sub-masks. *Top:* RV (*left*) and B_1 (*right*) data sets obtained with a depth selection. *Middle:* same, but with a wavelength selection. *Bottom:* same, but with a Landé factor selection. In all panels the black data points correspond to either the RV or the B_1 values obtained with the full mask, whereas the continuous lines represent the sinusoidal fit of the associated data set. The mean of the data set is subtracted to allow a simpler comparison. For RV estimates, the error bars are set to 30 m s^{-1} , as derived from the telluric line-based wavelength calibration of the spectra (Moutou et al. 2007), which is greater than the photon noise for each of these data sets. For B_1 the formal uncertainties are used. The displayed data sets are 3σ clipped to prevent outliers from affecting the results. For B_1 the densest epoch (2010) is displayed.

red part of the spectrum) the RV and B_1 estimates are highly compatible with the full mask values.

3.3. Landé factor case

An additional line parameter to examine is the Landé factor, considering that Johns-Krull & Valenti (1996) reported measurable Zeeman broadening in magnetic-sensitive optical lines for EV Lac. We selected lines with g_{eff} above and below 1.2, resulting in two sub-masks of 1649 and 1495 lines, respectively. The RV dispersion (semi-amplitude) shows a $<10\%$ (16%) improvement when using magnetically insensitive lines and a 20% (21%) degradation with the opposite sub-mask; the results for B_1 are similar to the full mask with a slight deterioration for both sub-masks, and the values are reasonably consistent within the error bars. We also tried using the product $\lambda_0 \cdot g_{\text{eff}}$ as selection criterion to have a more accurate measure of the magnetic susceptibility, but the result did not change.

3.4. Summary of parametric selection results

We also extended the initial mask to contain lines as shallow as 10%. With 9470 lines in total, we applied similar parametric thresholds (the depth case was modified to ensure same S/N) to investigate any benefit of the substantial increase in the number of lines. We found similar trends to the previous analysis, with a general degradation of the precision and of B_1 reliability, confirming that very shallow lines should be rejected when defining line masks.

From the results of this first approach, we conclude that building a sub-mask using a direct selection based on the line parameters does not significantly reduce the effect of activity jitter on RV measurements. A comparison between RV RMS and precision indeed confirms that the dominant source of RV variation in the data sets is the activity jitter, which is unchanged and one order of magnitude larger than photon noise regardless of the line selection (see Table 1). The presence of RV shifts when using different sub-masks emphasises the importance of always

Table 1. Summary of the RV and B_1 data set characteristics.

Selection	n_{lines}	RMS	Precision	K	χ^2_v	RMS _{res}
Radial velocity						
		[m s ⁻¹]	[m s ⁻¹]	[m s ⁻¹]		[m s ⁻¹]
Full	3240	167	5	124 ± 26	23.2	140
$d < 0.6$	1058	208	22	147 ± 32	36.6	176
$0.6 < d < 0.8$	926	183	10	141 ± 28	27.1	152
$d > 0.8$	1231	157	8	107 ± 25	22.0	136
$\lambda > 550$ nm	314	168	8	125 ± 26	23.6	141
$\lambda < 550$ nm	2872	173	7	121 ± 27	26.2	149
$g_{\text{eff}} > 1.2$	1649	199	8	149 ± 31	32.9	167
$g_{\text{eff}} < 1.2$	1495	151	7	104 ± 24	20.0	130
Longitudinal magnetic field						
		[G]	[G]	[G]		[G]
Full	3240	133	...	158 ± 15	10.6	48
$d < 0.6$	1058	200	...	222 ± 26	30.9	82
$0.6 < d < 0.8$	926	129	...	149 ± 16	12.7	53
$d > 0.8$	1231	152	...	190 ± 15	10.1	46
$\lambda > 550$ nm	314	128	...	148 ± 15	10.4	48
$\lambda < 550$ nm	2872	146	...	184 ± 15	11.6	50
$g_{\text{eff}} > 1.2$	1649	137	...	157 ± 17	14.8	55
$g_{\text{eff}} < 1.2$	1495	138	...	170 ± 14	8.9	51

Notes. The columns are: (1) parametric criteria used, (2) number of lines in the sub-mask, (3) RMS of the data set, (4) RV precision from the MC simulations, (5) semi-amplitude of the sinusoidal fit to the data set, (6) reduced χ^2 (three fit parameters and 57 observations for RV and 20 observations for B_1), and (7) RMS of the fit residuals. The reported values for B_1 refer to the epoch with the most observations (2010), which was used in Sect. 2, but the results are also analogous for 2007 (the second densest data set).

using the same mask for a RV time series (i.e. always excluding lines that for some observations are blended with telluric lines or fall outside the echelle order). Finally, this analysis confirms the robustness of B_1 because the measurements show a clear rotational modulation and are all reasonably consistent, provided that the mask contains deep lines.

4. Randomised selection

4.1. Basic principle

For the second selection approach, we applied a randomised algorithm to extract the sub-mask minimising the RV dispersion, which is inspired by the line-by-line method developed in Dumusque (2018). We cannot follow the same exact prescription because a RV measurement on individual lines implies an increase in photon noise, which becomes relevant in the optical especially for M dwarfs. At the same time, the high density of lines in the blue part of the spectrum makes their identification more challenging.

The idea is to build sub-masks with a randomly sampled number of lines (n_{sample}) from the full mask, apply LSD, and derive the RV time series. Because the number of line combinations (i.e. sub-masks) is very large, we stop the iteration when each line in the full mask has been drawn at least a certain amount of times (n_{stop}). An optimised exploration of the sub-mask space is performed using $n_{\text{sample}} = 50$ and $n_{\text{stop}} = 100$ (see Appendix A for more details), since ~ 9000 sub-masks are examined on average and a lower n_{sample} would inevitably deteriorate the performance (Fig. A.1).

The RV dispersion associated with each sub-mask is the criterion used to discriminate between stable and unstable

sub-masks (Fig. 4). From the RV RMS distribution, we isolate three groups of stable sub-masks: those with RMS lower than the 10th, 5th, and 1st percentile. For each group, we find the maximum number of draws and we build a sub-mask with lines drawn at least one-third of this maximum number ($f_{\text{select}} = 0.33$, see Appendix A). Finally, we obtain the RV time series from these three sub-masks and determine the best according to the associated RMS.

Overall, two caveats stem from the randomised nature of the approach: each complete run corresponds to sampling a different region of the sub-mask (i.e. line combination) space, and it is not possible to predict exactly which of the three percentile-selected sub-masks gives the lowest RMS. In our analysis we train the best sub-mask on the data set from 2010 since it has the largest number of observations (20), and because the activity signal is expected to lose coherency over timescales longer than months. Moreover, we do not remove lines in telluric windows from the full mask, as in Sect. 3, to further check the reliability of the extracted best sub-mask. The starting number of lines is then 3300. The summary of the results for the analyses in the following sections can be found in Table 2.

4.2. Training for stable lines

Figure 5 illustrates the output for an example run. The full mask is associated with a RV RMS of 182 m s⁻¹ and a semi-amplitude of 175 m s⁻¹ (after performing a sinusoidal fit similarly to Sect. 3). The best sub-mask in this case is composed of 198 lines, none of which fall in the telluric windows, and yields a $\sim 63\%$ reduction in the RV dispersion. Considering that a $>50\%$ RMS improvement is consistently achieved for multiple runs, we inspected the union of the output best sub-masks; in this case

Table 2. Summary of all tests and simulations outlined in Sect. 4.

Case	n_{lines}	RMS [m s ⁻¹]	Precision [m s ⁻¹]	K [m s ⁻¹]	χ_v^2	RMS _{res} [m s ⁻¹]
EV Lac						
Full mask on 2010	3300	182	4	175	23.7	134
Example run 10th percentile on 2010	666	79	11	105	1.2	30
Example run 5th percentile on 2010	636	79	19	104	1.3	31
Example run 1st percentile on 2010	198	67	14	93	1.2	30
Union of best sub-masks on 2010	721	68	8	86	1.4	32
Full mask on 2007	3300	225	5	129	60	204
2010-trained best sub-mask on 2007	198	118	17	142	6.2	66
2007-trained best sub-mask on 2007	26	82	16	77	5.7	64
Full mask on 2006	3300	249	4	282	42.6	147
2006-trained best sub-mask on 2010	7	259	24	140	78.4	244
Full mask on all epochs	3300	242	5	101	62.7	231
Union of 2010-trained sub-masks on all epochs	721	69	7	96	15.2	113
2010-trained worst RMS-based sub-mask on 2010	83	13342	44	12718	1.3×10^5	10041
Full mask on 2010 (T)	3240	133	5	172	3.3	50
2010-trained worst RMS-based sub-mask on 2010 (T)	2117	255	28	326	26.7	142
2010-trained worst K -based sub-mask on 2010 (T)	2209	246	19	373	7.6	76
AD Leo						
Full mask on 2008	3300	110	2	80	14.2	100
2008-trained best sub-mask on 2008	524	26	5	42	0.3	13
Union of EVLac-2010-trained best sub-masks on 2008	721	31	4	37	0.7	21
DS Leo						
Full mask on 2008	3300	37	2	23	1.5	34
2008-trained best sub-mask on 2008	571	20	3	18	0.35	16
2008-trained worst RMS-based sub-mask on 2008	800	143	6	51	24.4	138
2008-trained worst K -based sub-mask on 2008	845	59	3	20	4.2	57
Full mask without worst RMS-based sub-mask on 2008	2500	29	2	29	0.64	22

Notes. The columns are: (1) specific (sub-)mask and epoch considered, (2) number of lines in the sub-mask, (3) RMS of the data set, (4) RV precision from the MC simulations, (5) semi-amplitude of the sinusoidal fit to the data set, (6) reduced χ^2 , and (7) RMS of the fit residuals. The symbol ‘T’ indicates that telluric windows are removed from the full mask. The number of observations for EV Lac are 20 in 2010, 15 in 2007, 7 in 2006; for AD Leo 14 in 2008; and for DS Leo 26 in 2008.

Fig. 4. Distribution of the RV RMS associated with 9281 sub-masks of an example run with $n_{\text{sample}} = 50$ and $n_{\text{stop}} = 100$. Each RMS value is obtained after a 3σ clipping of the RV data set, which prevents outliers from contaminating the distinction between stable and unstable sub-masks. The RMS values are sorted in ascending order and truncated at 1 km s^{-1} for visualisation purposes (the maximum can reach up to 100 km s^{-1}). Shown are the 1st (black solid line) and 10th (dashed black line) percentiles of the distribution.

the S/N of the computed Stokes profile would benefit from an increased number of lines. We find that uniting two sub-masks (721 lines in total) reduces the RMS by the same amount as the

individual sub-masks, and that only 4 lines (out of 60) within the telluric windows are present in the sub-mask. Furthermore, the semi-amplitude is decreased by 51%, as shown in Fig. 6, reducing the RV modulation occurring at the stellar rotation period, and the RV precision remains around 5 m s^{-1} despite the smaller number of lines than the full mask. A visual comparison of the depth, wavelength, and g_{eff} distributions between the full mask and the best one does not reveal any particular trend (see Appendix B). Therefore, no line feature can be used to single out the best sub-mask directly, in agreement with the conclusions of Sect. 3.

The purpose of the randomised approach is to train the best sub-mask on the year with the largest number of observations, and subsequently use it to reduce the RV dispersion of the time series from other the epochs. We performed tests of the sub-mask portability by using the 2010-trained sub-masks on the 2007 data set (detailed in Appendix A), and concluded that there is approximately the same benefit as when applied to the 2010 data set.

We now compare the effects of using the 2007-trained best sub-mask on the 2007 data set with respect to the 2010-trained one. Starting from an initial 225 m s^{-1} dispersion, the two cases yield a 64 and 48% reduction, respectively, indicating that the

Fig. 5. Output from an example run of the randomised selection. Shown are the 3σ clipped RV data sets computed using the full mask (black) and the sub-masks associated with the 10th (light blue), 5th (dark blue), and 1st (green) percentiles of the RV RMS distribution.

Fig. 6. Phase-folded plot of the RV time series computed with the union of two best sub-masks (721 lines). The RV RMS of the data set is reduced by 63%, and the RV semi-amplitude by 51% relative to the full mask case. The decreased residual scatter around the fit should be noted.

benefit of the randomised approach is maximised when the data set examined coincides with the training data set. Even so, applying the 2010-trained best sub-mask on the 2007 data leads to a substantial improvement.

When the training is applied to a less-than-ideal data set (i.e. with few and sparse observations), the portability of our approach is compromised. We indeed tested the randomised algorithm on the 2006 observations (seven in total), and obtained a sub-mask yielding an impressive 73% improvement of the dispersion (from 249 to 67 m s⁻¹). However, when the same sub-mask was applied to the 2010 data set, we observed a severe degradation (42%) of the RV RMS. At the same time, using this sub-mask is no longer relevant, as it contained only seven lines. The photon noise in this case is increased by six times relative to the full mask. Finally, when all epochs were considered, the application of the 2010-trained best sub-mask led to a consistent RMS improvement of 45% (from 242 to 134 m s⁻¹).

Overall, because the RMS is blind to the source of dispersion, its systematic improvement does not imply that the stable lines extracted by our randomised approach are restricted to those insensitive to activity. Telluric windows, instrumental errors (e.g. bad spectral orders), possible errors in the line list, or specific combinations of lines all introduce scatter to some degree, and are thus filtered out with our algorithm. This is noticeable when all observations are considered. In this case the activity signal has lost coherency; thus, if the algorithm removes activity-sensitive lines only, using our sub-mask would be less beneficial.

Fig. 7. Comparison of the GLS periodograms when using two different masks. *Top:* GLS periodogram of the EV Lac 2010 RV data set obtained with the full mask. *Bottom:* same, but using the 2010-trained best sub-mask. The significance of the peak at the stellar rotation period decreases in the latter case, confirming the mitigating benefit of using the sub-mask derived from the randomised selection. There is a peak at 30 d showing an increase in power when the best sub-mask is applied. A period analysis of the window function (VanderPlas 2018) reveals that the peak is most likely due to the observing span (~ 2 months) and cadence of the 2010 data set.

An additional way to show the mitigating effect of the 2010-trained best sub-mask is to inspect its impact on the GLS periodogram of the RV data sets, as illustrated in Fig. 7. We note that the power (i.e. significance) of the peak associated with the stellar rotation period decreases of ~ 0.1 , implying that the corresponding activity signal is reduced. This feature occurs systematically also in the 2007 and full data sets when the 2010-trained best sub-mask is employed.

4.3. Training for unstable lines

We implement the randomised algorithm to work in the opposite direction, i.e. to isolate spectral lines that are susceptible to dispersive sources. If activity-sensitive lines are selected, the output data set could feature an enhanced modulation of the activity signal, therefore providing a more precise measurement of the stellar rotation period (useful for stellar physics and gyrochronology) and the possibility to model and filter the jitter efficiently.

The difference with respect to the previous training is that the sub-masks are generated considering the 90th, 95th, and 99th percentile of the RV RMS distribution. Because the sub-mask exploration given by the choice $(n_{\text{sample}}, n_{\text{stop}}) = (50, 100)$ also leads to line combinations with extreme RV RMS values (i.e. on $> \text{km s}^{-1}$ levels, see Fig. 4), the three sub-masks associated with these percentiles will inevitably contain a low number of lines (< 10) if built using $f_{\text{select}} = 0.33$, as for the stable lines. Therefore, we require that the number of draws to keep the line is at least one-tenth of the maximum number of draws for the percentile ($f_{\text{select}} = 0.1$). Finally, from each of the three sub-masks we remove the lines that are shared with the sub-masks obtained from the 10th, 5th, and 1st percentiles to additionally deteriorate the resulting RV dispersion.

The result is illustrated in Fig. 8. The worst sub-mask has 83 lines and the associated RV dispersion is increased from 182 to 13342 m s^{-1} (i.e. by 73 times). The measurements do not manifest an evident rotational modulation and span extreme values between -40 and 9 km s^{-1} , resulting in an artificially high RV semi-amplitude. Likewise, the union of the worst sub-masks from different runs of the algorithm does not yield useful insights.

We repeated the test, but cleaning the full mask of lines falling within telluric windows, similarly to the procedure described in Sect. 3. In this case the algorithm produces a sub-mask of 2117 lines and with a corresponding RMS of 255 m s^{-1} (Fig. 8), 1.9 times larger than the initial value without telluric windows (133 m s^{-1}). The photon noise level is nine times lower than the RV RMS and seven times larger than when using the full mask, which could be due to a poorer modelling of the Stokes I profile when distorted and unstable lines are searched. Compared to the full mask, no evident trend is displayed in the depth, wavelength, and g_{eff} distributions (see Appendix B). Contrary to when the telluric windows are present, the RV data set shows a clearer rotational modulation, meaning that the worst sub-mask may contain more activity-sensitive lines. This indicates the severe additional contamination that lines in telluric windows (or residuals from telluric correction) introduce when coexisting with the activity jitter as dispersion sources. In that scenario our algorithm does not precisely identify the most activity-impacted lines.

We tested whether a different sub-mask selection criterion can improve the extraction of activity-sensitive lines. Instead of using the RV RMS, which does not distinguish random noise from a coherent signal, we select based on the semi-amplitude of the sinusoidal fit of the RV data set, exploiting the modulated nature of the activity signal. In this case, the two-step algorithm performs a Levenberg-Marquardt least-squares sinusoidal fit for the RV data set corresponding to a generated sub-mask. The output sub-mask is then based on the distribution of K and should contain lines that are more sensitive to stellar activity than other dispersive sources. The output RV data set features a semi-amplitude increase from 172 to 373 m s^{-1} , a visible rotational modulation and a reduced scatter around the sinusoidal fit (Fig. 8), and a photon noise 13 times lower than the RMS, suggesting that the algorithm most likely isolates lines that are mainly sensitive to activity.

Lastly, shallow or low S/N lines at the bluest and reddest boundaries of the full mask may represent a possible source of confusion as they might bias the selection of the sub-mask and pollute the resulting RV dispersion measurement. We therefore discarded lines with effective S/N (i.e. S/N multiplied by normalised depth) lower than ten and repeated the test: no improvement was recorded for the identification of the worst sub-mask,

Fig. 8. Phase-folded plot of the 2010 RV time series of EV Lac computed with: the worst RMS-based sub-mask including telluric windows (*top*), the worst RMS-based sub-mask discarding telluric windows (*middle*), and the worst K -based sub-mask discarding telluric windows (*bottom*). The symbol “T” indicates that the telluric windows are removed from the start. The first case demonstrates how lines falling in telluric windows severely contaminate the RV measurements and thus prevent a precise selection of the worst sub-mask. The second case illustrates the improvement in finding the worst sub-mask containing activity-sensitive lines, providing a clear rotational modulation of the data set. The third case shows how selecting the sub-masks based on the RV semi-amplitude, i.e. a feature that is directly connected to activity, yields the most precise selection of activity-sensitive lines. The sinusoidal fit in each panel is computed analogously to Fig. 6.

and the resulting RV dispersion increased even further. This is explained considering that the bluest lines ($\sim 400 \text{ nm}$) are deep, and thus less likely to be affected by velocity fields (as we discussed in Sect. 3.1). In this sense, their presence stabilises the results as indicated by a lower RV RMS of the data set. The presence (or absence) of the reddest lines ($\sim 1000 \text{ nm}$) has no significant impact on the results since their number is negligible (< 20).

4.4. Training on other stars

We examine the efficiency and consistency of the randomised approach on the active M3 dwarf AD Leo (GJ 388) and the moderately active M1 dwarf DS Leo (GJ 410). AD Leo has a reported rotation period of 2.24 days (Morin et al. 2008), approximately half of the EV Lac period, and is slightly less active, with $L_X/L_{\text{bol}} = -3.62$ (0.5 dex less; Wright et al. 2011) and $\log R'_{\text{HK}} = -4.00$ (0.25 dex less; Boro Saikia et al. 2018). AD Leo is seen almost pole-on, and therefore the activity jitter is more moderate than for EV Lac. Instead, DS Leo is a slower rotator, with a period of 13.83 days (Hébrard et al. 2016), and

Fig. 9. Phase-folded plot of the 2008 RV time series (26 observations) of DS Leo computed with (from *top to bottom*) the full mask including telluric windows, the 2008-trained best sub-mask, the worst RMS-based sub-mask, and the worst K -based sub-mask. A stellar rotation period of 13.57 ± 0.04 d was used, computed via GLS periodogram, as described in Sect. 2. *Second panel:* remarkable reduction of both the RV dispersion and semi-amplitude, reaching the instrumental limitation of NARVAL (~ 30 m s $^{-1}$). The *third and fourth panels* display an RMS-based selection that is affected by different sources of dispersion (telluric contamination in particular) and an ineffective K -based selection following the low level of activity of the star, respectively.

is the least active: $L_X/L_{\text{bol}} = -3.80$ (0.7 dex less than EV Lac) and $\log R'_{\text{HK}} = -4.16$ (0.41 dex less than EV Lac). Therefore, activity is not the dominant source of variability for DS Leo. For the AD Leo and DS Leo analyses we did not remove the telluric windows from the initial mask.

For AD Leo we trained the best sub-mask on 14 optical observations collected in 2008. The RV dispersion of the data set computed with the full mask is 110 m s $^{-1}$, while our approach allows us to reach 26 m s $^{-1}$ (76% improvement), which is close to the instrumental stability of NARVAL (~ 30 m s $^{-1}$, Moutou et al. 2007). In comparison, applying the 2010-trained best sub-mask obtained for EV Lac results in a 66% decrease in RMS, which extends the portability of the sub-mask trained for EV Lac to other active stars, and suggests that stars with similar properties (e.g. comparable spectral type, activity level) and atmospheres have similar stable lines. When searching for the maximum

benefit overall, the sub-mask training should be performed on the densest data set of each star separately.

For DS Leo we applied the randomised approach on 26 optical observations collected in early 2008 (Fig. 9). Starting from a RV dispersion of 37 m s $^{-1}$ and semi-amplitude of 23 m s $^{-1}$ associated with the full mask, the 2008-trained best sub-mask yields a 46 and 22% reduction, respectively, reaching again the instrumental stability of NARVAL. This confirms that our approach is able to mitigate dispersion also on moderately active stars, where the contribution of telluric-affected lines is more important than EV Lac and AD Leo. In comparison to Hébrard et al. (2016), who employed HARPS-pol observations and Doppler mapping as the activity-filtering technique, our values of 20 and 18 m s $^{-1}$ for dispersion and semi-amplitude are a factor of 2.5 and 1.2 higher, respectively. The possibility of combining our randomised line selection with Doppler mapping represents an appealing perspective (Bellotti et al., in prep.).

We also attempted to isolate activity-sensitive lines using both an RMS and a semi-amplitude selection criterion. As DS Leo is less active than EV Lac, the randomised algorithm should in principle be less confused by the coexistence of different sources of noise. The results of the RMS-based selection are analogous although less extreme than EV Lac: the RV dispersion is amplified by a factor of 3.9 and there is no clear rotational modulation. The K -based selection increases the RMS by 1.5 and does not affect the semi-amplitude of the fit, as expected given the lower activity level. Moreover, an inspection of the RMS-based worst sub-mask content reveals that about 20 lines fall within telluric windows, at least ten lines more than when the randomised approach is applied on EV Lac. This further demonstrates that the randomised algorithm is capable of better discerning the sources of RV noise. Finally, we removed the 800 lines of the worst RMS-based sub-mask from the full mask (using 2500 lines in total), and note a 24% improvement in RV dispersion and a degradation of 30% in semi-amplitude, indicating that the best sub-mask training alone is already optimal, and yields a substantial improvement.

4.5. Training with injected planets

We now investigate the application of the randomised algorithm when a synthetic planetary signal is included in the RV data sets. We carried out planetary recovery tests for both EV Lac and DS Leo in order to study the detectability over two different activity regimes.

The planet injection was applied to all the collected spectra using

$$RV_p = K_p \sin\left(2\pi\left(\frac{t - T_0}{P_{\text{orb}}}\right) + \phi\right), \quad (2)$$

where we fixed $T_0 = 2450000$, $\phi = 0.0$, $P_{\text{orb}} = 10$ d, and we assumed circular orbits. This value of orbital period is chosen since it is different enough from the rotation period of the stars, and short enough to be clearly detected in all data sets. We considered three planets separately with a $2\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$, $3\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$, and $4\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$ signal ($1\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}} = 30$ m s $^{-1}$, i.e. the intrinsic stability of NARVAL), and corresponding to 0.3 – $0.6 M_{\text{Jup}}$ and 0.4 – $0.9 M_{\text{Jup}}$ planets for EV Lac and DS Leo, respectively. We note that the telluric contamination is not represented realistically in these simulations as the whole wavelength axis is coherently shifted during injection. However, this limitation is only marginal considering the negligible planet-induced shift compared to the displacement of telluric lines with respect to stellar lines throughout a year.

Table 3. Results of the planetary injection tests for EV Lac and DS Leo.

Case	n_{lines}	RMS [m s ⁻¹]	K [m s ⁻¹]	χ^2_{ν}	RMS _{res} [m s ⁻¹]	K_{res} [m s ⁻¹]	$\chi^2_{\nu,\text{res}}$	GLS power
EV Lac								
Full mask with $2\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$ planet	3300	244	96 ± 45	64.7	234	90 ± 41	59.2	0.08
Full mask with $2\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$ planet (T)	3240	169	120 ± 27	24.8	145	53 ± 28	23.2	0.07
10th percentile with $2\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$ planet	1133	139	99 ± 23	16.7	119	42 ± 22	15.6	0.06
5th percentile with $2\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$ planet	385	131	88 ± 21	15.4	114	44 ± 22	14.3	0.08
1st percentile with $2\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$ planet	58	121	77 ± 22	13.9	108	37 ± 22	13.1	0.05
Full mask with $3\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$ planet	3300	248	95 ± 46	66.9	238	108 ± 41	59.1	0.12
Full mask with $3\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$ planet (T)	3240	174	117 ± 28	27.0	151	82 ± 28	23.1	0.14
10th percentile with $3\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$ planet	1133	144	97 ± 23	15.6	125	71 ± 23	15.6	0.16
5th percentile with $3\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$ planet	385	136	85 ± 22	17.3	121	73 ± 23	14.2	0.18
1st percentile with $3\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$ planet	58	126	67 ± 22	16.0	116	59 ± 23	14.0	0.13
Full mask with $4\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$ planet	3300	253	92 ± 47	70.1	244	131 ± 41	59.0	0.16
Full mask with $4\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$ planet (T)	3240	180	115 ± 30	30.1	160	111 ± 28	23.1	0.23
10th percentile with $4\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$ planet	1133	151	94 ± 23	21.4	134	101 ± 25	15.6	0.27
5th percentile with $4\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$ planet	385	144	82 ± 22	20.2	131	102 ± 25	14.2	0.29
1st percentile with $4\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$ planet	58	134	62 ± 22	18.9	126	88 ± 26	14.3	0.24
DS Leo								
Full mask with $2\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$ planet	3300	75	26 ± 11	6.1	73	52 ± 9	4.4	0.27
Full mask with $2\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$ planet (T)	3240	57	20 ± 8	3.6	55	58 ± 6	1.5	0.59
10th percentile with $2\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$ planet	631	55	19 ± 8	3.3	53	53 ± 5	1.5	0.55
5th percentile with $2\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$ planet	396	54	19 ± 8	3.2	52	51 ± 5	1.5	0.52
1st percentile with $2\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$ planet	566	50	18 ± 7	2.7	48	44 ± 5	1.4	0.47
Full mask with $3\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$ planet	3300	149	30 ± 22	25.3	148	105 ± 18	18.5	0.27
Full mask with $3\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$ planet (T)	3240	76	27 ± 11	6.3	74	86 ± 5	1.6	0.74
10th percentile with $3\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$ planet	631	73	26 ± 10	5.8	71	81 ± 5	1.6	0.72
5th percentile with $3\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$ planet	396	72	26 ± 10	5.6	69	79 ± 5	1.7	0.71
1st percentile with $3\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$ planet	566	67	23 ± 10	4.9	65	72 ± 5	1.6	0.68
Full mask with $4\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$ planet	3300	106	41 ± 15	12.1	102	108 ± 9	4.8	0.60
Full mask with $4\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$ planet (T)	3240	97	35 ± 14	10.1	93	114 ± 6	1.8	0.82
10th percentile with $4\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$ planet	631	93	34 ± 13	9.3	90	109 ± 6	1.8	0.80
5th percentile with $4\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$ planet	396	92	34 ± 13	9.1	88	106 ± 6	1.9	0.72
1st percentile with $4\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$ planet	566	85	28 ± 13	8.0	83	99 ± 6	1.7	0.79

Notes. The columns are: (1) specific (sub-)mask considered, (2) number of lines in the sub-mask, (3) RMS of the data set, (4) semi-amplitude of the sinusoidal fit to the data set (phased at the stellar rotation period), (5) reduced χ^2 , (6) RMS of the fit residuals, (7) semi-amplitude of the residuals (phased at the injected orbital period), (8) reduced χ^2 of the residual sinusoidal fit, and (9) power of the injected P_{orb} peak when a GLS is applied on the residual data set. We consider a $2\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$, $3\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$, and $4\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$ circular planet on a 10 d orbit separately and train the best sub-masks on the densest epochs. The sub-masks are then used on the full time series for both stars. The symbol ‘T’ indicates that the telluric windows are removed from the full mask. Formal uncertainties for the semi-amplitude are reported.

The training of the best sub-masks is performed on the injected spectra of the densest year for the two stars, analogously to the previous sections. The three percentile best sub-masks are then applied to the full time series comprising 57 and 93 observations spanning 2005–2016 and 2006–2014 for EV Lac and DS Leo, respectively. Using the full time series allows us to have a time span that is more representative of a RV planet search, with an expected loss of coherency of the activity signal, but the sampling is not optimal, therefore hindering our planetary signal retrieval. The results for the two stars are summarised in Table 3; the RV precision is not reported since in all cases it is compatible with the values in Table 2 for each star.

For EV Lac, the dispersion of the RV data set computed with the full mask is $8\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$, hence no injected planetary signal is detectable. The application of the three percentile best sub-masks enables the signal to emerge instead. Compared to the full mask, for which there is more variability, the sub-mask cases

feature a >43% decrease in RMS, translating in a more constrained model (sinusoidal fit at the stellar rotation period), and therefore cleaner RV residuals. This is confirmed by the systematic reduction in χ^2_{ν} , even though its absolute estimate suggests that our method does not account entirely for the random activity. We also apply a GLS periodogram to the residuals and find that the power of the 10 d period peak increases (more significantly in the $4\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$ case) when the sub-masks are used (Fig. 10). By re-phasing the RV residuals with P_{orb} , we indeed reveal the expected planetary modulation (Fig. 11) and we extract a semi-amplitude, which is lower but consistent with the injected value within the uncertainties. Moreover, we observe that the best (i.e. lowest RMS) of the three percentile sub-mask is also the one that removes the planetary signal the most (with K residuals reduced by at least 30%). This indicates a possible trade-off in the choice of the percentile sub-mask, which should be considered on a case-by-case basis.

Fig. 10. GLS periodograms of the full RV time series for EV Lac. *Top:* periodogram of the data set obtained with the full mask and a $2\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$ injected planet. *Middle:* periodograms of the residuals (of a sinusoidal fit at the stellar rotation period) obtained with the three 2010-trained percentile sub-masks and a $2\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$ injected planet. *Bottom:* Periodograms of the residuals (of a sinusoidal fit at the stellar rotation period) obtained with the three 2010-trained percentile sub-masks and a $4\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$ injected planet. In each panel the stellar rotation period and injected planetary period are indicated by a dotted and solid red line, respectively. When the 2010-trained sub-masks are used a systematic quench of the peak is observed at the stellar rotation period and the rise in the peak is seen at the injected orbital period as the mass of the planet increases. In the $2\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$ case the planetary peak is not distinguishable because the dispersion is still twice as large while in the $4\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$ case the peak becomes the highest one (with FAP > 1%).

For DS Leo, the results are analogous and complementary to EV Lac since we recover all planetary signals within the

Fig. 11. Phase-folded RV data sets of EV Lac when using the full mask and the 10th, 5th, and 1st percentile sub-masks on all the epochs with a $2\sigma_{\text{NARVAL}}$ synthetic planet (red dashed line). The raw RV data sets phased at the stellar rotation period (*upper panel*) and the residuals to the sinusoidal fit phased at the planet orbital period (*bottom panel*) are illustrated. The planetary signal is clearly recovered when using the three percentile sub-masks, whereas the variability of the data set associated with the full mask does not enable a reliable recovery.

Fig. 12. Same as Fig. 11, but for DS Leo. No substantial difference is observed between using the full mask or the three percentile sub-masks, meaning that the planetary signal is recovered with the same confidence.

error bars (Fig. 12). With a lower activity level the improvement represented by using the three percentile sub-masks is only marginal, and the semi-amplitude of the corresponding RV residuals is consistent with the estimate of the full mask (less than 24% in all cases). This reinforces our finding that the randomised line down-selection does not significantly suppress the planetary signal with respect to the full mask. Similarly to EV Lac, we also observe that the lowest-RMS percentile sub-mask underestimates the retrieved semi-amplitude.

Removing the telluric windows from the start has a beneficial effect for the full mask (see Table 3) since the overall dispersion of the data set is decreased. In comparison, the output percentile sub-masks lead to both a lower dispersion and a more constrained sinusoidal fit of the RV residuals, quantified by a lower χ^2_{ν} value (especially for EV Lac). We also observe similar periodogram powers at the injected P_{orb} , both with the telluric-removed full mask and with the three sub-masks, further indicating that our method discerns planetary signals.

We performed a similar analysis considering only the two densest epochs for each star (2007 and 2010 for EV Lac, and 2008 and 2010 for DS Leo). The idea was to exploit the increased coherence of the activity signal and obtain two separate and improved sinusoidal fits at the stellar rotation period. We combined the respective residuals into a single data set and examined its periodic content analogously to the full time series case (GLS periodogram and re-phasing at P_{orb}). For EV Lac, the results with the sub-masks show no substantial change, while for DS Leo we underestimate the retrieved planetary semi-amplitude in a systematic way, probably following the low activity level of the star and thus the absence of a dominant signal to filter out.

The overall positive outcome of the planetary injection tests demonstrates that our randomised approach is capable of finding the least dispersive lines without prior information on telluric windows, while preserving the planetary signal. This is especially important in view of near-infrared RV planet searches, as an accurate telluric correction in this domain is notoriously challenging (Artigau et al. 2014).

5. Conclusions

We carried out a study of the effects of different line masks for least-squares deconvolution on the dispersion of RV data sets with the intent to build a mask that mitigates the effects of activity jitter. This is of particular importance for M dwarfs, given their notoriously high activity levels, and their key role in future small planet searches. Our method benefits from the multi-line nature of LSD since it results in a high S/N profile cleaned from line blends, and it is designed for highly dense spectra, for which the identification of individual activity-sensitive lines is more complicated.

We analysed two distinct line selection approaches for the active M dwarf EV Lac: a parametric method and a randomised method. With the parametric selection we chose spectral lines directly based on their depth, wavelength, or magnetic sensitivity, while for the randomised selection we employed an algorithm that examines several combinations of lines and identifies those that minimise the RV dispersion. We also tested whether the algorithm works in the opposite direction, whether it can identify sub-masks containing lines affected by activity, telluric lines, and other dispersive sources. The algorithm was applied to another active star (AD Leo) and a moderately active star (DS Leo) to validate its portability to different targets. Finally, the analysis was completed with planetary signal recovery tests for EV Lac and DS Leo. Our conclusions are summarised as follows:

1. A straightforward parametric selection is not sufficient to build a sub-mask to mitigate activity, as we report no significant reduction in the RV RMS of the resulting data sets. At the same time, regardless of the parametric selections examined, the estimates of the longitudinal magnetic field are retrieved consistently, demonstrating its reliability as magnetic activity tracer and the benefit of extracting information from circularly polarised starlight. We note that the full width at half maximum of high- g_{eff} lines can still be used to monitor the activity modulation on very active stars (Klein et al. 2021).
2. The randomised approach allows us to generate a sub-mask with an associated 63% decrease in RV RMS. The sub-mask is trained on 2010 (the densest data set), but provides systematic RV RMS reduction when applied to 2007 (48%) and the full time series (45%). The added benefit is the absence of

lines falling within telluric windows (without imposing a priori information) and leading to excessive dispersion, which will be particularly helpful to compensate telluric correction in the near-infrared.

3. The improvement of the 2010-trained best sub-mask of EV Lac can be transferred directly to another active star such as AD Leo, therefore extending the portability and possibly suggesting the definition of generally stable sub-mask. This is likely the consequence of similar properties between the stars (e.g. activity level, chemical composition, and spectral type). At the same time, a remarkable and efficient reduction in RV dispersion (and semi-amplitude) is achieved when the sub-mask training is applied directly on the star of interest, demonstrating the consistency of our randomised approach.
4. The coexistence of multiple sources of noise such as high activity and telluric residuals impedes the randomised algorithm from robustly identifying unstable sub-masks containing activity-sensitive lines only, which can potentially be used to model and filter out the activity jitter. The situation improves when lines within telluric windows are removed from the start or when a RV semi-amplitude selection criterion is employed since an evident rotational modulation at the stellar rotation period (typical of the activity signal) is present in both cases.
5. The planetary injection tests are successful for both EV Lac and DS Leo activity regimes. In the case of a high activity level, the sub-masks built with the randomised algorithm allow the RV variability to be reduced, and therefore simplify the planetary signal recovery, while there is no substantial difference between using the trained sub-masks and the full mask for lower activity levels. In either case, the algorithm is capable of preserving the planetary signal, with only a marginal degradation in semi-amplitude.

The main goal of our activity-mitigating method is to increase the sensitivity toward the detection of small planets in the habitable zone of M dwarfs. In a forthcoming paper (Bellotti et al., in prep.) we will extend the analysis to the near-infrared regime and investigate the integration of the sub-mask optimal extraction with previous modelling and filtering techniques such as Doppler imaging, Zeeman-Doppler imaging, and Gaussian process regression (Donati et al. 2016; Hébrard et al. 2016; Yu et al. 2017; Haywood et al. 2014).

Acknowledgements. We thank Xavier Dumusque for detailed comments on the RV precision that enabled us to improve this paper. We thank Xavier Bonfils and Jean-Francois Donati for the insightful suggestions on the interpretation of the algorithm output. This work is based on observations obtained at the Canada-France-Hawaii Telescope (CFHT) which is operated by the National Research Council of Canada, the Institut National des Sciences de l'Univers of the Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique of France, and the University of Hawaii. This work has made use of the VALD database, operated at Uppsala University, the Institute of Astronomy RAS in Moscow, and the University of Vienna; Astropy, 12 a community-developed core Python package for Astronomy (Astropy Collaboration 2013, 2018); NumPy (van der Walt et al. 2011); Matplotlib: Visualization with Python (Hunter 2007); SciPy (Virtanen et al. 2020). We acknowledge funding from the French National Research Agency (ANR) under contract number ANR-18-CE31-0019 (SPLaSH). X.D. acknowledges for funding in the framework of the Investissements d'Avenir program (ANR-15-IDEX-02), through the funding of the "Origin of Life" project of the Univ. Grenoble-Alpes.

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Appendix A: Control variables of the randomised approach

In this section we investigate the optimal control variables of the randomised approach, namely the number of sampled lines (n_{sample}) and the number of times each line has to be drawn for the algorithm to stop (n_{stop}). The purpose is to find a sweet spot between the achievable reduction of RV dispersion and the number of lines in the sub-mask (n_{lines}) and still obtain a moderate S/N improvement in the final LSD profile.

We consider a grid of (n_{sample} , n_{stop}) combinations for the following cases: $n_{\text{sample}}=[20, 50, 100, 200, 500, 1000, 2000]$ and $n_{\text{stop}}=[10, 20, 50, 100]$. For each value of n_{sample} we apply the randomised approach with $n_{\text{stop}}=100$ to obtain the largest sample of sub-masks or, equivalently, to explore the largest region of line combination space. Then, because the $n_{\text{stop}}=100$ run contains the lower n_{stop} cases by construction, we simply extract the corresponding sub-masks. This procedure enables us to save computational time and ensure consistency when comparing results given a certain n_{sample} . The number of sub-masks examined for the grid are reported in Table A.1.

Given that our randomised algorithm examines the 1st, 5th, and 10th percentiles of the RV RMS distribution to build the final sub-masks (see Sect. 4), the output of the simulation grid is threefold, as illustrated in Fig. A.1. In all cases, the number of lines in the sub-mask decreases systematically with a smaller number of samples (i.e. lower n_{sample}), while it is not affected by n_{stop} . The RV RMS correlates mainly with the number of sampled lines, reaching a minimum at $n_{\text{sample}}=50$ and rising again for $n_{\text{sample}}=20$, presumably due to the photon noise contribution when a small number of lines is used. The RMS also improves with increasing n_{stop} until it stabilises between $n_{\text{stop}} = 50$ and 100. Combining these features, we are able to locate the optimised control variables at (n_{sample} , n_{stop}) = (50, 100), ensuring a dense and statistically robust exploration of the sub-mask space. A visual inspection of the Stokes I profiles resulting from the best sub-masks of the grid reveals that our algorithm identifies deep and sharp lines reliably when n_{sample} is decreased, which further validates our optimisation. From Fig. A.1 we note that the output of our randomised algorithm can be strategically adapted according to the S/N tolerance of the observations: the best sub-mask is chosen based on the number of lines (hence, S/N) and on achievable RV precision.

Appendix A.1. Portability to other epochs

The simulated grid of sub-masks enables us to test their portability to other epochs in which the star has been observed. In particular, we examine whether the RV RMS improvement associated with each sub-mask can be transferred to the 2007 time series (15 observations) by performing LSD on this data set with the 2010-trained sub-masks of the grid. We then compute the RMS improvement ratio between 2007 and 2010, as shown in Fig. A.2. Except for a few outliers, indicating sub-masks with a predominant benefit for a certain year, we observe a general ratio close to 1.0, demonstrating that the RMS improvement is the same for both years. Furthermore, we note the absence of outliers when n_{stop} is large, confirming our previous choice of $n_{\text{stop}}=100$.

Appendix A.2. Selection of the best sub-masks

In our randomised algorithm, the stable sub-masks are isolated based on the 10th, 5th, and 1st percentiles of the RV RMS

Table A.1. Number of sub-masks examined for each (n_{sample} , n_{stop}) combination of the simulation grid.

n_{sample}	20	50	100	200	500	1000	2000
n_{stop}							
10	3918	1689	857	394	161	72	34
20	6448	2504	1389	715	244	116	54
50	13464	5295	2588	1342	521	233	108
100	23208	9281	4549	2345	880	447	200

distribution. Then the three final sub-masks (one for each percentile) are built including lines that are drawn at least a fraction (f_{select}) of the maximum number of draws for the specific percentile. The variable f_{select} is therefore an additional value to be optimised, as it determines the number of lines in the best sub-mask and affects the achievable RV precision.

The simulation tests for (n_{sample} , n_{stop}) were performed with $f_{\text{select}}=0.5$. Here, we start from the optimised (n_{sample} , $n_{\text{stop}})=(50,100)$ run and compare the results using $f_{\text{select}}=0.25$, 0.33, and 0.5. From Fig. A.3, we realise that $f_{\text{select}}=0.5$ is a strong constraint, given that we obtain a similar RV RMS for the other two cases, but with a smaller number of lines. Instead, the $f_{\text{select}}=0.25$ is a weak constraint, yielding a deterioration in both RMS and semi-amplitude; this is evident with additional runs of the randomised algorithm. We therefore conclude that $f_{\text{select}}=0.33$ is the appropriate value to obtain a substantial improvement in RMS while maintaining a moderately large number of lines in the final sub-masks.

Selecting lines for the three percentile sub-masks based on a fraction of the maximum number of draws (for that percentile) may lead to a lower number of lines, for example in the 5th percentile relative to the 1st. In fact, if only a few sub-masks fall below the 1st percentile of the RV RMS distribution, the maximum number of draws will inevitably be small, and consequently more lines will be selected in the corresponding percentile sub-mask.

Finally, we tested an alternative method of building the three percentile sub-masks and using them in LSD. Instead of rejecting lines that do not satisfy the constraint imposed by f_{select} , we kept all the lines of the sub-masks within one percentile and employed the number of draws as an additional weight in the LSD computation. More precisely, to compute the Stokes I profile, each line in the mask is weighted based on depth (Kochukhov et al. 2010)

$$w_I = \frac{d}{d_n}, \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where d_n is the normalisation depth (used to ensure $w_I = 1$). We therefore updated Eq.A.1 by multiplying it by the number of draws. We found a systematic deterioration in both RMS and semi-amplitude for all three percentile sub-masks, relative to the $f_{\text{select}}=0.33$ case, of about 20-30%.

Fig. A.1. Optimisation of the randomised algorithm control variables. The simulation grid for each $(n_{\text{sample}}, n_{\text{stop}})$ combination is shown, with data points coded by colour and size according to the RV RMS and number of lines within the sub-mask, respectively. The optimised $(n_{\text{sample}}, n_{\text{stop}})$ pair is (50, 100), ensuring both a precise RV data set and a dense exploration of the sub-mask space. The panels from left to right illustrate the 10th, 5th, and 1st percentile case.

Fig. A.2. Testing the portability of the 2010-trained sub-masks to the 2007 data set of EV Lac, for the simulated grid of $(n_{\text{sample}}, n_{\text{stop}})$ combinations. Almost all the sub-masks yield the same RV RMS improvement for both 2007 and 2010 (i.e. the improvement ratio is close to 1), demonstrating the portability of the randomised approach output beyond the training year. In a few cases the improvement ratio is either greater or lower than one, meaning that the benefit of the sub-mask is greater for 2007 or 2010, respectively. The panels from left to right illustrate the 10th, 5th, and 1st percentile case.

Fig. A.3. Test of the f_{select} variable in the randomised algorithm, i.e. the fraction determining the number of draws each line must have to be included in the three percentile sub-masks. From top to bottom: Using the full mask, $f_{\text{select}}=0.5$ sub-mask, $f_{\text{select}}=0.33$, and $f_{\text{select}}=0.25$. All the f_{select} cases refer to the 1st percentile sub-mask, as the other percentiles show deteriorated but analogous features. In each panel the solid line indicates the sinusoidal fit at the period found in Sect. 2. We observe that $f_{\text{select}}=0.33$ is the best trade-off between number of lines included and achievable RV RMS.

Appendix B: Properties of the trained masks

We compare the distributions of the line parameters for three different masks: the full mask without telluric windows a priori (3240 lines), the 2010-trained union of best sub-masks (721 lines), and the 2010-trained worst RMS-based sub-mask without telluric windows a priori (2117 lines). The training refers to the 2010 data set of EV Lac with the randomised approach.

Figure B.1 illustrates the distributions of line depth, wavelength, and Landé factor for the three masks. The depth distribution for the full mask spans between 0.4 and 1.0 times the continuum intensity, with one-third of the lines are deeper than 0.9 and with a mean of 0.73. The wavelength distribution features an almost exponential decay from 350 to 1080 nm and a mean of 433.1 nm, while the g_{eff} distribution ranges between 0.0 and 3.4, with a mean of 1.25 and two peaks at 1.0 and 1.5.

Apart from the different number of lines in the bins due to our randomised down-selection approach, the other two sub-masks do not feature particular trends or quantitative differences in the statistics, implying that it is not possible to straightforwardly build stable or unstable sub-masks with a selection based on these parameters.

Despite the absence of a particular feature in the distributions, the effects on Stokes I profiles of these masks are striking. From Fig. B.2 we observe how the union of the best sub-masks leads to deeper and narrower profiles than the full mask, which would result in a more precise RV estimate. On the contrary, the application of the worst sub-mask yields shallow and distorted profiles, therefore increasing the dispersion of the associated RV data set. These features help us demonstrate further the capability of our algorithm to discern stable and unstable lines.

Fig. B.1. Distributions of the line parameters for three examined masks: the full mask without telluric windows a priori (top row), union of best sub-masks (central row), and 2010-trained worst RMS-based sub-mask without telluric windows a priori (bottom row). The parameters shown are (from left to right) depth, wavelength, and Landé factor. The statistics (mean, median, and standard deviation) of the depth distributions is ($\mu=0.73$, $\tilde{\mu}=0.74$, $\sigma=0.19$), ($\mu=0.72$, $\tilde{\mu}=0.72$, $\sigma=0.18$), and ($\mu=0.71$, $\tilde{\mu}=0.71$, $\sigma=0.19$) for the three masks, respectively. Analogously, the wavelength distribution statistics (in nm) is ($\mu=433.1$, $\tilde{\mu}=401.2$, $\sigma=97.9$), ($\mu=454.6$, $\tilde{\mu}=424.3$, $\sigma=88.9$), and ($\mu=435.9$, $\tilde{\mu}=412.3$, $\sigma=75.8$) and the g_{eff} statistics is ($\mu=1.25$, $\tilde{\mu}=1.21$, $\sigma=0.41$), ($\mu=1.27$, $\tilde{\mu}=1.24$, $\sigma=0.42$), and ($\mu=1.26$, $\tilde{\mu}=1.22$, $\sigma=0.41$).

Fig. B.2. Time series of the Stokes I profiles for the 2010 observations of EV Lac computed with (Left) the full mask without telluric window a priori, (Middle) union of the 2010-trained best sub-masks, and (Right) the 2010-trained worst RMS-based sub-mask without telluric windows a priori. The Stokes profiles are shifted vertically for visibility, and sorted by ascending observation date. An increased sharpness can be observed when the union of best sub-masks is used, and a broad, distorted profile when the worst sub-mask is used, implying the presence of stable and unstable lines in the sub-masks, respectively.

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